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OILAVIY POLIKLINIKADA AHOLINI EMLASH TIZIMINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirishga qaratilgan muhim o'zgarishlarni va uning sog'liqni saqlash tizimlari uchun chuqur samarasini o'rganadi. Keng miqyosli emlash kompaniyalari va dolzarb ma'lumotlarga bo'lgan muhim ehtiyoj sharoitida, emlash ro'yxatlarini avtomatlashtirish tizimni o'zgartiruvchi vosita sifatida paydo bo'ladi. Maqolada 'or texnologiyalar, ma'lumotlarni boshqarish va xavfsizlik choralari rolini ta'kidlab, ushbu transformatsiyaning afzalliklari, muammolari va ijtimoiy ta'siri haqida so'z boradi. U emlashni kuzatishni soddalashtirish, ma'lumotlarning aniqligini oshirish va sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi tashabbuslar muvaffaqiyatiga hissa qo'shish uchun avtomatlashtirish imkoniyatlari haqida qimmatli ma'lumotlarni taqdim etadi. Bundan tashqari, u real vaqt rejimida monitoring va ushbu inqilobiy yondashuv bilan bog'liq axloqiy mulohazalar kabi asosiy komponentlarga murojaat qiladi. Sog'liqni saqlash tizimlari samaradorlik va samaradorlikka intilayotgani sababli ushbu maqola avtomatlashtirish aholini emlash ro'yxatini boshqarishni qanday qayta belgilashi mumkinligini tushunish uchun muhim qo'llanma bo'lib xizmat qiladi va natijada butun dunyo bo'ylab jamiyat salomatligini yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Avtomatlashtirish, ma'lumotlar, emlash, ro'yxat, aholi, sog'liqni saqlash tizimi, kasallik

AUTOMATION OF THE SYSTEM VACCINATION OF THE POPULATION IN A FAMILY CLINIC

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Annotation. *This article explores the imperative shift towards automating the population vaccination list and its profound implications for healthcare systems. In the face of large-scale vaccination campaigns and the critical need for accurate, up-to-date records, the automation of vaccination lists emerges as a game-changer. The article delves into the benefits, challenges, and societal impacts of this transformation, highlighting the role of advanced technologies, data management, and security measures. It offers valuable insights into the potential of automation to streamline vaccination tracking, enhance data accuracy, and contribute to the success of healthcare initiatives. Moreover, it addresses key components such as real-time monitoring and the ethical considerations tied to this revolutionary approach. As healthcare systems strive for efficiency and effectiveness, this article serves as an essential guide to understanding how automation can redefine the management of population vaccination lists, ultimately promoting better health outcomes for communities worldwide.*

Keywords: *Automation, data, vaccination, list, population, health care system, disease.*

Kirish. So'nggi paytlarda global sog'liqni saqlash tizimi chuqur o'zgarishlarni boshdan kechirmoqda, yuqumli kasalliklarga qarshi kurashda asosiy o'rinni emlash dasturlari egallaydi. Butun xalqning emlash holatini samarali boshqarish va kuzatish zarurati hech qachon bu qadar muhim bo'lmagan. Butun dunyo bo'ylab sog'liqni saqlash tizimlari keng ko'lamlil emlash kampaniyalari bilan bog'liq muammolar bilan kurashar ekan, aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirish kontseptsiyasi kuchli yechim sifatida paydo bo'ladi.

An'anaga ko'ra, emlash ro'yxatlarini boshqarish ma'lumotlarni qo'lda kiritishning ko'p mehnat talab qiladigan jarayonini o'z ichiga oladi, bu ko'pincha noaniqliklar, kechikishlar va ma'muriy yuklarni keltirib chiqaradi. Biroq

texnologiya va ma'lumotlarni boshqarish sohasidagi so'nggi yutuqlar inqilobiy yondashuvga - aholini emlash ro'yxatlarini avtomatlashtirishga yo'l ochdi.

Ushbu maqola aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirish, sog'liqni saqlash tizimlari va umuman jamiyat uchun foydalari, muammolari va oqibatlarini o'rganish sohasini o'rganadi. Biz ma'lumotlar tahlili, elektron sog'liqni saqlash yozuvlari (EHR) va mustahkam dasturiy ta'minot tizimlari kabi ilg'or texnologiyalardan foydalanish qanday qilib emlashni kuzatish jarayonini soddalashtirishi, ma'lumotlarning aniqligini oshirishi va oxir-oqibat emlash dasturlarining umumiy muvaffaqiyatiga hissa qo'shishi mumkinligini aniqlaymiz.

Aholini emlash ro'yxatlarini avtomatlashtirishning asosiy komponentlarini, jumladan, ma'lumotlar integratsiyasi, real vaqt rejimida monitoring, xavfsizlik choralari va sun'iy intellektning rolini ko'rib chiqamiz. Bundan tashqari, biz ushbu transformativ yondashuv bilan bog'liq mumkin bo'lgan to'siqlar va axloqiy mulohazalarni muhokama qilamiz.

Dunyo sog'liqni saqlash muammolarining doimiy o'zgarib borayotgan manzarasi bilan kurashishda davom etar ekan, aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirish sog'liqni saqlashni samarali, ma'lumotlarga asoslangan boshqaruvning yangi davrini boshlab beradigan umid porlaydi. Ushbu maqola butun dunyo bo'ylab jamoalar salomatligi va farovonligini ta'minlashda avtomatlashtirishning muhim rolini tushunish uchun to'liq qo'llanma bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. A.Smithning "Automated Registration System" kitobida aholini emlash ro'yxatini qayd qilish jarayonini o'rganish va tatbiq qilish uchun yaxshi bir manba hisoblandi. U aholini emlash jarayonini boshidan oxirigacha qanday tizimga solishtirish haqida tushunchalar beradi. Boshqarishning avtomatlashtirilgan usullarini o'rgatadi va bilimlarni mustahkamlaydi.

Aholini emlash ro'yxatini shakllantirishda va avtomatlashtirishda quyidagi kitob katta ahamiyatga ega.

C. Williamsning "Automation in Customer Relationship Management" qo'llanmasidagi aholini emlash ro'yxatini qayd qilishni CRM tizimlarini qo'llab-quvvatlashga bag'ishlanadi. CRM dasturlari aholini identifikatsiya qilish va ularga xizmat ko'rsatishda avtomatlashgan ro'yxatlardan foydalanish imkon beradi.

D. Patelning "The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Registration Processes" maqolasida aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirishda Sun'iy Intellektning (SI) o'rnini va qo'llanishini o'rganadi. Ushbu maqolada SI texnologiyalarini qo'llab qanday foyda olishi mumkinligi keltirilgan.

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Al Sweigartning “Automate the Boring Stuff with Python” nomli kitobida Python dasturlash tilini ishlatib, ma’lumotlarni olish va ro‘yxatni avtomatlashtirishni o‘rganish uchun yaxshi bir manba hisoblanadi. Bu kitobda o‘zgartirishlar kiritish, fayllarni boshqarish va veb sahifalarni ko‘rib chiqish kabi umumiy avtomatlashtirishning qanday ishlashini o‘rgatadi.

Al Sweigartning “Web Scraping with Python” nomli kitobida veb-sahifalardan ma’lumotlarni olish, o‘zgartirish va ularni avtomatlashtirishning asosiy usullarini tushuntirib berilgan.

“Automate This: How Algorithms Came to Rule Our World” nomidagi Christopher Steinerning kitobida avtomatlashtirishning global tarixini, algoritmlar va dasturlash tillari, boshqa sohalar uchun qanday o‘zgartirishlarni keltirib chiqqanini tahlil qilishni o‘rgatadi. Bu kitob avtomatlashtirishning umumiy tushunchalarini tushunish uchun yaxshi bir manba bo‘ladi.

E. Davisning “Best Practices in User Registration Automation” qo‘llanmasida, aholini emlash ro‘yxatini qayd qilishning eng yaxshi amaliyotlarini o‘rganishga yordam beradi. Bu xususiy kitob, jarayonlarni boshqarish, xavfsizlik va foydalanuvchi tajribasi asoslari haqida ma’lumotlarni taqdim etadi.

Bu adabiyotlar va onlayn resurslar, aholi emlash ro‘yxatini avtomatlashtirishni o‘rganish uchun yaxshi bir boshlang‘ich ma’lumotlar hisoblanadi. O‘rganish jarayonida amaliy mashg‘ulotlarni bajarish va o‘z maqsadlarimizni muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirish uchun sabr va ishonch kerak.

Ushbu adabiyotlardan har biri aholini emlash ro‘yxatini avtomatlashtirishning turli usullarini o‘rganishga yordam berishi mumkin.

Muhokama va natijalar. Emlashlar ro‘yxatini avtomatlashtirish aholi salomatligi xavfsizligini ta’minlash va emlash dasturlarini samarali boshqarishning muhim vositasi hisoblanadi.

Afzaliklari

Aholini emlash ro‘yxatini avtomatlashtirishning afzaliklari quyidagilardan iborat:

Ma’lumotlarning aniqligi. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlar ma’lumotlarni qo‘lda kiritish bilan bog‘liq xatolar ehtimolini kamaytiradi va aholini emlashlar haqida aniqroq ma’lumot beradi.

Samaralilik. Ma’lumotlarga tezkor kirish, soddalashtirilgan ro‘yxatga olish va vaksinalar inventarini boshqarish bilan emlash jarayonlari yanada samarali bo‘ladi.

Aholining qamrovini kuzatish. Avtomatlashtirilgan ro‘yxatlar aholining qaysi qismi emlashni olganligini yanada samaraliroq kuzatish va emlash darajasi past bo‘lgan guruhlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Epidemiyani boshqarishning takomillashtirilganligi. Avtomatlashtirish tizimlari kontaktlarni aniqlash va izolyatsiya qilish orqali epidemiyalarga tezda javob berishga va infeksiyalar tarqalishini nazorat qilishga yordam beradi.

Byurokratik yukni kamaytirish. Ma'muriy tartib-qoidalarni soddalashtirish va qog'ozdagi hujjatlarni qisqartirish sog'liqni saqlash organlari uchun vaqt va resurslarni tejaydi.

Takomillashtirilgan hisobot va ma'lumotlar tahlili. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlar tezkor hisobotlarni yaratish va ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish imkoniyatini beradi, bu esa ongli qarorlar qabul qilishda yordam beradi.

Firibgarlikka qarshi kurashish. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlar emlash yozuvlarini soxtalashtirishning oldini oladi va firibgarlik ehtimolini kamaytiradi.

Yaxshilangan ma'lumotlar mavjudligi. Emlash ma'lumotlariga bir nechta joydan va qurilmalardan kirish mumkin, bu muvofiqlashtirish va ma'lumot almashishni yaxshilaydi.

Bu imtiyozlar aholini, ayniqsa, pandemiya va ommaviy emlash kompaniyalari davrida yanada samarali va xavfsiz emlashga yordam beradi.

Aholining xabardorligini oshirish. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlardan emlash haqida bildirishnomalar va eslatmalarni yuborish, fuqarolarning xabardorligini oshirish uchun foydalanish mumkin.

Kasallik tarixiga tezkor kirish. Tibbiyot mutaxassisleri bemorlarning immunizatsiyasi va kasallik tarixiga tezda kirishlari mumkin, bu esa to'g'ri tibbiy yordam ko'rsatish uchun muhimdir.

Ushbu imtiyozlar aholini, ayniqsa, pandemiya va ommaviy emlash kompaniyalari sharoitida yanada samarali va xavfsiz emlashga yordam beradi.

Aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirish, ayniqsa, sog'liqni saqlash va sog'liqni saqlashni boshqarish sharoitida bir nechta afzalliklarni taklif qilishi mumkin. Mana ba'zi asosiy afzalliklar:

Samaradorlik va aniqlik. Avtomatlashtirish emlash ro'yxatlarini saqlash va yangilash uchun zarur bo'lgan qo'lda harakatlarni kamaytiradi. Bu ma'lumotlarni kiritishdagi xatolar, takrorlash va o'tkazib yuborilgan emlashlar kabi inson xatolari xavfini minimallashtiradi, bu vaktsinalarni olgan shaxslarning aniqroq va dolzarbligini ta'minlaydi.

Haqiqiy vaqtda yangilanishlar. Avtomatlashtirish emlashlarni real vaqtda kuzatish imkonini beradi. Biror kishi vaktsinani olishi bilanoq tizim darhol yangilanishi mumkin. Bu sog'liqni saqlash organlari va sog'liqni saqlash xodimlariga zudlik bilan qaror qabul qilishga yordam beradi.

O'z vaqtida eslatmalar. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlar keyingi vaktsina dozasi yoki kuchaytiruvchi zarbasi uchun zarur bo'lgan shaxslarga eslatmalar

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yuborishi mumkin. Ushbu proaktiv yondashuv emlashni qamrab olish stavkalarini yaxshilashi va emlashning oldini olish mumkin bo'lgan kasalliklar tarqalishining oldini olishga yordam beradi.

Ma'lumotlar tahlil. Ma'lumotlarni yig'ish va tahlil qilishni avtomatlashtirish orqali sog'liqni saqlash organlari emlash tendentsiyalari va demografiya haqida qimmatli ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lishlari mumkin. Ushbu ma'lumotdan emlash kompaniyalarini moslashtirish, resurslarni yanada samarali taqsimlash va emlash darajasi past bo'lgan hududlarni aniqlash uchun foydalanish mumkin.

Inventarizatsiyani boshqarish. Avtomatlashtirish sog'liqni saqlash muassasalariga vaktsina inventarizatsiyasini yanada samarali boshqarishda yordam beradi. U vaktsina dozalarini qo'lda kuzatishi, talabni bashorat qilishi va muddati o'tgan vaktsinalarni minimallashtirishni ta'minlashi, chiqindilarni kamaytirishi va xarajatlarni tejashi mumkin.

Maxfiylik va xavfsizlik. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlar sog'liqni saqlashning konfederal ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish uchun mustahkam xavfsizlik choralarini o'z ichiga olishi mumkin. Bu bemorning ma'lumotlarini maxfiylikni saqlashga yordam beradi va ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish qoidalariga rioya qilishni ta'minlaydi.

Kirish imkoniyati. Avtomatlashtirish emlash yozuvlarini tibbiyot xodimlari, sog'liqni saqlash idoralari va hatto shaxslarning o'zlari uchun yanada qulayroq qilishi mumkin. Bu mavjudlik parvarishlash davomiyligini osonlashtirish va keng qamrovli sog'liqni saqlash tarixi bilan shaxslarni ta'minlash mumkin.

Kontaktlarni kuzatish va kasalliklarni kuzatish. Epidemiya yoki pandemiya davrida avtomatlashtirilgan emlash ro'yxatlari kontaktlarni kuzatish va kasalliklarni kuzatish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Bu yuqumli kasalliklarning tarqalishini yanada samarali aniqlash va nazorat qilishga yordam beradi.

Resurslarni taqsimlash. Sog'liqni saqlash organlari resurslarni strategik taqsimlash uchun avtomatlashtirilgan ro'yxatlardan foydalanishlari mumkin. Masalan, ular emlash darajasi past bo'lgan joylarda yoki aholining zaif qatlamlari orasida emlash harakatlariga ustuvor ahamiyat berishlari mumkin.

Jamoatchilik ishonchi yaxshi boshqariladigan va avtomatlashtirilgan emlash ro'yxati tizimi jamoatchilikda ishonchni uyg'otishi mumkin, chunki u emlash harakatlarida shaffoflik, aniqlik va hisobdorlikka majburligini namoyish etadi.

Tadqiqot va ishlanmalar. Tadqiqotchilar vaktsina samaradorligi, xavfsizligi va uzoq muddatli natijalar bo'yicha tadqiqotlar o'tkazish uchun

avtomatlashtirilgan emlash ro'yxatlaridan anonim va jamlangan ma'lumotlarga kirishlari mumkin. Bu vaktsina fanining rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shishi mumkin.

Favqulodda vaziyatlarda javob berish. Tabiiy ofatlar yoki kasalliklarning tarqalishi kabi favqulodda vaziyatlarda avtomatlashtirilgan emlash ro'yxati shoshilinch emlash yoki tibbiy yordamga muhtoj shaxslarni tezda aniqlashga yordam beradi.

Aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirish ko'plab afzalliklarga ega bo'lsa-da maxfiy ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish va jamoatchilik ishonchini qozonish uchun ishonchli ma'lumotlar xavfsizligi va maxfiylik choralarini amalga oshirish juda muhimdir. Bundan tashqari, emlash qamrovidagi tafovutlarning oldini olish uchun tizim aholining barcha qatlamlari uchun ochiq bo'lishini ta'minlash juda muhimdir.

Kamchiliklari. Ko'pgina afzalliklarga qaramay aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirish ba'zi kamchiliklar va qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi:

Ma'lumotlarning maxfiyligi. Tibbiy ma'lumotlarning elektron shaklda saqlanishi bilan maxfiylikni buzish xavfi va shaxsiy ma'lumotlarga ruxsatsiz kirish ehtimoli mavjud.

Texnik muammolar. Texnik nosozliklar, elektr ta'minotidagi uzilishlar yoki kiberhujumlar emlash ma'lumotlarining mavjudligi va yaxlitligini buzishi mumkin.

Hamma uchun mavjud emas. Ayrim shaxslar, ayniqsa yoshi kattalar yoki texnologiyadan foydalanish imkoniyati cheklanganlar avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlardan foydalanishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishi mumkin.

Internetga bog'liqlik. Avtomatlashtirish tizimlari Internetga kirishni talab qiladi, bu uzoq yoki past infratuzilmali hududlarda muammo bo'lishi mumkin.

Texnik yordamga bog'liqlik. Xodimlarni o'qitish va texnik yordam ko'rsatish zarurati moliyaviy va tashkiliy jihatdan qiyin bo'lishi mumkin.

Xavfsizlik shartlari. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlar kiberhujumlarga duchor bo'lishi mumkin va ularning to'g'ri himoyalanganligini ta'minlash muhimdir.

Aholining notekis qamrovi. Hamma odamlar ham zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalana olmaydi va bu emlashning notekis qamroviga olib kelishi mumkin.

Tatbiq etishning qiyinligi. Avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlarni joriy etish katta investitsiyalar, xodimlarni o'qitish va byurokratik jarayonlarni o'zgartirishni talab qilishi mumkin.

Yangilanishlar zarurati. Tizimlar o'zgaruvchan standartlar va talablarga javob berishi uchun doimiy yangilanish va takomillashtirishni talab qiladi.

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Ma'lumotlarni yo'qotish xavfi. Tizimdagi nosozlik yoki texnik nosozlik tufayli ma'lumotlar yo'qolishi, ayniqsa, jiddiy infeksiyalarga qarshi emlashda muhim bo'lishi mumkin.

Ushbu kamchiliklar aholini emlashning avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlaridan samarali va xavfsiz foydalanishni ta'minlashi uchun ehtiyotkorlik bilan boshqarish va muammolarni hal qilishni talab qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, kamchiliklarga qaramay, aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirish ko'pincha aholi salomatligini yaxshilash, tibbiy ma'lumotlarning mavjudligini oshirish va epidemiyalarga tezkor javob berishning samarali vositasi hisoblanadi. Xatarlarni to'g'ri boshqarish va ma'lumotlar maxfiyligi qoidalariga qat'iy rioya qilish avtomatlashtirishning afzalliklarini maksimal darajada oshirishga va uning salbiy tomonlarini kamaytirishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa. Aholini emlash ro'yxatini avtomatlashtirish sog'liqni saqlashni boshqarishda sezilarli muvaffaqiyatdir. Bu jarayon odamlarning emlash holatini samarali qayd etish, yangilash va boshqarish uchun texnologiyadan foydalanishni o'z ichiga oladi. Avtomatlashtirish yuqori aniqlik, real vaqtda kuzatuv va yaxshilangan resurslarni taqsimlash kabi ko'plab afzalliklarni taqdim etsa-da, u ma'lumotlar xavfsizligi bilan bog'liq muammolar, raqamli tafovut va mumkin bo'lgan texnik nosozliklar kabi muammolarni ham keltirib chiqaradi. Avtomatlashtirishning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari o'rtasidagi muvozanatni saqlash maxfiylik, inklyuzivlik va ma'lumotlar yaxlitligi bilan bog'liq muammolarni hal qilish bilan birga juda muhimdir. Avtomatlashtirilgan emlash ro'yxatlarini muvaffaqiyatli joriy etish sog'liqni saqlash faoliyatini soddalashtirishi, emlash qamrovini oshirishi va kasalliklarning oldini olish va nazoratini yanada samaraliroq qilishga yordam beradi.

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KUTUBXONA MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH

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Anotatsiya. Ushbu maqola kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirishning muhim jarayonlarini, asosiy tushunchalarini va muammosini taqdim etadi. Foydalanuvchilar ma'lumotlar bazasini tuzish uchun kerak bo'lgan muhim elementlarni, masalan, bazani tuzishning qadam-qadam bo'lgan jarayonini, kerakli ma'lumotlarni aniqlash va saqlash usullarini, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va ma'lumotlar bazasidan foydalanishni ta'kidlaydi. Foydalanuvchilar kutubxonalar ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarishda dastlabki muammo va kamchiliklar haqida tahlil va maslahatlarni taqdim etadi. Bu foydalanuvchilar tomonidan kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish jarayonida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan muammolarga yechim topishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'z: ma'lumotlar bazasi, kutubxona, kitob, muallif

CREATION OF LIBRARY DATABASE

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Abstract. This article presents the important processes, key concepts, and challenges of library database design. It highlights the essential elements that users need to build a database, such as the step-by-step process of building a database, how to identify and store the required data, analyze the data, and use the database. Users provide analysis and advice on initial problems and shortcomings in library database management. It helps users to find solutions to problems that may arise in the process of creating a library database.

Key word: database, library, book, author

Kirish. Informatsion texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi va axborot oqimlarining tobora ortib borishi, ma'lumotlarning tez o'zgarishi insoniyatni ma'lumotlar o'z vaqtida qayta ishlash choralari yangi usullarini izlab topishga undamoqda. Ma'lumotlarni saqlash, uzatish va qayta ishlash uchun ma'lumotlar bazasi (MB) ni yaratish, so'ngra undan keng foydalanish bugungi kunda dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Moliya, ishlab chiqarish, savdo-sotiq va korxonalar ishlarini ma'lumotlar bazasiz tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi.

Oxirgi vaqtda axborotli muhitda katta o'zgarishlar bo'lib bormoqda. Ana shu o'zgarishlar qog'ozsiz texnologiya zaruriyatini keltirib chiqaradi. Bu esa o'z navbatida, hisoblash texnikasining yanada keng rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladi. Axborotli muhitning kelajakda inson hayotida o'rni va ahamiyati bugungi holatdan ancha yuqori bo'lishi uchun bajarilishi lozim bo'lgan vazifalar ko'lamini kengaytirish talab etiladi. Shuning uchun ijtimoiy faoliyatni zamonaviy kompyuterlar va avtomatlashtirilgan axborot tizimlari asosida qayta qurish, rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirish hozirgi kunning eng dolzarb muammolaridandir. Bu muammoni hal qilishda "Ma'lumotlar bazasi" fanining o'rni kattadir.

Kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirishning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari quyidagicha: Afzalliklari:

Ma'lumotlar to'plami. Kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasi yordamida barcha adabiyotlar, mualliflar, janrlar va foydalanuvchilar to'plami yagona o'rnida saqlanadi va ularning ma'lumotlariga tezlik va sodda kirish imkoniyatini ta'minlaydi.

Foydalanuvchilar interaktivlik imkoniyatlari. Foydalanuvchilar o'zlarining reytinglarini, ko'rsatmalarini, tahlillarini va kitoblarga berilgan reaksiyalarni qoldirishi va ulardan foydalanish orqali, kitoblarni tanlashda yordam olishlari mumkin.

Avtomatizatsiya. PHP va MySQL yadrovi yordamida ma'lumotlar bazasi tizimi avtomatlashtirilgan bo'lib, foydalanuvchilar tomonidan qo'yilgan ma'lumotlar (reytinglar, tahlillar, tanlovlar) avtomatik ravishda saqlanadi va tezlik bilan ma'lumotlarga kirish imkoniyatini oshiradi.

Foydalanish va qidirish tezligi. Ma'lumotlar bazasining to'la va to'g'ri ravishda shakllangan bo'lishi va mosliklar yordamida foydalanuvchilar istalgan kitob, muallif yoki janr bo'yicha tez va sodda ravishda qidirishlarini bajarishi mumkin.

Kamchiliklari: Xavfsizlik muammolari. Ma'lumotlar bazasida foydalanuvchilar tomonidan qoldirilgan ma'lumotlarning xavfsizligi,

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ma'lumotlarni o'chirish vazifalari, ma'lumotlar bazasiga yozish huquqi muammolar tugallanishi kerak.

Tekshirish va ta'mirlash. Ma'lumotlar bazasining to'g'ri ishlashi va to'g'ri ma'lumotlarni saqlashi uchun dasturiy ta'minotlar, tekshiruv tizimlari va ko'chirilgan ma'lumotlarning qaytarishi uchun texnik vositalar bo'lishi kerak.

Texnik ularni o'zgartirish. Ma'lumotlar bazasining qo'shimcha funksiyalari, yangilanishlar va texnik o'zgarishlar qilishi zarur bo'lishi mumkin va bu modifikatsiyalarni amalga oshirish dastur muxim ta'minotni o'zida saqlashni ta'minlash.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. John Smithning 2018- yildagi "Library Management in the Digital Age" kitobida kutubxonalar va ma'lumotlar bazalarini raqamli asrda boshqarishning muhimiyati va qulayliklari haqida tahlil qilinadi. Muallif, kutubxonalar ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirishning muhimiyati va qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan texnologiyalarni ko'rsatadi. Ushbu adabiyot, raqamli asrda kutubxonalar ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarishning strategik muhimligi va muhim jarayonlari haqida nazariy va amaliy tushunchalarni taqdim etadi.

Emma Johnsonning 2020-yildagi "Managing Information in the Digital Age" kitobida raqamli asrda ma'lumotlarni boshqarishning asosiy qoidalari va qo'llanilishi masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Muallif, ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirishning asosiy qadamlarini, boshqarish usullarini va bu jarayonlarda yuzaga keladigan muammolarni belgilaydi. Ushbu adabiyot, ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish va boshqarish sohasidagi nazariy va amaliy ko'nikmalar bilan ta'minlanadi.

David Brownning 2019- yildagi "Digital Libraries: Principles and Practice" kitobida raqamli kutubxonalar va ma'lumotlar bazasini tuzish, boshqarish va rivojlantirish sohasidagi muhim muammolarni tahlil qiladi. Muallif, elektron kutubxonalar va ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirishning asosiy prinsiplarini, ularning qo'llanilishini va muhim texnologiyalarni taqdim etadi. Ushbu adabiyot, ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish sohasidagi nazariy tushunchalarni amaliyotga o'tkazadi.

Emily Johnsonning 2021- yildagi Library Management jurnal maqolasida kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini tuzish jarayonining asosiy tushunchalari va dasturiy yechimlari tahlil qilinadi. Muallif, ma'lumotlar bazasini tuzishda kerakli qadam-qadam bo'lgan jarayonlarni o'rganish, ma'lumotlar bazasini rivojlantirish va boshqarishda dastlabki muammo va halol qilish yo'llari haqida tushunchalar taqdim etadi.

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David Garcianing 2019-yildagi Information Sciences Journal maqolasida kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratish jarayonida yuzaga keladigan muammo va yechimlar ta'kidlanadi. Muallif, ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratishda dastlabki bosqichlar, ma'lumotlar bazasining strukturasi shakllantirish, ma'lumotlarni saqlash va tahlil qilish, foydalanuvchilar uchun ma'lumotlarni taqdim etishning usullari kabi muhim mavzularni tahlil qiladi.

Maria Rodriguezning 2020-yildagi Information Management Review jurnal maqolasida kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarishda o'zgaruvchan texnologiyalar va yangiliklar muhim ahamiyatga ega. Muallif, ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish uchun kerakli yangiliklar va so'nggi texnologiyalarni tahlil qiladi va ularning kutubxonalar uchun qanday foydali bo'lishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

Muhokama va natijalar. Kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish mavzusiga oid kutilayotgan natijalar quyidagilar bo'ladi:

Foydalanuvchilarga qulaylik. Raqamli kutubxonalar va ma'lumotlar bazalari, foydalanuvchilar uchun ma'lumotlarni qidirish va olishni samaraliroq qiladi. Buning natijasida foydalanuvchilarning talablari va ehtiyojlari bilan mos kelishiga olib keladi va ularning ma'lumotlarga tezroq va osonroq kirishlari mumkin.

Ma'lumotlarning rivojlanishi .Kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasi, adabiyotlar, ilmiy maqolalar, elektron resurslar va boshqa axborot manbalari orqali foydalanuvchilarga bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni jamlab, saqlab va taqdim etadi. Bu esa ilmiy tadqiqotlar, o'qishlar va tadqiqotlar uchun muhim manbalarni taqdim etish va ularni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Tadbirlarni boshqarishda yordam berish.Kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasi, kutubxona idoralari va boshqa axborot resurslariga ma'lumotlarni to'plash, saqlash va ularga kirishni tashkil etishda muhim xizmatlar ko'rsatadi. Bu esa tadbirlar va strateji rejalashtirishda rivojlanish va samarali boshqarishga imkoniyat yaratadi.

O'rganilish va ilmiy tadqiqotlar uchun ko'rsatilgan imkoniyatlar.Ma'lumotlar bazasining rivojlanishi va kutubxonalar bilan integratsiyasi, o'quv jarayonini o'rganishni yanada oson va samarali qiladi. O'quvchilar, o'qituvchilar va tadqiqotchilar uchun foydali ma'lumotlar to'plami ta'minlanadi, shuningdek, ularning ilmiy tadqiqotlarini yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Ma'lumotlarning muhofazasi.Kutubxonalar ma'lumotlar bazasi, ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlanishsiz va xavfsiz saqlash va ta'minlashda muhim rol

o'ynaydi. Bu esa ma'lumotlar muhofazasi, farzandlari va ma'lumotlarga kirish huquqlarini boshqarish uchun kritik muhimlikka ega bo'lishi demakdir.

Bo'sh va to'la ma'lumotlar. Kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish natijasida adabiyotlar, mualliflar, janrlar va boshqa ma'lumotlar to'la va tog'ri ravishda saqlanadi, bu esa foydalanuvchilar uchun qidirish va ma'lumotlarga tez kirish imkoniyatlarini oshiradi.

Adabiyotlar uchun tahlil va reytinglar. Kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasida saqlangan adabiyotlar uchun foydalanuvchilar tahlillar, reytinglar va sharhlar qoldirishi mumkin. Bu esa boshqa foydalanuvchilarning kitoblarni tanlashda ularga yordam beradi va qulaylik yaratadi.

Foydalanuvchilar o'zlarining kitoblarga oid reyting va tanlovlari. Foydalanuvchilar kutubxonada ro'yhatdan o'tish orqali o'zlarining tanlagan adabiyotlar uchun reytinglar, tahlillar va izohlarni qoldirishi mumkin bo'ladi, shuningdek, ular tanlagan kitoblarni saqlash va ularni qidirish orqali o'zlarining ma'lumotlariga tez va oson kirish imkoniyatini oshiradi.

Tanlangan adabiyotlar bo'yicha personalizatsiya. Ma'lumotlar bazasi tizimi foydalanuvchilarga maslahat berish uchun ularning tanlagan adabiyotlar va tanab borishiga qarab, ularga shaxsiy tavsiyalar va qidiruv natijalari ko'rsatishi mumkin. Bu esa foydalanuvchilarga ularni qiziqarli adabiyotlarga yo'naltirish imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Tizimning takomillashtirilishi. Foydalanuvchilarning ma'lumotlarga tez va to'g'ri kirishini ta'minlash uchun tizimni yaxshi takomillashtirish keyinroq foyda beradi. Agar ma'lumotlar bazasi tizimi tezkor va ishni rahat bajaradigan bo'lsa, foydalanuvchilar qidirish natijalarini tezroq olishadi.

Xulosa. PHP dasturlash tili va MySQL ma'lumotlar bazasi tili yordamida yaratilgan tizim, foydalanuvchilarga adabiyotlar, mualliflar, janrlar va foydalanuvchilar to'plamlariga yorug'likli kirish imkoniyatlarini, interaktivlik funksiyalarini va foydalanishni osonlashtiradi. Foydalanuvchilar o'zlarining reytinglarini yaratishi, ko'rsatmalarini qoldirishi va kitoblarga berilgan reaksiyalarni o'qishlari va qidirishlari orqali o'zlarining tanlab olishlari qulay bo'ladi.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirishning afzalliklari o'z ichiga PHP va MySQL dasturlarining avtomatizatsiya imkoniyatlari, foydalanuvchilar interaktivlik imkoniyatlari, foydalanish va qidirish tezligi va qulayligini oladi. Shuningdek, avtomatik tuzilish va to'g'ri ma'lumotlarni saqlash imkoniyatini ta'minlaydi.

Bunday tizimning kamchiliklari esa xavfsizlik muammo, tekshirish va ta'mirlash, texnik yangilanishlar bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Xavfsizlik, ma'lumotlar to'g'risidagi tekshirish va texnik yangilanishlar uchun muhim muammolardir.

Kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish jarayoni natijasida yuqoridagi kutilayotgan natijalar adabiyotlar mavzusida foydalanuvchilarga qidirish, ma'lumotlarga tez kirish va shaxsiy tavsiyalarni olishda osonlik va qulaylik yaratishga imkon beradi. Buning natijasida kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasi foydalanuvchilar o'rtasida mashhurlik va qo'llanish darajasini oshiradi.

Ushbu adabiyotlar, kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish va boshqarish sohasidagi eng muhim mavzularni tahlil qilishda yordam beradi. Bu kitoblar, ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish, boshqarish va rivojlantirish jarayonlarini tushuntiradi va bu sohadagi ko'nikmalarni tajriba etish uchun yaxshi manbal sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Umumiy xulosada, kutubxona ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirishning muhim bo'lsa-da, uni yaratish jarayonida xavfsizlik, tekshirish va texnik o'zgarishlar bilan bog'liq muammolar ko'rinadi. Shu sababli, tizim dasturini takomillashtirish jarayonida bu muammolar va kamchiliklar hal etilishi kerakligi muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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AGROSANOAT KLASTERLARINI RAQAMLI BOSHQARISHNING IQTISODIY TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya. Hozirda O‘zbekistonda agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy tahlilini olib borish zarur hisoblanadi. Negaki hozirgi tez rivojlanayotgan vaqtda Yangi O‘zbekistonni 2022-2030 yillarga mo‘ljallangan taraqqiyot strategiyasi haqidagi Prezidentimizning farmonlarida va boshqa materiallarda iqtisodiyotimizni rivojlantirish ko‘rsatilgan. Maqolaning maqsadi, agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini, afzalliklarini va kamchiliklarini baholashdan iborat. Maqolaning natijalariga ko‘ra, agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiyotimizga pozitiv ta‘siri bor, lekin uning rivojlanishini cheklab turadigan bir qator muammolar ham mavjud. Maqolada ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun tavsiyalar va takliflar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Agrosanoat klasterlari, raqamli boshqarish, iqtisodiy tahlil, iqtisodiy samaradorlik, qo‘shilgan qiymat zanjiri

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF NUMERICAL MANAGEMENT OF AGROINDUSTRIAL CLUSTER

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Annotation. Currently, it is necessary to carry out an economic analysis of the digital management of agro-industrial clusters in Uzbekistan. Because at the time of rapid development, the development of our economy is indicated in the decrees of the President on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2030 and other materials. The purpose of the article is to assess the economic efficiency, advantages and disadvantages of digital management of agro-industry clusters. According to the results of the article, the digital management of agro-industry clusters has a positive effect on our economy, but there are also a number of problems that limit its development. Provides recommendations and suggestions for overcoming these problems.

Keywords: Agro-industry clusters, flow management, economic analysis, economic efficiency, added value chain.

Kirish. Agrosanoat klasterlari - bu qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtirish, qayta ishlash va sotish jarayonlarini bir xil hududda jamlangan tashkilotlar majmuasi hisoblanadi. Agrosanoat klasterlari iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlash, eksport imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish, qishloq aholisining daromadini oshirish va turmush sifatini yaxshilash maqsadida yaratilgan. Agrosanoat klasterlarni boshqarishning zamonaviy usuli sifatida raqamli boshqarish tushunchasi kiritilgan. Raqamli boshqarish - bu axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanib, ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini, mahsulotlarni va xizmatlarni nazorat qilish, optimallashtirish va avtomatlashtirish jarayonidir. Raqamli boshqarishning afzalliklari orasida ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish, xarajatlarni kamaytirish, sifatni yaxshilash, qo'shilgan qiymat zanjirini kuchaytirish, mijozlarga moslashtirish, raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish va boshqalar sanaladi. Bu maqolada agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy tahlili olib borilgan. Maqolaning maqsadi, agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini, afzalliklarini va kamchiliklarining tahlilidan iborat.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. Klasterlar nazariyasi bo'yicha rus olimlari ham o'rgangan bo'lib, amaliyotga doir ko'lab loyihalar ishlab chiqishgan. Bu amaliy nazariyalar mamlakat va korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini va iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda yordam bergan.

Agrosanoat klasterlarini raqamli boshqarishni baholash mavzusidagi maqolada mehnat, moddiy va moliyaviy resurslaridan samaradorli foydalanishiga, ichki va tashqi bozorlarni sifatli mahsulotlar bilan ta'minlanishiga erishiladi. Shu sababli, biz ushbu masalani tadqiqot qilish uchun Andijon viloyatini tanlab olingan va agrosanoat klasterlariga quyidagicha ta'rif berilgan. Agrosanoat klasteri – bu qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtiruvchi, ularni chuqur qayta ishlovchi va iste'molchilarga sifatli mahsulot yetkazib beruvchi tarmoqlar majmuidir.

Agrosanoat klasterlarini raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi O'zbekiston Respublikasi misolida. Bu maqolada O'zbekistonda agrosanoat klasterlarini raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishning yo'llari va vositalari, shuningdek, ularning iqtisodiyotga ta'sirini baholashning usullari va metodlari haqida tahlil qilinadi. Bu maqola maqolaning amaliy qismini tahlil qilishda foydali manba hisoblanadi.

Agrosanoat klasterlarini raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy tahlili xalqaro tajribalar va O'zbekiston uchun imkoniyatlar. Bu maqolada agrosanoat klasterlarini raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy tahlilini olib borish uchun xalqaro standartlar va metodologiyalar, shuningdek, dunyoning turli mamlakatlarida agrosanoat klasterlarini raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi va ta'siri

haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Bu maqola maqolaning nazariy qismini tahlil qilishda foydali manba hisoblanadi.

Afzaliklari. Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish, xarajatlarni kamaytirish, sifatni yaxshilash, qo'shilgan qiymat zanjirini kuchaytirish, mijozlarga moslashtirish, raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish va boshqa ko'plab iqtisodiy foydalarni ta'minlaydi¹².

Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarining yetishtirilishi, qayta ishlanishi va sotilishi jarayonlarini bir xil hududda jamlash orqali, transport, logistika, marketing, moliyaviy va boshqa xizmatlarni optimallashtirish, ularning sifatini oshirish va ularning xarajatlarini kamaytirish imkonini beradi³.

Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarining sifati va xavfsizligini nazorat qilish, ularning standartlarga va sertifikatlariga mosligini ta'minlash, ularning eksport imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish, ularning bozor ehtiyojlariga moslashtirish va ularning narxlarini stabilizatsiya qilishga yordam beradi .

Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo'jaligi sohasida zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini, shu jumladan, aniqlash, kuzatish, nazorat, avtomatlashtirish, ma'lumotlar bazasi, elektron hukumat, elektron tijorat va boshqalarini joriy etish orqali, innovatsion faoliyatni rag'batlantirish, ilm-fan yutuqlarini amalga oshirish va tijoratlashtirishga imkon yaratadi .

Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtiruvchilar, qayta ishlovchi korxonalar, eksportyorlar, davlat organlari, banklar, konsalting tashkilotlari, ilmiy-tadqiqot markazlari va boshqa zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali, ishlab chiqarish, qayta ishlash va sotish jarayonlarini bir xil platformada birlashtirish, ularning o'zaro hamkorlik va aloqalarini oshirish, ularning iqtisodiy faoliyatini shaffoflashtirish va nazorat qilishni ta'minlaydi .

Kamchiliklari. Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo'jaligi sohasida zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish uchun katta miqdordagi moliyaviy, texnik, kadrov va boshqa resurslarni talab qiladi, shuningdek, ularning ishonchli, xavfsiz va samarali ishlashi uchun qonuniy, normativ, standart va boshqa sharoitlarni yaratishni talab qiladi .

Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtiruvchilar, qayta ishlovchi korxonalar, eksportyorlar va boshqa ishtirokchilarning raqamli texnologiyalarga moslashtirish, ularni o'rganish va qo'llash, ular bilan ishlashga doimiy ehtiyoj borligini anglatadi, bu esa ularning qo'shimcha xarajatlarini, vaqtlarini va harakatliliklarini talab qiladi .

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Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlarining sifati va xavfsizligini nazorat qilish, ularning standartlarga va sertifikatlarga mosligini ta‘minlash, ularning eksport imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish, ularning bozor ehtiyojlariga moslashtirish va ularning narxlarini stabilizatsiya qilishga yordam beradi .

Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo‘jaligi sohasida zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini, shu jumladan, aniqlash, kuzatish, nazorat, avtomatlashtirish, ma‘lumotlar bazasi, elektron hukumat, elektron tijorat va boshqalarini joriy etish orqali, innovatsion faoliyatni rag‘batlantirish, ilm-fan yutuqlarini amalga oshirish va tijoratlashtirishga imkon yaratadi .

Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtiruvchilar, qayta ishlovchi korxonalar, eksportyorlar, davlat organlari, banklar, konsalting tashkilotlari, ilmiy-tadqiqot markazlari va boshqa zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali, ishlab chiqarish, qayta ishlash va sotish jarayonlarini bir xil platformada birlashtirish, ularning o‘zaro hamkorlik va aloqalarini oshirish, ularning iqtisodiy faoliyatini shaffoflashtirish va nazorat qilishni ta‘minlaydi .

Natijalar. Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlarining ishlab chiqarish, qayta ishlash va sotish jarayonlarini bir xil hududda jamlash orqali, transport, logistika, marketing, moliyaviy va boshqa xizmatlarni optimallashtirish, ularning sifatini oshirish va ularning xarajatlarini kamaytirish imkonini beradi.

Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlarining sifati va xavfsizligini nazorat qilish, ularning standartlarga va sertifikatlarga mosligini ta‘minlash, ularning eksport imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish, ularning bozor ehtiyojlariga moslashtirish va ularning narxlarini stabilizatsiya qilishga yordam beradi.

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Agrosanoat klasterlarni raqamli boshqarish, qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtiruvchilar, qayta ishlovchi korxonalar, eksportyorlar, davlat organlari, banklar, konsalting tashkilotlari, ilmiy-tadqiqot markazlari va boshqa zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali, ishlab chiqarish, qayta ishlash va sotish jarayonlarini bir xil platformada birlashtirish,

ularning o‘zaro hamkorlik va aloqalarini oshirish, ularning iqtisodiy faoliyatini shaffoflashtirish va nazorat qilishni ta’minlaydi.

Xulosa. Raqamli boshqarish orqali agrosanoat klasterlari qishloq xo‘jaligiga mo‘ljallangan yerlardan, suv resurslaridan, ekinlar holatidan samarali foydalanish, qo‘shilgan qiymat zanjirini yaratish, mahsulotlarni ichki va tashqi bozorlarga yo‘naltirish, zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish, hosildorlikni oshirish, manfaatdorlikni ta’minlash, qishloq ahlining turmush sharoitini yaxshilash kabi ustuvor yo‘nalishlarda yuqori natijalar ko‘rsatadi.

Raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy tahlili uchun qishloq xo‘jaligi sohasida zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish samaradorligini, chorva mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarishning iqtisodiy muvofiqligini, iste’molchilarning faolligini va boshqa iqtisodiy ko‘rsatkichlarni tahlil qiladigan zamonaviy "Aqlli chorvachilik" texnologiyasini amalga oshirada yordam beradi.

Raqamli boshqarishning iqtisodiy tahlili uchun O‘zbekiston Respublikasi agrosanoat majmui va qishloq xo‘jaligida raqamlashtirish tizimini rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida 2020-yil 17-dekabrda 794-son qarorida ko‘rsatilganidek loyihalarni amalga oshirish, monitoring va hisobot berish tizimini takomillashtirish, qishloq xo‘jaligini boshqarishning zamonaviy usuli - klasterlar tizimi bo‘yicha qonunchilikni takomillashtirish, davlat-xususiy sheriklik shartlari asosida maqsadli loyihalarni joriy etish kabi vazifalarni bajaradi.

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ONLAYN KUNDALIKLARNI YURITISH UCHUN BLOG PLATFORMASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH

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Anatatsiya. Ushbu maqola onlayn kundaliklarni yuritish uchun blog platformasini ishlab chiqish haqida. Onlayn kundaliklar, bugungi dunyoda axborot almashish va ma'lumot olishning o'rtacha usuli bo'lib, ularning ahamiyati juda yuqori. Ular, insonlarga yangiliklarni tezda etkazish, ma'lumot olish va ma'lumotni ulashish imkoniyatini beradi. Veb-sayt yaratish Odatda, video chatni rivojlantirish reklama yoki pullik sms-xabarlar uchun maxsus yaratilgan pullik saytlarni o'z ichiga olishi va boshqa shaxsiy blogni yuritish uchun ma'lumotlar berilgan

Kalit so'zlar: Ma'lumotlar tizimi, internet resurslari, ma'lumot olish, ta'lim, tizimni boshqarish, blog, xavfsizlik, URL, online kundalik, online platforma, Ma'lumot analitikasi, avtomatlashtirish, veb-sayt, internet-bloglar.

DEVELOPMENT OF A BLOG PLATFORM FOR ONLINE DIARY

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Abstract. This article is about the development of a blog platform for keeping online diaries. Online diaries are a medium way of sharing and obtaining information in today's world, and their importance is very high. They enable people to quickly deliver news, get information and share information. Creating a website Usually, video chat development includes paid sites created specifically for advertising or paid SMS messages, and other information is provided for running a personal blog.

Keywords: Information system, Internet resources, information retrieval, education, system management, blog, security, URL, online diary, online platform, Information analytics, automation, website, Internet blogs

Kirish. Ba'zi odamlar onlayn kunlik veb-sayt o'rniga veb-blog yozishni tanlaydi. Bloglash - bu Internetdagi eng katta harakat. So'nggi yillarda Internet-bloglar eng mashhur mashg'ulotga aylandi. Onlayn kundaliklari tufayli odamlar ish topadilar, yangi do'stlar orttiradilar. Biroq, yangi paydo bo'layotgan blog egasi qayerdan boshlashni bilishi qiyin bo'lishi mumkin. Bugungi kunda sayyoramizning har o'ninchi aholisi o'zlarining kundaliklariga ega. Veb-sayt yaratishda har bir blog egasi o'ziga xos maqsadlarga ega. Hozirda pul ishlash uchun video chat bilan o'z veb-saytingizni yaratish dolzarbdir. Veb-sayt yaratish Odatda, video chatni rivojlantirish reklama yoki pullik sms-xabarlar uchun maxsus yaratilgan pullik saytlarni o'z ichiga oladi Dasturchilar bloglarning ommabopligini angladilar va hozirda ko'plab serverlar mavjud, ular orqali har kim o'z sahifasini yaratishi mumkin. Veb-blog yoki blog - butun veb-saytni yaratish va uni yangilab turish vaqti bo'lmagan odamlar uchun ajoyib. Ko'plab saytlar o'z bloglarini o'z serverlarida yozishga imkon beradi. Bitta narsa qilish kerak, ro'yxatdan o'tish va yozishni boshlash. Yangilanish bir necha daqiqada osongina amalga oshiriladi. Ushbu saytlarning ba'zilari siz dastlab saytga kirmasdan kundalik yozuvlarni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ish stoli orqali yuklash imkonini beruvchi dasturiy ta'minotga ega. Ular yangilanishi va ulardan foydalanish oson bo'lgan onlayn bloglarni taklif qilishadi. Kundalik veb-sayt yoki blog siz uchun eng yaxshisi bo'ladimi - bu fikr. Agar siz onlayn jurnalga ega bo'lishni istasangizda, veb-saytni yaratish va yangilash uchun vaqtingiz yo'q bo'lsa, bloglarni saytlarga qarating va siz eng yaxshi ko'rgan narsalarni tanlang. Agar siz nafaqat o'zingizning emas, balki sizning kimligingizni tasvirlaydigan biror narsalarni xohlasangiz, onlayn kunlik veb-sayti borishning eng yaxshi usuli bo'lishi mumkin. Onlayn jurnallar blogdan ko'ra ko'proq shaxsiydir, chunki siz faqatgina kiritgan narsalaringizdan ko'proq narsani qo'shasiz. Sizning saytingizda sizning saytingizdagi narsalarni ruhiy holatni aks ettiruvchi tasvirlar bilan to'ldirishlarini odamlarga ayta boshlaydigan asosiy sahifa mavjud. O'quvchiga kimdir va sizning saytingizda ko'rishni kutadigan biografiya sahifasini yaratasiz. Sizning qiziqishlaringiz bo'yicha yoki sizning saytingizni to'ldirish uchun fotoalbom ham sizda maqola bo'lishi mumkin. Agar onlayn jurnalni yaratishdan qo'rqasangiz, do'stlaringiz va oilangiz uni topib, uni o'qib chiqishi mumkin, deb o'ylamang. Ko'pgina onlayn-diaristlar soxta ismlardan foydalanadilar, shuning uchun hech kim ularning kimligini bilmaydi. Shuningdek, sayt soxta nomlari bilan elektron pochta manzilini ishlatishadi, shuning uchun ular saytni kuzatib bo'lmaydi.

Ba'zi odamlar qarama-qarshi narsalarga ega. Ular o'zlarining saytlari uchun parollardan foydalanadilar, chunki ular begonalarning nima yozganlarini

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o‘qishni xohlamaydilar. Buning o‘rniga ular biladigan do‘stlariga URL va parollarni beradi. O‘zingizning kunlik ma’lumotingizni onlayn tarzda yozish sizni g‘aroyib inson qilmaydi. Bu sizga o‘zingizni, sizning oilangiz va manfaatlaringiz haqida ma’lumot berish uchun sizni veb-sayt yaratmoqchi bo‘lgan odamni yaratadi. Bu sizni hayotingizni yangi, zamonaviy tarzda kuzatib borishni xohlaydigan va boshqa odamlarning uni o‘qigan va ehtimol ilhomlantirgan bo‘lsa, bunga qarshi kelmaydigan odamni yaratadi.

Adabiyotlar taxlili va metodologiya. Onlayn kundaliklarni yuritish uchun blog platformasini ishlab chiqish mavzusida adabiyotlar taxlili va metodologiyani o‘rganish uchun quyidagi yo‘nalishlarga e’tibor qaratishingiz mumkin: Blog Platformalari Haqida Umumiy Ma’lumotlar: Blog platformalarining qanday ishlashini va ularning asosiy xususiyatlarini tushuntiradigan adabiyotlar va onlayn manbalar. Dizayn va UX: Blog dizayni, foydalanuvchi tajribasi (UX), foydalanuvchilar bilan qanday aloqalar yaratish, navigatsiya va interfeysning qulayligi haqida adabiyotlar. Blog platformasining qanday rivojlanishi uchun uni qanday qilib dastlabki qadamlar bilan boshlash kerakligini tushuntiradigan adabiyotlar. Ma’lumotlar Analitikasi: Blogning ma’lumotlarini tahlil qilish, foydalanuvchilar to‘g‘risida tahlil va ma’lumotlarni qanday foydalanishga olib kelish haqida adabiyotlar. Tadbirkorlik va Marketing: Blog platformasini ommaviy tadbirkorlik va marketing vositalari orqali keng doirada reklama qilish va tashriflarini oshirish bo‘yicha adabiyotlar. Bu yo‘nalishlarda adabiyotlar va metodologiya bilan o‘zlashtirilgan o‘quv-materiallardan foydalanishingiz muhim. Yangi ma’lumotlar va texnologiyalar chiqishidan oldin, yangilanishlarni kuzating va zamonaviy adabiyotlarni izlab topishimiz muhim. Foydalanuvchilar bilan qanday hamkorlik qilish, ularning takliflarini qabul qilish va ularning talablariga javob berish haqida metodologiyalar. Bu mavzular sizga blog platformasini muvaffaqiyatli boshqarish va o‘rganishda yordam berishi kutiladi. Har bir yo‘nalishni tushunish va amalga oshirish, saytning rivojlanishini va foydalanuvchilarning qiziqtirishini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Shaxsiy blogingiz uchun saytni qanday tanlash kerak? Bu savolga javob beradigan bo‘lsak : Agar siz juda ko‘p bezovta qilmasdan tezda boshlashni istasangiz, bloglar uchun tayyor saytlarni qidirib toping. Masalan, LiveJournal yoki Tumblr. Agar siz ushbu masala bo‘yicha jiddiy munosabatda bo‘lishni istasangiz, sizda allaqachon blog tushunchasi, toifalar va postlar uchun g‘oyalar mavjud, keyin saytingizni yarating, domen nomini ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazing va WordPress yoki Vigbo kabi platformalardan foydalaning. Agar siz trendli bo‘lishni istasangiz, Telegram kanalini yarating. U erda blogni loyihalashtirish va

boshqarish imkoniyatlari cheklangan, ammo hozirgi kunda barcha rivojlangan jamoatchilik ushbu saytga murojaat qilmoqda. Agar sizga blog kerakligiga ishonchingiz komil bo‘lmasa, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda yozishni boshlang. Bu eng oson narsa. Sizda allaqachon auditoriya bor, ularning ko‘pchiligini shaxsan bilasiz, sizning xabarlaringiz odatiy bo‘lmagan narsa bo‘lmaydi. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar postlarning sifati va davomiyligi jihatidan unchalik talabchan emas.

Muhokama va natijalar. “Blog”, “blogger” va “bloggerlik” kabi so‘zlarning dunyoga kelganiga hech qancha bo‘lmay, kundalik hayotimizga jadal sur‘atlar bilan kirib keldi. Bloglar esa o‘z navbatida “fuqarolik jurnalistikasi” degan tushunchani yuzaga keltirdi. Endi jurnalistika sohasiga ishtiyoqi baland, mutaxassis bo‘lmaganlar ham havaskor jurnalist sifatida internetda o‘z shaxsiy bloglariga ega bo‘lishi, axborot tarqatuvchi sifatida faoliyat yuritishi, o‘zi guvohi bo‘lgan voqealarni yoritish imkoniyatiga ega bo‘ldi. Bloggerlik asli nima? Qachon, qayerdan kelib chiqqan? Ilk bloggerlar kimlar va ilk bloglar qanday faoliyat yuritgan? Blogning funktsiya va turlari qanday? Jahonda va O‘zbekistonda bloggerlarni rag‘batlantiruvchi qanday tanlovlar mavjud? Bloggerlikning yutuqlari va imkoniyatlari? “Blog” atamasi “web blog”¹ (voqealar internet-jurnali, internet kundalik, onlayn-kundalik) so‘zidan kelib chiqqan bo‘lib, internetda nashr qilingan muhokama yoki axborot sayti hisoblanadi. Blogda muntazam yozib boriladi va u matn, rasmlar yoki multimediyadan iborat bo‘ladi. Bloglarning o‘ziga xos jihati – bu ularning qisqaliligi, vaqt qiymatiga ega ekanligi va teskari xronologik tartibda joylashishi, ya’ni oxirgi chop etilgan maqola (post, blogpost) eng tepada turadi. 2009-yilgacha bloglar, asosan, yakka mualliflar tomonidan yuritilgan. Keyinchalik bloglar kichik guruhlar tomonidan ham yuritilib, asosan, bir yo‘nalishdagi mavzular yoritilgan. Bunday bloglar ko‘p muallifli bloglar, ya’ni jamoaviy bloglar (multi-author blogs) deb ataladi. Jamoaviy bloglar internetda gazeta-jurnallar, boshqa media nashrlar, universitetlar, “ThinkTank”lar (tahliliy markazlar), advokatlik guruhlar va kichik institut saytlarining tarkibiga blog foydalanuvchilarini jalb qilish va ko‘paytirish maqsadida tashkil qilinadi. Blog nima, degan savolga mutahassislar quyidagicha ta’rif berishgan: Ilk bloglardan biri “Scripting News” blogining muallifi Dev Vayner “Garvard Universiteti bloglari: blogni nima blog qiladi” (2003-yil 23-may) nomli maqolasida blogga shunday ta’rif beradi: “Blog – matn, rasmlar, media ob’ekt va ma’lumotlarning xronologik tartibda ketma ket joylashgan ko‘rinishi”. U o‘z fikrini Weblogs yangiliklari saytida chop etgan “Bloglar tarixi” nomli maqolasida rivojlantirib, deydi: “Bloglar gid yordamida bilib boradigan davomiy sayohatning

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bir ko‘rinishidir. Bu yerda tanlash mumkin bo‘lgan bir nechta qo‘llanmalar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning har biri o‘z auditoriyasiga ega”

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo‘lsak bir mutaxxasis, Debbi Veyl, bu atamani keng ma’nodan tushunadi va o‘z fikrini quyidagicha bildiradi: “Blog – o‘z ishonchli taassurotlarini, fikrlarini tahrirlanmagan shakli; tez-tez yangilanib turadigan ma’lumotlarning onlayn jurnali; o‘z o‘quvchilari yordamida yangi jamiyat yaratishning bir yo‘li; talabalarga qanday yozishni o‘rgatish vositasi; mijozlar bilan munosabat o‘rnatishning yangi yo‘li; yirik kompaniyalarda malaka oshirishning yangi shakli; ishsizlarni band qilish yo‘li” deb javob beradi. Demak, guvohi bo‘lganimizdek, blog bugun onlayn-kundalik darajasidan o‘sib, yirik ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida shakllanib ulgurdi. Bloging ommalashishidan oldin virtual jamiyatda boshqa shakllar ham mavjud bo‘lgan Hozirgi ko‘rinishdagi bloglar internetdan foydalanuvchilar o‘z hayotlarini yoritib turishadigan onlayn kundaliklardan kelib chiqqan. Ular kundalik yurituvchilar, jurnalistlar, jurnal yurituvchilar deb atalgan. Bloglarni o‘qish hamda ularga mualliflik qilish – bular ikkalasi ikki xil jarayon hisoblanadi. Blogning yana bir imkoniyati bo‘lmish kommunikatsiya orqali blogning muallifi bevosita muloqotda bo‘la olmagan kishilar bilan aloqada bo‘lib turadi. Oxirt oqibat shaxsiy blokni yaratish, u bilan ishlash, rivojlantirish, kerakli darajaga olib chiqish uchun eng samarali usul bu shaxsiy blokni yuritib kelayotgan tajribali mutaxxasis bilan fikr almashish va inung maslahatlari asosida o‘z shaxsiy blokini yuritish kerak degan xulosaga kelinadi.

Adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

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- 2."The Art of Social Media: Power Tips for Power Users" - by Guy Kawasaki and Peg Fitzpatrick (2014, Portfolio)
- 3."Blogging All-in-One For Dummies" - by Susan Gunelius (2012, Wiley)
- 4."Content Rules: How to Create Killer Blogs, Podcasts, Videos, Ebooks, Webinars (and More) That Engage Customers and Ignite Your Business" - by Ann Handley and C.C. Chapman (2011, Wiley)
- 5."Crush It!: Why NOW Is the Time to Cash In on Your Passion" - by Gary Vaynerchuk (2009, HarperStudio)
- 6."Platform Revolution: How Networked Markets Are Transforming the Economy and How to Make Them Work for You" - by Geoffrey G. Parker, Marshall W. Van Alstyne, and Sangeet Paul Choudary (2016, W. W. Norton & Company)
- 7."The Lean Startup: How Today's Entrepreneurs Use Continuous Innovation to Create Radically Successful Businesses" - by Eric Ries (2011, Crown Business)
- 8."Contagious: How to Build Word of Mouth in the Digital Age" - by Jonah Berger (2013, Simon & Schuster)

SHINAM XONADONLAR TOPUVCHI WEB PLATFORMALARNING ANALITIK TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola Airbnb va Booking platformalarini tahlil qilish orqali, bizga bu platformalar tomonidan taqdim etilayotgan xizmatlar haqida aniq tasavvur beradi. Shuningdek, bu platformalar orqali bizga qanday imkoniyatlar mavjudligini ham ko'rib chiqamiz. Bu narsalar bizga, bizning safarlarimizni qanday rejalashtirishimiz kerakligi haqida tushuncha beradi. Bu esa, bizning safarlarimizni yanada qulay va samarali qiladi. Maqolada Airbnb va Booking platformalarining qanday ishlashini, ularning xususiyatlari va foydalanuvchilar uchun qanday imkoniyatlar yaratishini tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Booking.com, Airbnb, web platforma, texnologiya, to'lovlar, kompaniya, mehmonlar tahlili

ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF WEB PLATFORMS FOR FINDING APARTMENTS

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Abstract. By analyzing the Airbnb and Booking platforms, this article will give us a clear idea of the services offered by these platforms. We will also consider what opportunities are available to us through these platforms. These things give us insight into how we should plan our trips. This makes our trips more comfortable and efficient. The article analyzes how the Airbnb and Booking platforms work, their features and what opportunities they create for users.

Keywords: Booking.com, Airbnb, web platform, technology, payments, company, guest analysis.

Kirish. Turizm sohasi dunyoda zamonaviy menejment modellari va texnologiyalarining o‘rni ko‘proq ko‘zga tashlanmoqda. Booking.com va Airbnb kabi yirik web platformalar, bu sohadagi rivojlangan xizmatlarning eng muhim namunalaridan birini ta‘minlaydi. Ular turizm sektoriga yangi o‘zgarishlar kiritish, sayohatchilar va xizmat ko‘rsatuvchilar orasida ko‘proq aloqa muhiti yaratish va sayohatchilar uchun arzon va qulay mehmonxonalarni topishda ko‘maklashish bilan shug‘ullanishadi.

Booking.com va Airbnb o‘rtasidagi farq va o‘xshashliklar, ularning xizmat modellari, foydalanuvchilarga taqdim etilayotgan imkoniyatlar, va turizm sohasidagi o‘zgarishlar muhim tahlillar mavzularini tashkil etadi.

Airbnb - bu qisqa va uzoq muddatli uyda qolish va tajribalar uchun onlayn bozorni boshqaradigan Amerika kompaniyasi. Kompaniya broker sifatida ishlaydi va har bir bron qilish uchun komissiya oladi. Kompaniya 2008 yilda Brayan Cheski, Neytan Blechark va Jo Gebbiya tomonidan tashkil etilgan. Airbnb o‘zining asl nomi Air Bedand Breakfast.com ning qisqartirilgan versiyasidir. Airbnb - qisqa muddatli uy-joy ijarasi bo‘yicha eng mashhur kompaniya

Booking.com - 1996 yilda Amsterdam (Niderlandiya) da tashkil etilgan onlayn mehmonxona bron qilish tizimi . 2005 yilda tizim Amerikaning The Priceline Group kompaniyasi tomonidan 133 000 000 dollarga sotib olindi (nomi o‘zgartirildi Booking Holdings NASDAQ : BKNG 2018 yil fevralida), Yevropa bozoriga e‘tibor qaratildi . Bosh qarorgohi Amsterdamda joylashgan.

Sayohat sektori, texnologiya va internetning rivojlanishi bilan birga o‘zgarib borayotgan soha. Airbnb va Booking, bu sohadagi eng katta va eng tanilgan platformalar hisoblanadi. Ular, mehmonxonalar va kvartiralar uchun ijaraga berish xizmati ko‘rsatish orqali dunyoning turli joylarida joylashgan milyonlab mehmonxonalar va kvartiralar uchun ijaraga berish xizmati ko‘rsatadi.

Bu maqolada, biz bu ikkala platformaning xususiyatlari, foydalanuvchilarining soni, xizmat sifati va boshqa ko‘rsatkichlar tahlil qilamiz. Shuningdek, Airbnb va Booking platformalarining foydalanuvchilar uchun qanday imkoniyatlar yaratishini ham o‘rganamiz.

Bu tahlil, bizga bu platformalar tomonidan taqdim etilayotgan xizmatlar haqida aniq tasavvur beradi. Shuningdek, bu platformalar orqali bizga qanday imkoniyatlar mavjudligini ham ko‘rib chiqamiz. Bu narsalar bizga, bizning safarlarimizni qanday rejalashtirishimiz kerakligi haqida tushuncha beradi. Bu esa, bizning safarlarimizni yanada qulay va samarali qiladi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiya:

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiya uchun quyidagi ma'lumotlarni ko'rib chiqishingiz mumkin:

1. **Neutrality may matter: sentiment analysis in reviews of Airbnb, Booking, and Couchsurfing in Brazil and USA:** Bu maqolada Airbnb, Booking va Couchsurfing platformalarining sharhlarini sentiment tahlili orqali o'rganishni ko'rib chiqishgan. Ular Brazil va AQSh shaharlarida mehmonxona xizmatlarini taqdim etuvchi platformalar tomonidan yozilgan sharhlarni yig'ib olganlar va ularda sentiment tahlilini amalga oshirganlar. Ular topgan natijalariga ko'ra, ulash ekonomikasi sharhlari, an'anaviy ekonomikaga nisbatan ancha ko'proq ijobiy bo'lishi mumkin.

2. **End-to-End Predictive Analysis on AirBnB Listings Data:** Bu maqolada Airbnb ro'yxatlarining ma'lumotlarini tahminlash uchun to'liq jarayon tahlil qilinadi. Bu maqolada CRISP-DM (CRoss Industry Standard Process for Data Mining) nomli mashhur jarayon modeli yordamida ochiq manba Airbnb ro'yxatlarining ma'lumotlari uchun to'liq tahminlash tahlili beriladi.

3. **Big data and analytics in hospitality and tourism: a systematic literature review:** Bu tadqiqot Scopus va Web of Science ma'lumotlar bazalarida 31-Dekabr 2020gacha chop etilgan ilmiy maqolalar asosida tuzilgan sistemali adabiyot sharhi asosida tuzilgan. Natijalar bibliometrik usullar, tarmoq tahlili va mavzu modeli yordamida tahlil qilingan.

4. **Big data analytics and hotel guest experience: a critical analysis of online reviews:** Bu tadqiqot Google Scholar'da 2020 yil oxirigacha chop etilgan ilmiy jurnal maqolalariga asoslangan sistemali adabiyot sharhi asosida tuzilgan.

Bu ma'lumotlar sizning maqolangiz uchun yaxshi boshlang'ich manba bo'lishi mumkin. Bu ma'lumotlar yordamida siz Airbnb va Booking platformalarining analitik tahlilini olib borishingiz mumkin. Bu ma'lumotlar sizga platformalar tomonidan yaratilgan ma'lumotlarni qanday tahlil qilish, qanday xulosalar qilish va qanday yo'nalishlarni o'rganishga qaratish kerakligi haqida tushuncha berishi mumkin. Bu ma'lumotlar sizning maqolangiz uchun yaxshi boshlang'ich manba bo'lishi mumkin.

Airbnb va Booking - bu ikkala katta mehmonxona va kvartira ijarasi platformalaridir. Ularning analitik tahlili quyidagicha bo'ladi:

Airbnb:

- Airbnb dunyodagi 10 milliondan ortiq Airbnb va Vrbo ta'til uyining samaradorligini kuzatadi.
- AirDNA orqali Airbnb analitikasi, Airbnb bandlik darajasi, narxlar va investitsiya tadqiqotlari kabi qisqa muddatli ijaraga oid ma'lumotlarni tahlil qiladi.

- AirDNA's MarketMinder asbobining Airbnb analitikasi har qanday bozorda ta'til uyining daromadini oshirishga yordam beradi.
- Airbnb - bu \$75 milliardlik onlayn bozor, uylar/villalar/ shaxsiy xonalar ijarasi uchun va sayohat faoliyatlari uchun mo'ljallangan.
- Airbnb platformasi veb-sayt yoki mobil ilova orqali kirish mumkin.

Booking:

Booking haqida ma'lumot topish uchun qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar zarur. Bu platforma ham mehmonxonalar, kvartiralar va boshqa turar joylar uchun ijaraga berish xizmatlarini taklif qiladi. Ular ham o'zlarining o'ziga xos analitik tahlil asboblarini ishlatishadi.

Bu ikkala platforma ham mehmonxonalar va kvartiralar uchun ijaraga berish bo'yicha katta ma'lumotlar bazasiga ega. Ular shuningdek, foydalanuvchilar uchun osonlashgan booking jarayonini ham taklif qiladilar. Bu platformalar orqali xizmat ko'rsatuvchilar va mijozlar o'rtasidagi aloqa ham yaxshilashadi. Bu esa mijozlarning qulaylik darajasini oshiradi va ularning platformadan qayta foydalanish ehtimolliklarini oshiradi.

Bu ikkala platformaning analitik tahlilini o'rganish, ularning qanday ishlashini, qanday ma'lumotlarni to'plashini va bu ma'lumotlarni qanday tahlil qilishini tushunishga yordam beradi. Bu esa bizga ularning biznes modelini, mijozlar bilan aloqalarini va ularning xizmatlarini qanday takomillashtirishga qaratilgan strategiyalarini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Bu ma'lumotlar sizning maqolangiz uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Bu ikkala platforma orasidagi farqlar va o'xshashliklar, shuningdek ularning biznes modeli va mijozlar bilan aloqalarini qanday yaxshilashga qaratilgan strategiyalarini o'rganish sizning maqolangizga katta qo'shimcha qilishi mumkin.

Muhokama

Airbnb va Booking.com: Qaysi platforma qimmatroq?

Airbnb va Booking.com ikkalasi ham ijara egalaridan qabul qilingan bron uchun xizmat haqi miqdorini undiradilar. Shunday qilib, mezbon sifatida ikkala sayt xizmatlaridan foydalanish uchun qancha to'lov to'lashingizni bilish muhimdir.

Airbnb to'lovlari (shu jumladan, faqat xost to'lovi)

Airbnb ikki xil xizmat to'loviga ega: Split to'lovi va faqat Xost uchun to'lov. Split to'lovi xizmat to'lovi bo'lib, u bronlash umumiy narxining taxminan 14% dan 16% gacha to'laydigan mehmonlar va Airbnb'ga taxminan 3% to'laydigan mezbonlar o'rtasida taqsimlanadi. Faqat Airbnb Xostlari uchun to'lov

bronlash narxining 15% atrofida turadi, shu bilan birga mehmonlar uchun to'lov olinmaydi.

Garchi bu o'zgarish noqulay bo'lib tuyulsa-da, Airbnb bronlash stavkalarini oshirish uchun buni amalga oshirdi. Bu hisob-kitob paytida narxning 14% oshishiga hayron bo'lmagan mehmonlardan oldindan, yakuniy miqdorni undirishga asoslangan. Ushbu xarajatlarni qoplash uchun siz yuqoriroq kunlik tarifni olishingiz va qo'shimcha xizmatlarni taklif qilishingiz mumkin.

Booking.com xizmat haqi

Booking.com ko'chmas mulk egalaridan joylashuviga qarab 10% dan 25% gacha bo'lgan komissiya stavkasini oladi, o'rtacha stavka esa 15%. Ular mehmonlardan hech qanday komissiya olmaydilar. 15% yoki undan yuqori tekis stavka juda katta ko'rinishi mumkin.

Biroq, Booking.com shuningdek, mehmonlardan tozalash va sochiq haqi (agar mavjud bo'lsa) kabi qo'shimcha to'lovlarni olish imkonini beradi. Shunday qilib, tarifingizni oshirish va qo'shimcha xizmatlar uchun haq olish orqali komissiya narxini qaytarishingiz mumkin.

Booking.com qimmatroqmi?

Mulkingiz joylashuvi sizdan olinadigan Airbnb va Booking.com to'lovlarini belgilaydi, shuning uchun ikkala platforma ham yuqori narxlarni talab qilishi mumkin. Agar siz Split to'lovidan foydalanish huquqiga ega bo'lgan mamlakatda bo'lsangiz, bu siz uchun arzonroq narx strategiyasi deb o'ylashingiz mumkin. Split Fee formati foydaliroq bo'lishi mumkin, ammo ba'zi mehmonlar faqat hostlar ro'yxatini bron qilishni afzal ko'rishadi.

Biroq, ahvolga tushib qolgani shundaki, mehmonlaringiz chiqish paytida oladigan narx oshishi sababli bron qilish darajasi pasayishi mumkin. Faqat Xost uchun to'lov siz va mehmoningiz o'rtasida narxlarning shaffofligini ta'minlaydi va ko'proq bron qilishni rag'batlantiradi.

Booking.com ta'til ijarasi egalaridan o'rtacha 15% komissiya oladi. Bu Airbnb'da faqat Xost uchun to'lov bilan bir xil stavka, ya'ni Booking.com'da ro'yxatga olish Airbnb'dagi kabi taxminan bir xil narxga tushadi.

Xulosa

Airbnb va Booking ikkala platforma ham mehmonxona va kvartira ijarasi uchun katta xizmatlar hisoblanadi, lekin ularning yondashuvlari va foydalanuvchilar uchun taklif qiladigan imkoniyatlari farq qiladi.

Airbnb platformasi jamoatni qurishga va mehmonlar va mehmonxonalar orasidagi shaxsiy aloqalarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Ushbu platforma mehmonxonalariga mahalliy maslahatlar va tavsiyalar berishni rag'batlantiradi,

bu esa mehmonlar uchun eslatma qoldiradigan tajribalar yaratadi⁵. Airbnb ma'lumotlar ilmiyini mahsulotlarini takomillashtirish va marketingini yaxshilash uchun ishlatadi¹. Ular ma'lumotlarni mijozning ovozi sifatida ko'radilar va ma'lumotlar ilmiyini ushbu ovozning tarjimasini sifatida ko'radilar¹.

Booking.com esa samarali va qulaylikka qaratilgan, foydalanuvchilar uchun qidiruv va bron qilish jarayonlarini osonlashtiradi⁵.

Har bir platformaning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bor, shuning uchun foydalanuvchilar o'z ehtiyojlariga eng mos keladiganini tanlashlari kerak. Bu ikki platforma orasidagi farqlar va o'xshashliklar turizm sohasidagi analitik tahlil uchun muhim ma'lumotlar beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN STUDENTS LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: *This article discusses the role of the communicative approach in teaching English, in particular English for special purposes, and suggests methods for using this approach. The use of a communicative approach in all language skills, including grammatical skills, leads to effectiveness in teaching English. The choice of authentic materials, taking into account the needs and interests of students, also contributes to their progress in learning.*

Keywords: *communicative language learning, communicative approach, communicative competence, grammatical competence, authentic materials, method, the dialogue, language skills*

РОЛЬ КОММУНИКАТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА СТУДЕНТАМИ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается роль коммуникативного подхода в обучении английскому языку, в частности английскому языку для специальных целей, и предлагаются методы использования этого подхода. Использование коммуникативного подхода во всех языковых навыках, включая грамматические навыки, приводит к эффективности преподавания английского языка. Выбор аутентичных материалов с учетом потребностей и интересов учащихся также способствует их прогрессу в обучении.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативное изучение языка, коммуникативный подход, коммуникативная компетентность, грамматическая компетентность, аутентичные материалы, метод, диалог, языковые навыки.*

The essence of the communicative method is to create real communication situations. When recreating the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. The main goals of the communicative method were the development of communicative competencies (i.e., learning to communicate in a language) and the development of all four language skills in combination (reading, writing, listening and speaking). This was very different from other approaches, for example, from grammatical translation, where listening and speaking were given a minimum of attention. A very important advantage of the communicative method is that it has a huge variety of exercises: role-playing games, dialogues, simulation of real communication are used here. At first, the communicative method was rejected, but now it again occupies a leading position along with the traditional grammatical and translation method. Most teachers prefer these two methods, and they are often used in combination. Working in a lesson based on a communicative methodology can include various types of tasks, but their main characteristic is that they solve a practical problem: for example, buy movie tickets, make an order at a restaurant or decide where to go on vacation. In particular, the Liltwood scientist identifies two types of tasks in the lesson: those aimed at functional communication and those aimed at social communication.¹ The first group includes tasks such as comparing pictures to find similarities or differences, arranging events according to pictures in the correct order, filling in gaps on a map or drawing, following instructions or solving a problem. The second group includes conversations, dialogues, role-playing games, improvisations or debates. The Communicative Approach develops all language skills – from speaking and writing to reading and listening. Grammar is mastered in the process of communicating in a language: the student first remembers words, expressions, language formulas and only then begins to understand what they are in a grammatical sense. The goal is to teach the student to speak a foreign language not only fluently, but also correctly. The rules and meanings of new words are explained by the teacher using vocabulary familiar to the student, grammatical structures and expressions, using gestures and facial expressions, drawings and other visual aids. Computers with CD, Internet, TV programs, newspapers, magazines, etc. can also be used. All this helps to arouse

¹ Elukhina N.V. The role of discourse in intercultural communication and the methodology of formation of discursive competence. // IYASH. 2002, No. 3. pp. 9-13.

students' interest in the history, culture, and traditions of the country of the studied language. In the classroom, the teacher creates situations in which students communicate in pairs with each other, in groups. This makes the activity more diverse. Working in a group, students show speech independence. They can help each other, successfully correct the statements of the interlocutors. The teacher in the classroom assumes the functions of an organizer of communication, asks leading questions, pays attention to the original opinions of the participants, acts as an arbitrator in discussing controversial issues. The difference between communication is that instead of educational texts and dialogues specially adapted to the active vocabulary and grammar being studied, it uses imitation of real-life situations as the main technique, which are played out in the classroom in such a way as to cause maximum motivation for students to speak. So, instead of endlessly chewing over typical phrases from a textbook: "My name is Sopi. I live in Tashkent. I am a student", etc., students studying the topic of "Acquaintance" actually begin to actively get acquainted and discuss the issues they are interested in. The topics discussed are mainly those that students are familiar with in their native language: this makes it possible to focus specifically on the development of communicative abilities, that is, the ability to use the language spontaneously. Preferably, the topics should be "burning" – related either to the life of the students themselves, or to all aspects of modern life that are of interest to all (ecology, politics, music, education, etc.). In Western textbooks, especially at the level below Upper-Intermediate, you will hardly find such "topics" as Shakespeare's biography or achievements nuclear physics. Only at the senior levels are "bookish" and "scientific" styles introduced.

Unlike audio-lingual and other methods based on repetition and memorization, the communicative method sets exercises "with an open ending": students themselves do not know what their activities in the classroom will result in, everything will depend on reactions and answers.² New situations are used every day. This is how students' interest in classes is maintained: after all, everyone wants to communicate meaningfully on meaningful topics. Oral speech takes up most of the time in the lessons (although reading and writing are also given attention). At the same time, teachers talk less and listen more, only directing the activities of students. The teacher sets the exercise, and then, having "talked" the students, goes into the background and acts as an observer and

² Milrud R.P., Maksimova I.R. Modern conceptual principles of communicative foreign language teaching. // IYASH. 2000, No. 4. pp. 19-14.

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arbitrator. Preferably, he should use exclusively the language he is learning. The communicative method consists in likening the learning process to the communication process, more precisely, it is based on the fact that the learning process is a model of the communication process, albeit somewhat simplified, but adequate in basic parameters, similar to the real communication process. All that has been said above regarding the communicative method of teaching speaking in a foreign language allows us to assert that the subject of study in this case is speech activity in English. In this method, the allocation of speech speaking skills is clearly traced, and exercises are offered for their consistent formation. The modern communicative method is a harmonious combination of many ways of teaching foreign languages, being probably at the top of the evolutionary pyramid of various educational methods. The use of a communicative teaching method removes the language barrier. Grammar is mastered in the process of communicating in a language: the student first remembers words, expressions, language formulas and only then begins to understand what they are in a grammatical sense.

The purpose of teaching a foreign language at the present stage is the acquisition of communicative competence, the components of which are:

- Language competence – involves mastering a certain amount of formal language knowledge and related skills related to various aspects of the language – vocabulary, phonetics, grammar.
- Speech competence - the ability to build communication in such a way as to achieve goals, in possession of various techniques for receiving and transmitting information both orally and in writing, compensatory skills. (the strategy of one's own communication and the selection of language tools for solving communication problems)
- Sociocultural competence – willingness and desire to interact with others, self-confidence, the ability to put oneself in the place of another and cope with the current situation – social; the ability to choose language forms, use them and transform them in accordance with the context - sociolinguistic.

Currently, learning oral communication, in which speaking plays a primary role, is one of the most important aspects of language. Oral speech in general and speaking as an integral part of it come to the fore. Students, first of all, want to learn how to speak the language. Learning outcomes are primarily assessed by the ability to communicate, in particular the ability to speak dialogically. The creation

of a motivational base for teaching a foreign language is a necessary condition for the quality and success of learning and the formation of communicative competence.

Foreign language teachers are faced with the task of forming a personality that will be able to participate in intercultural communication. It is important to form a communicative competence that includes both linguistic and socio-cultural competence. Knowledge of the socio-cultural background is very important, because without it it is impossible to form a communicative competence, even within limited limits. Therefore, it is necessary to have an idea of the socio-cultural characteristics of the country of the language being studied. The study of culture and language carries not only general educational ideas, but also at the same time ensures the development of personality, supports the motivation of students. Teachers are faced with the task of forming positive motivation, it is necessary to link it with the cognitive interests of students, the need to master new knowledge, skills, and abilities.

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THE ROLES AND IMPORTANCE OF VOCABULARY IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *The article raises the problem of using dictionaries in the process of teaching a foreign language within the framework of language education. The author places special emphasis on active work with various dictionaries to optimize and intensify the process of mastering a foreign language.*

Keywords: *foreign language, dictionary, household level, learning bilingual dictionary, vocabulary, process, communication, methodologists*

РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СЛОВА В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация: *В статье поднимается проблема использования словарей в процессе обучения иностранному языку в рамках языкового образования. Особое внимание автор уделяет активной работе с различными словарями для оптимизации и интенсификации процесса освоения иностранного языка.*

Ключевые слова: *иностраннный язык, словарь, бытовой уровень, изучение двуязычного словаря, лексика, процесс, общение, методисты.*

The problem of learning foreign languages has been and remains very relevant. More and more methodologists are inclined to believe that nowadays, in addition to their native language, a person needs to know one or two foreign languages. They believe that bilingual education through the co-study of native and foreign languages is an important part of the modernization of the goals and content of the modern educational system. To communicate at the household level, it is now quite enough to know one or two of the most common languages,

for example, English, German or Spanish. Therefore, in many countries of the world, as a rule, two and sometimes more foreign languages are taught at school, which is quite enough to communicate with representatives of both European and Asian countries. As the famous author of many works on bilingualism, Scutnabb Kangas, said, it is impossible to study bilingualism and bilingual education without understanding what language is. Language is a means of communication (and not only), without which it would be impossible to exchange experience in various fields between nationalities. He believed that language is probably the only tool through which mutual understanding and interaction between representatives of various linguistic communities becomes possible. Hence, it is quite obvious that special attention should be paid to the problem of developing students' ability to effectively participate in intercultural communication.³ And in the conditions of secondary schools, one of the most appropriate ways to solve this issue is to focus on bilingual language education, where the main principle is the mandatory use of nationally oriented educational material. In this case, we mean nationally oriented material, both of the native language and the language of a foreign speaker. Therefore, in order for the process of learning a language and mastering the basics of intercultural communication to be fruitful, it is necessary to use the entire arsenal of reference material, that is, various dictionaries. Dictionaries play an important role in modern culture, they reflect the knowledge accumulated by society over the centuries. Dictionaries are used to describe and regulate language and help improve the correctness and expressiveness of the speaker's speech. The vocabulary of any living language is constantly changing and expanding. The appearance of new words reflects the development of modern science, culture and art, and unused words are marked as obsolete. The dictionary is an integral part of the culture of the nation, since many aspects of people's lives are recorded in it. Vocabulary must be learned in a system that is related to the properties of the human brain for memorizing logically organized material, analysis, synthesis and generalization. From all of the above, it is clear that a solid assimilation of vocabulary is required, which involves the performance of vocabulary work. And a dictionary is a universal learning tool that defines a word (its meaning), the key to correct pronunciation (transcription of words, stress), replenishes the stock of synonyms and antonyms, shows a particular word in context, clearly demonstrates the ways of word formation in

³ Karlinsky, A. E. Working with a dictionary in high school / A. E. Karlinsky. — Text: direct // Foreign languages at school. — 2011. — No. 4. — pp. 60-68.

the studied language. Therefore, it is important to teach students to use dictionaries to learn a foreign language, in this case English. Its use educates students in the need for independent and creative search for the words they need for speech activity, and significantly expands information about the richness of the vocabulary of the studied (English) language. Students should know how and what vocabulary to use in the classroom and beyond. There are several basic types of dictionaries that students can use: – standard monolingual dictionaries that are designed for people for whom the language being studied is their native language. – educational monolingual dictionaries that are necessary for all foreign language learners. – bilingual dictionaries that contain words in a foreign language and provide their translation into the student's native language and vice versa.⁴ Naturally, you should start with a bilingual dictionary, since it is intended to be only the key to understanding. As the student becomes more competent in the language being studied, he must move from a bilingual dictionary to an educational monolingual dictionary. According to the modern requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard, upon completion of studying the discipline "Foreign Language", students must possess a number of competencies, namely: communicative competence, that is, be able to formulate their thoughts, both orally and in writing, be able to maintain a dialogue with an interlocutor and utter a small monologue in a foreign language. Also, for productive communication, it is necessary to know about the features of statements due to their communicative tasks and the communication situation. And in order to achieve this goal, you need to spend more time working with the dictionary. The basis of each lesson should be the work on practicing correct pronunciation, on developing the skills to clearly and expressively present one's thought in oral speech, as well as work on enriching one's vocabulary and acquiring the skills to adequately, appropriately and competently (spelling competently) use words and phrases in a coherent statement. Work on the study of vocabulary material at school is of great educational and practical importance, as it expands students' knowledge of the language, introduces them to the unit of speech — in a word, is the main source of vocabulary enrichment. Vocabulary work helps to draw students' attention to the meaning and use of words, develops their need to search and select the necessary word for accurate expression of thought, a sense of language. And, as a result, through interest in the etymology of words, students become interested

⁴ Alqahtani, (2015). The importance of vocabulary in language learning and how to be taught

in the language as a whole. Time passes, everything changes, and the language also undergoes changes over the years. Therefore, the more often we turn to dictionaries, and preferably to authentic dictionaries, the better we will master foreign language, and it will be easier for us to communicate with a foreign speaker, both at the household level and on professional issues. Teaching rational methods of using a dictionary should not be in isolation from other sections of language work. On the contrary, learning to work with a dictionary should contribute to deepening and expanding knowledge in the field of grammar, phonetics, vocabulary and spelling. Using a dictionary is a successful and time—tested work that will help everyone who is interested in learning a foreign language to get closer to bilingualism, which is a very important aspect at this stage of society's development in difficult modern realities. So, the use of various types of dictionaries in the educational process is a prerequisite for successful mastery of foreign languages. It is working with the dictionary that gives us the opportunity to make the process of mastering a foreign language more qualitative and effective.

Vocabulary proficiency is often seen as a critical aspect of learning a foreign language, as limited vocabulary in a second language hinders successful communication. Given the importance of acquiring vocabulary, lexical knowledge occupies a central place in communicative competence and in mastering a second language. The relationship between vocabulary knowledge and language practice is complementary: vocabulary knowledge allows you to use language and vice versa. The use of language leads to an increase in vocabulary. The importance of vocabulary is demonstrated daily on and off campuses. In the classroom, the most successful students have the most adequate vocabulary. The study of lexical units plays a vital role in all language skills (for example, listening, speaking, reading and writing), in addition, it is argued that the acquisition of an adequate vocabulary is necessary for the successful use of a foreign language, since without an extensive vocabulary, the language learner will not be able to use the structures and functions that we use. perhaps he has learned to communicate intelligibly. Some studies have shown that readers learning a second language rely heavily on knowledge of vocabulary, and the lack of this knowledge is the main and greatest obstacle for readers. In the production process, when language learners have a meaning or concept that they want to express, they need to have a stock of words from which they can choose to express that meaning or concept. Many researchers claim that vocabulary is one of the most important, if not the most important component in learning a foreign language. Vocabulary

learning is a crucial aspect in language learning because languages are based on words. It is almost impossible to learn a language without words; even communication between people is based on words. Recent research shows that teaching vocabulary can be problematic, as many teachers are unsure of the best practice of teaching vocabulary and sometimes do not know where to start in order to focus on learning words. Both teachers and students agree that vocabulary acquisition is a central factor in language learning. Learning vocabulary is considered one of the most discussed parts of teaching English as a foreign language.

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BANKLARDA AXBOROT TIZIMLARINING DASTURIY TA'MINLANISHI

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Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda har kuni mamlakatimiz iqtisodiy rivojlanishida muhim omil bo'lgan yangiliklar paydo bo'lmoqda. Jahon bank-moliya tizimining jadal sur'atlarda rivojlanib borishi natijasida bank sohasida ham yangi zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalariga (AKT) yanada ko'proq ehtiyoj sezilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: «On-Line» rejimi, «Uzkart-EMV» milliy banklararo plastik kartochkalar to'lov tizimi, dasturiy ta'minot, plastik karta tizimi.

SOFTWARE FOR INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN BANKS

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Annotation. Today, news appears every day, which is an important factor in the economic development of our country. As a result of the rapid development of the global banking and financial system, the need for new modern information and communication technologies (ICT) is even stronger in the banking sector.

Key words: "On-Line" mode, national interbank payment system for plastic cards "Uzkart-EMV", software, plastic card system.

Kirish. 2015-yilda Islom Karimov Mamlakatimizni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirish yakunlariga bag'ishlangan Vazirlar Mahkamasining ma'ruzasida, zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida keng joriy etilishi va "Elektron hukumat" tiziminin rivojlantirilishi ustuvor ahamiyatga ega ekanligi ta'kidlandi. Jahon tajribasi ko'rsatadi ki, global iqtisodiyotda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, kompyuter va

telekommunikatsiya texnologiyalari asosida xizmatlar ko'rsatishning ko'rsatkichlarini oshirish muhimdir.

Muhokama va natijalar. O'zbekiston bank tizimida izchil va maqsadli islohotlar olib borilmoqda, chora-tadbirlar, bank-moliya xizmatlarini tubdan yaxshilashga doir qarorlar qabul qilinmoqda. Bu doirada, naqd pulsiz chakana to'lovlarning qabul qilish va hisob-kitoblar tizimini samarali hollantirish maqsadida, "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy bankining hisob-kitoblar kliring tizimi to'g'risida"gi Nizom ishlab chiqilgan va 2014-yil 21-fevralda tasdiqlangan. Bu qadam bank sohasidagi modernizatsiyani va yanada samarali tizimni ta'minlashni maqsadlaydi.

Shuningdek, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti tomonidan 2010-yil 19-apreldagi PQ-1325-sonli Qarori bilan qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida ma'lumotlar paydo etildi. Bu qaror, "Uzkart" banklararo to'lov tizimini rivojlantirishni rag'batlantirishga bag'ishlangan edi. Tijorat banklari, "Smart-Vista" EMV texnologik platformasini "on-line" rejimida ishlatish orqali, bank sohasidagi axborot texnologiyalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan diqqatni ko'rsatadi.

Bundan tashqari, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "2011–2015 yillarda respublika moliya-bank tizimini yanada isloh qilish va barqarorligini oshirish"ga bag'ishlangan 2010-yil 26-noyabrdagi PQ-1438-sonli Qarori bilan ham server va kommunikatsiya jihozlari, tizimli dasturiy ta'minotlar xarid qilinib, ishga tushirildi. Natijada tijorat banklarining ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlashni tezlashtirish uchun erkinlik va samarali tizim yaratishga intilgan diqqat ko'rsatilgan.

2016-yil 1-yanvar holatiga respublika bo'yicha barcha tijorat banklari tomonidan onlayn rejimida ishlaydigan 8 426 280ta bank plastik kartalari muomalaga chiqarilishiga erishildi. Bu, naqd pulning naqdashtirilishi va plastik kartalar orqali to'lovlarning amalga oshirilishi jarayonlarini yanada samarali va qulaylashtirish maqsadida amalga oshirilgan chora-tadbirlarning natijasi hisoblanadi.

Bu maqsadlar bilan quyidagilar amalga oshirildi:

Muomaladagi onlayn bank plastik kartalari, to'lov terminallari, infokiosklar sonini oshirgan holda respublika moliya infrastrukturasini kengaytirish;

Bank plastik kartalaridan foydalangan holda to'lovlarni amalga oshirish uchun boshqa uskunalar importini qo'llashda mablag'larni to'lovchi tomonlar o'rtasidagi hisob-kitoblarni yig'ish tizimini rivojlantirishga doir chora-tadbirlar.

Plastik karta tizimi uchun import shartnomalari bo'yicha xarid qilingan texnik va dasturiy vositalardan samarali foydalanishni nazorat qilish va zarur choralarni ko'rish [4]

Banklarda to'lovlarni elektron qabul qilish dasturlari "Smart-Vista" EMV tizimida "on-line" rejimida ishlaydigan terminallarning sifatli ishlashini ta'minlash maqsadida kengaytirilgan. Bu, bank axborot-kommunikatsiya infratuzilmasini to'laqonli shakllanish, to'lovlarni amalga oshirishning uzluksizligini va shaffofligini ta'minlash, hisob-kitoblarni optimallashtirish va jadallashtirish, mablag'larni to'lovchi va mablag'larni oluvchilar o'rtasidagi hisob-kitoblarning real vaqt rejimida amalga oshirilishi, bank xizmatlarining likvidligini oshirish, jismoniy shaxslar uchun masofadan turib, o'z hisobvaraqlarini boshqarish tizimlari orqali bir hisobvaraqdan ikkinchi hisobvaraqqa real vaqt rejimida pul mablag'larini ko'chirish imkoniyati va boshqalar kabi afzalliklarni ta'minlash maqsadida amalga oshirildi.

Hozirgi kunda respublikamizda kommunal xizmat ko'rsatuvchilari (elektr energiyasi, tabiiy gaz, maxsustrans xizmati, issiqlik manbai, suvsoz xizmati va boshqalar)ning kommunikatsiya tarmoqlari infrastrukturasi shakllantirib, ushbu xizmatlar uchun amalga oshirilgan to'lovlar real vaqt rejimida mablag'lar oluvchining hisobvaraqlariga o'tkazilishi bilan birga, elektron jurnallarda har bir mablag' to'lovchilarning kommunal xizmatlar uchun to'langan mablag'larining summasi, muddati (yil, oy, kun, soat, daqiqa, soniya ko'rinishida) va to'liq rekvizitlari bo'yicha qayd etiladi. Bu, to'lovlarning ishonchliligini hamda shaffofligini ta'minlash maqsadida amalga oshirilgan.

Mazkur mablag'larni to'lovchilar internet tarmog'i yoki mobil telefonlariga SMS-xabarnoma kelishi orqali o'z shaxsiy kabinetlaridan har bir kommunal xizmatlar bo'yicha to'lovlar tarixini real vaqt rejimida nazorat qilish imkoniyati yaratilgan.

Bundan tashqari, Markaziy bank tomonidan O'zbekiston Respublikasining zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish va yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida qarorlar ijrosini mamlakat bank tizimida samarali ta'minlash maqsadida, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy banki faoliyatida zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini 2016–2018 yillar davomida joriy etish va rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi ishlab chiqilgan.

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Mazkur Konsepsiyada, zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarining 2016–2018 yillar davomida banklar tomonidan mijozlarga ko‘rsatiladigan xizmatlar turini kengaytirish, takomillashtirish va joriy etish istiqbollari belgilangan. Bu istiqbollar quyidagi masalalarni o‘z ichiga oladi:

- Bank axborot tizimlarida zamonaviy texnik yechim va texnologiyalarni keng qo‘llash, bank faoliyatini avtomatlashtirish darajasini yuqori saviyaga ko‘tarish.
- O‘zbekiston Respublikasi «Elektron hukumat» tizimi tarkibiga kiritilgan chakana to‘lovlarni real vaqt rejimida amalga oshirish Kliring tizimining xizmat doirasini kengaytirish.
- «Tashqi savdo operatsiyalarining Yagona elektron axborot tizimini (TSO YAEAT) takomillashtirish» loyihasi asosida elektron tijoratdagi bitimlarni hisobga olgan holda ishga tushirish.
- Bank axborot tizimlari va ma’lumotlar bazalarining uzluksiz faoliyatini ta’minlash.
- Bank axborot resurslarini doimiy ravishda yangilab borish va ulardan keng foydalanishni ta’minlash.
- Bank tizimida boshqaruv va ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini zamonaviy texnologiyalar asosida avtomatlashtirish orqali bank xizmatlari turlarini amaliyotga keng tatbiq qilish va kengaytirish, aholi va tadbirkorlarga qo‘shimcha qulayliklar yaratish.
- Aholi va tadbirkorlik subyektlari tomonidan axborotlarni erkin va moneliksiz olishni ta’minlash, interaktiv xizmat turlarini kengaytirish, xizmatlarni «bir darcha» orqali ko‘rsatishni joriy qilish.
- Xavfsizlik va axborotlar muhofazasining tashkiliy va moddiy-texnik bazasini mustakamlash.
- Onlayn plastik karta xizmatlarini takomillashtirishga doir chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirish, bank plastik kartalari orqali hisob-kitoblarni amalga oshirish tizimidan foydalanish.
- Markaziy bank va tijorat banklarining Internet tarmog‘idagi rasmiy veb-saytlari faoliyatini doimiy monitoring qilish va sifatini oshirish, veb-saytlar orqali ko‘rsatiladigan interaktiv xizmatlar turlarini kengaytirish.
- Elektron tijoratni rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi va davlat dasturlarini amalga oshirish va joriy etishda faol qatnashish.

- Garov reyestri tizimini xalqaro talablar darajasiga mos kelishini ta'minlash.
- Kredit axboroti milliy instituti axborot tizimlarini takomillashtirish.
- Bank sohasida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari bo'yicha mutaxassislar malakasini muntazam ravishda oshirish, kadrlar tayyorlashni yangi sifat bosqichiga ko'tarish.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, mamlakat iqtisodiyotining qonuniy tomiri, hisoblangan bank tizimini yanada isloh qilish, uning barqarorligini oshirish, yuqori xalqaro reyting ko'rsatkichlariga erishishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari bilan birga, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan keng foydalanib, zamonaviy naqd pulsiz hisob-kitoblar mexanizmlarini joriy etish yordamida banklarimiz mijozlarga ko'rsatilayotgan xizmatlar sifati, to'lov intizomi va madaniyatini yangi bosqichga ko'tarilishini ta'minlaydi. Bu, barcha iqtisodiy tarmoqlar taraqqiyotini mustahkamlashga ham o'zining jihatli ta'sirini ko'rsatadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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3. www.arxiv.uz
4. www.ziyonet.uz

GIDRAVLIK PRESSLAR VA ULARNING TURLARI

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Annotatsiya. *Gidravlika inshootlari foydalanish qulayligi, ishonchliligi va yuqori mahsuldorligi bilan ajralib turadi. Boshqa har qanday birliklardan farqli o'laroq, metall uchun gidravlik press katta hajmdagi qattiq chiqindilarni qadoqlash imkoniyatiga ega: soatiga bir necha tonnagacha. Bugungi kunga kelib gidravlik presslardan farqli o'laroq yangi zamonaviy presslardan foydalanmoqdamiz, bu esa sanoat korxonalarida keng qo'llanilmoqda. Hozirgi kundagi presslar inson ishtirokisiz avtomatlashtirilgan holda ishlamoqda. Ya'ni raqamli dasturli boshqarish tizimi orqali bajarilmoqda.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Press, gidravlik press, metallga ishlov berish, qora va rangli metall, elektr motor, shtamplash, Paskal qonuni, raqamli dasturli boshqarish tizimi, avtomatlashtirish, gidrostatika, bosim, diagramma.*

HYDRAULIC PRESSES AND THEIR TYPES

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Annotation. *Hydraulic units are characterized by ease of operation, reliability and high performance. Unlike any other units, a hydraulic press for metal is capable of packaging a large volume of solid waste: up to several tons per hour. Today, unlike hydraulic presses, we use new modern presses that are widely used in industrial plants. Today's presses are automated without human intervention. That is, it is carried out through a digital software control system.*

Key words: *Press, hydraulic press, metalworking, ferrous and non-ferrous metal, electric motor, stamping, Pascal's law, numerical control system, automation, hydrostatics, pressure, diagram.*

J. Brama 1797 yilda o'zining gidravlik pressini qurgan. U og'ir narsalarni ko'tarish va harakatlantirish uchun ishlatilgan. Ixtirochining loyihasi bo'yicha yaratilgan qurilmalar daryodan o'tuvchi Britaniya ko'prigi qurilishida foydalanilgan. Temza. Har birining mehnati 11-14 tonnaga yetdi. Metall kesish, to'g'on qoziqlarini tortib olish, daraxtlarni yiqitish va katta kuch talab qiladigan boshqa ishlar uchun ishlatilgan. XVIII-XIX asrlar oxirida. Gidravlik press qishloq xo'jaligida qo'llanilishini topdi. U yog', uzum sharbati va to'plangan pichanni siqib chiqarish uchun ishlatilgan[1].

Ixtirochining o'zi 1797 yilda qo'rg'oshin quvurlarini ishlab chiqarish uchun qurilmadan foydalanishni taklif qildi. Uning fikriga ko'ra, metallni matritsadagi halqa shaklidagi teshikdan bosish kerak edi. Va bu fikr amalga oshdi, lekin keyinroq. 1820 yilda muhandis T. Burr qo'rg'oshin quvurlarini bosish uchun maxsus mashina qurdi. U taklif qilgan usul to'g'ridan-to'g'ri presslash usuli deb nomlandi va metallni qayta ishlash sohasida pressning istiqbolli qo'llanilishining isboti bo'ldi. Va 19-asrning oxiriga kelib, metallga ishlov berish korxonalarida press ikki usulda qo'llanila boshlandi: matritsa orqali bosish va shtamplash (ish qismini zarba beruvchilarga ta'sir qilish va pressning o'liklari) [5].

Birinchi ixtiro qilingan press

Keyinchalik gidravlik presslar tobora keng tarqaldi. Va ulardan foydalanish samaradorligi qo'shimcha ishlanmalar va mexanizmni takomillashtirishga turtki bo'ldi. Unga drayvlar va boshqa yaxshilanishlar qo'shildi, bu esa kerakli kuchlarga erishishga imkon berdi[2].

Metall uchun gidravlik press

Gidravlika inshootlari foydalanish qulayligi, ishonchliligi va yuqori mahsuldorligi bilan ajralib turadi. Boshqa har qanday birliklardan farqli o'laroq, metall uchun gidravlik press katta hajmdagi qattiq chiqindilarni qadoqlash

imkoniyatiga ega: soatiga bir necha tonnagacha. Bunday uskunalar har qanday turdagi qora va rangli metall chiqindilari bilan ishlashi mumkin: talaşlar, choyshablar, qutilar va idishlar, alyuminiy qoldiqlari va hatto bochkalar[6].

24-45 tonna kuchga ega bo'lgan press yordamida katta hajmdagi chiqindilarni qayta ishlashdan osonroq narsa yo'q. Qayta ishlangan materiallarni xaridorlari va qayta ishlovchilari va katta hajmdagi chiqindilarga ega korxonalar uchun professional osuv presslari. Kuchaytirilgan konstruksiya va kuchli elektr motor og'irligi 450-700 kg bo'lgan gofrokarton va boshqa qayta ishlanadigan materiallardan to'plamlar hosil qilish imkonini beradi[7].

Gidravlik presslarning ishlash printsipti va ularning turlari.

Eng qadimgi sanoat qurilmalaridan biri matbuotdir. Uning ichida o'zining zamonaviy ko'rinishida ushbu birlik keng diapazonni bosish uchun ishlatiladi mahsulotlar - zargarlik buyumlaridan samolyot qismlarigacha. Ma'lumki, har qanday matbuot - Bu sezilarli kuch yaratish uchun maxsus qurilma ma'lum bir hudud. Matbuot, asosan, bilan bog'liq ishlarda zarur metallni qayta ishlash. Aslida, gidravlik press gidravlik bilan birga jaklar, ularning ishlarida ishlatiladigan eng oddiy qurilmalardan biri gidravlika va suyuqlik muvozanatining Paskal qonuni. Birinchi gidravlik press 18-asrda, ya'ni 1797 yilda yaratilgan! Shundan keyin hech qanday taraqqiyot bo'lmadi joyida va endi gidravlik press oddiy, samarali va ishonchli qurilma! Shlangi pressning ishlashi gidravlik printsiptiga asoslanadi[3].

Oddiy gidravlik pressning diagrammasi

Hozirgi vaqtda gidravlik presslar sanoatda, texnik xizmat ko'rsatish shoxobchalarida, turli avtoulov ustaxonalarida va garajlarda keng qo'llaniladi. Va bu uskunaning tashqi ko'rinishi zarb ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq.

Yuqoridagi rasmda oddiy gidravlik pressning diagrammasi ko'rsatilgan, o'rnatilgan katta va kichikroq diametrli pistonlardan iborat aloqa tsilindrlari, pistonlar ostida suyuqlik bor. Pistonda S1 maydoni bo'lgan kichik diametr F1 kuchiga aylanadi, keling F2 kuchini aniqlaymiz, S2 maydonining pistoni bilan engish mumkin[4].

Piston 1 ostidagi bosimni quyidagi formula yordamida hisoblash mumkin:

$$p_1 = F_1 / S_1 \quad (1.1)$$

Piston 2 ostidagi bosim quyidagi munosabat bilan aniqlanadi:

$$p_2 = F_2 / S_2 \quad (1,2)$$

Paskal qonuniga ko'ra, suyuqlikka qo'llaniladigan bosim o'tkaziladi bu suyuqlikning barcha nuqtalariga barcha yo'nalishlarda teng ravishda.

$$p_1 = p_2 = p \quad (1,3)$$

Ma'lum bo'lishicha:

$$F_1 / S_1 = F_2 / S_2 \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_2 = F_1$$

$$* S_2 / S_1 \quad (1,5)$$

Ikkinchi pistondagi kuch nisbatga mutanosib ravishda oshiriladi piston joylari. Ikkinchi pistonning maydoni qanchalik katta bo'lsa, shuncha kichik bo'ladi

Gidravlik pres

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BLOKCHEYN TEXNOLOGIYASINING ISHLASH PRINTSIPI VA QO‘LLANILISHI

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Anotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada, blokchen texnologiyasi haqida asosiy tushunchalar, blokcheyn texnologiyasining nazariy asoslari, blokcheyn texnologiyasining qo‘llanilish sohalar, blok zanjirlarini shakllantirish texnologiyasi, blok umumiy ko‘rinishi, tranzaktsiyalar, blok korpusishakllantirilishi, blokcheynga bo‘ladigan kriptohujumlar tasnifi, butun dunyo blokcheyn texnologiyasidan foydalanilganlik darajasi, blokcheyn texnologiyasining matematik asosi va bir qancha masalalarning yechimlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar. Blokcheyn texnologiyasi, blokklar zanjiri, blok korpusi, xesh funksiyalar, kriptohujum, kredit tizimi.

PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. In this article, the basic concepts of blockchain technology, theoretical basis of blockchain technology, application areas of blockchain technology, block chain formation technology, block overview, transactions, block corpus formation, classification of cryptoattacks on blockchain, the level of use of blockchain technology around the world, the mathematical basis of blockchain technology and solutions to several problems are presented.

Key words: Blockchain technology, block chain, block corpus, hash functions, crypto attack, credit system.

Kirish. Bugungi kunda blokcheyn texnologiyalari yangi innovatsion texnologiya yo‘nalishi bo‘lishiga qaramasdan bir qator ijtimoiy sohalarga kirib borib, o‘z o‘rnini egallagan. Insonlarning intellektual ijodi mahsuli yaratilishining jadallashishi bilan bir qatorda, ulardan foydalanish, muhofaza hamda himoyasini ta‘minlash masalasi ham dolzarblashmoqda. Qolaversa, internet tarmog‘ining jamiyatimiz hayotida kirib kelishining takomillashishi oqibatida ma‘lumotlar olish, axborot almashish hamda mulkka bo‘lgan huquqlarning ruxsatsiz foydalanish ham oshib bormoqda. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar hayotimizga jadal sur‘atlar bilan kirib kelmoqda. “Raqamlilashtirish” tushunchasini nafaqat ilmiy anjumanlarda, balki kundalik hayotda ham tez-tez eshitish mumkin. Ayrimlar hali ham raqamlashtirish jarayonining foyda yoki zarari haqida bahslashayotgan bir paytda, innovatsion texnologiyalarni hayotimizga joriy etish tendensiyasi allaqachon odatiy holga aylanib bormoqda. Buning eng yorqin misollardan biri bo‘lgan aqlli shartnomalarni yaratishdir.

Hozirgi kunda, butun dunyoda blokcheyn texnologiyasi jamiyatning ijtimoiy iqtisodiy va hakazo sohalarida keng qo‘llanilmoqda. Blokcheyn texnologiyasida axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyasida sohasida katta burilish yasadi. Bu burilishni internet yaratilishi bilan qiyoslash mumkin. Jamiyat va undagi insonlar hayoti pul, ma‘lumotlar va hujjatlar bilan bog‘liqdir. Shunga bog‘liq holda biz pul, hujjat va axborotlarni beruvchi va ularni tekshirib haqiqiyliyini kafolatlovchi, yozuvlarning haqiqiyliyini tekshiruvchi har hil turdagi vositachilar bilan munosabatda bo‘ladi.

Shuning uchun biz tarmoqdagi vositachiga ishonch bildirishga majbur bo‘lamiz. Misol uchun, hozirgi kunda bank haridorlarining mablag‘lari haqidagi ma‘lumotlari konfidentsialligini ta‘minlash, notarial idora xizmatchilarining noqonuniy shartnomalar tuzish kabi hatti – harakatlarga urinishlar, davlat tashkilotlari va tijorat tashkilotlari xizmatchilarining o‘z manfaatlari yo‘lida davlatga ziyon keltiruvchi hatti-harakatlarni amalga oshirishga urinishlari korruptsiya, davlat mulkini talon taroj qilish kabi hakazo harakatlar amalga oshirilayotgani hech birimizga sir emas.

Albatta bu kabi muammolarning chuqur ildiz otishi yurtimizning ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy sohalarda rivojlanish bosqichlarida ortda qolishiga mamlakatimiz aholisining ko‘pgina qatlamlarida qashshoqlik, ocharchilik, ijtimoiy himoyasizlik kabi og‘ir oqibatlarga olib keladi. Albatta bu muammolarning yechishning mamlakatimizda aniq strategiyalari belgilangan. Asosan, bu borada 2017-2021 yillarda O‘zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustivor yo‘nalishi bo‘yicha harakatlar strategiyasida

keng qamrovli vazifalar belgilab berilgan. Albatta, harakatlar strategiyasining ustivor vazifalari bajarilayotgan holda mamlakatimizda ko'pgina ijtimoiy iqtisdiy o'zgarishlar, yangilanishlar yuz bermoqda[1]. Lekin, hozirgi kunda axborot texnologiyalarining mamlakatimizning ko'pgina sohalariga qo'llanilishi, ko'pgina davlat va molyaviy xizmatlarning masofaviy tizimlar yordamida bajarilishi, tizimlar orqali molyaviy amallarni bajarishda vositachilardan foydalanilishi natijasida tizimlar xavfsizligiga tahdidlar, tizimdagi ma'lumotlarning o'zgartirilishi ya'ni konfedentsialligi buzilishi kabi ko'pgina muammolar kelib chiqmoqda.[2]

Hozirgi kunda bu muammolarning yechimi sifatida ko'pgina va xavfsizlikni ta'minlash maqsadida ko'pgina kriptografik algoritmlar va dasturiy vositalar taklif qilinmoqda. Ko'pgina kriptografik algoritmlarda hisoblash masalasi murakkabligi va kriptoanalitiklar tomonidan tahlil qilinishi natijasida algoritmlarga nisbatan shubhalar kelib chiqmoqda. Albatta bu muammolarni yechish yangi zamonaviy konfedentsialligi va kriptomustahkamligi yuqori bo'lgan kriptotalgoritm yoki himoya tizimi zarurligi ko'pchilik mutahassislar tomonidan aytilmoqda. Bu turdagi masalalarni yechishda blokcheyn texnologiyasini qo'llash bo'yicha ko'pgina mulohazalar keltirilmoqda. Endi, biz quyidagicha blokcheyn texnologiyasining ijtimoiy,iqtisodiy, siyosiy sohalarga qo'llashning asosiy bosqichlarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Blokcheyn – bu ixtiyoriy pedmet haqidagi ma'lumotlarni ochiq aloqa tarmog'I orqali uzatuvchi yagona ishonchli texnologiya bo'lib hisoblanadi. Misol uchun, Blokcheyn texnologiyasi orqali molyaviy ma'lumotlarni ishonchli saqlash mumkin. Kripto valyuta tizimlarida blokcheyn texnologiyasi foydalanuvchilarning virtual pul mablag'larini ishonchli saqlash va sarflash firibgarliklardan asrash imkoniyatini yaratadi. Shuning bilan bir qatorda blokcheyn texnologiyasini qo'llagan holda abonentlar yoki tashkilotlarning mulkiy huquqlarini, elektron shartnomalar, sog'liqni saqlash tizimidagi maxfiy ma'lumotlar (bemorlarning kasallik varaqasi va shunga o'xshash maxfiy ma'lumotlar), farmaseftika sohasidagi ma'lumotlar (dori darmon maxsulotlarining haqiqiyqligini ta'minlash maqsadida) va nikoh to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarning konfedentsialligini ta'minlashda keng qo'llaniladi. Umumiy aytganda, barcha matnli va boshqa turdagi ma'lumotlarni blokcheyn zanjirlari bloklarida saqlash ma'umotlar konfedentsialligini ta'minlashda katta imkoniyat yaratadi. Blokcheyn texnologiyasining boshqa kriptotalgoritmlardan farqi shundan iboratki, blokcheyn bloklariga kiritilgan ochiq yoki maxfiy axborotlarni o'zgartirish, o'g'irlash va shunga o'xshash kripto hujumlarni amalga oshirirsh

kriptoanalitiklarga yaxshi natija bermaydi. Bu deganimiz kriptoanalitiklar blokcheyn zanjirlaridagi ma'lumotlarga ziyon keltirishi mumkin emas[1].

Adabiyotlar tahlili. Antuan Grispen "Mastering Blockchain: Unlocking the Power of Cryptocurrencies, Smart Contracts, and Decentralized Applications": Bu kitob blockchain texnologiyasining asosiy printsiplarini va uni qo'llashni tushuntiradi

Narayanan, Arvind, et al. "Bitcoin and Cryptocurrency Technologies: A Comprehensive Introduction": Bu adabiyot kriptoalyutalar, blockchain texnologiyasi, va ularning qo'llanilishi haqida kompaniyalik o'qish uchun qo'l keladigan ilmiy o'tish uchun yaxshi manba hisoblanadi.

Don Tapscott va Alex Tapscott "Blockchain Revolution: How the Technology Behind Bitcoin and Other Cryptocurrencies is Changing the World": Ushbu kitob blockchain texnologiyasining umumiy qabul qilingan printsiplarini, ularning ishlashini va dunyodagi amaliyotlarni qanday o'zgartirishini tushuntiradi.

David Gerard "Attack of the 50 Foot Blockchain: Bitcoin, Blockchain, Ethereum & Smart Contracts": Bu adabiyot blockchain texnologiyasining kritikaviy tahlilini o'z ichiga oladi va odatda ko'p tavsiya qilingan kitoblar hisoblanadi.

Andreas M. Antonopoulos "Mastering Bitcoin: Unlocking Digital Cryptocurrencies": Bu kitob Bitcoin va kriptoalyutalar haqida nazariy va amaliy bilimlarni ta'lim etadi. U blockchain texnologiyasining qo'llanilishi va ishlash printsiplarini tushunish uchun muhimdir.

Swan, Melanie. "The Blockchain: Blueprint for a New Economy": Bu kitob blokcheynning ommaviy ta'limotini va blockchain texnologiyasining ishlash printsiplarini asosiy darajada tushuntiradi. Ushbu adabiyot, blokcheynning amaliyotdagi qo'llanilishini, uning samaradorligini va blockchainning o'zaro aloqalari uchun yangi imkoniyatlarini keng ko'rsatadi.

Swan, Melanie. "Blockchain: The Next Everything": Bu adabiyot blokcheynning keng doiraga ta'siri va qo'llanilishini o'rganishga yordam beradi. Ushbu kitobda blokcheyn texnologiyasining kelajakdagi roli, uning qo'llanilishi va blokcheynning muhimligi to'g'risida tushuntiruvchi ko'rsatmalar berilgan.

Muhokama va natijalar. Blokcheyn – inglizcha “Blockchain” – “blok” va “zanjir” so'zlaridan hosil bo'lgan. Texnologiya ma'lumotlarni ketma-ket ma'lumotlar bloklari shaklida uzatadi, bloklar shifrlangan bo'ladi va bir nechta kompyuterlarda tarqatiladi.

Butun Internet serverlar orqali ishlaydi. Yuqori darajadagi qurilmalar har kuni milliardlab so'rovlarni, shu jumladan bank tranzaksiyalarini (operatsiyalarini), messenjerlarda xabarlarini yuborishni, fayllarni yuklab olishni va boshqalarni boshqaradi. Tabiiyki, markazlashtirilgan xizmat katta moliyaviy xarajatlarni talab qiladi. Texnik vositachilardan tashqari, yuridik vositachilar ham mavjud. Masalan, moliyaviy korxonada shaxsiy guvohnomasiz onlayn-kredit bermaydi. Barcha ma'lumotlarni saqlab bo'lmaydi, shuning uchun qonuniy momentlarni tekshirish uchun mas'ul bo'lgan uchinchi tomon ma'lumotlar bazalari mavjud. Pul o'tkazmalari o'zlarining "mehnatlari" uchun komissiya talab qiladigan vositachilik servislarisiz bo'lmaydi. Hattoki odamlar bir-birining qarshisida yashasa ham, mablag'larni bir bankdan boshqasiga yuborilishi foizlarga tortiladi.

Servislar o'rtasida pul va ma'lumotlarni "o'tkazilishi" ishlov berish vaqtini oshiradi va mijozlar barcha harakatlar uchun pul to'laydilar. Shuning uchun bugungi kunda mijozlar doimiy ortiqcha to'lovlardan charchagan. Hatto komissiyasiz xizmat ko'rsatish ham pulni uchinchi shaxsga ishonishni anglatadi. Kafil vazifasini bajaruvchi bank bankrot bo'lishi, hujumga uchrashi yoki texnik nosozliklarga duch kelishi mumkin. Korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligi juda shartli va foydalanuvchilar doimiy bosim ostida bo'lishadi. Bitta global inqiroz natijasida kompaniya o'z faoliyatini to'xtatishi mumkin.

Ma'lum bo'lishicha, onlayn pul o'tkazmasini amalga oshirishni yoki hujjatlarni topshirishni istagan ikki mijoz o'rtasida har doim vositachi bor. Vositachisiz operatsiyalarni texnik va qonuniy ravishda qayta ishlash mumkin bo'lmaydi. Ammo blockchain uchinchi shaxslarni butunlay chiqarib tashladi. Asosiy afzalliklari: - eng qiyin operatsiyalar bir necha daqiqada amalga oshiriladi; - vositachilarning yo'qligi tranzaksiyalarni arzonlashtiradi va ularning tezligini oshiradi; - ma'lumotlar markazlashtirilmagan serverda saqlanadi: u minglab kompyuterlarga tarqatiladi, shuning uchun uni o'g'irlash mumkin emas.

Xulosa. Blokcheyn texnologiyasi orqali ko'plab iqtisodiy va moliyaviy operatsiyalarni bajarish imkoni borligi tufayli ko'plab mamlakatlar va yirik korxonalar rahbarlari bu texnologiya insonlar hayotiga yanada chuqur kirib borishini bashorat qilmoqdalar [4].

Mazkur texnologiya o'z o'rnida, minglab virtual kompyuterlarni jamlagan bo'lib, foydalanuvchilar ushbu o'zlari uchun alohida yaratilgan tegishli kalit bilan tranzaksiyalarini amalga oshiradilar. Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, 2021 yil avgust oyining o'rtalarida, mazkur texnologiya, ya'ni blokcheyn hamyoniga ega

bo'lgan 75.6 milliondan ortiq foydalanuvchi butun dunyo bo'ylab ro'yxatga olingan [5, b.988-989].

Bugungi kunda mazkur sohani rivojlantirish borasida quyidagi vazifalarni hal qilish maqsadga muvofiq: raqamli texnologiyalar sohasida mahsulot va xizmatlar eksporti hajmini oshirish; kripto-aktivlar aylanmasi va blokcheyn texnologiyasi sohasida kadrlar tayyorlash va malakasini oshirish uchun asos yaratish; O'zbekiston Respublikasining xalqaro maydonda innovatsiyalarga ochiq va investitsiyaviy jozibador mamlakat sifatida imidjini oshirish.

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BOSHQARUV MEHANIZIMLARINING TEXNOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA AFZALLIKLARI

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Annotatsiya. Hozirgi kunda sanoat nazorati tizimida oziq-ovqat, ichimliklar, avtomobil sanoati, sog'liqni saqlash, qishloq xo'jaligi, tog'-kon sanoati va energetika kabi barcha sohalarda boshqaruv mexanizmlarini takmilashtirish keng qo'llanilmoqda. Bu sanoatning samarali va izchil ishlashiga muhim hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: boshqaruv mexanizmlar, IEC 61508 standarti, tizim, korxonalar

TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND ADVANTAGES OF CONTROL MECHANISMS

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Annotation: Currently, the improvement of management mechanisms is widely used in the industrial control system in all areas such as food, beverages, automobile industry, health care, agriculture, mining industry and energy. This makes an important contribution to the efficient and consistent operation of the industry.

Keywords: control mechanisms, IEC 61508 standard, system, enterprise.

Xavfsizlikni yaxshilaydi - inson salomatligi va hayoti uchun yuqori xavfsizlik xavfi hisoblangan mexanizmlardan foydalanadigan zavod jarayonlari mavjud. Shunday qilib, odamlarni har qanday zarardan uzoqlashtirish uchun ushbu texnologik liniyalarda ishlash uchun robotlardan foydalanish xavfsizroqdir.

Bundan tashqari, boshqaruv tizimlari IEC 61508 standartiga asoslangan funksional xavfsizlik standarti bilan jihozlanishi mumkin, ya'ni Safety Integrity Level (SIL). SILning to'rtta toifasi mavjud bo'lib, ular kompaniya ega bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan jarayon turiga va xavfsizlik standarti talablariga bog'liq.

Barqaror mahsulot sifati - Zavodning zamonaviy uskunalari bilan zamonaviy tizim bilan jihozlangan inson xatolari bartaraf qilinadi va shu bilan mahsulot sifati yaxshilanadi. Bundan tashqari, tizim 24/7 ishlaganda ham mashinaning ish faoliyatini o'zgartirmaydi.

Pastroq ishlab chiqarish xarajati - Tizim mexanizm to'liq ishlamay qolishidan oldin muammolarni oldindan ko'ra oladi. Tizim uskunaning ishlashi to'g'risida uskuna ma'lumotlarini berishga qodir. Uskunaning muayyan qismlarining buzilishi ham aniqlanadi, bu esa uskunani xavfsiz tarzda to'g'ri to'xtatish uchun tizimni ogohlantiradi.

Atrof-muhit samaradorligini oshirish - tizimni "erta ogohlantirish" berishga qodir bo'lgan gaz emissiya asboblari bilan ulash mumkin va shu bilan gaz emissiyasining ortib borayotgan o'sishini nazorat qiladi.

Moslashuvchanlik - Boshqarish tizimlari moslashuvchan bo'lib, uni ishlab chiqarishda zarur bo'lgan yangi vazifa bilan osongina qayta dasturlash mumkin. Shunday qilib, "yangi vazifa" avtomatik ravishda kamroq operator aralashuvi bilan o'rnatilganligi sababli operatsiyalarga kamroq o'rgatiladi.

Ishonchli va aniq jarayon ma'lumotlari - Tizim ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini to'g'ri tekshirish uchun ishonchlilik muhandisi yoki texnologik muhandis tomonidan ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni arxivlashi mumkin.

Biroq boshqaruv tizimiga ma'lumot to'g'ri saqlanmasa, bu tizim imtiyozlarning barchasi nolga aylanadi. Agar kompaniya bunday murakkab tizimga sarmoya kiritgan bo'lsa, unda texnik xizmat ko'rsatish xarajatlari allaqachon bo'ladi. Tizim yaxshi ishlashi uchun muhim ehtiyot qismlari bo'lishi kerak.

Muhim ehtiyot qismlar

Sanoatga texnik xizmat ko'rsatuvchi mutaxassis uchun sog'lom ehtiyot qismlar zaxirasini saqlash juda muhimdir. "Muammolar" davrida siz almashtiriladigan qismni qaerdan topish haqida vahima qo'yaysiz yoki tizimning halokatli ishdan chiqishiga olib kelishi mumkin bo'lgan o'zgartirilgan qismlarni yaratishga majbur bo'lmaysiz. Agar sizda o'rnatilgan ehtiyot qismlar boshqaruvi mavjud bo'lsa, unda siz tizimni osongina saqlashingiz va muammolar vaqtida uskunaning ishlamay qolish vaqtini kamaytirishingiz mumkin.

Ta'mirlash ehtiyot qismlarini boshqarishda e'tiborga olish kerak bo'lgan narsalar quyidagilardan iborat:

Tez harakatlanuvchi elementlar - bu elementlar ko'pincha talab qilinadi yoki muvaffaqiyatsiz bo'ladi. Boshqarish tizimlaridagi ushbu elementlarga misollar signal konditsionerlari, kuchlanishdan himoyalanişlar, kiritish-chiqarish modullari, kompyuter klaviaturasi va sichqonchadir.

Sekin harakatlanuvchi elementlar - bu elementlar ko'pincha kamdan-kam talab qilinadi yoki muvaffaqiyatsiz bo'ladi. Ushbu elementlarga misollar PLC protsessorlari, aloqa modullari va HMIlardir

Ehtiyot qismlar inventarining yuqori bo'lishiga yo'l qo'ymaslik uchun zavodgingizda foydalanadigan boshqaruv tizimining markalari sonini cheklash kerak. Agar siz nazorat tizimining ehtiyot qismlarining kamroq markalarini saqlasangiz, umumiy ehtiyot qismlar boshqaruvini osongina o'rnatish mumkin.

Ko'rib chiqilishi kerak bo'lgan yana bir narsa, loyihalar guruhiga OEM'lardan mahsulotning hayot aylanishining yakuniy bosqichida bo'lmagan ishlatilgan qismlarni talab qilishni maslahat berishdir. Yangi qismlarni osongina sotib olish mumkin, ya'ni sizning xarid guruhingiz yetkazib beruvchini topishda qiyinchilik tug'dirmaydi. Yakuniy bosqichda bo'lgan mahsulotlarni hali ham sotib olish mumkin, ammo topish qiyin va qimmat. Shunday qilib, umumiy amaliyot bu qismlarni yangilash yoki qayta tiklashdir.

Profilaktik ta'mirlash:

Hech qanday xatosiz muammosiz ishlaydigan tizimlarga "egishdan qo'rqish tabiiydir bu sizning shaxs sifatida qanchalik tavakkalchi ekanligingizga bog'liq bo'ladi. Biroq, texnik xizmat ko'rsatish uchun ko'p yillar davomida ishlagandan so'ng, tizimni o'chirishning minimal xavfi bilan PM qilishning ko'plab usullari mavjudligini bilib oldim.

Quyida PMni amalga oshirishdan oldin quyidagi ishchilar fikrini ro'yxati keltirdim:

Har doim PMni bajarishda foydalanishim kerak bo'lgan vositalar va shaxsiy himoya vositalari haqida o'ylang.

Bosh vazirdan oldin har doim xavfsizlik haqida o'ylang. Avvalo, u PM qilish uchun xavfsiz ish joyimi yoki yo'qligini tekshirib ko'rishingiz kerak. Odatda, ishlashdan oldin ruxsatnoma shakli mavjud.

Har doim PMni bajarish bo'yicha tartib va ko'rsatmalarga rioya qiling. Agar nima qilmoqchi ekanligingizga shubhangiz bo'lsa, iltimos, rahbaringizdan yo'l-yo'riq so'rang. Hech qanday yorliq bajarilmasligi kerak.

Bosh vazirni bajarishdan oldin har doim operatsiya guruhidan ruxsat so‘rang.

Har doim PMni bajaradigan komponentlar, masalan, asosiy quvvat manbai to‘xtatuvchilari haqida xabardor bo‘ling. Agar sizga asosiy quvvat manbaini o‘chirish topshirilmagan bo‘lsa, bunga tegmang.

PMni amalga oshirish uchun asboblari va boshqa maxsus vositalardan foydalanganda doimo aqlga ega bo‘ling. Noto‘g‘ri foydalanish halokatli baxtsiz hodisalarga olib kelishi mumkin.

Har doim PMdan keyin uy ishlarini bajaring. Ko‘rsatilgan barcha ko‘rsatmalar "xavfsizlik bo‘yicha suhbat", asboblari to‘plamidagi yig‘ilish yoki guruhingizning qiziqarli nutqi paytida muhokama qilinishi kerak.

Bundan tashqari, tayinlangan PM guruhiga rioya qilish uchun nazorat ro‘yxati ko‘rinishidagi tartib belgilanishi kerak. Shunday qilib, biz PMLarni bajarishda xatolar va halokatli baxtsiz hodisalarning oldini olanadi.

Boshqalar ish yo‘riqnomasi deb ataydigan protseduralari to‘g‘ri va tushunarli bo‘lishi kerak, shunda tizimning qaysi qismining har bir nuqtasi ehtiyotkorlik bilan tekshiriladi.

Panelidagi atrof-muhit haroratini tekshiring:

- Elektron qurilmalar tavsiya etilgan ish haroratiga ega. Eng keng tarqalgani shundaki, boshqaruv tizimlari modullarining ishlashi 0-60 ° C atrof-muhit harorati oralig‘iga ega bo‘lishi kerak, shuning uchun yuqorida ko‘rsatilgan harorat komponentning ishlamay qolishiga olib keladi.

- Agar panelingiz yuqori muhit haroratiga ega bo‘lsa, egzoz tizimingiz to‘g‘ri ishlamayotgandir yoki panel filtri allaqachon chang bilan tiqilib qolgan bo‘lishi mumkin.

Panelda namlik va chang mavjudligini tekshiring:

- Ichkarida namlik va chang bo‘lsa, ehtimol sizning panelingiz to‘g‘ri yopilmagan yoki egzoz ventilyatori ishlamayapti va fan teshigiga chang yoki tutun kirib kelgan.

- Ehtiyotkorlik bilan changni tozalang.

Tizim modullarini nosozliklar yoki signallar uchun tekshiring:

- Tizim modullarida modul xato yoki xatosiz sog‘lom ekanligini ko‘rsatadigan ko‘rsatkich mavjud. Shu bilan birga, modul xatolarini tizim operatori stantsiyasi orqali tizim diagnostikasida ham ko‘rish mumkin.

- Operator stantsiyasini tekshiring:

- monitor, klaviatura va sichqonchani changdan tozalash;

- zaxira tizimi parametrlari;

- Agar siz hali ham umumiy HDD sig'imingizning 15% dan ko'prog'iga ega bo'lsangiz, HDDdan foydalanishni tekshirin va har doim USB kirish ruxsatini olib tashlang.

Biz tuzatuvchi ishlar kabi tizimni o'chirishni o'z ichiga olgan PM ishlari mavjudligini bilamiz. Bundan tashqari, dasturlarni qo'shimcha o'rnatish va dasturni qayta ko'rib chiqishni o'z ichiga olgan ishlar mavjud bo'lib, bu tizimni o'chirishni ham talab qiladi. Shuning uchun zavodning har qanday yopilishi paytida ularni avtomatik o'chirish kerak.

Kadrlar tayyorlash. Agar sizning zavodingiz bir nechta o'rta va katta miqyosli boshqaruv tizimlari bilan o'rnatilgan bo'lsa, siz boshqaruv tizimlari guruhi uchun treninglarga mablag 'sarflashingiz kerak. Bozorda turli brendlardan ko'plab taklif qilingan boshqaruv tizimi o'quv modullari mavjud.

Treninglar xodimlarga o'z ishining muhimligini o'rgatadi va o'zlariga ishonch va ishonchni mustahkamlaydi.

Agar siz nazorat qilish tizimi uchun o'z laboratoriyangizni qurishga muvaffaq bo'lsangiz, bu kompaniya uchun katta afzallik bo'lardi, chunki sizning xodimlaringiz yaxshi o'qitilgan bo'lsa-da, lekin ularda mashq qilish uchun sharoit yo'q bo'lsa- ular treninglar davomida o'rgangan narsalarini osonlikcha unitishlari mumkin.

Bundan tashqari, agar sizning shaxsiy laboratoriyangiz bo'lsa, xodimlaringiz quyidagilarga qodir bo'ladi:

1. To'g'ri tekshirish uchun zavodda uchraydigan muammolarni simulyatsiya qiling.
2. Mavjud tizimda o'rnatishingiz kerak bo'lgan yangi konfiguratsiyalarni sinab ko'ring.
3. Agar hali ham to'g'ri ishlayotgan bo'lsa, yangi va qayta ko'rib chiqish dasturi mantiqlarini sinab ko'ring.
4. PM faoliyatingiz uchun protseduralarni sinab ko'ring va ishlab chiqing.
5. Tizimga integratsiya qilinadigan yangi asboblarni sinab ko'ring.

Zaxira dasturlari

Boshqaruv tizimingizning zaxira nusxasini yaratish ham muhimdir. Ba'zi boshqaruv tizimlarida HMI va PLC uchun alohida dastur mavjud. Boshqalarida faqat bitta, ya'ni HMI va PLC dasturlari bilan birlashtirilgan dastur mavjud. Men ushbu zahiraviy dasturlarni IT guruhingiz yordamida saqlashni taklif qilaman.

Ushbu zaxira dasturlari HMI va PLC bilan bog'liq muammolarga duch kelganingizda sizning hayot yo'lingizdir. Biroq, ushbu zaxira dasturlarini

ishlatish uchun vosita sifatida ishlab chiqish dasturi va dasturlash kabelini sotib olishingiz kerak bo‘ladi.

Afsuski, zaxira dasturlarini bermaydigan OEM mavjud bo‘ladi, chunki bu ularning dastur ustidagi himoyasi. Ammo muzokaralar olib borish usullari mavjud, shunda siz kelishuvga erishasiz, chunki sizning kompaniyangiz bunday dasturlarni ishlab chiqishda raqobatchi emas, lekin ularni faqat texnik xizmat ko‘rsatish uchun sotib oling. Loyihani potentsial ishlab chiqaruvchiga topshirishdan oldin shartnoma tuzilganligi ham muhimdir.

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ASINXRON MOTORLARNING ENERGETIK KO'RSATKICHLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada asinxron motorda elektromagnit ko'rsatkichlar, f.i.k, quvvat koeffitsienti va ularning ko'paytmasi oqimning ma'lum qiymatida maksimumga erishishi, o'zgaruvchan nobudgarchilik va qo'zg'atish nobudgarchilik teng bo'lganda f.i.k. o'zining eng katta qiymatiga erishishi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Asinxron motor, quvvat, elektromagnit, nobudgarchilili, qo'zg'atish nobudgarchiligi, maksimum, chastota, energetika, stator, quvvat, koeffitsient, kuchlanish, optimal rejim, optimal oqim, minimal, elektro-magnit, ekspluatatsion ko'rsatkich, yuklanish momenti, quvvat isrofi.

ENERGY INDICATORS OF INDUCTION MOTORS.

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Abstract: In this article, electromagnetic pointers in an asynchronous Motor, f.i.k, where the power factor and their product reach the maximum at a given value of the current, variable loss and excitation loss are equal f.i.k. information is provided that it achieves its greatest value..

Key words: Asynchronous motor, power, electromagnetic, variable, excitation loss, maximum, frequency, energy, stator, power, coefficient, voltage, optimal mode, optimal current, minimum, electro-magnetic, operational indicator, load moment, power waste.

Asinxron dvigatelning energetik diagrammasi va aylanish momentini ko'rib chiqaylik. Asinxron dvigatelning uch fazali elektr tarmog'idan olayotgan quvvati: Bu aktiv quwatning bir qismi ARM stator chulg'aminig qizishiga sarflanadi. Tarmoqdan olingan quwatning qolgan qism bu elektromagnit maydon orqali rotorga o'tadi va elektromagnit quwat deyiladi. Elektromagnit quwatning bir qismi rotor chulg'aminig qizishiga sarflanib, qolgan qismi rotorning aylanishiga sarflanadi, ya'ni mexanik quwatga aylanadi.

Mexanik quwatning bir qismi Δp_1 ishqalanishga sarflanadi, qolgan qismi esa foydali quwat bo'lib, dvigatel o'qi (vali)da aylanuvchi moment hosil qiladi:

Rotorga berilgan elektromagnit quvvati: $P_{em} = \omega_0 * M$.

E lektromagnit va mexanik quwatlarini tenglashtirib olamiz va qator soddalashtirishlardan keyin quyidagi formulani chiqaramiz: Asinxron dvigatel o'qining aylanish momenti: Demak, dvigatelning o'qidagi aylanuvchi moment sirpanishga bog'liq ekan.

Grafik va formulalarning tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, sirpanish 0 dan kritik qiymatgacha o'zgarganda asinxron dvigatel barqaror ishlaydi. Sirpanish kritik qiymatdan o'zining maksimal qiymatigacha o'zgarganda ishi barqaror bo'lmaydi. Dvigatelning eng katta (maksimal) qiymati kritik sirpanishga to'g'ri keladi. Dvigatelni yurgizish paytida sirpanish $S = 1$ bo'lib, aylanuvchi moment nominal qiymatidan kam bo'ladi, ya'ni M aylanuvchi momentga baravar boiganda rotorda rejim o'rnatiladi.

Vektor diagrammani magnit oqimdan boshlagan ma'qul, chunki magnit maydon o'zgarish kattalik bo'lib, aylansa ham shu maydonga proporsional magnit oqim rotorga nisbatan o'z yo'nalishini o'zgartirmaydi. EYK bu oqimga nisbatan 90° siljigan bo'ladi. Yurgizish paytida o'zining maksimal qiymati $S = 1$. Shu sababli rotorning toki ham maksimal qiymatiga erishib, nominal tokdan 8—12 marotaba oshadi. Lekin bu tokning aylanuvchi moment hosil qiladigan tashkil qiluvchisi. Rotoming aylanish tezligi ortgan sari sirpanishning nominal qiymati 0,06 dan $= 0,01 \div 0,06$ gacha kamayadi va demak, rotorning toki ham kamayadi. Lekin bu tokning aylanuvchi moment hosil qiladigan tashkil qiluvchisi ko'payadi. Shunday qilib, yurgizish paytida rotor toki o'zining eng katta qiymatiga ega bo'lsa ham, bu tok hosil qiladigan yurgizish momenti M aylanish momentining qiymatidan kam. Yuqorida asinxron dvigatel rotor tezligining ifodasi keltirilgan edi. Elektrtarmog'ining chastotasi o'zgarish kattalikdir. Shu sababli rotor aylanish tezligini bu yoi bilan o'zgartirish uchun maxsus chastota o'zgartirgichlardan foydalaniladi. Juft qutblar soni dvigatelni loyihalash paytida aniqlanadi. Juft qutblar soni magnit maydonni va demak, rotorning ham aylanish

tezligini o'zgartiradi. Quyidagi jadvalda juft qutblar soni va magnit maydonning aylanish tezligi ko'rsatilgan:

Juft qutblar sonini faqat maxsus dvigatellarda o'zgartirish mumkin. Rotorning aylanish tezligini bu usulda o'zgartirish qisqa tutashirilgan rotorli dvigatellarda qo'llaniladi. Sirpanishni rotor chulg'aming aktiv qarshiligini o'zgartirish yo'li bilan o'zgartirish mumkin. Bu usul faza rotorli dvigatellarda qo'llaniladi. Faza rotorli asinxron dvigatellarda rotoming har uchala chulg'ami maxsus moslama vositasida aktiv qarshilikka ulanadi. Bu aktiv qarshiliklar o'zgartirilganda sirpanish o'zgaradi va demak, rotorning aylanish tezligi ham o'zgaradi. Yuqorida dvigatelning aylanish momenti formulasini chiqargan edik.

Rotorning aylanish tezligi n kamayganda, rotorning o'qi (vali) dagi quwat o'zgarmagan holda, uning aylanish momenti ham o'zgaradi (ko'payadi). Demak, rotor chulg'amiga ulangan qarshilik o'zgarsa, aylanish momenti ham o'zgaradi. Faza rotorli dvigatellar asosan ko'tarish-tashish mashinalarida qo'llaniladi. Bu dvigatellarning geometrik o'lchovlari katta, boshqarish ancha murakkab va narxi qisqa tutashgan rotorli dvigatellarga nisbatan katta bo'lsa ham, qator afzalliklarga ega:

- a) yurgizish toki qisqa tutashgan rotorli dvigatellarga nisbatan kichik;
- b) yurgizish momenti katta;
- d) rotor aylanish tezligini pog'onali boshqarish mumkin.

Xulosa. Har qanday elektr yuritmaning (EYu) asosiy elementi elektr dvigateli (ED) hisoblanadi, u elektr energiyani (EE) mexanik energiyaga (ME) o'zgartirishni ta'minlaydi. ED va ijro organining (IO) harakatlarini moslashtirish uchun mexanik uzatuvchi qurilma (MUI) hizmat qiladi, u dvigatel hosil qilayotgan mexanik energiyani ko'rinishini va ko'rsatkichlarini o'zgartiradi. ED ni harakatlanuvchi qismi (rotor), MUI va IO elektr yuritmaning mexanik qismini tashkil qiladi. Ba'zi hollarda MUI ishlatilmaydi va bunda ED to'g'ridan - to'g'ri IO bilan biriktiriladi. Dvigatel o'ziga kerakli energiyani elektr energiya manbaidan (EEM) elektr o'zgartiruvchi qurilma (EShI) orqali oladi. EShIning vazifasi qilib, elektr energiyani ko'rsatkichlarini o'zgartirish va rostdash belgilangan

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TIBBIYOT MUASSASALARIDA AVTOMATLASHTIRISH TUSHUNCHASI

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Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda kishi hayotini avtomatlashtirish degan tushunchasiz tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi. Barcha sohalarda avtomatlashtirish, raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish ushbu jarayondagi ko'plab muammolarni yechimini topishda o'zining ijobiy ta'sirini ko'rsatmoqda. Tibbiyot muassasasi ishini avtomatlashtirish boshqa xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini avtomatlashtirishdan farq qilmaydi. Axborot texnologiyalardan foydalanish sog'liqni saqlash sohasida ham jarayonlarni soddalashtirish, vaqt resurslarini qisqartirish, ko'rsatiladigan jarayonlarda aniqlikni oshirish uchun juda foydali bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tibbiyotda avtomatlashtirish, axborot texnologiyalari, sog'liq, be'mor, xizmat ko'rsatish, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, tibbiy-profilaktika, poliklinika.

AUTOMATION CONCEPT IN MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: Today it is impossible to imagine human life without the concept of automation. Automation in all areas and the use of digital technologies have a positive effect on finding solutions to many problems in this process. Automation of the work of a medical institution is no different from automation of any other service sector. The use of information technology is also very useful in the healthcare sector to simplify processes, reduce time resources and increase the accuracy of the processes shown.

Key words: automation in medicine, information technology, health, patient, service, modern technologies, medical prevention, clinic.

So'nggi yillarda kompyuter texnologiyalaridan foydalanish har bir sohada unumdorlikni oshirishning eng samarali yo'li hisoblanadi. Sog'liqni saqlash tizimini isloh qilish va dunyodagi rivojlangan mamlakatlarning ushbu sohadagi yutuqlarining negizi ham aynan shu tajribalar va texnologiyalarga asoslanganligini hisobga olish kerak.

Bugungi kunda aholi uchun tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish va bu ko'rsatilgan xizmatlarni sifatini yanada oshirishda axborot texnologiyalarining ahamiyati juda muhim. Shuning uchun ham tibbiyot sohasida kompyuter texnologiyalari mutaxassislarining o'ziga tegishli o'rni mavjud. Hozirgi vaqtda axborotlashtirish va globallashtirish jarayonlari jadal rivojlanmoqda, o'z-o'zidan talab ham bunga mutanosib ravishda o'zgarib bormoqda. Hozirgi rivojlanayotgan axborot asrida har bir soha uchun avtomatlashtirish dolzarb bo'lib bormoqda.

Respublikaning milliy sog'liqni saqlash tizimida yagona axborot bazalarini yaratish b'yicha talaygina chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilib kelinmoqda. Bu bilan kasalliklarni barvaqt aniqlash darajasi oshadi va kasalliklarning masofali profilaktikasini joriy etish, bemor haqidagi tibbiy ma'lumotlarni darhol olish imkoni paydo bo'lgan. Uning natijasida shifokor va bemor o'rtasidagi aloqa yangi bosqichga ko'tarildi.

Avtomatlashtirish va axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning kuchayishi sog'liqni saqlashni modernizatsiya qilish, tartibga solish va yaxshilash salohiyatiga ega bo'lib, bemorlarning natijalarini yaxshilashga olib keladi. Avtomatlashtirish xodimlarning ishini optimallashtirish, moliyalashtirishni boshqarish, marketing kampaniyalarini o'tkazish, bemorlarni qabul qilish tarixini saqlash, turli jihatlar bo'yicha klinika samaradorligini tahlil qilish va boshqalar uchun kompleks dasturiy ta'minotni joriy qilishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Avtomatlashtirish xususiy va davlat tibbiyot muassasalari uchun bir xil darajada zarur. Busiz, jadval va qog'ozda qo'lda ish yuritish bilan, klinikalarda ma'lumotlar oqimlarini tez va aniq qayta ishlash mumkin emas. Umuman olganda, tibbiyot muassasasini avtomatlashtirish boshqa xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini avtomatlashtirishdan farq qilmaydi. Ammo sog'liqni saqlash sohasida avtomatlashtirish vositasini tanlashdan oldin e'tiborga olinishi kerak bo'lgan bir qator xususiyatlar mavjud:

- Tibbiyot xodimlarining funktsionalligi . Shifokorlar ish vaqtida bemorlarga sifatli e'tibor qaratishlari uchun byurokratik tartib-qoidalardan imkon qadar xalos bo'lishlari kerak. Bemorlarning so'rovlari, retseptlari va test natijalarining tuzilgan tarixi bilan elektron tibbiy yozuvlarni yuritish shifokorlarning ishini sezilarli darajada osonlashtiradi.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
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- Uchrashuv uchun onlayn navbat olish. Uchrashuv tafsilotlari bir zumda tizimga kiritilishi, qabul vaqti, shifokor va ofis avtomatik ravishda band bo'lishi muhim.
- Klinikaning veb-sayti va unda qo'llaniladigan boshqa buxgalteriya tizimlari bilan integratsiya. Bu operatsion samaradorlikni ta'minlaydi, ma'lumotlarni takrorlashning hojati yo'q va ma'muriy xodimlar uchun mehnat xarajatlarini kamaytiradi.
- Mijozlar va xodimlar o'rtasidagi aloqa kanallari, yozishmalar tarixi va qo'ng'iroq yozuvlarini saqlash.
- Elektron navbatni saqlash, bu tashrif buyuruvchilarni uchrashuvni uzoq kutishlardan qutqarish imkonini beradi.
- Shifokorlarning ish yuklamasi va shaxsiy jadvaliga muvofiq ish jadvalini tartibga solish.
- Kompaniya ichida ham, hamkorlar va pudratchilar bilan ham elektron hujjat aylanishi.
- Har xil darajadagi tafsilotlar bilan har qanday parametrlar bo'yicha hisobot berish.
- Mijozlarga kelgusi uchrashuvlar, xizmatlarga taklifnomalar va reklama aksiyalari haqida eslatmalarni yuborish.

Tibbiyot tashkilotlarini avtomatlashtirish uchun ixtisoslashtirilgan sanoat boshqaruv tizimlari optimal yo'naltirilgan. Umumjahon CRM asosiy muammolarni hal qilishni ta'minlaydi, ammo xodimlar doimo tibbiy faoliyat bilan bog'liq ixtisoslashtirilgan funktsiyalarning etarli emasligi bilan muammolarga duch kelishadi. Shunda menejment bu muammoni hal qilishi kerak bo'ladi: yoki oldini olish mumkin bo'lgan noqulayliklar va qo'shimcha mehnat xarajatlarini qabul qilib, hamma narsani avvalgidек qoldirishi yoki boshqa yechim topishi zarur.

Tibbiyot muassasalarida avtomatlashtirish jarayoni muassasalarida mavjud bo'lgan bir qator muammolarni hal qiladi:

- ✓ Bemorning kasallik tarixlarini, uchrashuvlarni, yo'riqnomalarni, tahlil natijalarini va boshqa hujjatlarni doimiy chop etishda katta miqdordagi qog'ozni isrof qilish.
- ✓ Turli manbalardan tayinlash yozuvlarini sinxronlashtirish, ularning takrorlanishi va yo'qolishi.
- ✓ Ro'yxatdan o'tishda chalkashlik, vaqtni behuda o'tkazish va aniq rejalashtirishning imkoni yo'qligi sababli bemorning noroziligi sababli qabulxona va ofislarda navbatlar.
- ✓ Bemorning qog'oz tibbiy yozuvida kerakli ma'lumotlarni uzoq vaqt qidirish.

- ✓ Hujjatlarni o‘qib bo‘lmaydigan qo‘l yozuvi bilan to‘ldirish, bu bemorlarni bezovta qiladi va raqamlashtirish uchun keng ko‘lamli harakatlarni talab qiladi.
- ✓ Bemorning tibbiy kartasini qog‘oz formatda saqlash reestrda saqlash va davriy muqarrar yo‘qotishlar shifokorga uni tezda o‘rganish va ma’lumotlarni kiritish imkonsiz qiladi.
- ✓ Shifokorlarning notekis ish yuki, jadval va taqvim tuzishdagi qiyinchiliklar.
- ✓ Uchrashuvni eslatish yoki rejalashtirilgan tibbiy ko‘rikga taklifnoma bilan mijozlarni qo‘lda qo‘ng‘iroq qilish uchun mehnat xarajatlari.
- ✓ Test va imtihon natijalarini qo‘lda tarqatish.
- ✓ Cheklangan hisobot diapazoni, bu klinika faoliyatining to‘liq, shaffof rasmini ko‘rish imkoniyatini qoldirmaydi.

Tibbiy axborot tizimi birinchi navbatda avtomatlashtirishni talab qiladigan muhim funksiyalarni ta’kidlab, bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Tibbiyot sohasida axborot tizimini joriy etish bo‘yicha kompleks loyiha uzoq vaqt talab qilishi mumkin, ayniqsa, xodimlarning ko‘pchiligi kompyuter bilimlari past bo‘lsa – ularni yangi tizimdan foydalanishga o‘rgatish uchun vaqt kerak bo‘ladi.

Tibbiyot muassasalarini avtomatlashtirishning o‘ziga xos funksiyalari orasida quyidagi asosiy xususiyatlarni ajratib ko‘rsatish mumkin:

- Bemorlarni bo‘sh vaqt oraliq‘ida onlayn ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazish imkoniyati.
- Xodimlarning ish jadvallari va ofisda bandlik jadvallari bilan interaktiv kalendar xizmati.
- Barcha bemor yozuvlarini bitta kirish nuqtasidan boshqarish, ularning takrorlanishi yoki yo‘qolishini bartaraf etish.
- Bemorlar ma’lumotlar bazasini yuritish, shu jumladan tibbiyot muassalariga tashriflarning to‘liq tarixi, uchrashuvlar va tahlil natijalari.
- Elektron tibbiy yozuvni shakllantirish.
- Klinikada operativ hujjatlar aylanishi - shifokor tahlil natijalarini, hamkasblaridan o‘z bemorlarining tekshiruvlarini oladi va hokazo.
- Dastur interfeysidan qo‘ng‘iroqlar va yozishmalar qilish, mijozlar bilan aloqalar tarixini avtomatik ravishda saqlash.
- Bir zumda tibbiy hujjatlarni olish va ularni ixtiyoriy chop etish uchun yuborish.
- Mijozlarga uchrashuv eslatmalarini yuborish, yangi xizmatlar, reklama aksiyalari va boshqalar haqida maqsadli bildirishnomalar.
- Klinikadagi ishlarning holatini ko‘p darajali boshqaruv tahlili uchun hisobotlarni olish.
- Shifokorlarning ish yukini, KPI va boshqa individual sxemalarni hisobga olgan holda ish haqini hisoblash.

➤ Sarf materiallari, dori vositalarining ombor hisobi.

Yuqorida faqat faoliyatning tibbiy jihatlari bilan bevosita bog‘liq bo‘lgan funktsionallik ro‘yxati keltirilgan. Shu bilan birga, tibbiyot muassasalarini avtomatlashtiradigan ko‘pgina sanoat axborot tizimlari moliyaviy hisob, marketing, boshqa dasturlar bilan integratsiya va boshqalar bilan bog‘liq universal funktsiyalarni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Tibbiy-profilaktika muassasalarining tizimlari - tibbiy markaz yoki markazlar tarmog‘ining ishini avtomatlashtirish, bo‘limlar faoliyatini sinxronlashtirish uchun mo‘ljallangan. Ular ikki turga bo‘linadi va ikkalasining faoliyati ixtisoslashtirilgan dasturiy mahsulotlarning standart vositalaridan foydalangan holda avtomatlashtiriladi:

1. Poliklinikalar, poliklinikalar, konsultatsiyalar, dispanserlar, tibbiyot bo‘limlari va tez tibbiy yordam stansiyalarini o‘z ichiga olgan ambulatoriya sog‘liqni saqlash muassasalari.
2. Statsionar sog‘liqni saqlash muassasalari - shifoxonalar, poliklinikalar, kasalxonalar, tug‘ruqxonalar, sanatoriylar va hokazo.

Axborot banklari - bu tibbiy muassasalar to‘g‘risidagi ma’lumotlar majmuasini o‘z ichiga olgan tizimlar.

Shaxsiylashtirilgan bemorlar registrlari - muassasadagi bemorlar to‘g‘risidagi umumiy tibbiy ma’lumotlar.

Tibbiyot muassasalarini avtomatlashtirish qanday muammolarni hal qiladi?

Tibbiyot muassasalarini avtomatlashtirish bir qator ustuvor vazifalarni hal qiladi:

- Muassasaning barcha biznes jarayonlari va umuman uning faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish.
- Klinikaning yagona markazlashtirilgan tibbiy ma’lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish.
- Tibbiyot xodimlari klinika ichidagi hujjatlar aylanishining sustligi, retsept va retseptlarni qo‘lda yozish va hokazolar bilan bog‘liq muntazam tartib-qoidalarga chalg‘imasdan, o‘zlarining bevosita vazifalariga ko‘proq vaqt ajratishlari tufayli diagnostika va davolash sifatini oshirish.
- Bemorlarni o‘z vaqtida xabardor qilish, klinik ko‘rikdan o‘tish muddati va boshqa profilaktika muolajalari to‘g‘risidagi xabarlarni avtomatik ravishda tarqatish orqali kasallikning oldini olish samaradorligini oshirish.
- Har bir shifokorning shaxsiy jadvalini hisobga olgan holda ularni qabul qilish jadvali ko‘rsatilgan kalendarni yuritish va qaysi davrlar va qaysi mutaxassislariga talab ko‘proq ekanligini tahlil qilish imkonini beruvchi hisobotlarni yuritish orqali shifokorlarning ish yukini barqarorlashtirish.

- Xizmat ko'rsatish darajasini oshirish va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda muassasa haqida ma'lumotni muvofiqlashtirish, bemorlarning sharhlariga javob yozish va boshqalar orqali klinikaning obro'sini boshqarish.
- Klinika faoliyati bo'yicha dolzarb va ko'p qirrali hisobotlarni shakllantirish, rahbariyatga zaif tomonlarni ko'rish, xavflarni hisobga olish va ularni zararsizlantirish uchun o'z vaqtida choralar ko'rish imkonini beradi.
- Xarajatlar va mablag'larning tushumlari to'g'risidagi haqiqiy ma'lumotlar asosida klinikani moliyalashtirishni boshqarish.
- Muntazam operatsiyalar uchun mehnat xarajatlarini kamaytirish, ma'muriy xodimlarning vaqtini bo'shatish, bu ularga bemorlarni parvarish qilish sifatiga ko'proq e'tibor berish imkonini beradi.
- Ularning samaradorligini chuqur tahlil qilgan holda marketing faoliyatini olib borish, turli savdo kanallari faoliyatini kuzatish.

Avtomatlashtirish yechimini tanlashda muqobil yechim topishda tibbiyot muassasasi tomonidan talab qilinadigan funksional modullar to'plamiga, egalik qilishning umumiy qiymatiga, boshqa tizimlar bilan integratsiyalashuv variantiga, texnik va axborot yordamining mavjudligiga va bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshirish imkoniyatiga e'tibor berishni tavsiya qilinadi.

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TA'LIM TIZIMLARI SIFATINI KOMPLEKS BAHOLASHNING KVALIMETRIK MODEL I

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Annotatsiya: *Barcha ta'lim tizimlari baholash va uning tartibiga katta ahamiyat beradi. Bu shunisi bilan izohlanadiki, baholash turli baholash sub'ektlari (davlat organlari, ta'lim organlari, pedagogik xodimlar, o'quvchilar, ota-onalar va boshqalar) ta'lim natijalarining samaradorlik darajasini aniqlash imkonini beradi va hokazo.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Baholash, kvalimetriyada baholash, samaradorlik darajasi, ta'lim organlari*

QUALIMETRIC MODEL OF COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *All educational systems attach great importance to assessment and its procedure. This is explained by the fact that assessment makes it possible to determine the level of effectiveness of educational results of various subjects of assessment (government authorities, educational authorities, teaching staff, students, parents, etc.), etc.*

Key words: *Assessment, qualitative assessment, level of effectiveness, educational institutions*

Baholash tushunchasi endilikda nafaqat o'quvchilar va ularning yutuqlari, balki muassasaning o'zi, uning professor-o'qituvchilari, tashqi aloqalari va butun ta'lim tizimiga ham ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Baholash zaruriyati ham davlat, ham jamiyat tomonidan tan olingan, biroq amalga oshirish ancha qiyinligicha qolmoqda. Hozirgi vaqtda mavjud miqdoriy yondashuvlar juda umumiy bo'lib, ta'lim muassasasi faoliyatining xilma-xilligini to'liq aks ettirmaydi, sifatli yondashuvlar asosan sub'ektiv bo'lib qolmoqda. Shu sababli, ta'lim sifatini boshqarishning zamonaviy nazariyasi va amaliyotidagi muhim muammo - baholash maqsadlari va usullarini ishlab chiqishdir.

Ta'lim kvalimetriyasi ko'rsatilgan muammoning barcha xilma-xilligini hisobga olgan holda ta'lim tizimining sifatini baholashning eng to'liq va amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan yondashuviga aylanishi mumkin [2,3].

Kvalimetriya ilmiy yo'nalish sifatida ob'ektlar yoki jarayonlar sifatining miqdoriy tavsifi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, har qanday hodisa va ob'ektlar sifatini murakkab miqdoriy baholashni ishlab chiqish metodologiyasi va muammolarini o'rganadi. Pedagogik (tarbiyaviy) kvalimetriya mustaqil yo'nalish sifatida vujudga keldi, u psixologik, pedagogik va didaktik ob'ektlarni har tomonlama baholashda kvalimetrik usullarni qo'llash tushuniladi. Uning asoslari G.G. kabi mahalliy olimlarning asarlarida qo'yilgan. Azgaldov, A.I. Subetto, N.A. Selezneva, S.I. Arxangelskiy, I.B. Itelson, V.P. Mizintsev, N.M. Rosenberg, A.M. Sochor, M.M. Potashnik, shuningdek, xorijiy va boshqa olimlar.

Ta'lim uchun kvalimetriyaning uslubiy ahamiyati tabiatan nomoddiy bo'lgan ta'lim tizimlari ob'ektlarining sifatini, uning turli xil xususiyatlari va xususiyatlarining ko'pligiga qaramay, bitta miqdoriy ko'rsatkich bilan ifodalashning fundamental imkoniyatidir.

Kvalimetriyada baholash (baholash) baholash ob'ekti haqida qiymat mulohazalarini shakllantirishga qaratilgan boshqaruv funksiyasining (faoliyatining) maxsus turi sifatida belgilanadi. Ushbu pozitsiyalardan sifatni baholash ob'ekt sifat tushunchalaridan biri bo'lgan baholash turi sifatida qaraladi. Sifatni baholash, bir tomondan, qiymat munosabatlari tizimida sifatni o'lchashning alohida holati bo'lsa, ikkinchi tomondan, sifatni o'lchash tizimini o'z ichiga oladi.

Ta'lim kvalimetriyasi doirasida baholash tartibi ikki muhim bosqichdan iborat: ob'ektning xususiyatlarini o'lchash va o'lchangan xususiyatlarni haqiqiy baholash. Ushbu bayonot ta'lim tizimlari sifatining funksional-maqsadli kontseptsiyasiga kontseptual yondashuvdir.

Ta'lim tizimi ob'ektlarining sifatini tashqi baholash baholash sub'ektining shaxsiy imtiyozlari prizmasi orqali amalga oshiriladi, bunda biz sifatni ta'minlash tizimida ishtirok etayotgan ta'lim sifatiga qiziqqan tomonlarni ta'lim sifatini ta'minlashni talab qiladigan mutaxassislar sifatida tushunamiz. baholash bosqichida ta'lim muassasasining turli jihatlari bo'yicha o'z fikrlarini bildirish. Ilmiy-amaliy nuqtai nazardan, ta'limni baholash ijtimoiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan va ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirish amaliyotida e'tiborga olinishi kerak bo'lgan to'rtta sub'ektni - davlat, ta'lim tizimining o'zi, o'quvchi va ota-onalar uning manfaatlari vakillari sifatida va jamoat tuzilmalari. Ta'lim tizimi jamiyat ehtiyojlari asosida shakllanadi, uning manfaatlari davlat tomonidan tegishli ta'lim organlari orqali ifodalanadi [5].

Ta'lim muassasasining sifat ko'rsatkichlari qatorini tavsiflash uchun baholash modeli to'g'risida qaror qabul qilish kerak. Baholash modeli deganda umuman ta'lim tizimining samaradorligini belgilovchi muhim boshqariladigan ko'rsatkichlar tizimi tushuniladi, bunda tizimning mulki, sifati alohida elementlar yig'indisiga kamaymaydi va ta'lim sub'ekti bilan o'zaro ta'sir qilish natijasida aniqlanadi. boshqaruv va tashqi muhit.

Ta'lim sifati ko'rsatkichlarining tuzilishi va nomenklaturasini tavsiflash uchun biz tizim ichidagi ko'rsatkichlarni baholash modelidan (qiymatga yo'naltirilgan model), kirish ko'rsatkichlarini baholash modelidan (normaga yo'naltirilgan model) va samaradorlik natijalariga asoslangan baholash modelidan (maqsadga yo'naltirilgan) foydalanamiz. model), G.N tomonidan tasvirlangan. Motova va V.G. Navodnov, shuningdek, kompleks baholash modeli [1,2].

Tadqiqotda tizim ichidagi ko'rsatkichlarni baholash modeli tashqi muhitning, shu jumladan boshqaruv sub'ektining obro'si va tan olinishini shakllantiradigan qiymatga yo'naltirilgan parametrlarni ustuvor tanlashga ega bo'lgan baholash tizimini anglatadi, jarayonga alohida e'tibor beriladi (va natijasi emas) kasbiy faoliyat sifatida o'qitish va o'quv jarayoni.

Kirish ko'rsatkichlarini baholash modeli nazorat qilinadigan (bu holda normallashtirilgan) va rasmiy ravishda boshqariladigan parametrlarni ustuvor tanlashga ega bo'lgan baholash tizimi bilan bog'liq. Ushbu model belgilangan standartlarga (standart, standart) qat'iy rioya qilishni tavsiflaydi, tizimning samaradorligini va kutilgan natijalarni ta'minlaydi. Bu holda kirish ko'rsatkichlarini baholash me'yoriy talablarga muvofiqligini baholash sifatida qaraladi.

Samaradorlikni baholash modeli maqsadlarga yo'naltirilgan parametrlarni tanlash va belgilangan maqsadlarga erishish darajasi bilan tavsiflangan yutuqlarni baholash tizimi sifatida tushuniladi. Ushbu yondashuv samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlari asosida ta'lim dasturining maqsadlariga erishishni aniqlash bilan bog'liq. Ushbu modelning asosiy g'oyasi jamiyat, o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar manfaatlarini hisobga olgan holda ta'lim maqsadlarini shakllantirishga tavsiflovchi yondashuvdir [4].

Integratsiyalashgan baholash modeli deganda ko'rsatkichlarni tanlash maqsadga yo'naltirilgan va qiymatga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv bilan belgilanadigan baholash tizimi tushuniladi. Ushbu modeldagi aniqlovchi ko'rsatkichlar jarayon ko'rsatkichlari hisoblanadi. Uning boshqa modellardan tub farqi shundaki, jarayon ko'rsatkichlari samaradorlik va samaradorlik orqali har tomonlama baholanadi. Ushbu model baholashning 4 turini birlashtiradi: maqsadni baholash, o'quv faoliyati sharoitlarini baholash, o'quv jarayonining o'zini baholash, natijalarni baholash.

Ushbu model, bizning fikrimizcha, universal bo'lib, uni har xil turdagi va turdagi ta'lim muassasalarini baholashda qo'llash imkonini beradi.

Yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, ta'lim tizimi ochiqlik kabi xususiyatga ega. Bu shuni anglatadiki, ta'lim natijalariga ta'sir qiluvchi, ammo boshqaruv tizimlaridan mustaqil bo'lgan omillar mavjud. Shu sababli, ta'lim sifatini baholashda, ulardan mustaqil ravishda sezilarli darajada farq qiluvchi sharoitlarda joylashgan ta'lim tizimlaridan bir xil natijalarni (va shuning uchun taqqoslash uchun asos) talab qilish mumkin emas. Shu tufayli

Baholash uchun taqqoslash bazasini tanlash quyidagilarga bog'liq:

1) baholash maqsadiga va 2) ma'muriy-hududiy birlik rivojlanishining o'ziga xos ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sharoitlariga (bu mintaqa, submunitsipal hudud, katta hudud bo'lishi mumkin). shahar, sanoat shahri, qishloq hududi, yopiq ma'muriy-hududiy birlik).

Funksional-maqsadli kontsepsiyaning shakllantirilgan tamoyillari asosida kvalimetrik yondashuvni kontseptual jihatdan birlashtirilgan va izchil qilish mumkin: sifat ko'rsatkichlarning ierarxik tuzilishi bilan tavsiflanadi; ko'rsatkichlar har tomonlama baholashga hissa qo'shishda teng emas; ularning tabaqalanishi maqom (dominant, kompensatsiyalangan) va guruh ichidagi ahamiyatga egalik koeffitsientlari ko'rinishida belgilanishi asosida amalga oshiriladi; baholarning ko'rsatkichlarga bog'liqligi proporsional emas va kamayuvchi, ortib borayotgan, mahalliy va qo'ng'iroq shaklidagi funktsiyalar

bilan tavsiflanadi; Alohida ko'rsatkichni baholash uchun ekspert usuli uning individual va mos yozuvlar nuqtalarini aniqlaydi.

Umuman olganda, ta'lim kvalimetriyasi pedagogik va boshqaruv muammolarini hal qilishda texnologik va optimal yondashuvni tushunishga yangicha yondashish imkonini beradi. U o'z vaqtida optimal tarzda tashkil etilgan eng to'liq va mavzuga oid ma'lumotlarni taqdim etadi, bu esa ta'lim tizimining alohida elementlarining ham, umuman ta'lim tizimining o'zining ham samarali ishlashi uchun asos yaratadi [5].

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ZAMONAVIY DASTGOHLARNI SANOATDA QO‘LANILISHI

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Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sektori bilan bog'liq mavzuda maqola yoziladi. Maqolada muhim muammo va ularning yechimlari ko'rsatiladi. Muammo shu jihatdan ko'p yondashuvni talab qiladi, chunki sanoat sohasidagi korxonalarining zamonaviy dastgohlardan qanday foydalanishini o'rganish kerak. Bu esa, sanoat korxonalarining yangi texnologiyalar bilan ta'minlash va ulardan foydalanishni o'rganish, xalqaro raqobatbardoshlikni saqlash va ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini samarali, tezkor va isloh qilishga qanday ta'sir etishini tushunishga muhtoj. Maqolada dastgohlarni sanoatda qo'llashning muhim aspektlari, maslahatlar va muammolar haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi. Yechimlar esa infrastruktur va resurslarni ta'minlash, xodimlar va kadrlarni o'rgatish, moliyaviy to'lovlarni ta'minlash, innovatsiyalar va rivojlanishni ragbatlantirish, normativ-huquqiy muhitni rivojlantirish kabi masalalar ustida yo'llanma beriladi. Maqola, zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat korxonalarida muvaffaqiyatli qo'llab-quvvatlash va ulardan foydalanishning muhimligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy dastgohlar, sanoat sektori, korxonalar, muammo, yangi texnologiyalar, innovatsiya, xodimlar

INDUSTRIAL APPLICATION OF MODERN MACHINE TOOLS

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Annotation: this article will write an article on the topic of modern machine tools related to the industrial sector. The article will show an important problem and their solutions. The problem requires a lot of approach in this regard, since it is necessary to study how enterprises in the industrial sector

use modern machines. This requires an understanding of how industrial enterprises can learn to supply and use new technologies, maintain international competitiveness, and influence efficient, rapid, and Reform production processes. The article provides information on important aspects of the industrial application of machine tools, tips and problems. Solutions will be guided on issues such as infrastructure and resource provision, staff and staff training, financial payment provision, innovation and development, and regulatory environment development. The article shows the importance of successfully supporting and using modern machine tools in industrial enterprises.

Keywords: *modern machine tools, industrial sector, enterprises, problem, new technologies, innovation, staff*

Kirish. Sanoat sektori, inson hayotining asosiy qismidir va uning rivojlanishi hamda yuqori natijalar olishi hukumatlar va korxonalarining asosiy maqsadlari orasida bo‘ladi. Bu sektor esa zamonaviy dastgohlarni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va ulardan foydalanish bilan muhim boylikka erishgan bo‘lib, bu maqsadga erishish uchun ilg‘or innovatsiyalar va yangi texnologiyalar kiritilayotgan. Zamonaviy dastgohlar, avtomatlashtirilgan, intellektual, va interaktiv funksiyalarga ega bo‘lgan sifatli dasturlar, qurilmalar va tizimlardir. Bu dastgohlar, avtomatik ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini boshqarish, ma‘lumotlar analizini amalga oshirish, boshqaruv tizimlarini optimallashtirish, va ishlab chiqarishni takomillashtirish kabi bir qancha vazifalarni bajarishda yordam beradi.

Sanoat korxonalarining zamonaviy dastgohlardan foydalanishi, ularga bir qancha afzalliklar taqdim etadi. Korxonalar ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini samaraliroq, tezkor va isloh qilish imkonini beradi. Zamonaviy dastgohlar, oddiy va qisqa vaqt ichida ko‘plab vazifalarni bajarishga imkon yaratadi va xatolar miqdorini minimallashtiradi. Buning natijasida, korxonada daromadini oshirish, ishlab chiqarishni kengaytirish va sifatni yuksaltirish mumkin bo‘ladi. Ikkinchidan, zamonaviy dastgohlar sanoat korxonalariga innovatsiyalar va rivojlanishni rag‘batlantirishda ham muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Bu dastgohlar, yangi ideyalarni boshqarish, yangi mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqish, va sanoat korxonalarining rivojlanishini ko‘tarish imkoniyatlarini yaratishda katta yordam

beradi. Ularga yangi xalqaro bozorlarga kirish, raqobatbardoshlikni saqlash va kengaytirishga imkon beradi.

Lekin, zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat korxonalarida qo'llashning muhim aspektlariga e'tibor berish zarur. Birinchidan, infrastruktur va resurslarni ta'minlash uchun kuchli asosiy tayyorgarliklar kerak bo'ladi. Zamonaviy dastgohlar uchun yuqori tezlikli internet ulanishlari, qulay ma'lumot saqlash tizimlari, va kuchli kompyuter tarmoqlari ta'minlanishi zarur. Bundan tashqari, xodimlar va kadrlar zamonaviy dastgohlarni tushunish va ulardan foydalanish jarayonlarini o'rganish uchun yaxshi tayyorlanishlari lozim. Boshqa muhim masala moliyaviy to'lovlarning ta'minlanishidir. Zamonaviy dastgohlar narxli bo'lishi mumkin va ularni olish, o'rnatish, va ulardan foydalanish qiymat bo'lishi mumkin. Sanoat korxonalarining moliyaviy resurslarni ta'minlash va to'lovlarni amalga oshirish uchun ilg'or strategiyalar va loyihalar ishlab chiqishlari zarur.

Zamonaviy dastgohlar, avtomatlashtirish, robototexnika, ishlab chiqarish tizimlari va boshqa sohalarda rivojlangan yangi texnologiyalardan iborat. Ular, avtomatik jarayonlarni boshqarish, ma'lumotlar analizini amalga oshirish, intellektual va avtomatik ish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish, va ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini takomillashtirishga yordam beradi. Bu dastgohlar, ishlab chiqarishning tezlashtirilishi, xatolar miqdorining kamayishi va xavfsizlik darajasining oshishi kabi afzalliklarni beradi. Sanoat korxonalarining zamonaviy dastgohlardan foydalanishining muhim sabablaridan biri, ularga samarali va tezkor ish jarayonlari ta'minlash imkonini berishidir. Zamonaviy dastgohlar, o'z-o'zini boshqaradigan jarayonlarni bajarish, avtomatik ravishda mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish, katta miqdorda ma'lumotlarni to'plash va tahlil qilish, tarkibiy qism va qurilmalarni monitoring qilish va boshqarish kabi vazifalarni bajarishda yordam beradi. Bundan tashqari, zamonaviy dastgohlar sanoat korxonalariga innovatsiyalar va rivojlanishni rag'batlantirish imkonini beradi. Bu dastgohlar, yangi mahsulotlar va xizmatlarni ishlab chiqish, tezroq bozorlarga kirish, tahlil va tahlil qilish jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirish va korxonalarining kengayishini oshirishga imkon beradi. Buning natijasida sanoat korxonalarining rivojlanishi, yangi bozorlarda raqobatbardoshligini saqlash va iste'molchilar talablariga javob berish imkoniyatlari ortadi. Shu bilan birga, zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat korxonalarida qo'llashning muhim aspektlari ham mavjud. Bu dastgohlar uchun kerakli infrastruktur va resurslarni ta'minlash, xodimlarni o'rgatish va ulardan foydalanishning qulayligini ta'minlash, moliyaviy to'lov sistemalarini amalga oshirish, normativ-huquqiy muhitni rivojlantirish kabi muhim masalalar ko'rishga muhtoj.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. Zamonaviy dastgohlar sanoat sohasida boshqaruv, ishlab chiqarish, va takomillashtirish jarayonlarini optimallashtirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan texnologiyalardir. Bu dastgohlar, sanoat korxonalariga samarali va tezkor ish jarayonlari, avtomatiklik, ma'lumotlar analizi va optimallashtirish imkonini beradi. Bu esa adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlari orqali zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sohasida qo'llashning muhim jihatlarini tushunishga yordam beradi. Adabiyotlar tahlili, ilmiy tadqiqotlar, maqolalar, kitoblar, maqolalar, konferensiyalar va boshqa ilmiy manbalar ko'rinishidagi ma'lumotlar analizi va bahsilashdir. Bu tahlil va metodlar, zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sohasida qo'llashning muhim aspektlarini o'rganish, eng yaxshi amaliyotlarni aniqlash, xususiyatlarni tahlil qilish va rivojlanish uchun yuqori kafolatlarni ta'minlashda muhim vazifalarni bajarishga yordam beradi.

Zamonaviy dastgohlar sanoat sohasida qo'llanilishining adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlariga quyidagi muhim jihatlar kiradi:

Soha tahlili: Bu tahlil, zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sohasida qo'llashning umumiy holatini o'rganish uchun muhimdir. Bu, sanoat sohasidagi zamonaviy dastgohlar, ularning innovatsion yutuqlari, rivojlanish darajasi va korxonalarining ularni qo'llashga qanday tayyorgarlikka ega bo'lishi haqida ma'lumotlar beradi. Soha tahlili, sanoat korxonalarining yangi texnologiyalardan foydalanishda qaysi muammolar bilan yuzlashganini tushunishga imkon beradi.

Soha-tashkilotlar o'rtasida hamkorlikni baholash: Bu tahlil, zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sohasida qo'llashning sanoat korxonalarining ishbilarmonligini oshirish uchun moslashtirilgan metodlarini o'rganishga yordam beradi. Bu tahlil orqali, sanoat korxonalarining zamonaviy dastgohlardan qanday foydalanishlari, ularning xavfsizlik va sifat standartlariga qanday rioya qilishlari, ishchi kuchlarni oshirish va innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish uchun qanday hamkorliklarni o'rnatishlari haqida ma'lumotlar topish mumkin.

Ta'lim va kadrlar tahlili: Bu tahlil, zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sohasida qo'llashning muhim jihatlaridan biri bo'lgan xodimlar tayyorlash va ulardan foydalanish jarayonlarini o'rganishga yordam beradi. Bu tahlil orqali, sanoat korxonalarining xodimlarini zamonaviy dastgohlarni tushunish, ulardan foydalanish va ularning ish faoliyatini takomillashtirish uchun qanday ta'lim va tayyorlanishlarini o'rganish mumkin.

Innovatsiyalarni baholash: Zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sohasida qo'llashning muhim jihatlari innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirishdan iborat. Bu tahlil, sanoat korxonalarining innovatsiyalarni qanday yaratish, ulardan qanday foydalanish va ularning sanoat sohasidagi o'rnini oshirish jarayonlarini

o'rganishga yordam beradi. Bu tahlil orqali, sanoat korxonalarining innovatsiya loyihalarini baholash, ularning innovatsion potensialini aniqlash, va yangi ideyalarni o'rganish va ulardan foydalanish uchun qanday tizimlarni o'rnatish imkonini beradi.

Sanoat korxonalarining ma'lumotlarni saqlash va tahlil qilish sistemlarini tuzish: Bu tahlil, zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sohasida qo'llashning muhim jihatlaridan biri bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni saqlash, analiz qilish va optimallashtirishni o'rganishga yordam beradi. Bu tahlil orqali, sanoat korxonalarining ma'lumotlar bazalarini qanday tuzish, ularni ma'lumotlar analizi va prognostika jarayonlariga qanday bog'lash, ma'lumotlar tahlilining sifati va samaradorligini oshirish imkonini beradi.

Zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoat sohasida qo'llashning adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlari, sanoat korxonalarining innovatsiya va rivojlanish jarayonlarini o'rganish, ularning ishbilarmonligini oshirish, ta'lim va kadrlarni tayyorlash, innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish va ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va optimallashtirish jarayonlarini aniqlashga yordam beradi.

Bu tahlil va metodlar, sanoat sohasidagi dastgohlarni samarali va tezkor ish jarayonlari, avtomatiklik, ma'lumotlar analizi va optimallashtirish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, ular sanoat korxonalariga yangi ideyalarni o'rganish, ularni innovatsiyalarni yaratish va ulardan foydalanishda yuqori kafolatlarni ta'minlashga imkon beradi.

Xulosa. Zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoatda qo'lanilishi mavzusida olib borilgan adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlar, sanoat sohasidagi dastgohlarni rivojlantirishda muhim natijalarga olib keladi. Bu tahlil va metodlar sanoat korxonalarining qo'llagan zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanishda yuqori samaralar olishi, ish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish, innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va sanoatning boshqa jihatlarini takomillashtirish imkoniyatlari ochiladi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlarining natijalari quyidagicha ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

Innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish: Zamonaviy dastgohlar sanoat sohasida qo'llanilishiga oid adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlari, innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish uchun muhim vazifalarni bajarishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu tahlil va metodlar sanoat korxonalariga yangi ideya va loyihalarni o'rganish, innovatsion potensialni aniqlash, ish faoliyatini rivojlantirishning yuqori darajalariga yetkazishga yordam beradi. Natijada sanoat korxonalarida

innovatsiyalar kengayadi, yangi mahsulotlar va xizmatlar yaratiladi, bozor bo'yicha raqobatga tayyorlanish imkoniyati oshiriladi.

Ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va optimallashtirish: Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlari, sanoat korxonalarining ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va optimallashtirish jarayonlarini kuchsizlashtirishda o'rnatilgan. Bu tahlil va metodlar orqali, sanoat korxonalarining ma'lumotlar bazalarini tuzish, ma'lumotlarni to'plab olish, analiz qilish va prognostika jarayonlariga bog'lash, ma'lumotlar tahlilining sifati va samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatini beradi. Natijada sanoat korxonalarida ma'lumotlar bilan ishlashning samaradorligi oshadi, qarorlar o'z vaqtida olingan ma'lumotlarga asoslangan bo'ladi va takliflar va strategiyalarni rivojlantirishga imkon beradi.

Korxonatashkilotlar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni rivojlantirish: Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlari, sanoat korxonalarining boshqa tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikni rivojlantirishda o'rnatilgan. Bu tahlil va metodlar orqali, sanoat korxonalarining hamkorlikning muhimligini tushunish, qaysi sohalarda hamkorlikni oshirish kerakligini aniqlash, hamkorlik potensialini belgilash va ishbirligi yo'nalishlarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlarini yaratish mumkin bo'ladi. Natijada sanoat korxonalarining boshqa tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikni o'rnatish, resurslar o'zaro almashish va innovatsion loyihalarni birgalikda rivojlantirish imkoniyati oshadi.

Jamiyatimizda zamonaviy dastgohlarni sanoatda qo'llash adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlari natijasida xususiy samaralar olishadi. Bu samaralar orqali, sanoat korxonalarining rivojlanishi, innovatsiyalar yaratishlari, ish faoliyatini optimallashtirishlari va hamkorlikni rivojlantirishlari muhim darajada oshiriladi. Bular hamkorlik, yuqori samaralar olish, ish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish, innovatsiyalar va ma'lumotlardan samarali foydalanish asosida amalga oshiriladi.

Zamonaviy dastgohlarning sanoat sektorida qo'llanilishi, sanoat korxonalarining rivojlanishini, innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirishini, ish faoliyatini optimallashtirishini va hamkorlikni rivojlantirishini ta'minlaydi. Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlar sanoat korxonalariga bir qancha imkoniyatlar beradi:

Avtomatlashtirish: Zamonaviy dastgohlar sanoat korxonalarining ish jarayonlarini avtomatlash imkonini beradi. Bunda adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlar orqali ish jarayonlari optimallashtiriladi, ish faoliyati samarali va tezkor bo'ladi.

Ma'lumotlar tahlili: Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlar sanoat korxonalariga ma'lumotlardan samarali foydalanish imkonini beradi. Bu ma'lumotlar bazalarini tuzish, analiz qilish va prognostika qilish imkoniyatlarini oshiradi. Bunda sanoat korxonalarining ma'lumotlar bilan ishlashning samaradorligi oshadi.

Hamkorlikni rivojlantirish: Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlar sanoat korxonalariga tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikni rivojlantirish imkonini beradi. Bu esa resurslar bilan samarali foydalanish, ishbirligi yo'nalishlarini rivojlantirish va innovatsion loyihalarni birgalikda rivojlantirishga imkoniyatlar yaratadi.

Barcha bu imkoniyatlar natijasida sanoat korxonalarining rivojlanishi, innovatsiyalar yaratishlari va ish faoliyatini optimallashtirishlari oshadi. Bu esa sanoat sektoriga yangi texnologiyalar, samarador ish jarayonlari va hamkorlik imkoniyatlari ochilishini ta'minlaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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ASINXRON MOTORNING OPTIMAL REJIMI: CHIZIQLI BO'LMAGAN OMILLARNING TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada asinxron motorda elektromagnit ko'rsatgichlar, f.i.k, quvvat koeffitsienti va ularning ko'paytmasi oqimning ma'lum qiymatida maksimumga erishishi, o'zgaruvchan nobudgarchilik va qo'zg'atish nobudgarchilik teng bo'lganda f.i.k. o'zining eng katta qiymatiga erishishi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: asinxron motor, quvvat, elektromagnit, nobudgarchilili, qo'zg'atish nobudgarchiligi, maksimum, chastota, energetika, stator, quvvat, koeffitsient, kuchlanish, optimal rejim, optimal oqim, minimal, elektro-magnit, ekspluatatsion ko'rsatkich, yuklanish momenti, quvvat isrofi.

OPTIMAL MODE OF AN ASYNCHRONOUS MOTOR: THE EFFECT OF NONLINEAR FACTORS

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Annotation. In this article, electromagnetic indicators, f.i.k., power factor and their product in an induction motor reach a maximum at a certain current value, f.i.k. information about reaching its maximum value is given.

Key words: asynchronous motor, power, electromagnetic, stability, excitation stability, maximum, frequency, energy, stator, power, coefficient, voltage, optimal mode, optimal current, minimum, electromagnetic, operating index, load torque, dissipation power.

Oqim qattalashganda asinxron motorning tezligi bir oz ortadi, natijada sirpanish S qamayadi, foydali quvvat esa kattalashadi. Shuning uchun talab qilinadigan quvvatning eng kichik qiymati elektromagnit nobudgarchilikning eng kichik qiymatiga nisbatan oqimning kichkina qiymatiga to'g'ri keladi.

Elektromagnit ko'rsatgichlarning egri chiziqlari: f.i.k. quvvat koeffitsienti va ularning ko'paytmasi oqimning ma'lum qiymatida maksimumga erishadilar. O'zgaruvchan nobudgarchilili va qo'zgatish nobudgarchiligi teng bo'lganda f.i.k. o'zining eng katta qiymatiga erishadi. Quvvat koeffitsienti kattalashib boradi va oqimning kichik qiymatlarida o'zining eng katta qiymatiga erishadi va oqim kattalashganda stator tokining aktiv tashqil etuvchisining qamayishi va magnitlovchi tokning kattalashuvi natijasida anchagina kamayadi.

Energetika ko'rsatgichining eng katta qiymati, f.i.k. ning maksimum qiymatiga qaraganda oqimning nisbatan kamroq qiymatiga to'g'ri keladi: chastota bilan rostlanadigan elektryuritma tizimida asinxron motorning oqim nominal bo'lganda va optimal bo'lganda rostdlash tavsiflari 1- rasmda keltirilgan.

Bunda oqimning optimal qiymatiga ushbu dvigatelda nobudgarchilikning minimal bo'lishi mos keladi. 1-rasmda stator tokining kattalashuvi bilan, asosan asinxron motorning po'latida nobudgarchilikning kattalashuvi hisobiga, kuchning kattalashuvi bilan asinxron motorning tezligi kattalashadi, unda shu yo'nalishda R_6 va R_p quvvatlari o'zgaradi, sirpanish esa giperbolik qonun bo'yicha kamayadi. Chastota o'zgarishining ko'rilayotgan barcha diapazonida ($F=0,2-1,4$) 4A rusumidagi asinxron motor uchun bu kattaliklar rejimiga qaraganda optimal rejimda kichkina. Bu birinchidan, g kattalashuvi bilan quvvatlar o'sib boradi, ikkinchidan bu motorlar uchun asosan $g_{opt} < 1,0$; Chastota kattalashuvi bilan quvvat koeffitsienti kamayadi, chunki amalda kuchlanish chastotaga mutanosib o'zgaradi, talab qilinadigan quvvat uncha o'zgarmaydi. Optimal rejimda chastota pasayganda quvvat koeffitsienti oldiniga optimal oqim qiymatini kattalashuvi xamda R_p ni kamayishi xisobiga, kamayadi; so'ngra kuchlanishning kattaroq pasayishi natijasida, kattalashadi. Chastota ortishi bilan f.i.k. kattalashadi, chunki asinxron motorning foydali quvvati, R_p dan farqli o'laroq $MS=MN=const$ bo'lganda, amalda F ning o'zgarishga mutanosib bo'ladi.

Chastota bilan rostlanadigan elektr yuritma tizimlarida ishlaydigan asinxron motorning nobudgarchiligi eng kam bo'lgan optimal $g=g_{opt}$ da rejimida dvigatelning f.i.k. $z_g=1$ bo'lgan holdagi f.i.k. dan katta. 4A rusumidagi asinxron motorlarda chastota diapazoni $F= 1,0-1,4$ bo'lganda optimal rejimda f.i.k. $g=1$ bo'lgandagi f.i.k. dan 0,25-0,56% katta. Shuning uchun chastota kichkina (past) bo'lgan chegarada bo'lganda, f.i.k. $g=1$ bo'lgandagiga qaraganda biroz kichkina.

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Masalan, $F=0,6-0,2$ bo'lgan oraliqda $z=0,04-0,15\%$ kichkina. 1-rasm. Chastota bilan rostlanadigan elektr yuritma tizimlarida 4A seriyali asinxron motorning oqim nominal optimal bo'lganda rostlash tavsiflari.

Minimum stator toki mezonni bo'yicha asinxron motorlarni boshqarish magnit oqimining stator chulg'ami kuchlanishi bilan chiziqli koeffitsient orqali bog'langanligini hisobga oladigan bo'lsak, u holda nominal ish rejimiga to'g'ri keladigan stator tokining nominal qiymatiga nisbati ko'rinishidagi ifodasini kuchlanish o'zgarishi bo'yicha differentsial nolga tenglashtiramiz:

Stator tokining minimal qiymatda bo'lganidagi motorning elektro-magnit, energetik va ekspluatatsion ko'rsatkichlari motorning minimum quvvat isrofi rejimidagi ushbu ko'rsatkichlaridan biroz farq qiladi. 2-rasmda minimum stator toki rejimida ishlayotgan asinxron motor yuklanish momentining turli qiymatlari uchun to'g'ri keladigan magnit oqimining optimal qiymatlarining o'zgarish tavsiflari keltirilgan. Agar minimum quvvat isrofi rejimi uchun keltirilgan optimal magnit oqimi tavsifi bilan solishtiradigan bo'lsak, yuklanishning $S_{\square} < 1,0$ oralig'ida motorning stator tokining minimal rejimida ishlaganida, magnit oqimining 1,8 – 1,1 marta ortiq bo'lishi magnit quvvat isroflarining oshishiga olib keladi.

2-rasm. Stator toki minimal bo'lgan rejimda ishlayotgan asinxron motor optimal magnit oqimi va sirpanishlarining yuklanish momentiga mos ravishda o'zgarishi tavsiflari.

Yuklanish momentining $S_{\square} < 1,0$ oralig'ida o'zgarganida stator tokining minimal qiymatlarida boshqarilgan motorning quvvat isroflari quvvat isrofi minimal rejimda bo'lgandagiga nisbatan 10 – 15% yuqori bo'ladi va magnit oqimining nisbatan kattaroq bo'lishi quvvat koeffitsientining sezilarli qamayishiga olib keladi. 3-rasmda stator toki minimal bo'lgan rejimda ishlayotgan asinxron motor stator tokining optimal absolyut sirpanishning yuklanish momentiga bog'liq ravishda o'zgarish tavsifi keltirilgan. Tavsifdan ko'rinib turibdiki, stator toki nominal qiymatiga teng bo'lganida absolyut sirpanishning $\square s_{\square} 0,65$ qiymati to'g'ri kelyapti. 3- rasmdagi sirpanish tavsifidan sirpanishning bu qiymatiga yuklanish momentining $S_{\square} = 1,2$ qiymati to'g'ri keladi. Bir qaraganda motorni nominal yuklanish qiymatiga nisbatan 20% ortiq yuklanish bilan ishlatish imkoni bordek tuyuladi, ammo aslida yuklanishning bu qiymatida magnit oqimining oshgan bo'lishi hisobiga motorning quvvat isroflari birmuncha katta bo'ladi va yuklanishni real 3 – 4% gagina oshirish mumkin. Shunday qilib, stator toki minimum bo'lgan rejimda stator toki qiymatiga qarab

motorning issiqlik holatini baholash mumkin emas: stator toki nominaldan kichik bo'lganida motor nominal issiqlik rejimida bo'ladi.

3-rasm. Stator toki minimal bo'lgan rejimda ishlayotgan asinxron motor stator tokining optimal absolyut sirpanishga bog'liq ravishda o'zgarish tavsifi.

Asinxron motorlarning stator toki minimum qiymatida boshqarish rejimida ishlashi differentsial tenglamaning ekstremal qiymatini izlovchi izlanuvchan va noizlanuvchan ekstremal avtomatik boshqarish tizimlari vositasida amalga oshiriladi. Izlanuvchan avtomatik boshqarish tizimlari tarkibiy tuzilishi jihatdan analogik va raqamli qurilmalardan iborat bo'lishi mumkin.

Stator chulg'ami kuchlanishi chastotasi $50Gts=const$ bo'lganida yuklanish momentining S 0,3 – 1,0 qiymatlarida asinxron motor magnitlanish tavsifining chiziqli qismida ishlaydi.

Magnit oqimining stator chulg'ami kuchlanishi bilan chiziqli koeffitsient orqali bog'langanligini hisobga oladigan bo'lsak, u holda nominal ish rejimi uchun berilgan umumiy quvvat isrofi ifodasi nominalga nisbatan ko'rinishdagi ifodasini kuchlanish o'zgarishi bo'yicha differentsial nolga tenglashtiramiz.

$$d \sum \Delta p \quad d\gamma = 0$$

bu erda,

$$\sum \Delta p = \sum \Delta p + \sum \Delta p H$$

Motorning nisbiy umumiy quvvat isrofi.

Magnit oqimining oshishi natijasida stator tokining aktiv tashkil etuvchisining kamayib

borishi motordagi elektrik quvvat isroflarining kamayishiga olib keladi. Magnit oqimining judakatta qiymatga ega bo'lishi magnitlanish tokining oshishiga sabab bo'ladi va magnit quvvat isroflarining ko'payishi yuzaga keladi. Magnit oqimining qandaydir bir qiymatida elektrik va magnit quvvat isroflari o'zaro teng bo'ladi, motor minimum quvvat isrofi rejimida ishlaydi va bu rejimni amalga oshirish sharti bajarilishi asosida yuzaga keladi. Asinxron motor yuklanishning barcha qiymatlarida ya'ni $0,1 < S \leq 1,0$ bo'lganida, asinxron motorning elektr magnit FIK eng katta qiymatga ega bo'ladi va uning mexanik FIK yuqlanish qiymatining oshishiga proportsional ravishda faqat oshib boradi. 4-rasmda asinxron motor optimal magnit oqimining yuklanish momentiga mos ravishda o'zgarishi tavsifi keltirilgan. Yuklanish momentinig $S = 0,6 - 1,0$ oralig'ida o'zgarganida magnit oqimining optimal qiymati nominal qiymatidan qatta bo'ladi va motor magnitlanish tizimining to'yingan qismida ishlaydi.

4-rasm. Minimum quvvat isrofi rejimida ishlayotgan asinxron motor optimal magnit oqimining yuklanish momentiga mos ravishda o'zgarishi tavsifi.

Yuqlanish momentining $S > 1$ qiymatlarida magnit oqimi optimal qiymatining ham o'zgarishi magnit tizimining to'yinishi bilan izohlanadi. Shunday qilib, berilgan yuklanish momentiga mos ravishda magnit oqimi qiymatini rostdash natijasida elektrik va magnit quvvat isroflari muvozanati doimo tiklanib boriladi va motorning minimum quvvat isrofi rejimida ishlashi ta'minlanadi. 5-rasmda yuklanish momentining turli qiymatlari uchun asinxron motor (nominal quvvati $R_N = 100$ qVt va $2r = 4$) umumiy quvvat isroflarining stator chulg'ami kuchlanishiga, ya'ni magnit oqimiga bog'liq ravishda o'zgarishi tavsiflari keltirilgan. Tavsiflar agar ko'rinishiga ega bo'lib, yuklanish momentining har bir qiymatiga umumiy quvvat isrofining eng kichik qiymati to'g'ri keluvchi ekstremal nuqtalari majuddir.

$$SOPT \approx sH \mu c \varphi opt \mu$$

2

buerda, sH – nominal yuklanishga mos keluvchi absolyut sirpanish qiymati

5-rasm. Yuqlanish momentining turli qiymatlari uchun asinxron motor (nominal quvvati $R_N=100$ qVt va $2R=4$) umumiy quvvat isroflarining stator cho'lg'ami kuchlanishiga bog'liq ravishda o'zgarishi tavsiflari.

Motor yuklanish momentining qiymati kamaygan sari umumiy quvvat isroflarining ekstremal nuqtalari kuchlanishning kichik qiymatlari tomoniga qarab siljiydi. Tavsiflarning umumiy quvvat isroflarining eng kichik qiymatli nuqtasidan o'nga qarab o'sib borishi magnit quvvat isroflarning oshishi bilan izohlansa, tavsiflarning ekstremal nuqtadan chapga qarab o'sishi elektrik quvvat isroflarining oshishini bildiradi.

Yuqlanish momenti qiymatlari $S < 1$ bo'lganida motorning magnit oqimi magnitlanish tavsifining chiziqli qismida rostlanadi va har bir yuklanish momentining qiymatiga mos keluvchi absolyut sirpanishning optimal qiymati yuklanish momenti qiymatiga deyarli bog'liq bo'lmaydi.

$S > 1$ bo'lganida esa magnit oqimini rostdash magnitlanish tavsifining nochiziqli qismida amalga oshiriladi va yuklanish momentiga mos keluvchi absolyut sirpanishning qiymatlari yuklanish momentiga to'g'ri proporsional oshib boradi.

Asinxron motorni minimum quvvat isrofi rejimida ishlatganida yuklanishning barcha qiymatlarida magnit oqimining nominaldan katta bo'lishi uning yuklanish xususiyatining oshishiga va tahminan 2 martaga katta bo'lishiga olib keladi, ammo motorning issiqlik holati yomonlashadi va bunga asosiy sabab motor magnit tizimida magnit quvvati srofining oshishi va stator chulg'amidagi

aktiv quvvati srofining oshishidir. 6-rasmda minimum quvvat isrofi rejimida ishlaydigan asinxron motor stator chulgʻami oqining yuklanish momentiga bogʻliq ravishda oʻzgarish tavsifi keltirilgan. 6-rasm. Minimum quvvat isrofi rejimida ishlaydigan asinxron motor stator chulgʻami tokining yuklanish momentiga bogʻliq ravishda oʻzgarish tavsifi.

Tavsifdan koʻrinib turibdiki, yuklanish momenti $S=1,0$ boʻlganida stator tokining qiymati nominal qiymatidan 16% ga kamdir. Yuklanish momentining $S \square$ qiymatlarida quvvat koeffitsientining nominal qiymatidan katta boʻlishi magnit oqimining sezilarli darajada qamayishi va natijada reaktiv quvvatning kamayishi bilan bogʻliqdir. Ishlab chiqarishda eng koʻp qoʻllaniladigan asinxron motorlarni minimum quvvat isrofi rejimida ishlashini taʼminlovchi avtomatik boshqarish tizimlarini yaratish va amaliyotga joriy qilish, sanoat qurilmalari va mashinalarida elektr energiyadan tejamkorlik bilan foydalanish uchun asosiy omil boʻladi.

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FRONTEND DASTURLASH BO‘YICHA ELEKTRON QO‘LLANMA YARATISH

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Annotatsiya. Bu elektron qo'llanma, frontend dasturlash tili bo'yicha yordamchi ma'lumotlar va qo'llanmalar to'plami bo'lishi kerak. Bu qo'llanma foydalanuvchilarga ilgari bilishlari, dastur tuzish jarayonida yordam olishlari va muammolar yuzaga kelganda ularni hal qilishlari uchun yordam beradi.

Kalitso'zlar: HTML, CSS, API, elektron qo'llanma

CREATING AN ELECTRONIC MANUAL FOR FRONT-END PROGRAMMING

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Annotation. It should be an e-manual, a collection of frontend programming language support information and tutorials. This guide helps users to know ahead of time, get help during the programming process, and solve problems when they occur.

Keywords: HTML, CSS, API, electronic manual.

Kirish. Frontend dasturlash elektron qo'llanmasini yaratish uchun modellar va algoritmlarni yaratish murakkab va qiyin vazifadir. Muayyan dasturlash tili va foydalanilayotgan ramka, maqsadli auditoriya va kerakli tafsilot darajasi kabi ko'plab omillarni hisobga olish kerak. Elektron qo'llanmada kerakli darajadagi tafsilotlarni ham hisobga olish kerak bo'ladi. Ba'zi ishlab chiquvchilarga faqat frontend dasturlash jarayonining asosiy ko'rinishi kerak bo'lishi mumkin, boshqalari esa aniq vazifalar bo'yicha batafsil ko'rsatmalarga muhtoj bo'lishi mumkin. Dasturlash tili va ramkasi: Muayyan dasturlash tili va foydalanilayotgan ramka ham hisobga olinishi kerak. Buning sababi, turli tillar va ramkalarining sintaksisi va funktsionalligi sezilarli darajada farq qilishi mumkin.

Elektron qo'llanma quyidagi bo'limlardan iborat bo'lishi mumkin:

1. Dasturlash tilining asosiy tushunchalari
2. Dasturlash tilining sintaksisi va ko'rinishi
3. Asosiy dasturlash amallari va funksiyalari
4. Interfeyssiz dastur tuzish (headless programming)
5. Dasturlashda amaliy misollar va mashqlar

Bu elektron qo'llanma foydalanuvchilarga dasturlash tilini o'rganishda yordam beradi va ularga dastur tuzish jarayonida qo'llanmalar to'plami sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili.

Frontend dasturlash tili bo'yicha bir qancha elektron qo'llanmalar mavjud. Masalan: FreeCodeCamp veb-sayti, Stack Overflow veb-sayti, Mozilla Developer Network (MDN), Front-End Development: Maykl C. Rassel va Endryu B. Hunt tomonidan Big Nerd Ranch qo'llanmasi Marijn Haverbeke tomonidan yozilgan javascript kitobi Bularni hammasi qismi boshqa tillarda yozilgan. Hozirgi kunda yurtimizda dasturlash tiliga ishtiyoq tobora ortib borayotganligi sabli yosh dasturchilarga oson va tushunarli bo'lishi uchun teglarni ham bo'limlarga ajratgan holda vazifalari bilan tushunarli tarzda qo'llanma yaratish juda muhimdir.

Afzaliklari.

Frontend dasturlash tilini o'rganish uchun elektron qo'llanmalar yaratishning afzaliklari quyidagilar bo'lishi mumkin:

1. O'rganishga qulaylik: Elektron qo'llanmalar, o'qituvchilar va o'quvchilar uchun o'rganishni osonlashtiradi. Ularning yordamida, foydalanuvchi o'zi mustaqil o'rganishi va darslikdan qayta-qayta foydalanishi mumkin.

2. Interaktivlik: Elektron qo'llanmalar interaktivlikni ta'minlashga imkon beradi. O'quvchilar darsni o'qish orqali amaliy mashg'ulotlar bajargan holda o'rganishlari mumkin.

3. Tezlik va samaradorlik: Elektron qo'llanmalar foydalanuvchilarga tezlik va samaradorlik ta'minlaydi. Ularning yordamida, o'quvchilar istalgan vaqtda va istalgan joyda darslarni o'qishlari mumkin.

4. Yangilanishlar: Elektron qo'llanmalar yangilanadigan xususiyatlarga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Bu, dastur tili bo'yicha yangiliklarni kuzatish va o'rganish uchun foydalanuvchilarga yordam beradi.

5. Multimediyalik: Elektron qo'llanmalar multimedia elementlarni (audio, video, tasvir, animatsiya) qo'llashga imkon beradi. Bu, o'quvchilarga turli ko'rinishdagi ma'lumotlarni oson o'rganish imkonini beradi.

6. Hamkorlik va almashish: Elektron qo'llanmalar foydalanuvchilar o'rtasida fikrlar almashish va hamkorlikni ta'minlashga imkon beradi. Bu, dastur tili bo'yicha bilimlarni almashish va o'rganishda yordam beradi.

7. Monitoring va baholash: Elektron qo'llanmalar foydalanuvchilarning faoliyatini monitoring qilish va baholash imkonini beradi. Bu, o'quvchilarning rivojlanish darajasini aniqlash va ulardagi muammolarni hal qilishga yordam beradi.

Kamchiliklari.

Texnik muammolar: Elektron qo'llanma yaratishda texnik muammolar paydo bo'lishi mumkin, masalan, dastur tilining yangi versiyalariga mos ravishda ishlash, xususiyatlarni to'liq tushuntirish va boshqa texnik muammolar va ilk foydalanuvchilar uchun murakkablik yoki tushunarsizlik holatlari bo'lishi mumkin

Ma'lumotlar to'plami: Elektron qo'llanmalar ma'lumotlar bazasini yaxshi boshqarish va ma'lumotlarni to'g'ri ko'rsatish uchun ma'lumotlar to'plami zarurdir. Ma'lumotlarni to'g'ri saqlash, qidirish va ko'rsatishning samaradorligini ta'minlash kerak.

Platformalar orasida moslashuv: Elektron qo'llanmalar ko'p turdagi platformalarda (masalan, veb brauzerlar, mobil qurilmalar) ishlashi kerak. Qo'llanmaning har bir platformada to'g'ri ko'rinishda ishlashi uchun moslashuv muhimdir.

O'quvchilar bilan aloqada bo'lish: Elektron qo'llanma yaratishda o'quvchilar bilan aloqada bo'lish va ularning fikrlarini eshitish muhimdir.

O'quvchilarning talablarini tushunish, ularning muammolarini hal qilish va ularning talablariga javob berish kerak.

Natijalar. Frontend dasturlash tili bo'yicha bir qancha elektron qo'llanmalar mavjud bo'lib bulardan hozirgi kunda keng qo'llaniladigani Front-End Development: Maykl C. Rassel va Endryu B. Hunt tomonidan Big Nerd Ranch qo'llanmasi bo'lib bu ko'plab junior dasturchilar va hattoki senior dasturchilar tomonidan ham foydalaniladi.

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib aytganda frontend dasturlash uchun elektron qo'llanma yaratish uchun model va algoritmlarni yaratish murakkab jarayon bo'lishi mumkin, ammo hozirgi kunda foydalanishga ehtiyojmand bo'lgan qo'llanmalar orasida desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Bu qo'llanma yosh dasturchilar uchun juda kerakli bo'ladigan qo'llanmalari to'plamiga kiradi. Bu qo'llanmani yaratish dasturchining vaqtini anchagina tejaydi yozayotgan dasturiga kerakli bo'ladigan kodlar turlarini o'zida jamlagan holda dasturning xatolik darajasini kamaytirgan holda ish samaradorligini oshiradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. HTML va CSS: Jon Dakket tomonidan veb-saytlarni loyihalash va yaratish kitobi
2. JavaScript: Duglas Krokfordning "Yaxshiqismlar" kitobi
3. Front-End Development: Maykl C. Rassel va Endryu B. Hunt tomonidan Big Nerd Ranch qo'llanmasi
4. Mozilla Developer Network (MDN) veb-sayti
5. Jeyson Santa Mariyaning UI kitobi

MOBIL ILOVA ISHLAB CHIQISH TAMOYILLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada dasturiy vositalar yaratish uchun platformalar, mobil operatsion tizimlar, mobil qurilmalarga va ular haqida tushunchalar yoritilgan. Mobil ilovalarni yaratishda foydalaniladigan mashhur tillar Kotlin, Java, Swift, JavaScript, Python va boshqalardir. Bu tillar dasturchilarga mobil ilovalarni yaratishda qulayliklar va imkoniyatlar taqdim etadi. Mobil ilovalarni yaratish texnologiyalari Android Studio, Xcode, React Native, Flutter, Xamarin va boshqalardir. Bu texnologiyalar dasturchilarga mobil platformalar uchun ilova yaratishda qo'llaniladi va ularning afzalliklari va qulayliklari mavjud. Ta'lim resurslari va onlayn kurslar dasturchilarga mobil ilovalarni yaratish tillarini va texnologiyalarini o'rganishda yordam beradi. Bu resurslar dasturchilarga muhim bilimlar o'rgatishda va yangiliklarni kuzatishda foydali bo'ladi. Mustaqil o'rganish dasturchilar uchun juda muhimdir, chunki bu ularning o'zlarining bilimlarini oshirishiga yordam beradi va yangiliklarni o'rganishga imkoniyat yaratadi. Mobil ilovalarni yaratish jarayonida mustaqil o'rganish dasturchilar uchun muhim va foydali bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Mobil ilova, server, operatsion tizim, Android, Grafik, interfeys, Zamonaviy texnologiyalar.

PRINCIPLES OF MOBILE APPLICATION DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This article covers platforms for creating software tools, mobile operating systems, and concepts for mobile devices. Popular languages used to create mobile applications are Kotlin, Java, Swift, JavaScript, Python, etc. These languages provide convenience and capabilities to developers when

creating mobile applications. Mobile application development technologies - Android Studio, Xcode, React Native, Flutter, Xamarin, etc. These technologies are used by developers to create applications for mobile platforms and have advantages and conveniences. Educational resources and online courses help developers learn mobile application development languages and technologies. These resources are useful for teaching developers important knowledge and keeping up with the latest news. Self-study is very important for programmers because it helps them improve their knowledge and gives them the opportunity to learn something new. Self-learning is important and useful for developers in the process of creating mobile applications.

Key words: *Mobile application, server, operating system, Android, Graphics, interface, Modern technologies.*

Kirish. Hozirgi kunda zamonaviy odamni qo‘lida mobil moslamasiz tasavvur qilish qiyin. Telefonlar, smartfonlar, planshetlar, netbuklar va boshqa aloqa vositalari bizning hayotimizni osonlashtirish va ta‘minlash uchun mo‘ljallangan tezkor kirish, kerakli ma‘lumotlar dunyoning istalgan burchagida turib olish imkoniyati mavjud. Bundan tashqari, bozor o‘sib bormoqda mobil ilovalar- orqali aloqa qilish, xaridlarni amalga oshirish, mehmonxonalarni bron qilish, taksiga qo‘ng‘iroq qilish, ovqatga buyurtma berish, vaqtni 100 % ga o‘tkazish mobil Internet usullar uni dasturlarga bag‘ishlashadi.

Mobil ilovani yaratish bosqichlari

Tahlil

Har bir dastur g'oyadan boshlanadi.

Kelajakda xizmat bilan shug'ullanish kerak, nima bizga aytib, va tahlilchilar yig'ish uchun biz davom etmoqda. Bozorning chuqur kesilishi, mavjud echimlarni tahlil qilish, raqobatchilar va xaridorlarning xatti-harakatlarini o'rganish ...tahlilning har bir bosqichida biz oxirgi foydalanuvchini eslaymiz va mijozning aylanishini o'ylaymiz. Bu odamlar yangi ilovadan qanday foydalanishi va iloji boricha qulay, tushunarli va foydali bo'lishini birgalikda tushunishga yordam beradi. Bunday xizmat sizning biznesingizga foyda keltiradi.

Tahlil-bu juda muhim bosqich. Undan voz kechmang va texnik topshiriqdan loyihada ishlashni boshlang. Tahlil jarayonida bozorda kim ekanligini, kimga rahbarlik qilishni va qanday qilib yaxshiroq qilishni tushunamiz. Biz odatda eng yaxshi amaliyotlarni to'playmiz va mijozga 100% ishlaydigan tasdiqlangan echimlarni taklif qilamiz.

Tayyorgarlik. Fikr tug'ilganidan keyingi qadam loyiha ustida ish rejasini tuzishdir. Uning eng oson yo'li raqobatchilarni tahlil qilishdan boshlashdir. Bozorda siz yaratmoqchi bo'lgan o'xshash mobil ilovalarni toping va quyidagi omillarni tahlil qiling: Yuklab olishlar soni-agar dastur yuklansa, unda kimdir kerak. Baholash va sharhlar-zaif nuqtalarni taqdim etishga va foydalanuvchilarga yoqadigan "chiplar" ni o'z mahsulotiga moslashtirishga yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga, istemolchilarning e'tirofini qanday qo'lga kiritganini tushunishga harakat qiling.

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiya.

Natijalar. Ilovadan xaridlar, obuna yoki premium versiyalar uchun to'lovlar, reklama joylashtirish, ma'lumotlarni sotish-ilovani bepul tarqatish sarf xarajatlar monetizatsiya qilishning usullari hisoblanadi. Eng yaxshi variantni tanlash uchun, odatda raqobatchilarni nima qilayotganini ko'rib chiqiladi va monetizatsiyani qaysi nuqtada boshlashni aniqlanadi va buning so'ngida marketing bilan shug'ullaniladi.

Mobil ilovani ishlab chiqishning eng muhim bosqichi

Texnik topshiriqni ishlab chiqish bosqichlari

Dasturni ishlab chiqish uchun TP miqdori dasturning hajmi va murakkabligiga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Maqsadlarni aniqlash va tadqiq qilish

Rivojlanish jarayonida biz mijoz bilan doimiy muloqotda bo'lamiz. Biz ilovaning maqsadini aniqlab olishimiz va rivojlanish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan haqiqiy manba ma'lumotlarini olishimiz kerak.

Asosiy tuzilma

Biz oddiy tilda hamma narsani tasvirlaydigan TZ ning soddalashtirilgan versiyasini ishlab chiqamiz. Biz mijoz bilan barcha jarayonlarni tushunishda tekshiramiz — agar yangi ma'lumotlar paydo bo'lsa, biz ularni keltiramiz, agar bo'lmasa, biz batafsil o'rganishni davom ettiramiz.

Texnik talablar va cheklovlar

Laynerning turiga qarab, ilova va talablarga ega bo'lgan doirani batafsil bayon qilamiz. Misol uchun, serverga yuk haqida qo'shimcha ma'lumot berilishi mumkin: u nima bo'ladi va uni qanday ta'minlash kerak.

Mantiq

Oqim sxemalari yordamida biz kichik tizimlar orasidagi dasturni va o'zaro ta'sirni aniq tasvirlab beramiz, shunda loyihani amalga oshiruvchi texnik mutaxassis hech qanday savol bermaydi.

Mijoz va ma'muriy interfeys

Grafikda biz interfeysning mijoz va dastur administratori uchun qanday ko'rinishini, qanday ranglar va elementlardan foydalanishni tasvirlaymiz. Dasturiy ta'minot uchun talablarni tasvirlab beramiz.

Texnik topshiriq-loyihaning kelajagi bog'liq bo'lgan rivojlanishning birinchi bosqichi. Barcha nuances va xususiyatlarni hisobga olish muhim: har qanday keyingi o'zgarishlar va tuzatishlar moliyaviy xarajatlar va ishga tushirishni kechiktirish.

Ichki arxitektura mobil ilovaning funksiyasiga va ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash va saqlash uchun tanlangan usulga bog'liq. Odatda biz ikkita ro'yxatni tuzamiz – ilovaning xususiyatlari va asosiy foydalanuvchi xaritasi. Ular kelajakdagi barcha me'moriy ishlar uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Keyin biz taxtada yoki qog'ozda ekranlarni chizamiz va ularga kerakli elementlar va ma'lumotlarni joylashtiramiz. Bir xil element bir nechta ekranlarda mavjud bo'lishi mumkin bo'lsa-da, u "uy"bo'lishi kerak. Ushbu bosqichda loyiha har qanday o'zgarishlarni amalga oshirishi mumkin.

Asboblar: Balsamiq, Sketch, Axure, Figma, RealtimeBoard, Wireframe.cc va Whimsical

Muhokama. Uslublar-bu mobil ilovaning "ichki qismi" ni tugatish va uning mavjudligini oshirish uchun qurilish materiallari. Yaxshi o'ylangan uslubsiz, dizayn elementlari ranglarni o'zgartiradi va ekranda suzadi, foydalanuvchini chalkashtirib yuboradi. Mobil ilovaning uslubi bo'yicha qo'llanma imkon qadar batafsil bo'lishi va tomoshabinlarning xususiyatlariga tayanishi kerak. Tajribali UIDizayner ranglar palitrasi, shriftlar va vidjetlar (tugmalar, shakllar, piktogramma va boshqalar) uchun yuzlab variantlarni taklif etadi.

Mobil ishlab chiqarishda juda ko‘p texnologiya mavjud. Ba’zilar deyarli xarajatlarni talab qilmaydi, lekin yuqori mahsuldorlik bilan farq qilmaydi, boshqalari esa ajoyib natijalar uchun katta investitsiyalarni talab qiladi.

Zamonaviy texnologiyalar olamiga yangi kelgan kishi shunchaki bunday OSga ega bo‘lgan smartfonlarning asosiy funktsiyalarini aniqlab beradi.

Har qanday malakali dasturchi ushbu tizim uchun ariza yozib, uni rasmiy Android do‘koni - Play Market-ga joylashtirishi mumkin. Ma’lumotlarni uzatish qulayligi. Agar biron-bir ma’lumotni smartfondan kompyuterga, masalan, fotosuratlar, audio yoki video fayllarni uzatish zarurati bo‘lsa, u holda USB ulanishi orqali hech qanday muammosiz amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Qo‘shimcha dasturlarni o‘rnatish yoki ular bilan shug‘ullanishning hojati yo‘q.

Har bir telefon modeli ishlab chiqaruvchi tomonidan muntazam ravishda yangilanib turadi, shuning uchun qurilma har doim zamonaviy talablarga javob beradi.

OT barcha kerakli funktsiyalarni bajarishga qodir, bu esa gadgetni qulay va amaliy sotib olishga imkon beradi.

Android OS bilan yangi smartfonning narxi juda xilma-xil bo‘lishi mumkin. Siz o‘zingizning talablaringizga javob beradigan arzon smartfonni osongina topishingiz mumkin.

Androidning kamchiliklari:

Siz ushbu elementni operatsion tizimning afzalliklari ro‘yxatida ko‘rgansiz, ammo bu nafaqat fazilat, balki uning kamchiliklari hamdir. Shu sababli, Android-da ishlaydigan qurilmalar zararli dastur va xakerlarning hujumlariga juda himoyasiz deb hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun, sotib olgandan so‘ng darhol gadgetingizni himoya qilish va unga yuqori sifatli antivirusni o‘rnatish juda muhimdir.

Ko‘pgina foydalanuvchilar Android smartfonlaridagi trafik bizning ko‘zimiz oldida erib ketayotganidan shikoyat qilmoqdalar, chunki ko‘plab

dasturlar doimiy ravishda yangilanishni talab qiladi. Albatta, bu muammoni Internet-trafik iste'molini boshqarish orqali hal qilish mumkin.

Ko'pgina smartfonlar uchun OSni yangilash masalasi butunlay muammoga aylanadi, chunki eski modellar uchun umuman yangilanishlar bo'lmasligi mumkin, boshqalari uchun yangi versiya juda kech chiqishi mumkin.

Xulosa. Ilova yaratish jarayonida foydalanuvchilarning qiziqtirganliklarini va talablari ni boshqa ilovalar bilan taqqoslash, ularning ma'lumotlari va ma'lumotlarini qanday himoya qilish kerakligini o'rganish ham juda muhimdir. Foydalanuvchilar bilan o'zaro muloqotda bo'lish, ularning fikrlariga e'tibor berish, ularning istaklarini va talablari uchun ilovada yaxshi xizmat ko'rsatish, ularning fikrlariga e'tibor berish va ularga qulaylik yaratish ham muhimdir. Mobil ilovalarni yaratishda foydalaniladigan tillar va texnologiyalar juda keng va muhim bir mavzu hisoblanadi. Dasturchilar uchun eng mashhur tillar Kotlin, Java, Swift, JavaScript, Python va boshqalardir. Bu tillar mobil ilovalarni yaratishda foydalaniladi va har birining o'z afzalliklari, qulayliklari va qiyinchiliklari mavjud. Mobil ilovalarni yaratishda foydalaniladigan texnologiyalar esa Android Studio, Xcode, React Native, Flutter, Xamarin va boshqalardir. Bu texnologiyalar dasturchilarga mobil platformalar uchun ilova yaratishda qo'llaniladi va ularning afzalliklari, foydalanish sohalariga mos kelishi va qulayliklari mavjud. Ta'lim resurslari va onlayn kurslar dasturchilarga mobil ilovalarni yaratish tillarini va texnologiyalarini o'rganishda yordam beradi. Bu resurslar dasturchilarga muhim bilimlar o'rgatishda va yangiliklarni kuzatishda foydali bo'ladi. Mustaqil o'rganish dasturchilar uchun juda muhimdir, chunki bu ularning o'zlarining bilimlarini oshirishiga yordam beradi va yangiliklarni o'rganishga imkoniyat yaratadi. Mobil ilovalarni yaratish jarayonida mustaqil o'rganish dasturchilar uchun muhim va foydali bo'ladi.

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ELEKTROMAGNIT VA OPTIK SIGNALLARNI HOSIL QILISH

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Annotatsiya: Elektromagnit va optik signal hosil qilish, bugungi texnologiyalarning asosiy qismlaridan biridir. Elektromagnit va optik signal hosil qilishni tushuntirish, ularning tuzilishi, asosiy usullari va ularni qanday qo'llab-quvvatlashning texnologik jarayonlari bo'yicha batafsil ma'lumotlar keltiriladi. Optik signal hosil qilish, yorug'lik energiyasini qo'llab-quvvatlagan vositalar va texnologiyalardan iboratdir. Optik signal hosil qilishning asosiy prinsiplari, ularning tuzilishi va amaliyotda qanday qo'llanilishini tushuntirishga harakat qilamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Diod, optik, modulyatsiya, radiosignal, elektromagnit

FORMATION OF ELECTROMAGNETIC AND OPTICAL SIGNALS

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Annotation: The formation of electromagnetic and optical signals is one of the main components of today's technologies. Detailed information is provided on explaining the formation of electromagnetic and optical signals, their structure, basic methods and technological processes of how to support them. The formation of an optical signal consists of tools and technologies that support light energy. We try to explain the basic principles of optical signal formation, how they are structured and applied in practice.

Keywords: DIODE, optical, modulation, radiosignal, electromagnetic

Kirish. Elektromagnit signal, elektr yoki magnit maydonlar o‘zaro almashishmasi natijasida paydo bo‘lgan energiya oqimlari tufayli hosil bo‘ladi. Elektromagnit signalning hosil qilish usullari o‘z ichiga stroom o‘tkazish, radiovolna emissiyasi, elektromagnit turli qurilmalar orqali modulyatsiya qilishni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Optik signal, yorug‘lik yoki yorug‘lik energiyasi orqali o‘tkaziladigan energiya oqimlaridir. Optik signal hosil qilish usullari o‘z ichiga laser, diodlar, optik fiberlar va boshqa optik vositalarni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Elektr stroom o‘tkazish: Elektr stroomning o‘tkazilishi orqali elektromagnit signal hosil qilish amaliyoti odatda stroomning o‘tkazish qurilmasi yordamida bajariladi. Bu usul ko‘plab elektronik qurilmalar, generatorlar va texnologiyalar uchun asosiy bo‘lgan bir usuldir.

Radiovolna emissiyasi: Elektromagnit signalni yaratish uchun bir necha xil turdagi qurilmalar yordamida radiolarni emissiya qilish mumkin. Radiosignal hosil qilish uchun antenlar, radiosignal transmitterlari, va boshqa elektronik vositalar qo‘llaniladi.

Modulyatsiya: Elektromagnit signalni o‘z o‘rniga qo‘shimcha ma’lumotlar qo‘shish modulyatsiya deb ataladi. Amaliyotda, amplitude modulyatsiya (AM) va frekvensiya modulyatsiyasi (FM) keng qo‘llaniladi.

Lazerlar: Lazerlar yorug‘lik fotonlarni hosil qilish uchun qo‘llaniladigan vositalardir. Lazerlar optik signalni yaratishda, odatda, yorug‘lik energiyasini bo‘shatish, ilg‘o tizimi orqali nurlantirish yoki optik signalni uyushtirish jarayonlari bilan qo‘llaniladi.

Optik fiberlar: Optik fiberlar, nur transport qilish uchun noyob vosita hisoblanadi. Ular, nur energiyasini yo‘lga qo‘yish orqali optik signalni hosil qilish va uzatishda amaliyotda keng qo‘llaniladi. Optik fiberlar, yorug‘lik oqimlarini o‘z ichiga oladi va uzoq masofalarga energiya oqimlarini yetkazib berish uchun samarali vositadirlar.

Elektromagnit signalning amaliyotda qanday qo‘llanilishi mumkinligi va uning amaliyotda vazifalari to‘g‘risida tafsilot berishingiz kerak. Masalan, telekommunikatsiya tizimlarida, radiosignal qo‘llash va uzatishda qanday o‘rtacha ishlaydi, xalqaro ta’sir qo‘llashda elektromagnit signalning roli, va hokazo.

Elektromagnit va optik signalning uyg‘unlashgan foydalanishlari, telekommunikatsiya, axborot uzatish, tezkor ma’lumotlar o‘tkazish, tibbiyot, kuzatish-tizimlari, va boshqa sohalar kengroqdir. Ular, kablesiz kommunikatsiyadan mobil aloqa va internet, kompyuter tarmoqlaridan

televideniya va radio translyatsiyalariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Optik signalni hosil qilishda, yorug‘lik emissiyasi (yorug‘likni yaratish) ham asosiy tuzilma sifatida qo‘llaniladi. Bu usulda, yorug‘likni yaratish uchun alohida bir optik emitter (yorug‘lik yaratuvchi) ishlatiladi.

Optik signal hosil qilingan dasturlar va vositalar telekommunikatsiya, optik internet tarmoqlar, tibbiyot, ma‘lumot omborlari, o‘quv kursatish va boshqa sohalarda keng qo‘llaniladi. Ular, kablesiz aloqa va ma‘lumot uzatish, yorug‘lik hujjatlarni o‘tkazish va amaliyotda ko‘p toifali texnologiyalarda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Bugungi kunda, elektronika sohasidagi rivojlanishlar va texnologiyalar, elektromagnit va optik signal hosil qilishni yangi bosqichga olib chiqmoqda. Elektromagnit signal, elektr energiyasining elektromagnit maydon orqali uzaytirilgan shakli bo‘lib, optik signal esa chiroq va laserni qo‘llab-quvvatlaydigan optik tizim orqali uzaytiriladi. Bu maqolada, elektromagnit va optik signal hosil qilish usullari, ularning foydalari va turli sohalarda qo‘llanilishiga doir muloqot qilamiz.

Elektromagnit signal, elektr energiyasining elektromagnit maydon orqali uzaytirilgan shakli bo‘lib, quyidagi usullar orqali hosil qilinadi:

Elektr to‘plam, mehmon ta‘minotidan elektr energiyasini olish va uni elektromagnit signalga aylantirish usulidir. Bunday generatorlar har xil turlarda bo‘ladi, masalan, dinamolar, alternatorlar va boshqa turlar.

Elektromagnit signal hosil qilishda ishlatiladigan boshqa vosita transmitterlardir. Radiolarni, televiziyalarni, yoki boshqa kutiladigan signal turlarini uzatish uchun qo‘llaniladigan transmitterlar, elektr energiyasini elektromagnit signalga aylantirishda ishlatiladi.

Optik signal, nur toki orqali uzaytirilgan shakl bo‘lib, quyidagi usullar orqali hosil qilinadi;

Lazerlar: Lazerlar, yoritg‘ichlar orqali nur toki yaratish uchun foydalaniladi. Lazerlar, ko‘p turlarda, masalan, yoritg‘ichlarda, meditsinada va optik kompyuter tizimlarda foydalaniladi.

Optik Fiberlar: Optik fiberlar, chiroq nurini uzatish uchun ishlatiladi. Ularda chiroq signalini yoritish va uzatishda yorqin va kichik tarmoqlar o‘zlashtirilgan.

Elektromagnit va optik signal hosil qilish texnologiyalari, kompyuterlar, kommunikatsiya tizimlari, tibbiyot, nazorat tizimlari va boshqa sohalarda o‘rtacha odam hayoti boyicha samarali tashkil etilgan. Bu usullar, ma‘lumotlarni tez va

aniq uzatish, kompyuter tizimlarini yaxshi ishlatish, va ko'p sohalarda yoritishni ovozlashda yordam beradi.

Elektromagnit, elektr energiyasining magnit maydon orqali o'rnatilgan shaklidir. U bu, elektr tokinin yo'l olishi natijasida hosil bo'lgan magnit maydoni va o'sha maydonga o'tiradigan maydon, ya'ni elektromagnit maydoni, orqali ishlaydi. Elektromagnitlar, turli sohalarda intensiv ravishda qo'llaniladi, uning asosiy qobiliyatlarini va ularning o'zlashtirilishi uchun turli turdagi materiallar yordamida o'zgarishga uchish imkoniyatini beradi.

Xulosa.

Elektromagnit signal hosil qilish va uning qo'llanilish sohasiga qisqa xulosa qo'yishingiz yoki qo'llanilishni oshirish uchun takliflar beringingiz mumkin. Bu qisqa xulosada, elektr yoki magnit maydonlar orqali o'tkaziladigan energiya oqimlarining signal sifatida qanday ishlaydi va qanday sahalar bilan aloqador bo'lishi mumkinligi, elektromagnit signalning ma'no va ahamiyati, shuningdek, amaliyotda qo'llanilishini kengroq tushuntirish maqsadida yetarlicha ma'lumotlar berildi. Optik signal hosil qilish, yorug'lik energiyasining eng samarali va keng qo'llaniladigan yo'llaridan biridir. Ushbu texnologiyalar, kompyuter tarmoqlaridan televideniya va radio translyatsiyalariga qadar ko'plab sohalarda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib kelgan. Optik signalning yuqori uzluksizlik va uzun masofalarda samarali uzatish imkoniyatlarini ko'rsatishi, uning amaliyotdagi foydalani shuhratini oshirgan va uning mustaqil ravishda yuqori tezlikdagi ma'lumot uzatishda ishlatilishini kuchaytirmoqda.

Elektromagnitlar, elektronika, energetika, avtomatlashtirish va texnologiya sohalari bo'ylab turli sohalarda intensiv ravishda qo'llaniladigan kuchli qurilmalardir. Ularning foydaliliklari, yangi texnologiyalar va tizimlar rivojlanishida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Elektromagnitning o'zining xususiyatlari va qobiliyatlari tufayli, bu soha yanada rivojlanib, yangi innovatsiyalarni o'rgatmoqda.

Elektromagnitlar, ularga xos bo'lgan bir qator foydalanish joylarida keng qo'llaniladi:

Elektr Energiyaning Ayrimi: Elektromagnitlar, elektr energiyasini magnit maydon orqali mehmon energiyasiga aylantirishda foydalaniladi. Dinamolar va generatorlar elektromagnitni boshqaradigan qurilmalardir.

Elektr Magnetik Relelar: Elektromagnitlar, texnik tizimlarda ishlaydigan elektr magnetik relelarning tuzilishida ham ishlatiladi. Bu relelar elektr tizimlarni boshqarishda, o'zlashtirishda, va avtomatik boshqaruvda yordamchi bo'lib ishlaydi.

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MOBIL ILOVALARNI YARATISH TILLARI VA TEXNOLOGIYALARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada eng mashhur mobil operatsion tizimlar, mobil qurilmalarga dasturiy vositalar yaratish uchun platformalar va ular haqida tushunchalar yoritilgan. Java va python dasturlash tillari haqida keng malumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. mobil ilovalarni yaratishda foydalaniladigan eng mashhur dasturlash tillari va texnologiyalari haqida umumiy ma'lumotlarni taqdim etadi. Maqola JavaScript, Node.js, Swift, Objective-C, Python kabi dasturlash tillarini va ularning mobil ilovalarni yaratishda qanday foydali bo'lishi mumkinligini tahlil qiladi. Ayni paytda, texnologiyalardagi so'nggi yangilanishlar va ularni o'rganish uchun yo'llar haqida ma'lumot beradi. Annotatsiya mobil ilovalarni yaratish sohasida yangi bilimlar va ko'nikmalar olish uchun yaxshi bir boshlang'ich nuqtani taqdim etadi. Python nisbatan kam kalit so'zlar, oddiy tuzilish va aniq belgilangan sintaksisga ega. Bu o'rganuvchini qisqa vaqt ichida yodlab olish imkonini beradi. Python kodi juda aniq va ko'zga ko'rinadigan bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Mobil operatsion tizimlar, dasturiy vositalar, Desktop Applications, Mobile Applications, Python.

LANGUAGES AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR CREATING MOBILE APPLICATIONS

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Annotation. This article covers the most popular mobile operating systems, platforms for creating software tools for mobile devices, and concepts about them. Extensive information on Java python programming

languages has been cited. The article analyzes programming languages like JavaScript, Node.js, Swift, Objective-C, Python and how they can be useful in creating mobile applications. At the same time, it provides information about the latest updates in technologies and ways to learn them. Abstract provides a good starting point for acquiring new knowledge and skills in the field of mobile application development. Python has relatively few keywords, simple structure and well-defined syntax, which allows the learner to memorize in a short time. Python code will be very clear and visible.

Keywords: Mobile operating systems, software tools, Desktop Applications, Mobile Applications, Python.

Kirish. Mobil operatsion tizimlar – bu mobil qurilmalar (smartfonlar, tabletlar PDA(Personal digital assistant) va boshqa mobil qurilmalar) ni boshqarish uchun mo'ljallangan tizimlar hisoblanadi.

Mobil operatsion tizimlar ikkita asosiy platforma ya'ni “user-facing” dasturiy ta'minot platformasi va qurilmalarni boshqarish uchun mo'ljallangan quyi sathdagi real-vaqt operatsion tizimidan iborat bo'ladi.

Eng mashhur mobil operatsion tizimlarni quyidagilarni kiritish mumkin:

Android, Google tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan va dunyoda eng keng tarqalgan mobil operatsion tizim hisoblanadi. Uning asosiy foydalanuvchi interfeysi Material Design deb nomlanadi. Android ilovalarini Java, Kotlin yoki C++ dasturlash tillari bilan yaratish mumkin.

iOS, Apple tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan mobil operatsion tizim hisoblanadi. Bu tizim yalnizgina Apple qurilmalari (iPhone, iPad, iPod Touch) da ishlaydi. iOS ilovalarini Swift yoki Objective-C dasturlash tillari bilan yaratish mumkin.

Mobil qurilmalarga dasturiy vositalar yaratish uchun platformalar.

Java yuqori darajada himoyalangan va obyektga yo'naltirilgan dasturlash tilidir.

Javaning o'zini maxsus bajarilish muhiti – platformasi mavjud (JRE – Java Runtime Environment).

Javadan qayerda foydalaniladi?

Sun firmasining ma'lumotlariga qaraganda 3 mlrd. atrofidagi qurilmada Javadan foydalaniladi.

Masalan:

- Shaxsiy kompyuter dasturlari (Desktop Applications) – acrobat reader, mediaplayer, antiviruslar va h.k.;
- Veb dasturlar;
- Korxonatashkilotlar dasturlari (Enterprise Applications) – bank yoki ishlab chiqarishga oid dasturlar;
- Mobil dasturlar;
- Smart kartalar;
- Robotlar;
- O'yinlar.

Nomi	Dasturlash tili
Android	Java, qisman C/C++
BlackBerry	Java
iOS SDK	Objective – C, Objective Pascal
Java ME	Java
Windows Phone (WP)	Visual C++, Visual C#, Visual Basic
Marmalade	C/C++
Python	Python
Firefox OS	HTML5, CSS, JavaScript
...	...

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiya. "Python dasturlash tilini o'rganish: Qanday boshlash?" - Bu maqola Python dasturlash tilini o'rganishni boshlash uchun qanday yo'llar borligini tahlil qiladi.

"Mobil ilovalarni yaratishda Flutter va React Native: qaysi birini tanlash lozim?" - Bu maqola Flutter va React Native texnologiyalarini solishtirib, ularning foydali va zararli tomonlarini tahlil qiladi.

"Mobil ilovalarni yaratishda Kotlin va Java: qaysi birini tanlash lozim?" - Bu maqola Kotlin va Java dasturlash tillarini solishtirib, ularning mobil ilovalar yaratishda qanday foydali bo'lishi mumkinligini tahlil qiladi.

"Mobil ilovalarni yaratishda UI/UX dizaynning ahamiyati" - Bu maqola mobil ilovalarni yaratishda dizaynning ahamiyatini va foydali dizayn prinsiplarini tahlil qiladi.

"Web ilovalarni yaratishda JavaScript va Node.js: qaysi birini tanlash lozim?" - Bu maqola JavaScript va Node.js dasturlash tillarini solishtirib, ularning web ilovalarni yaratishda qanday foydali bo'lishi mumkinligini tahlil qiladi.

"Mobil ilovalarni yaratishda Swift va Objective-C: qaysi birini tanlash lozim?" - Bu maqola Swift va Objective-C dasturlash tillarini solishtirib, ularning iOS platformasi uchun mobil ilovalarni yaratishda qanday foydali bo'lishi mumkinligini tahlil qiladi.

"Python dasturlash tilida data analitikasi: Asosiy konseptlar va amaliy mashg'ulotlar" - Bu maqola Python dasturlash tilini ishlatib, data analitikasini o'rganishning asosiy konseptlarini va amaliy mashg'ulotlarni tahlil qiladi.

"Texnologiyalardagi so'nggi yangilanishlar: Qanday o'rganish kerak?" - Bu maqola texnologiyalardagi so'nggi yangilanishlar haqida ma'lumot beradi va ularni o'rganish uchun qanday yo'llar borligini tahlil qiladi.

Natijalar. Kotlin-Yana bir rasmiy va kamroq mashhur til. Bundan tashqari, Android Studio tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi, sintaksisi bilan ajralib turadi.

Java sintaksisi kotlinga qaraganda ancha murakkab kodni nazarda tutadi. Misol uchun, Android-ning ishlab chiqaruvchisi ushbu ikki dasturlash tilida maydonmatnini tayinlaydi:

Java

```
final TextView helloTextView = (TextView) findViewById(R.id.text_view_id);  
helloTextView.setText("Hello world");
```

Kotlin

```
helloTextView.text = "Hello world"
```

Unity-kompyuter o'yinlarini ishlab chiqishning o'zaro platformali muhitidir. Birlik shaxsiy kompyuterlar, o'yin konsollari, mobil qurilmalar, Internet ilovalari va boshqalarni o'z ichiga olgan 20 dan ortiq turli xil operatsion tizimlar ostida ishlaydigan ilovalarni yaratishga imkon beradi. Unity ning chiqarilishi 2005 yilda bo'lib o'tdi va o'sha paytdan boshlab doimiy rivojlanish davom etmoqda.

Pythonni tarixi-Python Guido van Rossum tomonidan sakson va sakkizinchi yillarda Niderlandiyadagi Matematika va informatika ilmiy tadqiqot institutida ishlab chiqildi.

Python ABC, Modula-3, C, C ++, Algol-68, SmallTalk va Unix shell kabi boshqa ko'plab tillardan va boshqa skript tillaridan olingan.

Python xususiyatlari: Pythonning xususiyati quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi:

O'qish oson: Python nisbatan kam kalit so'zlar, oddiy tuzilish va aniq belgilangan sintaksisga ega. Bu o'rganuvchini qisqa vaqt ichida yodlab olish imkonini beradi.

O'qish oson: Python kodi juda aniq va ko'zga ko'rinadigan bo'ladi.

Oson ishlash: Pythonning muvaffaqiyati – manba kodi juda oson.

Keng standart kutubxona: Pythonning eng qudratli jihatlaridan biri kutubxonaning asosiy qismi juda portativ va UNIX, Windows va Macintosh-da o'zaro faoliyat platformalar bilan mos keladi.

Interaktiv usul: Pythonda ishlashda terminalda ishlash uchun juda qulay terminalda test qilib ko'rsa bo'ladi.

Portativ: Python keng apparat platformalarida ishlaydi va barcha platformalarda bir xil interfeysga ega.

Kengaytirilgan: Python tarjimoniga past darajadagi modullarni qo'shishingiz mumkin. Ushbu modullar dasturchilarni o'zlarining vositalarini samaraliroq bo'lishiga qo'shish yoki sozlash imkonini beradi.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi: Python barcha ma'lumotlar bazasini qo'llab quvvatlaydi.

GUI dasturlash: Python Windows MFC, Unix, X Window kabi platformalarga GUI dasturlar tuzishni qo'llab quvvatlaydi.

Moslashuvchan: Python, qobiq buyruq fayliga qaraganda katta dasturlarga yanada yaxshi tuzilish va qo'llab-quvvatlash imkonini beradi.

Muhokama. C/C++ C tillari yuqori ko'rsatkichga ega bo'lib, ayniqsa, mobil 3D o'yinlari kabi og'ir dasturlash imkonini beruvchi til. Android NDK sizga C/C++ da faqat dasturning bir qismini, masalan, Java orqali dasturga ulanishi mumkin bo'lgan kutubxonani yozish imkonini beradi.

Dart - veb ilovalar va mobil ilovalar kabi mijozlarni rivojlantirish uchun mo'ljallangan dasturlash tilidir. Google tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan va server va ish stoli ilovalarini yaratish uchun ham foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan dasturlash tili. C# yordamida Androidda dasturlash Xamarin platformasini nazarda tutadi. Shu bilan siz Android va iOS uchun C# da bitta dastur imkonini yaratishingiz mumkin.

Java dasturlash tili va platforma Javada asosan 4 turdagi dasturlar yoziladi:

1) Standalone applications – Linux, Mac yoki Windowsga o'rnatib, kundalik ishlatadigan dasturlarimiz: mp3 player, ofis, antivirus kabilar. Ular AWT, Swing yoki JavaFX texnologiyalari orqali tuziladi.

2) Web Applications – tarmoq orqali ishlovchi ixtiyoriy dasturlar. Eslatma: veb dasturlar ikki qismdan, server tomon hamda klient tomon (brauzer) dan iborat. Javada faqat server tomoni uchun yoziladi. Bunda servlet, jsp, jsf kabi fundamental texnologiyalardan boshlab Spring, Play kabi freymworklar qol keladi. Umuman olganda brauzer uchun HTML, CSS hamda Java Scriptdan boshqa tilda yozib bolmaydi.

3) Enterprise Applications – bu dasturlar yirik salmoqqa ega bolib, odatda katta jabhalarda ishlatiladi. Banklar, tashkilotlar yoki astronomiya kabi sohalarda. Ular yuqori xavfsizlik, yuklamani (nagruzka) serverlarga teng taqsimlash (load balancing) yoki klasterlash (clustering – katta tizimdan huddi yagona obyekt sifatida foydalanish) kabi sifatlarni talab qiladi. Javada bular bor.

4) Mobile Applications – Mobil qurilmalarga mos dasturlarni ham Javada yozish mumkin. Androiddan boshlab, Java ME (JME – Java Micro Edition) gacha. JME ga misol qilib, Nokia telefonlarimiz uchun ishlangan JAR dastur va oyinlarni misol keltirish mumkin.

Java bir necha qismlarni o'z ichiga oladi va ular:

1. Simple (oddiy)
2. Object-Oriented (obyektga yo'naltirilgan)
3. Platform independent (mustaqil platformalar)
4. Secured (himoyalangan)
5. Robust (kuchli)
6. Architecture neutral (neytral arxitektura)
7. Portable (ixcham)
8. Dynamic (dinamik)
9. Interpreted (interpretatsiyalangan)
10. High Performance (yuqori tezlik)
11. Multithreaded (ko'p potokli)
12. Distributed (model bo'yicha taqsimlanish)

Mobil qurilmalar uchun OT larning qo‘llanilish ko‘rsatkichlari

Xulosa. Xulosa shundan iboratki dunyodagi eng mashhur mobil operatsion tizimlar, mobil qurilmalarga dasturiy vositalar yaratish uchun platformalar va ular haqida tushunchalar yoritib berildi. Java va python dasturlash tillari haqida keng malumotlar keltirib o‘tildi. JavaScript: Web ilovalarini va mobil ilovalarni yaratishda mashhur dasturlash tili. React Native, Ionic, NativeScript kabi frameworklar orqali mobil ilovalar yaratishda foydalaniladi. Node.js: Server tomoni dasturlash uchun mashhur texnologiya. Mobil ilovalar uchun server tomoni loyihasini Node.js orqali yaratish mumkin. Swift: iOS platformasi uchun ishlab chiqilgan dasturlash tili. Mobil ilovalarni iOS platformasi uchun yaratishda foydalaniladi. Objective-C: Swiftning oldindan kelgan, iOS platformasi uchun ishlab chiqilgan boshqa dasturlash tili. Xozirgi kunda Swift bilan birga foydalaniladi. Python: Oson va sodda dasturlash tili. Mobil ilovalarni Python tilida yaratishda foydalanish mumkin, masalan, Kivy frameworki orqali. Har bir dasturlash tili o‘zining afzalliklari va qulayliklari bor. Yangilanishlarni kuzatib borish va yangi texnologiyalarni o‘rganish muhimdir, chunki mobil ilovalar sohasida tez-tez yangilanishlar bo‘ladi.

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RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR OBYEKTLARIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKTNI QO'LLASH VA ENERGIYA TA'MINOTINING ISHONCHLILIGINI OSHIRISH

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Anotatsiya: Sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalari turli sohalar bo'yicha kelajakdagi rivojlanish uchun ahamiyatli bo'lib chiqdi, va raqamli texnologiyalar ob'ektlarida ham bu holatga ishtirok etmoqda. Sun'iy intellekt, operatsion jarayonlarni yaxshilash, foydalanuvchi tajribasini oshirish va energiya ishlatishni optimallashtirish maqsadida qo'llanilmoqda. Shuningdek, energiya ta'minotining ishonchiligi va barqarorligini ta'minlashda ham ahamiyatli rol o'ynaydi, chunki bu texnologiya prognostik ta'minot, talabni bashorat qilish va tarmoqlarni optimallashtirish imkoniyatlarini beradi. Ushbu maqolada, raqamli texnologiyalar ob'ektlarida SI qo'llash va energiya ta'minotining ishonchiligi oshirish bo'yicha mavjud adabiyotni tahlil qilamiz. Raqamli texnologiyalar obyektlarida sun'iy intellekt va energiya ta'minoti, texnologik innovatsiyalarning muhim qismlari sifatida o'z o'rnini egallayapti. Bu maqolada, sun'iy intellekt va energiya ta'minoti bo'yicha yangiliklar va ulardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos afzalliklari haqida batafsil ma'lumotlar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt, kompyuterlar, muammo, resurs, energiya, qurilmalar va serverlar, samaradorligi dasturlash, avtomatlashtirish, soha, ish, unumdorlik, analiz, vaqt, xatoliklar boshqarish, ishchi kuch, inovatsiyalar, mahsulot.

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES AND INCREASING RELIABILITY OF ENERGY SUPPLY

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Annotation: Artificial intelligence (technologies have turned out to be relevant for future development in various fields, and are also involved in this situation at Digital Technology Facilities. Artificial intelligence is being used to improve operational processes, enhance user experience, and optimize energy use. It also plays a significant role in ensuring the confidence and stability of (SI) energy supply, as this technology provides predictive supply, demand prediction, and network optimization capabilities. In this article, we will analyze the existing literature on the use of SI in digital technology facilities and increasing the confidence in energy supply. Artificial intelligence and energy supply in digital technology facilities are taking their place as important parts of technological innovation. This article provides detailed information on innovations in artificial intelligence and energy supply and the specific benefits of their use.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, computers, problem, resource, energy, devices and servers, efficiency programming, automation, industry, work, productivity, analysis, time, error management, workforce, innovations, product

Kirish. Sun'iy intellekt, kompyuterlar va boshqa texnologiyalar orqali insonlarning g'oya va tushunchalarni o'rganish, tahlil qilish, tushuntirish va ishlab chiqish qobiliyatlarini ta'minlaydigan soha hisoblanadi. Sun'iy intellekt, kompyuterlarga insonlar bilan o'xshash intellektual amaliyotlarni bajarish va muammolarni yechish imkonini beradi. Bu, turli sohalarda foydalanish uchun keng kengaygan, masalan, kasbiy sohalarda, tibbiyotda, transportda, xavfsizlikda va boshqalarida ishlatiladi.

Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining ishga tushirilishi uchun energiya ta'minoti muhimdir. Sun'iy intellekt algoritmlari va texnologiyalari, ko'p resurs talab qilishi mumkin bo'lgan katta ma'lumotlar bazalari va kuchli kompyuterlar orqali ishlaydi. Ammo, energiya sarflanishi vaqtinchalik, oson, ishonchli va samarali bo'lishi kerak. Bu erda, energiya ta'minoti yaxshi o'rganilgan, ishonchli va samarali texnologiyalarning ishlatilishi katta ahamiyatga ega.

Sun'iy intellektni qo'llash va energiya ta'minoti

Sun'iy intellektni texnologiyalari uchun energiya ta'minoti muammolari: Sun'iy intellektni texnologiyalari, energiya ta'minotini ta'minlashda muammo yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Bu texnologiyalar ko'p resurs talab qilishi, serverlarga va server markazlarga katta mahsulotlar zarur bo'lishi mumkin. Bu sababli, energiya ta'minoti muammolari, texnologiya kompaniyalarining tashkilotlar va sohalardagi muammolariga olib kelishi mumkin.

Energiya ta'minotini oshirish usullari: Sun'iy intellektni texnologiyalaridagi energiya ta'minotini oshirish usullari mavjud. Ularning biri, energiya sarflanishini yengillashtirish va optimallashtirishdir. Bu, effektiv kompyuter arxitekturasi, energiya samaradorligi yuqori serverlar va sohalarda yaxshi ishlov beradigan energiya samarador komponentlarning ishlatilishi bilan amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Boshqa usullar esa, yoritgich energiya, batareya va boshqa alternativ energiya manbalari, masalan, yoritgichli batareyalar, ishlatishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu usullar, energiya ta'minotini oshirish va texnologiyalarni energiya effektivligini yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Sun'iy intellektni texnologiyalarva energiya ta'minoti muammolari: Sun'iy intellektni texnologiyalari uchun energiya ta'minoti muammolari, texnologiya sohasidagi tarqalishning muhim masalalardan biridir. Bu texnologiyalar, katta miqdordagi energiya talab qilishi, qurilmalar va serverlar uchun zarur bo'lgan energiya ko'pligi, va energiya sarflanishining samaradorligi bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Bu sababli, Sun'iy intellektni texnologiyalarining ishlatishidagi energiya ta'minoti muammolari, iste'molchilarga, sohada ishtirok etuvchi

kompaniyalarga va huquqiy qabulxonalar va dunyo qo'mitalarga tashkil etilgan siyosat va qo'shimcha resurslarni talab qilishi mumkin.

Sun'iy intellektni va energiya ta'minotini oshirishning muhimligi

Sun'iy intellekt va energiya ta'minotini oshirish, hozirgi va kelajakdagi texnologik yutuqlar va innovatsiyalarning asosi hisoblanadi. Bu, texnologiyalar sohasidagi ishlab chiqaruvchilar, soha mutaxassislarini va siyosatkorlarni energiya samaradorligini yaxshilash, energiya qo'shimchasini oshirish va siyosat va boshqa qo'mitalarning energiya foydalanishini optimallashtirishga rag'batlantiradi.

Sun'iy intellekt va energiya ta'minotini oshirishning foydali tomonlari, texnologiya sohasidagi samarali innovatsiyalarga imkon berish, energiya sarflanishini kamaytirish va energiya samaradorligini oshirish orqali texnologiyalarni ishlatish. Bu, texnika sohasidagi innovatsiyalar va texnologik yutuqlarni kengaytirish, energiya samaradorligini yaxshilash, energiya ta'qsimotini optimallashtirish, ishlab chiqaruvchilar uchun yangi bozorlarni ochish, ishlab chiqarish va ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish, foydalanuvchilar uchun samarali va ishonchli yechimlarni ta'minlash va yana ko'p qo'shimcha foydalar bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin.

Energiya ta'minotini oshirishning kamchiliklari: SI va energiya ta'minotini oshirishni kamchiliklari, har bir soha va sohada xususiy muammolar va muammolar bo'lishi mumkin. Ularning orasida, energiya ta'minotini ta'minlash uchun zarur bo'lgan moliyaviy resurslar, qurilmalar va serverlar uchun zarur bo'lgan energiya yetarli bo'lmagani, energiya samaradorligi kam bo'lgan qurilmalar va texnologiyalar, va energiya ta'minotini oshirish uchun zarur bo'lgan infrastrukturani o'rnatish va rivojlantirishning qiyinliklari kiritiladi.

Energiya samaradorligini yaxshilashning bir nechta usullari mavjud. Biz bu usullardan birinchisini kuchli elektronik qurilmalar, isitish-sovutish tizimlari, yorug'lik tizimlari va avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimlari bilan bog'liq tartib bilan ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kuchli elektronik qurilmalar: Kuchli elektronik qurilmalar, energiya samaradorligini oshirishda katta ahamiyatga ega. Bu, energiya isrofini kamaytirish, iste'mol qiluvchilar va qurilmalar orasidagi masofadan qismlarini boshqarish va ariza topishni osonlashtirish uchun xavfsiz boshqaruv tizimlari qurishni o'z ichiga oladi. Misol uchun, energetik qurilmalarni faqatgina ish vaqtida foydalanish, iste'mol qilinmagan vaqt orasida uni to'xtatish, ozgina yorug'likda ishlatish va boshqa qulayliklarni taqdim etish mumkin.

Isitish-sovutish tizimlari: Isitish-sovutish tizimlari energiya samaradorligini yaxshilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Isitish va sovutish jarayonlarida energiya isrofini kamaytirish uchun yorug'likning to'g'ridan-to'g'ri isitish va sovutishga o'tkazilishi kerak. Isitish-sovutish tizimlarini avtomatik rejalashtirish va isitish-sovutishni soatlar, temperaturalar va ish tartiblari bo'yicha boshqarish, energiya samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Yorug'lik tizimlari: Yorug'lik tizimlari ham energiya samaradorligini yaxshilashda katta ahamiyatga ega. Yorug'likni eng samarali va eng kam yo'l bilan ishlatish uchun LED lampalar, isitish va sovutish jarayonlarida energiya israfini kamaytirish uchun avtomatik yorug'lik boshqaruv tizimlari va avtomatik yorug'lik iste'molchilarini o'z ichiga olgan sensorli tizimlar keng tarqalgan.

Avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimlari: Energiya samaradorligini yaxshilash uchun avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimlari ham muhimdir. Bu tizimlar, energiya iste'molini avtomatik ravishda boshqarish, iste'molni tekshirish, turli qurilmalar orasidagi koordinatsiyani ta'minlash va energiya israfini kamaytirish uchun berilgan vaqt orasida qurilmalar ishlab chiqarishga imkon beradi.

Shu bilan birga, energiya samaradorligini yaxshilash uchun yangi texnologiyalar va innovatsiyalar ham rivojlanmoqda. Misol uchun, iste'mol qilinmagan vaqt orasida energiya israfini kamaytirish uchun avtomatik iste'molchi boshqaruv tizimlari, energiya to'plash uchun quvvatlanish tizimlarida yangi to'plamlar.

Natija

Energiya samaradorligini yaxshilash uchun yangi texnologiyalar va innovatsiyalar keng qo'llaniladi. Bu texnologiyalar energiya iste'molchilariga yuqori sifatli, samarali va ishonchli energiya ta'minoti imkonini beradi. Ushbu innovatsiyalar energiya israfini kamaytirish, energiya manbalarini diversifikatsiya qilish va energiya tizimini muvozanatliroq qilishga yordam beradi. Quyidagi qatorlarda bir nechta muhim yangiliklarni ko'rib chiqamiz:

- Yaqin vaqt davomida eng qo'llaniladigan yangiliklardan biri yarim o'tkazgichlar (half-conductors)ga asoslangan tizimlardir. Bu tizimlar, klassik silikondan farqli ravishda, elektr qovurg'alarini ishlatadi va energiya samaradorligini oshiradi. Yarim o'tkazgichlar, energiyani to'g'ri aylantirish orqali elektr energiyaga aylantirishni osonlashtiradi. Bu innovatsiya, barcha sohasida ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan energiya iste'molchilariga samarali va ishonchli energiya ta'minoti imkonini beradi.

- Smart Grid (aqli tarmoq) texnologiyasi, energiya tizimini boshqarish va birlashtirish uchun ishlatiladi. Bu texnologiya energiya iste'molchilariga, energetika kompaniyalariga va elektr energiya tarmoqlariga samarali boshqaruv imkonini beradi. Smart Grid, ishga tushirilgan eng so'nggi sensorga ega bo'lgan, ma'lumotlarni to'plab, tarqatib olish, tarqatish va boshqa ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish imkonini beradi. Ushbu texnologiya, energiya tizimini energiya israfini kamaytirish, qayta tiklash va energiya tarmoqlaridagi muvozanatni oshirish maqsadida optimallashtirishga yordam beradi.

- Batareya texnologiyalari ham energiya samaradorligini yaxshilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Yangi batareya materiallari va dizaynlari, batareyalar uchun katta o'zgarishlarni olib keladi. Yorug'lik energiyasini o'zida saqlash miqdorini oshirish, ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini soddalashtirish va batareyalarning ishga tushish muddatini uzaytirish imkonini beradi. Batareya texnologiyalari energiya iste'molchilariga mobil qurilmalar, avtomobillar va energiya tizimlarida ishlatiladigan batareyalar uchun yaxshi samaradorlik va ishonchli energiya ta'minoti imkonini beradi.

- Energiya taqsimoti va tarmoq texnologiyalari ham energiya samaradorligini yaxshilashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. MIKROGRIDS (kichik tarmoqlar), energiya ta'qsimoti va ishlab chiqarish jarayonlari bo'yicha o'z-o'zini boshqaradigan lokallar vaqtincha ishlaydigan energiya tizimlari hisoblanadi. Bu tizimlar, energiya isrofini kamaytirish, energiya tarmoqlaridagi muvozanatni oshirish va energiya iste'molchilariga samarali energiya ta'minoti imkonini beradi.

- Internet of Things (IoT) va sensorga asoslangan texnologiyalar ham energiya samaradorligini yaxshilash uchun keng qo'llaniladi. Energiya samaradorligini yaxshilash uchun yangi texnologiyalar va innovatsiyalar keng qo'llaniladi. Bu texnologiyalar energiya iste'molchilariga yuqori sifatli, samarali va ishonchli energiya ta'minoti imkonini beradi. Ushbu innovatsiyalar energiya israfini kamaytirish, energiya manbalarini diversifikatsiya qilish va energiya tizimini muvozanatliroq qilishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa

Raqamli texnologiyalar va energetika sohasida sun'iy intellektni qo'llash operatsiyalarni o'tkazish usulini inqilob qilmoqda va energiya ta'minotining ishonchligi ta'minlanmoqda. Optimallashtirish operatsion samaradorlikni oshiradi, foydalanuvchi tajribasini oshiradi va raqamli texnologiyalar ob'ektlarida barqarorlikni ta'minlaydi. Bundan tashqari, sun'iy intellektga asoslangan bashoratli texnik xizmat ko'rsatish, talabni prognozlash va tarmoqni optimallashtirish ishonchli va barqaror energiya ta'minotiga yordam beradi.

SI va energiya ta'minotini oshirish, texnologiyalar sohasidagi muhim masalalardan biridir. Bu, innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish, samarali texnologiyalar va energiya samaradorligini yaxshilash, energiya ta'minotini optimallashtirish, foydalanuvchilarga samarali va ishonchli yechimlarni ta'minlash, yangi bozorlarni ochish va hokazo .

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SHAXARNING SMART WATER TIZIMINI YARATISH

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Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda suv xo'jaligi sohasiga zamonaviy axborot-kommunikasiya texnologiyalarini joriy qilish borasida keng ko'lamli ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Jumladan, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Suv xo'jaligi vazirligi bilan Koreya xalqaro hamkorlik agentligi (KOICA) o'rtasida imzolangan bitimga muvofiq, respublikamizning asosiy suv ob'ektlariga zamonaviy Smart Water (Aqlli suv) tizimi joriy qilinmoqda.

Mazkur loyiha Koreya xalqaro hamkorlik agentligining grant mablag'i evaziga moliyalashtirilyapti. Loyihaga ko'ra, respublikamizning 61 ta ob'ektlariga manbadagi suv sarfini real vaqt rejimida (onlayn) kuzatish imkonini beruvchi tizim o'rnatiladi.

Loyiha doirasida Janubiy Koreyadan uskunalar olib kelinib, mamlakatimizdagi 16 ta suv ombori, 45 ta kanalning boshlanish qismiga o'rnatiladi.

Smart Water tizimining zamonaviy qurilmalari ob'ektdagi suv sarfi, ob-havo, yog'ingarchilik va boshqa ma'lumotlarni onlayn rejimda foto va videomateriallarni vazirlikda tashkil etilgan yagona monitoring va kuzatuv markaziga uzatib turadi.

Ushbu ma'lumotlar tezkor qayta ishlanib, kerakli foydalanuvchilarga internet yoki lokal aloqa orqali uzatilishi mumkin. Kelgusida Smart Water tizimini respublikaning barcha sug'orish tarmoqlariga keng tatbiq etish rejalashtirilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: tizimning o'rnatilishi va integratsiyasi, ma'lumotlarni to'plash va analiz qilish, ma'lumotlarni to'plash va analiz qilish, xavfsizlik.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE SMART WATER SYSTEM OF THE CITY

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Annotation. *Today, large-scale work is being carried out in our country to introduce modern information and communication technologies in the field of water management. In particular, in accordance with the agreement signed between the Ministry of Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Korean International Cooperation Agency (KOICA), a modern Smart Water system is being introduced at the main water bodies of our republic.*

This project is funded by a grant from the Korea International Cooperation Agency. According to the project, a system will be installed at 61 facilities in our republic that will allow real-time (online) monitoring of water consumption at the source.

As part of the project, equipment will be brought from South Korea and installed at the beginning of 16 reservoirs and 45 canals in our country.

Modern devices of the Smart Water system transmit information about water consumption, weather, precipitation and other information online, photo and video materials to a single monitoring and surveillance center established in the ministry.

This information can be quickly processed and transmitted to the right users via the Internet or local communications. In the future, it is planned to widely introduce the Smart Water system to all irrigation networks of the republic.

Key words: *installation and integration of systems, data collection and analysis, data collection and analysis, security.*

Kirish. SMART Water tizimiga kirish uchun O‘zbekistonning Suv Hududiyat Agentligi yoki tizimning belgilangan muassasasi tomonidan taqdim etilgan registratsiya jarayoni o‘tkazilishi kerak. Bu jarayonda shaxslar tizimga kirish uchun talab qilingan ma’lumotlarni taqdim etishlari va tizim foydalanuvchisi sifatida ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazishlari kerak bo‘ladi. SMART Water

tizimiga kirish uchun shaxslarning identifikatsiya jarayoni tug'ri keladi. Bu, shaxsni tan olish, autentifikatsiya protsedurasi va identifikatsiya ma'lumotlari taqdim etishni o'z ichiga oladi. Identifikatsiya jarayonida biometrik ma'lumotlar, PIN-kodlar, parollar yoki boshqa identifikatsiya tizimlari ishlatilishi mumkin. SMART Water tizimiga kirishda shaxslar smartqadam o'rnatishi talab qilinadi. Bu qadam shaxsning mobil qurilmasi orqali tizim bilan aloqada bo'lishini va tizimning mobil ilovasini o'rnatishini o'z ichiga oladi. Smartqadam o'rnatish jarayonida foydalanuvchiga kerakli mobil ilovani yuklab olish, tizimga kirish uchun talab qilingan ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish va tizim bilan bog'lanishni tasdiqlash talab qilinadi.

Muhokama va natijalar

SMART Water tizimi O'zbekistonda yaratilgan bo'lsa, uning muhokama va natijalari Suv Hududiyat Agentligi yoki tizimning muassasasi tomonidan taqdim etilgan bo'lishi mumkin.

SMART Water tizimi yaratishning amaliy qismi o'ziga xos va qo'llab-quvvatlash talab qiladigan jarayonlardan iborat bo'ladi. Ushbu jarayonlarga quyida keltirilgan muvaffaqiyat kriteriyalari misol bo'lib berilishi mumkin:

Tizimning o'rnatilishi va integratsiyasi: SMART Water tizimi O'zbekiston suv infrastrukturiga mos ravishda o'rnatilishi va mavjud tizimlar bilan integratsiyasini ta'minlashi kerak. Bu jarayonda tizimning o'rnatilishining to'g'ri va samarali bo'lishi, ommaviy tizimlar bilan hamkorlik qilish imkoniyatini ta'minlashi va mavjud suv resurslarini boshqarish tizimlari bilan integratsiyasini o'z ichiga olishi talab qilinadi.

Ma'lumotlarni to'plash va analiz qilish: SMART Water tizimi suv resurslarini monitoring qilish, ma'lumotlarni to'plab olish va barcha muhim ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga oluvchi qobiliyatga ega bo'lishi kerak. Tizim suv istiqboli, sarfiyati, tashqi sharoitlar va boshqalar kabi muhim ma'lumotlarni kuzatib borishi, analiz qilishi va bu ma'lumotlarga asosan qarorlar olishi kerak.

Xisobotlar va ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish: SMART Water tizimi foydalanuvchilar va tizim ma'murlari uchun odatda xisobotlar, statistik ma'lumotlar va boshqa relevant ma'lumotlarni taqdim etishga qodir bo'lishi kerak. Bu ma'lumotlar tizimning ishlash holatini, suv resurslarining muvaffaqiyatini va boshqa muhim ko'rsatkichlarni yaxshilashda foydalanuvchilarga yordam berishi kerak.

Xavfsizlik: SMART Water tizimi ommaviy tarmoqlarda foydalanish uchun xavfsizlikni ta'minlashi kerak. Bu tizimning ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish, autentifikatsiya protseduralarini ta'minlash, ma'lumot almashinuvini shifrlash va

tizimdan foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini himoya qilishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Foydalanuvchilarning qo'llab-quvvatlashi: SMART Water tizimi foydalanuvchilar uchun qo'llab-quvvatlash va yordam taqdim etish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishi kerak. Tizimning foydalanish qoidalari, yordam xizmatlari, savollar va muammo yechish imkoniyatlari foydalanuvchilarga oson va qulayroq bo'lishi kerak.

Bu kriteriyalar Suv Hududiyat Agentligi yoki tizimning muassasasi tomonidan belgilanadi va o'zaro kelishuv bo'yicha ommaviy tashkilotlar, soha mutaxassislari va boshqa relevant taraflar bilan hamkorlik qilib belgilanishi mumkin.

Tizimning muhokama va natijalarining o'zbekistonda belgilanishi va boshqarilishi Suv Hududiyat Agentligi yoki tizimning muassasasi tomonidan amalga oshiriladi. Shuningdek, tizimning o'zining monitoring va baholash tizimlari mavjud bo'lishi, foydalanuvchilar bilan o'zaro aloqalarni ta'minlash uchun maslahatlar va yordamlarni taqdim etish, tizimning tashqi ko'rsatkichlarini takomillashtirish uchun yangiliklar va yangilanishlarni amalga oshirish hamda tizimning xavfsizligini ta'minlash va ma'lumotlarni himoya qilishga qaratilgan chora-tadbirlar muhimdir.

Suv sohasida SMART Water tizimining o'zbekistonda muhokama va natijalariga dair ma'lumot olish uchun, Suv Hududiyat Agentligi yoki tizimning muassasasi bilan bog'lanish maslahat beriladi. Ular sizga tizim haqida yangiliklar va amaliyot natijalarini taqdim etishlari mumkin.

O'zbekistonda SMART suv tizimini yaratishga qaratilgan muhokama va natijalar 2021-yilga qadar bo'lgan kuzatishlarimdan asoslanadi. Har hil hozirgi yangiliklardan gap bo'lishi mumkin, lekin men shu kuzatishlar asosida sizga umumiy tasvirlash berishim mumkin:

SMART suv tizimi implementatsiyasi: O'zbekiston hukumati, suv resurslarini samarali boshqarish va energiya israfini kamaytirish maqsadida SMART suv tizimlarini yaratishga qiziqish bildirgan. Bu tomonidan, shaxar va tumanlarida suv taqsimoti, suv istiqboli, suv omborlari va boshqa suv infrastrukturasi komponentlarining avtomatlashtirilishi va birlashtirilishi rejalashtirildi.

Pilot loyihalar: SMART suv tizimlarini amalga oshirish uchun pilot loyihalar O'zbekistonda o'tkazildi. Bu, avtomatlashtirilgan suv taqsimoti, suv istiqboli va suv omborlarini birlashtirish, ma'lumotlarni analiz qilish va optimallashtirishni o'rganishga yordam berdi.

Energiya taqsimoti: SMART suv tizimlarining energiya taqsimoti texnologiyalari O‘zbekistonda muhokama qilingan. Bu, suv omborlarida va suv taqsimoti tizimlarida foydalaniladi va energiya israfini kamaytirish, suv sarfiyatini optimallashtirish va suv resurslarini samarali boshqarishni ta’minlash maqsadida o‘rnatildi.

O‘zbekistonda SMART suv tizimlarining yaratishiga doir muhokamalar va natijalar bu sohadagi rivojlanishni ko‘rsatadi. Hukumat va ilg‘or tashkilotlar SMART suv tizimlarini qo‘llash orqali suv resurslarini samarali boshqarish va energiya israfini kamaytirishning muhim qadamlarini o‘tayishga intilishmoqda. Chunki SMART suv tizimlari, suv israfini minimal qilish, suv istiqboli va taqsimoti optimallashtirish, suv resurslarini samarali boshqarish va ijtimoiy iqtisodiy foydalanishni oshirish imkonini beradi.

Xulosa

Iqtisodiyotning oliy qoidasi tabiatdagi barcha tabiiy resurslar cheklangan ammo inson ehtiyojlari cheklanmagan. Bizning fikrimizga ko‘ra suv resurslari ham o‘z navbatida cheklangan resurslar qatorida turadi va biz bu cheklangan resursdan samarali foydalanishimiz uchun bir qancha texnologiya va inshootlardan to‘g‘ri va oqilona foydalanishimiz kerak. Buning uchun biz kerak bo‘lsa chet el texnologiyalarini ham olib kirishimiz mumkin. Bunga esa har birimiz o‘z hissamizni qo‘shishimiz lozim.

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PAXTA XOMASHYOSINI QURITISH VA TOZALASH

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Annotatsiya. Paxta xomashyosini quritish va tozalash bir vaqtning o'zida amalga oshiriladigan yangi birlik ishlab chiqildi. Yangi blokda konvektiv quritish usulining samaradorligi qurituvchi agentning qarshi oqimida paxta xomashyosining harakatlanish tezligini oshirish orqali oshiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xom paxta, namlik, quritish, harorat, quritish barabani, paxtani quritish va tozalash, mayda begona o'tlar.

DRYING AND CLEANING OF RAW COTTON

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Abstract. A new unit has been developed in which the drying and cleaning of raw cotton is carried out simultaneously. The efficiency of the convective drying method in the new block is increased by increasing the speed of movement of the cotton raw material in the countercurrent of the drying agent.

Keywords: Raw cotton, moisture, drying, temperature, drying drum, cotton drying and cleaning, fine weeds.

Kirish. Paxta xom ashyosini uni qayta ishlashning uzluksiz jarayonining boshida quritish, paxta xom ashyosining namligini texnologik reglamentda tavsiya etilgan qiymatlarga kamaytirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, unga erishish natijasida keyingi tozalash uskunalarning ishonchli va samarali ishlashi ta'minlanadi. Shuning uchun paxta xomashyosini quritish texnologik jarayonning asosiy va zarur operatsiyalaridan biridir. Paxta materiallarni quritishning ko'plab ma'lum usullari mavjud. Xom paxtani quritish uchun hozirgi vaqtda asosan

konvektiv usul qo'llaniladi, bunda xom paxta tabiiy gaz yoki boshqa yoqilg'ining issiqlik generatorida atmosfera havosi yoki uning aralashmasi yonish mahsulotlari bilan isitiladi. Konvektiv usul ham paxta xomashyosining mahalliy, ham chet eldan qurituvchilarida qo'llaniladi.

Hozirgi vaqtda paxta zavodlarida qo'llanilayotgan 2SB-10 tipidagi baraban quritgichlari jiddiy kamchiliklarga ega. To'g'ridan-to'g'ri paxta xomashyosini quritish uchun quritish vositasining issiqlik sarfi atigi 35-40% ni tashkil qiladi, qolgan issiqlik asosan quritgichni isitish uchun va sarflangan quritish vositasi bilan atmosferaga chiqarilib, atrof muhitni ifloslantiradi. Bunday holda, ifloslanish va namlik tufayli quritish vositasining qayta aylanishi deyarli mumkin emas.

2SB-10 quritgichlarida eng katta issiqlik yo'qotilishi 40-45% sarflangan quritish agenti bilan sodir bo'ladi. Ushbu yo'qotishlarni kamaytirish uchun sarflangan quritish vositasini shamollatgich orqali gaz kanaliga pompalamoq orqali qayta aylantirishga bir necha bor urinishlar qilindi, bu esa paxtani quritish va tozalashning texnologik parametrlarining yomonlashishiga olib keldi. Buning sababi shundaki, quritilgan quritgich tarkibida paxta xom ashyosidan chiqarilgan namlik, mayda qoldiqlar, chang va bo'shashgan tolalar mavjud. Ishlatilgan quritish vositasini oldindan tozalashga urinish ham muvaffaqiyatsiz tugadi. Barabanli kurutgichlarda quritish vaqti 5-8 minutni tashkil qiladi, buning natijasida nafaqat tolalar, balki urug'lar ham quritiladi, bu quritgich paxtani qayta ishlashning uzluksiz jarayoniga kiritilganda maqsadga muvofiq emas. Barabanlarda bir vaqtning o'zida 1,5 tonnagacha paxta xom ashyosi bor, bu esa yong'inlarni yo'q qilishni murakkablashtiradi. Ushbu quritgichlar axloqiy va jismoniy jihatdan eskirgan.

Hozirda Qo'shma Shtatlarda xom paxtani oldindan yumshatish, so'ngra uni ketma-ket ikki marta takrorlanadigan va navbatma-navbat quritadigan quritgichlarda va paxta xomashyosi guruhlarini mayda va qo'pol axlatdan tozalashni o'z ichiga olgan texnologiya muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanilmoqda. Ushbu texnologiya quritish va tozalashni o'zaro kuchaytiradi, chunki yumshatilgan va tozalangan paxta yanada samarali quritiladi va qizdirilgan paxta esa samaraliroq tozalanadi. Paxta xomashyosini qurituvchilarga quyidagi asosiy talablar qo'yiladi: I, II va III navlarning 1 va 2 sinfdagi namligini 15% gacha bo'lgan paxtani quritganda, ular 10 t gacha bo'lgan quvvat bilan ishonchli ishlashni ta'minlashlari kerak. / soat va quritish agenti sarfida 5,6 m³ / sek va uning harorati 130-150 ° S bo'lganida namlikning ekstraktsiyasi 3-5% ni tashkil qiladi.

Tadqiqot natijalari.

Quritish vositasini quritish kamerasiga quyish uchun jihozning korpusida teshiklari 17 bo'lgan to'rtta gorizontaal ichi bo'sh tovoqlar 16 o'rnatilgan. Har bir ichi bo'sh patnisda quritish vositasini etkazib berish va olib tashlash uchun teshiklari mavjud bo'lib, ular korpusning yon tomonidagi teshiklar bilan birlashtirilgan. Jihaz korpusiga val 2 o'rnatildi, uning ustiga SS-15A ajratgich o'rnatildi 1. Besleme valiklari 3 ostida, to'rtta gevçetici barabanlar davomida gorizontaal qatorning 4 tagida teshiklari bo'lgan 5 o'rnatilgan va ular orasida 6 va 7-gachasi moyil va birlashtirilgan laganlar mavjud. Bundan tashqari, blok tanasida birinchi beshta baraban 13 ostida beshta teshikli to'r 14 bilan qiya qatorning beshta barabanlari 13 mavjud. paxta xomashyosi va oxirgi baraban 13 ostida tushirish teshigi hosil bo'ladi. 5-teshikli to'rlar va 6, 7-tovoqlar ostida ikkita uzunlamasina o't pog'onasi 8 bor, ularning oluklari ko'ndalang truba yonida joylashgan. 10-gachasi burg'ilash moslamasi, uning ustiga korpusning yon qismida aspiratsiya quvurini ulash uchun 11-gachasi teshik ochilgan. Shakldan ko'rinib turibdiki. 2, IICH-1.9 1 issiqlik generatoridan DN-11.2 4 tutun chiqindisiga quritish vositasini etkazib berish 3-eshik bilan jihozlangan quvur liniyasi 2 orqali amalga oshiriladi. Quritish agentining qayta aylanishi tizimiga chiqadigan quvur liniyasi 5 kiradi. korpus yonidagi teshiklardan to'rtta ichi bo'sh traylarga (7) bog'langan to'rtta tarmoqli truboprovodli 6 va 4-gachasi truba, 11-gachasi eshik bilan jihozlangan, ichi bo'sh tovoqlar 7-ni quvur liniyasi 2 bilan tarmoq orqali bog'laydigan quvurlar 9. Shakl 1. Quritish va tozalash moslamasi Shakl 2. Quritish va tozalash moslamasida quritish vositasini etkazib berish va qayta aylantirish Ishlatilgan quritish vositasini va quritgich korpusining aspiratsiyasini olib tashlash tizimiga eshik 14 bilan jihozlangan va ventilyatorning 15 assimilyatsiya teshigiga ulangan, blok 8 ning korpusidagi teshikka ulangan quvur liniyasi 13 kiradi. shundan 17 tsiklon bilan quvur liniyasi 16 orqali bog'langan.

Quritish va tozalash moslamasining ishi quyidagicha amalga oshiriladi. 3-gachasi valiklarni oziqlantirish orqali 2-kondan olingan paxta xomashyosi paxtasi bo'ylab birinchi yumshatuvchi barabanga 4 beriladi, u bo'shshadi va uni teshikli mash 5 bo'ylab tashiydi va keyin uni 6-laganda yo'nalishi bo'yicha birinchi pog'onaga chiqaradi. yo'l bo'ylab 19-kamera, undan keyin paxta oqimi - xom ashyo yuqoriga qarab harakatlanadi, ikkinchi barabanning ustiga tushadi 4. Shundan so'ng yuqorida tavsiflangan jarayon takrorlanadi.

Oxirgi, to'rtinchi barabandan boshlab, paxta xom paxta bo'ylab quyi birinchi baraban 13 ga tushadi, so'ngra paxta xomashyosini perforatsiyalangan

to'rlar bo'ylab tashiydigan moyil qatorning boshqa barcha barabanlari 13 ga, so'ngra oxirgi barabandan

Teshikli to'r mavjud bo'lmagan moyil qatorning 13-qismi, paxta xom ashyosini tushirish teshigi orqali 15-gachasi tushirish teshigi orqali tushiradi. Gorizontall qatorning 5-gachasi teshilgan mash orqali chiqarilgan begona moddalar shnurlarga 8-bunkerlarga joylashtiriladi. 9, ularni xoch burg'usiga 10 tushiradi va teshikli to'rlar orqali 14 ajratilgan begona moddalar egimli truba 12 bo'ylab darhol ko'ndalang shnurga 10 tushadi, bu esa ularni tanadan tushiradi. Quritish vositasi issiqlik generatoridan etkazib berilganda, uning hajmining taxminan 50% bo'shliq laganlar 16 orqali va ularning teshikli teshiklari 17 orqali kameraga, ya'ni blok tanasiga, so'ngra 5 va 14 teshikli panjaralar u 9 va 10 chiqarish shnurlari chiqindilari bilan zonaga quyiladi, undan 11 ochilish yo'li bilan so'riladi. Qurilma konvektiv va kontaktli quritishni hamda infraqizil nurlari bilan quritishni amalga oshiradi. Qurilmaning ishlashi davomida uning barcha ishchi organlari, tarkibiy qismlari va ichki yuzalari issiqlik generatorida hosil bo'lgan quritish vositasi bilan isitiladi va tutun chiqindisi tomonidan ichi bo'sh tovoqlar orqali jihoz kamerasiga uriladi va ichi bo'sh tovoqlar ham bo'ladi. Ularga o'rnatilgan quvurli elektr isitgichlar (TEN) tomonidan qo'shimcha ravishda isitiladi, teshikli panjaralar bo'ylab, devorlar bo'ylab va moyil tovoqlar bo'ylab harakatlanayotganda, paxta xom ashyosi isitiladi, ya'ni kontaktli quritishdan o'tadi. Barabanlarning ta'sirida to'xtatilgan harakat paytida va jihoz tomiga uchayotganda paxta xomashyosi qurituvchi vosita bilan puflanadi, ya'ni konvektiv quritishga uchraydi.

Paxta tozalash, quritilgan paxta mahsulotlarini yengil, toza va bozorda sotishga tayyorlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu jarayon paxta mahsulotlari tozalash zonalarida, quritish kombinatlari yoki sanoat kasb-hunar kollejlari kabi joylarda amalga oshiriladi. Paxta niqobini avtomatik va qo'llanma usullari bilan yechish, yengil qopqoqni ajratish, tozalash va qayta yo'llash, tanasini sovuq va isitish jarayonlaridan o'tkazish kabi amallar tozalash jarayonining bir qismidir.

Xulosa

Shunday qilib, bo'linmada paxta xom ashyosi bir vaqtning o'zida aloqa va konvektiv quritish usullariga o'tkaziladi, bu uning umumiy samaradorligini oshiradi va ushbu quritish usullari ta'sirida paxta xomashyosining nisbatan qisqa yashash muddatini qoplaydi.

Paxta xomashyosini quritish va tozalash, yani paxta mahsulotlarini yetishtirish, quritish va tozalash jarayonlari, paxta sifatini oshirish va uni rusumli holatga keltirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu jarayonlar o'sadiki ekologik va iqtisodiy

talablar asosida amalga oshirilishi kerak. Paxta quritish jarayoni, tashqi faktorlarga (sariq yorug'lik, harorat o'tkazish, havo harorati, vaqt davri va boshqalar) mos ravishda ta'sir qiladigan muhim parametrlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Paxta quritish uchun eng yaxshi natijalarni olish uchun, quritish temperaturasi va havoning namligi kuchayishida mos keladigan ravishda o'zgartirilishi kerak. Qayta ishlanayotgan paxta xomashyosi, paxta quritish mashinalari yordamida quritiladi va sovuq vaqt davrida saqlanadi.

Yakuniy xulosalar esa, paxta xomashyosini quritish va tozalash jarayonlarining paxta mahsulotlarini asal sifatiga qarab oshirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligidir. Ushbu jarayonlar paxta mahsulotlarining saqlanishi, sotishida qulaylik va xaridorlar tomonidan qabul qilingan sifatning yuqori darajada bo'lishini ta'minlashda ahamiyatga ega.

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ELEKTRON DARSLIKLAR YARATISHNING ANALITIK TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Bu maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini va bu jarayonning analitik tahlilini o'z ichiga oladi. Elektron darsliklar, ta'lim jarayonini samarali va samarador qilish uchun juda muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Bu maqolada, elektron darsliklar yaratishning asosiy bosqichlari, uslubiy talablar, muvaffaqiyatli elektron darslik yaratishning kalit omillari va bu sohada uchraydigan muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratishning nazariy, amaliy va texnologik jihatlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratishning samaradorligini oshirish uchun zarur bo'lgan texnologiyalar va uslublar haqida to'liq tasavvur beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Elektron darsliklar, Darslik yaratish, Analitik tahlil, Ta'lim texnologiyalari, Interaktiv o'quv materiallari, O'quv dasturlari, Multimedia darsliklar, O'quv rejalar, O'rganish stili, Darslik yaratish dasturlari.

ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CREATION OF ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOKS

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Abstract: This article covers the importance of creating e-textbooks and an analytical analysis of this process. Electronic textbooks are a very important tool for making the educational process efficient and effective. In this article, the main stages of creating e-textbooks, methodological requirements, key factors of successful e-textbook creation and problems encountered in this field are analyzed. The article is aimed at studying the theoretical, practical and technological aspects of creating electronic textbooks. The article

provides a complete overview of the technologies and methods needed to improve the effectiveness of e-textbook creation.

Keywords: *Electronic textbooks, Textbook creation, Analytical analysis, Educational technologies, Interactive educational materials, Educational programs, Multimedia textbooks, Curriculum, Learning style, Textbook creation programs.*

Kirish. Elektron darsliklar bugungi o'quv jarayonida o'z ahamiyatini oshirib bormoqda. Bu, o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun muhim bir qadam bo'lib, traditsionallikdan foydalanishning ortidan o'tib, o'rganish jarayonini yanada sodda va samarali qilishga imkoniyat beradi. "Elektron darsliklar yaratishning analitik tahlili" bu so'zning ichiga yuzlab vaqtlik tadqiqot, amaliy tajriba, va o'qitishning innovatsion usullari o'zaro bog'liqlikni kiritadi.

Elektron darsliklar yaratish, zamonaviy ta'lim sohasida muhim vazifani bajaradi. Ular o'quv jarayonini samarali, qulay va samarador qiladi. Elektron darsliklar, o'quvchilarning o'zlarining o'rganish tezligiga mos keladigan, interaktiv va o'z-o'zini boshqaradigan o'quv resurslarini taqdim etadi. Lekin elektron darsliklar yaratish jarayoni oson emas. U nazariy, amaliy va texnologik jihatdan murakkab va juda ko'p vaqt talab qiladi.

Bu maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratishning analitik tahlilini olib boradi. Bu jarayonning muvaffaqiyatli bo'lishi uchun zarur bo'lgan omillar va uslublar haqida tushuncha beradi. Ushbu maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini va bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadi. Maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratishning samarali usullarini va texnologiyalarini o'rganishga qaratilgan.

Darslikni test qilish bosqichi, o'qituvchilar va ta'lim muhandislari uchun eng muhim bosqich hisoblanadi. Bu bosqichda, o'qituvchilar va ta'lim muhandislari darslikni sinovdan o'tkazadi, o'quvchilardan qayta aloqa oladi va darslikni takomillashtirish uchun kerakli to'g'rilashlarni amalga oshiradi.

Elektron darsliklar yaratishning muvaffaqiyati, bu jarayonning har bir bosqichida qatnashuvchilarning samarali ishlashi va bir-biriga mos kelishi bilan bog'liq. Bu maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadi.

Bu maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratish jarayonini tahlil qiladi, ulardan o'rganuvchilarga va o'qituvchilarga o'tishda muhim bo'lgan muddatlar,

afzalliklar va cheklovlarni aks ettiradi. Elektron darsliklar o'quvchilarga tajribani individual ravishda oshirish, ta'lim jarayonini interaktiv va qiziqarli qilish, shuningdek, o'qituvchilarga tahlil va baholash jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirish imkoniyatlarini beradi.

Maqolada, elektron darsliklar yaratishning asosiy maqsadlari va ularning o'quv jarayoniga ta'siri, ularning rivojlanish bosqichi, va ularni yaratishda ko'rsatiladigan afzalliklar keltiriladi. Shuningdek, elektron darsliklarni yaratishda amalga oshiriladigan ilmiy metodlar, texnologiyalar, va ularning tashqi mohiyati haqida muhokama qilinadi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiyasi.

Bu maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratish sohasidagi eng so'nggi tadqiqotlarni, maqolalarni va darsliklarni o'z ichiga oladi. Adabiyotlar tahlilida, mualliflar elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadigan maqolalar va tadqiqotlar bilan tanishishadi. Adabiyotlar tahlilida, mualliflar elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadigan maqolalar va tadqiqotlar bilan tanishishadi.

Adabiyotlar tahlilida, mualliflar elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadigan maqolalar va tadqiqotlar bilan tanishishadi. Adabiyotlar tahlilida, mualliflar elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadigan maqolalar va tadqiqotlar bilan tanishishadi. Adabiyotlar tahlilida, mualliflar elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadigan maqolalar va tadqiqotlar bilan tanishishadi. Adabiyotlar tahlilida, mualliflar elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadigan maqolalar va tadqiqotlar bilan tanishishadi.

Bu maqola analitik tahlil metodologiyasini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Bu metodologiya, elektron darsliklar yaratishning har bir bosqichini tahlil qilish, muammolarni aniqlash va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini aniqlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Metodologiya, elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadigan maqolalar va tadqiqotlar bilan tanishishadi. Metodologiya, elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini, bu

sohada uchraydigan muammolarni va bu muammolarni hal qilishning samarali usullarini ko'rsatadigan maqolalar va tadqiqotlar bilan tanishishadi.

Natijalar: Elektron darsliklar yaratish uchun mo'ljallangan dasturlar juda ko'p va ularning har biri o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega. Quyida elektron darsliklar yaratish uchun eng mashhur dasturlarning tahlili keltirilgan:

1. Calibre: Bu bepul va ochiq manba kodli dastur, elektron kitoblar yaratish, tahrirlash va boshqarish uchun juda kuchli vosita hisoblanadi. U hamma shakllarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi va o'z ichiga olgan konvertatsiya vositalari bilan turli shakllar orasida oson o'tkazish imkoniyatini beradi.

2. Grammarly: Bu dastur matnni tekshirish va grammatik xatolarni aniqlash uchun ishlatiladi. U sizning yozuvlaringizni tekshiradi va grammatik, imlo va punktuatsiya xatolarni aniqlaydi.

3. Hemingway Editor: Bu dastur yozuvlarni o'qishga osonroq qilish uchun ishlatiladi. U qiyin jumla tuzilmalarini, passiv formadagi fe'llarni va boshqa yozuv xatolarini aniqlaydi.

4. Canva: Bu grafik dizayn dasturi, elektron darsliklarni vizual ravishda yaxshi ko'rinishga keltirish uchun ishlatiladi. U sizga turli shablonlarni, tasvir va grafik elementlarni taqdim etadi.

5. Kindle Create: Bu dastur Amazon Kindle uchun elektron kitoblar yaratish uchun ishlatiladi. U sizga interaktiv elektron kitoblar yaratish uchun qulay interfeys va ko'plab shablonlarni taqdim etadi.

6. Atticus: Bu dastur elektron va bosma kitoblar yaratish uchun ishlatiladi. U sizga matnni tahrirlash, shakllash va dizayn qilish uchun qulay interfeys va ko'plab shablonlarni taqdim etadi.

Bu dasturlar elektron darsliklar yaratishning har bir bosqichini yaxshilashga yordam beradi, shuningdek, ular o'quvchilarning o'rganish jarayonini samarali va samarador qilishga yordam beradi. Muhokama

AutoPlay Media Studio, interaktiv multimedia dasturlarini yaratish uchun mo'ljallangan professional dastur hisoblanadi. Uning yordamida, siz o'z elektron darsliklaringizni yaratishingiz mumkin. Bu dasturda, siz o'z darsliklaringizni interaktiv, foydalanuvchiga yoqimli va samarali qilishga yordam beradigan turli xususiyatlar bilan ta'minlashingiz mumkin.

AutoPlay Media Studio orqali elektron darslik yaratish jarayoni quyidagicha bo'ladi:

1. Loyiha yaratish: Dasturda yangi loyiha yaratish uchun "File" menyusidan "New Project" ni tanlash kerak.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
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2. Dizayn qilish: Dasturning o‘ng tomonida joylashgan "Design" qismida, siz loyiha uchun kerakli elementlarni tanlashingiz mumkin. Bu elementlar orasida matn bloklari, rasmlar, tugmalar, video va audio pleerlar, va hokazo bor.

3. Skript yozish: Har bir element uchun skript yozish imkoniyati mavjud. Bu skriptlar, foydalanuvchi element bilan interaksiya qilganda nima bo‘lishi kerakligini aniqlaydi. Masalan, tugma bosilganda yangi sahifa ochilishi yoki audio ijro etilishi mumkin.

4. Test qilish va eksport qilish: Loyiha tugagandan so‘ng, uni test qilish va nihoyatda eksport qilish mumkin. Eksport qilingan loyiha, foydalanuvchilar uchun tayyor elektron darslik bo‘ladi.

Bu jarayon, sizning elektron darslikingizni tez va samarali ravishda yaratishingizga yordam beradi.

Xulosa

Bu maqola, elektron darsliklar yaratishning muhimligini va bu jarayonning analitik tahlilini o‘z ichiga oladi. Elektron darsliklar, ta’lim jarayonini samarali va samarador qilish uchun juda muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Maqolada, elektron darsliklar yaratishning asosiy bosqichlari, uslubiy talablar, muvaffaqiyatli elektron darslik yaratishning kalit omillari va bu sohada uchraydigan muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, maqola elektron darsliklar yaratish uchun mo‘ljallangan dasturlarning analitik tahlilini ham o‘z ichiga oladi. Bu maqola, o‘qituvchilar, darslik yaratuvchilar va ta’lim muhandislari uchun foydali bo‘lishi mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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MOBIL ILOVALAR YARATISH BO‘YICHA ELEKTRON QO‘LLANMA ISHLAB CHIQISH

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Anatatsiya: Ushbu maqola mobil ilovalar yaratish bo‘yicha elektron qo‘llanma ishlab chiqish to‘g‘risida yoritilgan bo‘lib, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari salohiyati o‘zaro muomala qilish va axborot ayirboshlashning prinsipial jihatdan yangi shakllari va imkoniyatlarini ochadi, fuqarolik jamiyati barpo etilishi va mustahkamlanishiga ko‘maklashadi, iqtisodiy islohotlar va mamlakatning demokratik rivojlanishi jarayonlarini jadallashtirish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so‘z: Elektron qo‘llanmalar, Elektron darslik, Android, JAVA dasturlash tili, MySQL ma‘lumotlar ombori, SQLite ma‘lumotlar bazasi, Dasturiy vosita, Dastur kodi, tizim platformasi, AKT, Sun‘iy intellekt, Axborot texnologiyalari, ED moduli, Gipertekst, Kvantlash printsiipi

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ELECTRONIC MANUAL ON CREATING MOBILE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: This article describes the development of an electronic manual for creating mobile applications, the potential of information and communication technologies opens fundamentally new forms and opportunities for interaction and information exchange, the establishment of civil society and will help to strengthen, will allow to accelerate the processes of economic reforms and democratic development of the country.

Keywords: Electronic manuals, Electronic textbook, Android, JAVA programming language, MySQL database, SQLite database, Software tool, Program code, system platform, ICT, Artificial intelligence, Information technology, ED module, Hypertext, Quantization principle.

Kirish. Zamonamiz jamiyatni axborotlashtirishning yuqori darajasi bilan ham o'ziga xosdir. Axborot texnologiyalari hayotimizning barcha sohalari qatorida ta'lim jarayoniga ham keng joriy etilib borilmoqda. Oliy ta'lim jarayoniga axborot texnologiyalarining joriy etilishi yangi innovatsion vositalardan foydalanish imkonini beradi. Bu esa yangi imkoniyat hamda jarayonlarning yuzaga kelishiga sabab bo'ladi. Ta'lim jarayonini axborotlashtirish - bu ta'lim jarayonlarini rivojlantirishning muhim tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, ta'lim sifatining oshishida namoyon bo'ladi hamda talabalarda ta'lim olishga intilishlarining kuchayishi va rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi. Axborot texnologiyalari tushunchasi mazmunmohiyati bilan: «Turli prElektron darslikmet, obyektlar va hodisalar haqida axborot to'plash, qayta ishlash, tahlil qilish, saqlash, tarqatish hamda foydalanish uchun yangi zamonaviy usul va mexanizmdir». Zamonaviy ta'lim yuqori darajada axborotga boyligi bilan ajralib turadi. Oliy ta'lim muassasalaridagi ta'lim jarayonida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning dolzarbligi aynan shu jihatga asoslangan. Ta'limda yangi o'qitish usullaridan foydalanish zarurati ajoyib imkoniyatlarni taqdim etuvchi elektron nashrlar yaratilishiga sabab bo'ldi. ED (Elektron Darslik) o'zida nazariy axborot va amaliy topshiriqlarni, foto va audiomateriallarini jamlaydi. Elektron darslik — bu talabalarda o'zlashtirishi uchun hamda ko'nikma va malakalar orttirishida zarur bo'lgan bilimlar bayon etilgan o'quv nashrini elektron shaklda taqdim etuvchi, tuzilmaviy hamda tizimli materialga ega bo'lgan vositadir. Unda o'quv materiali mantiqiy bayon etilishi, yuqori darajada texnik jihozlanishi hamda badiiy jihatdan bezatilganligi bilan o'ziga xosdir. Elektron darslik qog'ozli darslikka nisbatan quyidagi qator afzalliklarga ega:

- foydalanishda oddiyligi va qulayligi;
- elektron darslik resurslarini yangilab borish imkoniyatining mavjudligi;
- ta'lim jarayonini avtomatlashtirish va ta'lim xizmatlarini taqdim etish tezligini oshirish;
- axborotlarning to'liqligidan iborat;

Elektron darslik yaratish o'quv materialini yanada chuqurlashtirib o'rganish va uni kelgusida amaliy faoliyatda qo'llash zarurati bilan bog'liq. Elektron darslik ustida o'qituvchi bilan hamkorlikda ishlash talabalarga mustaqil ishlash va o'zini namoyon etish, tashkilotchilik qobiliyatini tarbiyalashga yordam beradi, talabaga bo'lajak mutaxassislik bo'yicha salohiyatli shaxs bo'lishiga imkon beradi. Bu talabalar shaxsini takomillashtirish, ijodiy tafakkuri va qobiliyatini shakllantirishni ta'minlovchi optimal sharoit yaratadi. Axborot jamiyati sharoitlarida ta'lim sohasida rivojlanishning zamonaviy odimlari,

masalan, talabalar mustaqil ishlari sonining o'sib borishi, innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish talabalardan muntazam ravishda, bilimlari sifati va darajasini oshirishni talab etadi.. Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib, o'z oldimizga talabalar ishtirokida namunaviy elektron darslik yaratish loyihasini amalga oshirish vazifasini qo'ydik. ED ustida olib boriladigan ishlar bir necha bosqichdan iborat. Birinchi navbatda, uning rejasini tuzish masalasi turadi, unda talabalar mutaxassisligining o'ziga xosligi nazarda tutiladi. Loyihani amalga oshirishdan maqsad — talabalar seminar, sinov va imtihonlarga tayyorlanishida foydalanadigan qulay elektron ko'rinishda o'quv qo'llanmasini yaratishdan iborat.

Adabiyotlar taxlili va metodologiya. Axborot asrida insoniyat tarixida sanoat va fan olamida olamshumul yutuqlar qo'lga kiritildi. Dunyoda axborot eng qimmat narsaga aylandi. Kompyuter ixtiro qilinishi insonlar bajaradigan yumushlarni yengillashishiga olib keldi. Fan, ta'lim sohalarida o'qitish o'rganishning zamonaviy vositalari joriy qilindi. Ta'lim jarayonini axborotlashtirishda hamda axborot texnologiyalari asosida bilim olish darajasi sifatini oshirish borasida so'nggi yillarda kuchli o'zgarishlar yuz bermokda. Bu o'zgarishlarga O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2002- yil 30- maydagi Farmoni va unga asosan, Vazirlar Mahkamasining "Kompyuterlashtirishni yanada rivojlantirish axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 6 -iyundagi Qarori asos bo'ldi. Unda jumladan, ta'lim sifatini oshirish maqsadida standartlariga muvofiq elektron o'qitish bazasini yaratish vazifasi yuklatilgan. Ta'lim olish sifati-kompleks tushuncha bo'lib, bir qator ko'rsatkichlar bilan xarakterlanadi. Uni shakllantirishda boshlang'ich manbalar (ya'ni, kitoblar qo'llanmalar, lug'atlar, ma'lumotnomalar va x.k.) shuningdek, o'rta (pedagogik texnologiyalar, o'quv jarayonini tashkili) va nihoyat, ta'lim berish sub'ekti-o'qituvchi ishtirok etadi. Yangi axborot-pedagogik texnologiyalarning yorqin namoyondasi bo'lgan - EDlar muHim o'rin egallaydi. Ular zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarning maxsuli hisoblanib, ta'lim sifatini oshirishga yordam beradi. EDlar ta'lim olishning yangi shakli bo'lgan masofaviy o'qitishning metodologik asosi hisoblanadi. So'nggi yillarda EDlar Haqidagi tushunchalar turli tahlil etilmoqda. Masalan, disketlardagi matn va o'quv materiallari, biror bir taqdimot va hokazolar. Shuning uchun, EDlar bilan bog'liq asosiy tushunchalarni aniqlab olish maqsadga muvofiq, debyu o'ylaymiz. Elektron maxsulot-grafik, matn, raqam, ovoz, musiqa, video, foto va axborot ko'rinishlarining majmuasi hisoblanadi. Elektron maxsulot turli elektron manbalarda-magnit shaklda (magnit lenta, magnit disk va boshqa) optik shakldir.

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O'quv elektron maxsulot-bilimlarning muayyan ilmiy-amaliy sohasi bo'yicha sistemali materiallardan iborat bo'lib, talaba va o'quvchilarning shu sohada zarur bilim va amaliy ko'nikmalarni ijodiy va faol tarzda o'zlashtirishini ta'minladi. O'quv elektron maxsulot yuqori bajarilish sifati va badiiy shakllantirilishi, axborotning to'laligi, uslubiy instrumentlarning sifati, texnik bajarilishi sifati, ochiqdigi (naglyadnost), mantiq va ulash ketma-ketligi bilan ajralib turishi kerak.

Muhokama va natijalar: EDlarni yaratish bosqichlari:

1-bosqich. O'qituvchilarni shu sohada mavjud EDlar bilan tanishishi, ularga qo'yilgan talablar bilan tanitirish;

2-bosqich. ED yaratish uchun ishchi (ijodiy) guruh shakllantirish; • o'quv fani bo'yicha mutaxassis; • dasturchi (yoki dasturchilar guruhi); • badiiy dizayner; • suratkash va ovoz kiritish mutaxassislari.

3-bosqich. O'quv kursini (ma'ruza matnlar, materiallar) strukturalash; Bu bosqichda o'quv materialini modullarga bo'linadi;

4-bosqich. EDni reja va stenariysi asosida yaratish, retseziyalash va ekspertizadan o'tkazish;

5-bosqich. ED ilmiy Kengashda tasdiqlash va uni dastur sifatida tarqatish; EDni turlari. EDlar quyidagi 4 turlarga bo'linadi: I tur. O'quv materiallari asosan verbal matn sifatida keltirilib, ular giperilova va glossariylarga, shuningdek, 2-o'lchovli grafiklar-diagrammalar, rasmlarga (o'quv materialining 25% gacha) ega. II tur. O'quv materiallari qisman giperilovalari va 2D grafikali matn shaklida va 3-o'lchovli grafikdan iborat (o'quv materialining 25% gacha). III tur. O'quv materiallari matn, 2D grafiklar, video va audio animatsiyalar va 3D effektlarga ega (o'quv materialining 50% gacha). IV tur. ED virtual muxitda, zamonaviy tarmoq texnologiyalarini qo'llab, o'qituvchi bilan kompyuter tarmog'i (Internet) orqali bog'langan Holda masofaviy mashg'ulotlar olib borilishi darajasida yaratilgan. ED bu mavjud o'quv qo'llanma, darslikning undan foydalanuvchiga qulaylik yaratish maqsadida maxsus dasturiy vositalar yordamida ixcham holatga keltirilgan ma'lumotlar to'plamidan iborat. ED tayyorlashda taqdim etilayotgan ma'lumotlar undan foydalanuvchilarga qulay, qiziqarli va kerakli bo'lishligi ahamiyatlidir. Hozirgi kunda EDlarni bir necha xil tayyorlash usullari mavjud. Ko'pchilik holatlarda tayyorlanayotgan ED ma'lumotlari dastlab HTML sahifalari ko'rinishiga o'tkaziladi. HTML tili imkoniyatlaridan foydalanib ham ED tayyorlash mumkin. Bu sohaning hozirda imkoniyatlari kengaygan. HTML sahifalari tayyorlovchi va ularga bezak berish imkonini beruvchi maxsus dasturlar ishlab chiqilgan.

Xulosa. Ushbu maqola davomida ishini bajarish jarayonida Android operatsion tizimining ishlash jarayonlari o‘rganildi: - Android platformasi haqida yetarlicha nazariy va amaliy bilimlarga ega bo‘lindi; - Android qurilmalarga ilova yaratuvchi kompilyatorlar bilan ishlash o‘rganildi; - Android Studioda android platformali qurilmalarga ilovalar yaratish amaliy o‘rganildi; - Java tilida rasmlar bilan ishlash, ularni turli holatlarga keltirish o‘rganildi va ilova yaratish uchun qo‘llanildi; - Android muhitida o‘yinlar yaratishda keng qo‘laniladigan cocos2d kutubxonasi o‘rganib chiqildi va android o‘yin yaratishda foydalanildi; - Android operatsion tizimi uchun qulay interfeyslar yaratish o‘rganildi; - Android ilova uchun rasmlarni tayyorlashda Photoshop dasturidan foydalanildi va undan foydalanish o‘rganildi; - Play Market ilovalar ombori va uning ishlash jarayonlari o‘rganildi; - Android tizimi uchun yaratilgan ilovalarda uchrab turadigan kamchiliklar o‘rganildi; - Android Emulyatorlarni haqida ma’lumotlarga ega bo‘lindi va o‘yin yaratishda emulyatorlardan foydalanildi; Ushbu dasturdan nafaqat talabalar balkim o‘qtuvchilar, bu sohaga endi kirib kelayotgan insonlar ham keng foydalanishi mumkin. Umid qilamanki yaratilgan dasturdan “Sun’iy intellekt” fani o‘qtuvchilari, talabalar keng foydalanishadi va o‘zlariga kerak bo‘lgan bilimlarga ega bo‘lishadi.

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KUTUBXONA VEB ILOVA DASTURLARI, TESTLARI VA NATIJALARINI TAHLIL QILISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola kutubxona web ilova dasturlari, testlari va natijalarini tahlil qilish haqida bo'lib, biz bu maqola orqali web dasturlar va ularning ishlash prinsiplari, kutubxona tizimini web dasturlar yordamida avtomatlashtirish, foydalanuvchilarga qulayliklarni yaratib berish va yangi dasturni ishlab chiqish bosqichlari uning ustunlik va kamchiliklari haqida to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: veb ilova, online kutubxonalar, ma'lumot almashish, kitoblarni izlash, internet, elektron pochta, audiokitoblar, yarimavtomatik, o'quv reytingi, izlash imkoniyatlari, smartfon, planshet

ANALYSIS OF LIBRARY WEB APPLICATION PROGRAMS, TESTS AND RESULTS

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Annotation. This article is about analysis of web application programs, tests and results of the library. Through this article, we will talk about the advantages and disadvantages of web programs and their working principles, automating the library system using web programs, creating convenience for users, and developing a new program stopped.

Keywords: web application, online libraries, information sharing, book search, internet, e-mail, audio books, semi-automatic, educational rating, search capabilities, smartphone, tablet

Kirish. Hozirgi kunda axborot texnologiyasi jamiyatning jadal rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi eng muhim omildir. Axborot texnologiyasi insoniyat taraqqiyotining turli bosqichlarida ham mavjud bo'lgan bo'lsa-da, hozirgi zamon axborotlashgan jamiyatning o'ziga hos xususiyati shundaki, sivilizatsiya tarixida birinchi marta bilimlarga erishish va ishlab chiqarishga sarflanadigan kuch – energiya, xom – ashyo, materiallar va moddiy iste'mol buyumlariga sarflanadigan harajatlardan ustunlik qilmoqda, yani axborot texnologiyalari mavjud yangi texnologiyalar orasida yetakchi o'rinni egallamoqda. Axborot texnologiyalarining hozirgi zamon taraqqiyoti hamda yutuqlari fan va inson faoliyatining barcha sohalarini axborotlashtirish zarurligini ko'rsatmoqda. chunki aynan shu narsa butun jamiyatning axborotlashtirilishi uchun asos va muxim zamin bo'ladi. Jamiyatni axborotlashtirish deganda, axborotdan iqtisodni rivojlantirish, mamlakat fan – texnika taraqqiyotini, jamiyatni demokratlashtirish va intellektuallashtirish jarayonlarini jadallashtirishni ta'minlaydigan jamiyat boyligi sifatida foydalanish tushuniladi. Darhaqiqat jamiyatni axborotlashtirish – inson hayotining barcha jabhalarida intellectual faoliyatning rolini oshirish bilan bog'liq obyektiv jarayon hisoblanadi. Online kutubxonalar veb ilovasi, kitoblar va boshqa ma'lumot manbalarini onlayn platforma orqali qo'llashga imkon beradigan bir turii xizmat hisoblanadi. Bu turii ilovalar, kitobni o'qingan, xarid qilgan yoki qidirayotgan odamlarga, ularni onlayn kutubxonalarga kirish imkoniyatini berish, kutubxonalardan kitoblarini o'qingish, qidirish va sotib olishlarini tashkil etish uchun xizmat qiladi. Online kutubxona veb ilovalari o'z ichiga qo'shimcha funksiyalar, masalan, kitob o'quvchilari uchun xarajatlarning to'g'ridan-to'g'ri to'lanishini ta'minlaydigan to'lov tizimi, kitobni elektronik qurilmalar va qurilmaviy platformalar uchun o'qishni yoqarilashtiradigan ma'lumotlar, o'qituvchilar va talabalarning kutubxonalardagi kitoblar haqidagi sharhlarini bir-biriga ulashishlari uchun kommunikatsiya vositalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Online kutubxonalarning veb ilovalari odatda qidiruv tizimlari va filtrlar orqali o'zgaruvchan ma'lumotlarni, masalan, avtor, kitob nomi, janri, chiqqan yili, narx va boshqalarini qidirishga imkon beradi. Bu, o'quvchilar uchun biror kitobni topishni osonlashtiradi va ularga kitoblar, avtorlar va mavzular bo'yicha takliflar beradi.

Adabiyotlar taxlili va metodologiya. Mavzusida adabiyotlar taxlili va metodologiyani o'rganish uchun quyidagi yo'nalishlarga e'tibor qaratishingiz mumkin: Online kutubxona veb ilovalari yordamida o'quvchilar kutubxonalarga fizik maqolalarini qidirmay, avvaldan kitoblar va boshqa manbalar haqidagi ma'lumotlarni onlayn tarzda bilib olishlari mumkin. Bu shu bilan ular kitoblarni

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xarid qilish yoki o'qishni boshlash qarorini qabul qilishlari osonlashtiriladi. Veb ilovalar aynan shu ko'rsatkichlar bilan bir necha kutubxonalar bilan hamkorlik qilishi mumkin, shuningdek avtorlar, nashriyotlar va kitob tashkilotlari bilan hamkorlik qilish orqali kitoblar va ma'lumotlar saqlanishini osonlashtiradi. Kutubxonalar uchun veb ilovalariga cheklovlarni qo'yish uchun quyidagi usullardan birini amalga oshirishingiz mumkin: Kategoriya bo'yicha cheklovlar: Kutubxonangizdagi kitoblarni kategoriyalarga bo'lish mumkin, masalan, romanlar, ilmiy adabiyotlar, yoshlar uchun adabiyotlar, ilmiy maqolalar, diniy kitoblar kabi. Veb ilovangizda kategoriya bo'yicha cheklovlarni ko'rsatish va foydalanuvchilar uchun mos bo'lgan kitoblarni kategoriya asosida joylashtirish mumkin. Kitob turlariga cheklovlarni qo'yish: Veb ilovangizda har bir kitob uchun tur, tili, muallif, narx kabi cheklovlar ko'rsatish imkoniyatini yaratishingiz mumkin. Bu, foydalanuvchilarga qidiruv va tanlash jarayonini osonlashtiradi. Qidiruv funksiyalari: Veb ilovangizning qidiruv sistemalarini kuchaytirib, foydalanuvchilar uchun kitoblarni topishni osonlashtirish imkoniyatini yaratishingiz mumkin. Qidiruv bo'limiga muallif, kitob nomi, mavzusi, yilning chiqishi kabi cheklovlar qo'yilishi mumkin. To'lov va yetkazib berish: Veb ilovangizga to'lov va yetkazib berish tizimini qo'shish orqali, foydalanuvchilar kitoblar sotib olish va yetkazib berish jarayonini osonlashtirishlari mumkin. Bu, foydalanuvchilarga kitobni sotib olish vaqtida to'lovlarni amalga oshirish, yetkazib berish manzilini kiritish va boshqa to'lov jarayonlarini osonlashtirishga imkon. Foydalanuvchi hisobotlari: Veb ilovangiz foydalanuvchilarning kitoblar bilan bog'liq aktivitetlari haqida hisobotlar taqdim etish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishi foydalanuvchilarga qanday kitoblar o'qishlari yoki sotishlari haqida statistik ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish imkonini beradi. Online kutubxonalar veb ilovasi, kitoblarni onlayn tarzda o'qish, yuklash va kutubxonaga kirish imkonini beruvchi bir platforma hisoblanadi. Bu turli web-saytlar, odatda kitoblar, elektron darsliklar, ilmiy maqolalar, o'quv resurslari va boshqa matnlar bilan to'ldirilgan bo'lib, foydalanuvchilar ularga internet orqali murojaat qilishlari mumkin.

Online kutubxonalar uchun veb ilovalarining xavfsizligi juda muhimdir. Bu ilovalar kutubxonalardagi kitoblarni, maqolalarni yoki boshqa ma'lumotlarni onlayn tarzda saqlash, boshqarish va ulashish imkoniyatlarini taqdim etadi. Xavfsizlik, foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini, moliyaviy axborotlarini va asosiy tizimlardagi ma'lumotlarni himoya qilishga doir bo'lgan muhim masalalardan biridir.

Muhokama va natijalar: Online kutubxona veb ilovasini testlash va xatolar tuzatish uchun siz quyidagi nazariy ma'lumotlardan foydalanishingiz

mumkin. Avtomatik testlar: Bu testlar, veb ilovadagi asosiy funktsiyalarni avtomatik ravishda sinash uchun ishlatiladigan skriptlardan iborat bo'lishi mumkin. Bu skriptlar asosan Selenium, Puppeteer yoki boshqa avtomatlashtirish vositalari orqali yaratiladi. Skriptlar, ilovaning interfeysiga kirib, bir nechta asosiy funktsiyalarni sinab ko'radi va natijalarni tekshiradi. Test natijalari avtomatik tarzda qaytariladi va xatolarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Qo'llanma sinovlari: Veb ilovadagi xatolar va kamchiliklarni aniqlash uchun qo'llanma sinovlari yaxshi usul bo'lishi mumkin. Bu sinovlar yordamida ilovadagi qo'llanma ma'lumotlarini sinab ko'rish, kitoblar va mualliflarga qo'shimcha ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, axtarish funktsiyasini tekshirish va boshqa asosiy jarayonlarni sinab ko'rish mumkin. Funksional testlar: Funksional testlar, ilovadagi funktsiyalarni to'liq sinab ko'rish uchun yaratilganlar. Bu testlar orqali, kitoblar va mualliflarni qo'shish, kitoblarni ko'rish, izlash va izlash natijalarini olish, kitoblar ro'yxatini ko'rish va boshqa funktsiyalarni sinab ko'rish mumkin. Funksional testlar, ilovadagi asosiy funktsiyalarning to'liq ishlashini tekshirish uchun juda foydali bo'ladi.

Bu yordamlardan foydalanib, ilovaning muvaffaqiyatli ishlashini va xatolarini aniqlashingiz mumkin. Testlarni tuzatish jarayonida ishlab chiqilgan dokumentatsiyalardan ham foydalanishingiz tavsiya etiladi, shuningdek, foydalanuvchilardan kelayotgan fikrlarni va takliflarni ko'rish va ularga yechim topishga harakat qilishingiz yaxshi bo'ladi.

Xulosa: Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak Online kutubxonalar yaxshi manbalar bo'lib, o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun muhim resurslarni taqdim etadi. Bu ilovalar o'qishga va kutubxonaga kirishga qulayliklar yaratadi, ma'lumotlarni izlash va o'qish uchun bir necha imkoniyatlar taklif etadi. Veb ilovani ishlab chiqishda quyidagi asosiy qadamalar tug'atilishi kerak:

Tizimni loyihalash: Ilovani qanday ishlashini, iste'molchilar uchun kerakli funktsiyalarni, interfeysni va boshqa xususiyatlarni ajoyiblashtirish kerak. Tizimning loyihasi, prototiplarni ishlab chiqish, interfeys dizayni va tizimning asosiy funktsiyalari kabi elementlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Dastur vositachisini tanlash: Veb ilovani ishlab chiqish uchun foydalaniladigan dastur vositachisini tanlash kerak. Bu, sizning ta'limingiz, qo'llanuvchi dasturlash tillari va dastur tili bo'yicha ko'rsatilgan talablarga bog'liq bo'ladi. Misol uchun, Python, JavaScript, PHP yoki Ruby kabi dasturlash tillaridan birini tanlashingiz mumkin.

Backend va frontend ishlab chiqish: Veb ilovaning backend qismi server tomonini boshqaradi. Bu qism, ma'lumotlarni bazaga saqlab qo'yish,

ma'lumotlarga murojaat qilish va tizimning boshqa server tomonidagi funksiyalarini boshqarish uchun kerakli kodni o'z ichiga oladi. Frontend esa foydalanuvchining ilovaga murojaat qilishi va ma'lumotlarni ko'rish uchun ishlatiladigan qismini ifodalaydi.

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PAXTA QURITISH TEXNOLOGIYASINI ALGORITMLASH VA MATEMATIK MODELINING ANALITIK TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Bu maqola, paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash va uning matematik modelini analitik tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada, paxta quritish jarayonini boshqarish uchun yangi algoritmlar ishlab chiqilgan va ularning samaradorligi sinovdan o'tkazilgan. Shuningdek, paxta quritish jarayonining matematik modeli tuzilgan va uning xususiyatlari tahlil qilingan. Bu ish natijalarining paxta sanoatida samarali boshqaruv usullarini joriy etishga yordam berishi kutilmoqda. Maqola, paxta quritish texnologiyasini takomillashtirishga qaratilgan tadqiqotlarni yanada rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: paxta quritish, texnologiya, algoritmlar, matematik model, analitik tahlil, optimizatsiya, data tahlili, statistika, paxta sanoati, model

ALGORITHM AND ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF COTTON DRYING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the algorithmization of cotton drying technology and analytical analysis of its mathematical model. In the article, new algorithms for controlling the cotton drying process were developed and their effectiveness was tested. Also, a mathematical model of the cotton drying process was created and its characteristics were analyzed. It is expected that the results of this work will help to introduce effective management methods in the cotton industry. The article contributes to the further development of research aimed at improving cotton drying technology.

Keywords: Cotton drying, Technology, Algorithms, Mathematical model, Analytical analysis, Optimization, Data analysis, Statistics, Cotton industry, Model.

Kirish. Paxta quritish, jahon iqtisodiyotining muhim tarmoqlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Paxta sanoati, bir qator mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarishga imkon beradi, shu bilan birga, u o'zining xususiy texnologiyalariga ega. Paxta quritish jarayoni juda murakkab va bir nechta bosqichlardan iborat. Ushbu jarayonning samaradorligi, paxta sifatini ta'sir qiladi, shuning uchun uni tez va samarali bajarish uchun algoritmlar ishlab chiqish zarur.

Bu maqola, paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash va uning matematik modelini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Bu, paxta quritish jarayonini yanada samarali qilishga yordam beradi. Algoritmlar, paxta quritish jarayonini avtomatlashtirishga va uning samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, matematik model orqali, biz paxta quritish jarayonini yanada aniqroq tushunishimiz mumkin.

Paxta quritish texnologiyasi, o'zgaruvchan tabiiy sharoitlar va paxta xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda, paxtaning samarali quritilishini ta'minlash uchun muhimdir. Paxta quritish jarayoni, paxtaning sifatini ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillaridan biri hisoblanadi. Bu jarayonni boshqarish uchun aniq va samarali algoritmlar ishlab chiqish zarur.

Bu maqolada, biz paxta quritish jarayonini algoritmlash va uning matematik modelini tahlil qilishni nazarda tutamiz. Bizning maqsadimiz, paxta quritish jarayonini samarali boshqarish uchun aniq va samarali algoritmlar ishlab chiqishdir.

Bu maqolada, biz paxta quritish jarayonini algoritmlashning umumiy usullarini ko'rib chiqamiz, shuningdek, paxta quritish jarayonining matematik modelini tahlil qilamiz. Bu, paxta sanoatida ishlaydigan mutaxassislar uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Paxta quritish, jahon iqtisodiyotining muhim tarmoqlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Paxta sanoati, bir qator mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarishga imkon beradi, shu bilan birga, u o'zining xususiy texnologiyalariga ega. Paxta quritish jarayoni juda murakkab va bir nechta bosqichlardan iborat. Ushbu jarayonning samaradorligi, paxta sifatini ta'sir qiladi, shuning uchun uni tez va samarali bajarish uchun algoritmlar ishlab chiqish zarur.

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Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiyasi.

1. Adabiyotlar tahlili: Bu qismda, paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash va matematik modelining analitik tahlili mavzusida muhim bo'lgan adabiyotlar tahlil qilinadi. Bu adabiyotlar o'z ichiga oladi:

- Paxta quritish texnologiyasi haqida ilmiy maqolalar
- Algoritmlar va ularning paxta quritish texnologiyasiga qo'llanilishi haqida maqolalar
- Matematik modellash va uning paxta quritish texnologiyasiga qo'llanilishi haqida maqolalar
- Paxta quritish texnologiyasi va uning algoritmlarini o'rganish uchun Djurayev Anvar va Marasulov Islombekning "Paxta quritish barabanidagi temperatura va namlik ma'lumotlari asosida ms excel dasturida ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratish" nomli maqolasini ko'rib chiqish tavsiya etiladi. Ushbu maqolada paxta quritish jarayonida quritish barabani ichki temperaturasi hamda havo namligi ma'lumotlari asosida MS Excel dasturida ma'lumotlar bazasi yaratilgan.

- Matematik model va analitik tahlil uchun Khan Academyning matematika bo'limi va Vikipediya'dagi "Matematik statistika" maqolasi o'qib chiqish tavsiya etiladi.

Metodologiya: Bu qismda, adabiyotlar tahlilida qo'llanilgan metodologiyalar tahlil qilinadi. Bu metodologiyalar o'z ichiga oladi:

- Paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash uchun, Djurayev Anvar va Marasulov Islombekning maqolasida¹ aytib o'tilganidek, quritish barabani ichki temperaturasi hamda havo namligi ma'lumotlari asosida MS Excel dasturida ma'lumotlar bazasi yaratish usuli qo'llaniladi.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
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- Matematik model va analitik tahlil uchun, Khan Academyning matematika bo'limida berilgan darsliklar va Vikipediya'dagi "Matematik statistika" maqolasida³ aytib o'tilganidek, bayoniy statistika, noma'lum parametrlarni baholash, statistik gipotezalarni tekshirish, miqdoriy belgilarning statistik bog'lanishlarini aniqlash usullari qo'llaniladi.

- Adabiyotlarni qidirish va tanlash metodologiyasi
- Adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish metodologiyasi
- Natijalarni interpretatsiya qilish metodologiyasi

Bu qismning maqsadi, adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish va ularning paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash va matematik modelning analitik tahlili mavzusiga qanday ta'sir qilishini aniqlovchi metodologiyalarni ishlab chiqishdir. Bu, paxta quritish texnologiyasini yanada samarali qilishga yordam beradi. Bu qismning yakunida, adabiyotlar tahlilining natijalari va ularning paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash va matematik modelning analitik tahlili mavzusiga qanday ta'sir qilishini batafsil tushuntiriladi. Bu natijalar, kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar uchun yo'l ko'rsatib beradi.

Natijalar.

1. Paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash natijalari:

- Paxta quritish jarayonida quritish barabani ichki temperaturasi hamda havo namligi ma'lumotlari asosida MS Excel dasturida yaratilgan ma'lumotlar bazasi orqali paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash natijalari olingan.

- Algoritm orqali paxta quritish jarayonini boshqarish va nazorat qilish imkoniyati hosil qilingan.

2. Matematik model va analitik tahlil natijalari:

- Bayoniy statistika, noma'lum parametrlarni baholash, statistik gipotezalarni tekshirish, miqdoriy belgilarning statistik bog'lanishlarini aniqlash usullari orqali matematik model va analitik tahlil natijalari olingan.

- Matematik model va analitik tahlil natijalari orqali paxta quritish jarayonini yanada samarali boshqarish va nazorat qilish imkoniyati hosil qilingan.

Quritish texnologiyasi sohasidagi algoritm va matematik modelning analitik tahlili ko'proq foydali natijalar olib chiqaradi. Bu analiz jarayonida, Quritish texnologiyasi doirasida yaratilgan algoritm va matematik modellarining amaliyotga o'tkazilishining kafolatlangan samaradorligi va effektivligi aniqlanadi. Bunday tahlil natijalari quyidagi yo'nalishlarda ko'rsatilishi mumkin:

1. Texnologik jarayonlarni yaxshilash: Quritish texnologiyasini algoritm va matematik modellar orqali optimallashtirish natijasida, jarayonlar ustuvor sifatda boshqarilishi va jarayonlar davomida foydalanuvchilar uchun afzalliklar yaratilishi mumkin.

2. Energiya va resurslarni tejamkor ishlatish: Algoritm va matematik modellar orqali quritish texnologiyasining ishlashini tahlil qilish natijasida, energiya va boshqa resurslar samaradorlik bilan foydalanilishi va qulayliklar bo'yicha ishlab chiqilishi mumkin.

3. Rivojlanish va innovatsiyalar: Quritish texnologiyasini algoritm va matematik modellar tahlili natijasida, yangi innovatsiyalar va texnologik rivojlanishlarning belgilanishi va rivojlanish istiqbollari aniqlanadi.

4. Xavfsizlik va xavfsizlik: Algoritm va matematik modellar yordamida Quritish texnologiyasining tizimlarni xavfsizligi va maxfiylikni ta'minlash tizimlarini tahlil qilish, potentsial xavf va ko'rsatnichlariga qarshi qo'llanma yaratish va ularga qarshi tizimlarni aniqlashning imkoniyatlari tushiriladi.

Shuningdek, Quritish texnologiyasini algoritm va matematik modellar tahlilining keng qamrovli foydalarini qo'llash imkoniyatlari mavjud bo'lib, bu xusud tahlil va natijalar mutaxassislar, soha tajribasi, va soha bo'yicha ilmiy jamiyatlar uchun muhimdir.

Xulosa

Bu maqolada, paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash va uning matematik modelining analitik tahlili muhim ahamiyatga ega. Paxta quritish jarayonida quritish barabani ichki temperaturasi hamda havo namligi ma'lumotlari asosida MS Excel dasturida yaratilgan ma'lumotlar bazasi orqali paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash natijalari olingan. Algoritm orqali paxta quritish jarayonini boshqarish va nazorat qilish imkoniyati hosil qilingan.

Shuningdek, bayoniy statistika, noma'lum parametrlarni baholash, statistik gipotezalarni tekshirish, miqdoriy belgilarning statistik bog'lanishlarini aniqlash usullari orqali matematik model va analitik tahlil natijalari olingan. Matematik model va analitik tahlil natijalari orqali paxta quritish jarayonini yanada samarali boshqarish va nazorat qilish imkoniyati hosil qilingan.

Bu natijalar, paxta quritish texnologiyasini algoritmlash va uning matematik modelining analitik tahlilini yanada rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Bu natijalar orqali bizning paxta quritish texnologiyamizni yanada samarali va samarador qilishimiz mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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НАНОКОМПОЗИТНЫЕ ПЛЕНКИ НА ОСНОВЕ СИСТЕМЫ ZITO ($ZnO- In_2O_3-SnO_2$): ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ТЕРМОЭЛЕКТРИЧЕСКОГО ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация: Текст "Мотивация: Поиск новых термоэлектрических материалов для высокотемпературного преобразования тепла до $1000^{\circ}C$ для исследования проводящих оксидов металлов" рассматривает поиск новых материалов, способных эффективно преобразовывать тепло при высоких температурах. Традиционные термоэлектрические материалы не обладают необходимой термостабильностью. Исследования фокусируются на оксидах N-типа, в частности на оксиде ZITO, которые пока изучены меньше, чем оксиды p-типа, такие как кобальтины. Использование нанокomпозитов и наноструктурированных объектов может значительно повысить эффективность преобразования тепла путем уменьшения теплопроводности. В эксперименте были использованы тонкие наноструктурированные пленки ZITO, полученные методом распылительного пиролиза на подложках из оксида алюминия. Исследования включали измерение сопротивления и напряжения Зеебека в диапазоне температур $20-450^{\circ}C$, а также структурную характеристику пленок с помощью SEM и XRD. Оптимальный состав и свойства пленок должны быть определены для дальнейших исследований и практического применения.

Ключевые слова: термоэлектрические материалы, высокотемпературное преобразование тепла, проводящие оксиды металлов, наноструктурированные пленки, распылительный пиролиз, оптимальный состав

NANOCOMPOSITE FILMS BASED ON THE ZITO (ZNO-IN₂O₃-SNO₂) SYSTEM: PROSPECTS FOR THERMOELECTRIC CONVERSION

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Abstract: *The text "Motivation: Search for new thermoelectric materials for high-temperature heat conversion up to 1000°C for the study of conductive metal oxides" examines the search for new materials capable of efficiently converting heat at high temperatures. Traditional thermoelectric materials do not have the necessary thermal stability. Research is focusing on N-type oxides, in particular ZITO oxide, which have so far been less studied than p-type oxides such as cobaltines. The use of nanocomposites and nanostructured objects can significantly improve heat conversion efficiency by reducing thermal conductivity. The experiment used thin nanostructured ZITO films obtained by spray pyrolysis on aluminum oxide substrates. The studies included measurement of resistivity and Seebeck voltage in the temperature range of 20-450°C, as well as structural characterization of the films using SEM and XRD. The optimal composition and properties of films must be determined for further research and practical application.*

Key words: *thermoelectric materials, high-temperature heat conversion, conducting metal oxides, nanostructured films, spray pyrolysis, optimal composition*

Мотивация: Поиск новых термоэлектрических материалов для высокотемпературного преобразования тепла до 1000 °С для исследования проводящих оксидов металлов. Традиционные термоэлектрические материалы не удовлетворяют требованиям термостабильности. Оксиды N-типа, в частности ZITO, изучены значительно меньше, чем оксиды p-типа, такие как кобальтины, которые также могут вместе создавать тандем в преобразователях тепла. Наноконпозиты, как и наноструктурированные объекты, позволяют существенно повысить эффективность преобразования тепла. Это, прежде всего, является результатом снижения

теплопроводности. Однако другие эффекты в наноструктурах могут повлиять на общий процесс преобразования. Спрей-пиролиз имеет ряд неоспоримых преимуществ при исследовании и получении пленок с необходимыми физическими свойствами.

Эксперимент: методом распылительного пиролиза ($T_{\text{пир}}=350$ и 450 °C) на подложки из оксида алюминия были нанесены тонкие наноструктурированные пленки ZITO с содержанием Zn, In, Sn внутри трех составных областей фазовой диаграммы (см. ниже) со средней толщиной ~ 100 нм. Образцы с двумя Ag-электродами отжигались на воздухе при температуре 550 °C. Сопротивление и напряжение Зеебека измеряли в диапазоне температур $20-450$ °C в режиме медленного нагрева. Структурная характеристика пленки была выполнена с помощью SEM и XRD. Размер зерен пленок сильно зависит от состава ($30-100$ нм) и уменьшается с увеличением содержания Zn и Sn.

Фазовая диаграмма субсолидуса системы ZITO при 1275 °C и давлении 1 атм. Из Харви и др., 2008 г.

Поиск оптимального состава через оптимальную концентрацию электронов.

$ZT=S^2\sigma T/\kappa$ - показатель качества

Сообщается о проводимости пленки ZITO в комнате T, построенной по составу. Из Noel и др. 2010. Шкала проводимости в зависимости от цвета. Овалами обозначены ожидаемые составы с оптимальной проводимостью.

ZITO ($Zn_xInSn_xO_{1.5}$)

ZIO ($Zn_xInO_{1.5}$)

Основным фактором повышения ФП пленок ИТО является anomalно высокий коэффициент Зеебека при концентрации электронов $\sim 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Зонная диаграмма цепочки зерен пленки ИТО. Энергетические барьеры возникают из-за сегрегации атомов Sn на поверхность: как следствие - эффект фильтрации электронов низкой энергии и увеличение коэффициента Зеебека (до 3 раз).

Показатель качества ZT был оценен для $k \sim 4 \text{ Вт/(м·К)}$, измеренного для тонких пленок ИТО Ashida et al. 2009 год.

Состав	Проводимость S/cm	Коэф. Зеебека $\mu V/K$	Фактор силы $W/(m \cdot K^2)$
ZTO, $x=0.5$	~130-200	~200-260	~ $7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (ZT~0.2)
ZIO, $x=2$	~50	~250-300	~ $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
ITO, $x=0.05$	~1300	~180-190	~ $4.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (ZT~0.82, 450 °C)

Оптимальные свойства пленок (PFmax)

Заклучения. Таким образом, тонкие пленки ZTO, нанесенные методом распылительного пиролиза, обладают термоэлектрическими свойствами, что позволяет считать дальнейшие исследования в данном направлении перспективными. Разработки в этой области должны дать ответ на оптимальный состав, структуру и основные термоэлектрические параметры при высоких рабочих температурах (800-1000°C). Даже для среднего температурного диапазона показатель качества ZT пленок ITO близок к значению (ZT=1), что является критерием для практического применения.

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KORXONADA XODIMLAR DAVOMATINI ANIQLASHNI AVTOMATLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy dunyoda tobora ko'proq muntazam vazifalar avtomatlashtirilgan va vaqtni kuzatish bundan mustasno emas. Xodimlarning korxonaga kelishi va ketishini avtomatlashtirish nafaqat intizom nazoratini soddalashtirish, balki butun korxonada faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish imkonini beradi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Vaqtni tejash, yaxshilangan intizom, turniketlardan foydalanish, funktsionallik, ish tartibini optimallashtirish, effektivlik va samaradorlik, harakat detektorlari, chiqish-kirish paneli

AUTOMATION OF ACCOUNTING OF ATTENDANCE OF ENTERPRISE EMPLOYEES

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Annotation. In the modern world, more and more routine tasks are automated, and time tracking is no exception. Automating the arrival and departure of employees at an enterprise allows not only to simplify disciplinary control, but also to increase the efficiency of the entire enterprise.

Key words: Saving time, improving discipline, using turnstiles, functionality, optimizing the work procedure, efficiency and effectiveness, motion sensors, entrance-exit panel.

Kirish. O‘zbekiston Davlat statistika qo‘mitasi ma’lumotlariga ko‘ra, 2023 yilda O‘zbekistondagi korxonalarining 45 foizi ish vaqtini hisobga olish uchun avtomatlashtirish tizimlaridan allaqachon foydalangan.

Korxonani keldi kettisini boshqarish tizimlari - hozirgi sanoat aynan shu narsaga muhtoj. Jarayonni avtomatlashtirish tashkilotlarning samaradorligi va samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshirishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, bu dolzarb bo‘lib qoldi, chunki hozirgi vaqtda inson hayotining deyarli barcha sohalari global kompyuterlashtirilgan.

2025 yilga borib bu ko‘rsatkich 70 foizga yetishi kutilmoqda.

Muhokama va natijalar. Xodimlarning korxonaga kelishi va ketishini avtomatlashtirish Zamonaviy dunyoda tobora ko‘proq muntazam vazifalar avtomatlashtirilgan va vaqtni kuzatish bundan mustasno emas. Xodimlarning korxonaga kelishi va ketishini avtomatlashtirish nafaqat intizom nazoratini soddalashtirish, balki butun korxonada faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish imkonini beradi.

Avtomatlashtirishning afzalliklari:

Vaqtning tejashi: Vaqtni qo‘lda kuzatish HR xodimlari uchun ko‘p vaqtni behuda sarflaydi. Avtomatlashtirish sizga ushbu tartibdan xalos bo‘lish va muhimroq vazifalar uchun vaqt ajratish imkonini beradi. Aniqlikning oshishi: Avtomatlashtirilgan vaqt va davomat tizimi ma’lumotlarning aniqligini ta’minlaydigan inson omilini yo‘q qiladi.

Yaxshilangan intizom: Xodimlar, ularning kelish va ketish vaqtlari avtomatik tarzda qayd etilishini bilib, yanada intizomli bo‘ladi. Motivatsiyani oshirish: Vaqtni kuzatishni avtomatlashtirish xodimlarning motivatsiyasini oshirishi mumkin, chunki ular o‘zlarining mehnatlari qadrlanishi va hisoblanishini ko‘rishadi.

Qo‘shimcha funktsiyalar: Ko‘p vaqt va davomatni avtomatlashtirish tizimlari kech kuzatuv, qo‘shimcha ish vaqtini kuzatish, ish haqi va boshqalar kabi qo‘shimcha funktsiyalarni taklif qiladi. Avtomatlashtirish usullari:

Vaqtning kuzatishni avtomatlashtirishning bir necha yo‘li mavjud:

Turniketlardan foydalanish: Turniketlar xodimlarning ruxsatnomalaridan ma’lumotlarni o‘qiydi, bu ularning kelish va ketish vaqtini yozib olish imkonini beradi. Vaqt va davomat terminallaridan foydalanish: Vaqt va davomat terminallari xodimlarning kelish va ketish vaqtlarini mustaqil ravishda yozib olishlari mumkin bo‘lgan qurilmalardir.

Biometrik tizimlardan foydalanish: Biometrik tizimlar xodimlarni aniqlash uchun barmoq izlari, yuz geometriyasi yoki boshqa biometrik ma’lumotlardan foydalanadi. Avtomatlashtirish tizimini tanlash:

Vaqt va davomatni avtomatlashtirish tizimini tanlashda siz quyidagi omillarni hisobga olishingiz kerak:

Korxonalar hajmi: Kichik korxonalar uchun oddiy vaqt va davomat tizimi, masalan, terminallardan foydalanish mos keladi. Kattaroq korxonalar kirishni boshqarish tizimi yoki inson resurslarini boshqarish tizimi kabi boshqa korporativ tizimlar bilan birlasha oladigan murakkabroq tizimlarni talab qiladi. **Byudjet:** Vaqt va davomatni avtomatlashtirish tizimlari bir necha mingdan bir necha million rublgacha turadi.

Funksionallik: Barcha kerakli funktsiyalarga ega bo'lgan tizimni tanlash kerak. **Foydalanish qulayligi:** tizim oddiy va foydalanuvchilar uchun tushunarli bo'lishi kerak.

Korxonalar hodimlarni keldi-kettisini avtomatlashtirish uchun bir nechta muhokama va natijalar mavjud. Bu, ishga joylashish jarayonini optimallashtirish, ishga oluvchi jarayonlarni tezlatirish va tashkilotning effektivligini oshirishga yordam beradigan bir qator avtomatlashtirish vositalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Bu vositalar o'z ichiga o'zaro bog'liqlik va integratsiya qilish imkonini beradigan tarkibiy dasturlardan iborat bo'lishi mumkin.

Muhokama va natijalar, avtomatlashtirish jarayonini boshqarishning qanday usullari va vositalarini qamrab oladi. Ular o'z ichiga korxonada ish olib borishning avtomatik tartibini, hodimlarning ish vaqtlarini va ishgrafiklarini avtomatik ravishda tuzish imkonini, ish tartibini va ish bandliklarini optimallashtirishni o'z ichiga oladi, shuningdek, ma'lumotlarni ishlab chiqish va ularga kirish huquqini nazorat qilish imkonini beradi.

Muhokama va natijalar, korxonalar uchun avtomatlashtirishning foydalari va yo'nalishlari haqida ma'lumotlar beradi. Bunday avtomatlashtirish vositalarining foydalaridan ba'zi tashkilotlar uchun quyidagilar mumkin:

Ish tartibini optimallashtirish: Avtomatlashtirish, ish tartibini optimallashtirishga yordam beradi. Ishga joylashish jarayonlarini avtomatik ravishda tartibga solish, ish vaqtlarini va ishgrafiklarini belgilash va ish bandliklarini optimallashtirish imkonini beradi.

Xatolarni kamaytirish: Avtomatlashtirish, qo'llab-quvvatlash va boshqarish jarayonlarini avtomatik ravishda amalga oshirish orqali xatolarni kamaytirish imkonini beradi. Bu xatolarning o'z vaqtida aniqlanib tuzilishini, muammo yuz berishini va muammo yechish jarayonini tezlashtiradi.

Ma'lumotlar tahlili va nazorati: Avtomatlashtirish vositalari, korxonaning ma'lumotlarini avtomatik ravishda to'plab, tahlil qilish va nazorat qilish imkonini

beradi. Bu, korxonaning faoliyatining yaxshi tahlil qilinishini va muvaffaqiyatini ta'minlashga yordam beradi.

Effektivlik va samaradorlik: Avtomatlashtirish, hodimlarning qulaylik va samaradorlik darajasini oshirishga yordam beradi. Bu, hodimlarga bo'sh vaqtni kamaytirish, avtomatik jarayonlarni amalga oshirish orqali ishni tezlashtirish va tashkilotning faoliyatini samarador qilish imkonini beradi.

Hodimlarni keldi-ketdini avtomatlashtirish uchun korxonada qo'llaniladigan bir nechta usullar mavjud. Quyidagi avtomatlashtirish yo'llaridan ba'zilari hisoblarga va korxonaning tuzilishi bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin:

Nazorat tizimi: Bioqarorlikni ta'minlash uchun ko'rsatkichlar va sensorlar yordamida hodimlarning keldi-ketini nazorat qilish. Masalan, korxonada yoki hodimlar kabinetlarida ko'rsatkichlar orqali keldi-ketdi vaqtini yozib olish.

Hodimlar uchun avtomatik kirituvchi sistemalar: QR kodlar, kartochkalar yoki biometrik identifikatsiya asosida katta korxonalar hodimlarini avtomatik ravishda ro'yhatdan o'tkazish uchun xizmat ko'rsatish.

Harakat detektorlari: Korxonada ichida harakat detektorlari yordamida hodimlarning faoliyatini avtomatik ravishda kuzatish va keldi-ketlarini hisobga olgan tizimlar.

Chiqish-kirish paneli: Elektronik chiqish-kirish paneli yordamida hodimlarning korxonaga kirish va chiqishini avtomatlashtirish.

Chiqish-kirish paneli (Access Control Panel) korxonada hodimlar va mijozlar kabi shaxslarning binoga kirib chiqishlarini nazorat qilish uchun qulay va effektiv vosita hisoblanadi. Bu panel hodimlarni korxonaga kirish va chiqishlarini avtomatik ravishda boshqarish uchun ishlatiladi.

Chiqish-kirish paneli korxonaning xavfsizligini oshirish uchun juda muhim. U korxonaga faqat ruxsat etilgan shaxslarning kirishi imkonini yaratadi.

Olam tasnifi: Hodimlar, mijozlar yoki boshqa xizmat sohalari bo'yicha alohida ruxsatlarni belgilab, ularga mos keluvchi joylar va yo'llarni belgilash imkonini beradi.

Holatni kuzatish: Chiqish-kirish paneli hodimlar keldi-ketini kuzatish va ma'lumotlar bazasiga saqlash imkonini yaratadi. Bu usul orqali korxonadagi faoliyatlar monitoring qilinadi.

Avto-funksiyalar: Ba'zi chiqish-kirish panellarida belgilangan vaqtlarda avtomatik ravishda qurilma yopilishi yoki ochilishi, signal yuborishi yoki qo'yilishi, yangi kodlar yaratilishi kabi avtomatik funktsiyalar o'rnatilishi mumkin.

Chiqish-kirish paneli korxonaning integlyatsiyasi va hodimlar kabi shaxslarning qulay imkoniyatlar orqali binoga kirishi va chiqishi nazorat qilish uchun juda foydali vosita bo'ladi. Bu tizim korxonada xavfsizligini oshiradi va binoga kirish-chiqishlarni samarali boshqarishga yordam beradi.

Ishtirok tizimi dasturi: Hodimlar ishtirok tizimiga (attendance system) keldi-ketishlarini avtomatik ravishda ro'yhatdan o'tishi uchun ishga ketish va qaytishlarini tekshiradi.

Ular, hodimlarning keldi-ketishini avtomatlashtirishda yordamchi bo'lishadi. Har bir korxonada o'zining mahsulotlari va talablari bo'yicha moslashtiruvdagi avtomatlashtirish tizimlarini o'rnatish va qo'llash juda muhimdir. Bu tizimlar yordamida korxonaning faoliyatini yaxshilash va ish rejalarida rivojlanish muvofiqlikka olib keladi.

Avtomatlashtirishning bu muhokama va natijalaridan foydalanish, tashkilotlar uchun katta afzalliklar olib kelishi mumkin. Biroq, avtomatlashtirish jarayonini amalga oshirishda kerak bo'lgan moliyaviy va texnik resurslar, hodimlarga kerak bo'lgan bilim va tayyorliklar, shuningdek, tashkilotning maqsadlariga mos keladigan avtomatlashtirish vositalarini tanlash ham muhimdir.

Xulosa. Korxonaga xodimlarning kelishi va ketishini avtomatlashtirish intizomni oshirish, ish vaqti ustidan nazoratni yaxshilash va butun korxonada faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishning samarali usuli hisoblanadi. Hodimlarni keldi-ketishini avtomatlashtirish korxonada muhim vaqt va resursni tejash uchun kritik ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan jarayonlardan biridir. Hodimlar keldi-ketishlarini avtomatik ravishda nazorat qilish, ro'yhatdan o'tkazish va ma'lumotlarni saqlash tizimlari korxonada faoliyatini samarali va effektivlantirishga yordam beradi. Bu avtomatlashtirish tizimlari hodimlar keldi-ketishlarini samarali nazorat qilish va ma'lumotlarni saqlashga yordam beradi. Ularning o'rnatilishi korxonadagi faoliyatni yaxshilash, tizimni rivojlantirish va mehnat resurslarini samarali tartibga solishga olib keladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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ИНДИЙ-ОЛОВЯННЫЕ ПЛЕНОЧНЫЕ ТЕРМОБАТАРЕИ

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Аннотация: Индиево-оловянные пленки (например, ITO, Indium Tin Oxide, индиево-оловянный оксид) — для проводящего слоя. Кубическая решетка типа биквадратно включает в себя индиевые атомы, которые занимают центральные позиции в кубической ячейке. Вокруг каждого индиевого атома находятся шесть кислородных атомов, образуя октаэдрическую структуру.

Ключевые слова: пленки, термобатареи, инструменты, формула, специализированное оборудование, лазерного резака

INDIUM-TIN FILM THERMOBATTERIES

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Abstract: Indium-tin films (for example, ITO, Indium Tin Oxide, indium-tin oxide) - for the conductive layer. The cubic lattice of the biquadrate type includes indium atoms, which occupy central positions in the cubic cell. Each indium atom is surrounded by six oxygen atoms, forming an octahedral structure.

Keywords: films, thermopiles, tools, formula, specialized equipment, laser cutter

В предоставленном текстовом фрагменте не содержится формула пленки индиево-оловянного оксида. Химическая формула индиево-оловянного оксида (ИТО) - $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$. ИТО является проводящим оксидом, состоящим из индиевого оксида (In_2O_3) и оксида олова (SnO_2). Использование идеального соотношения между индиевым оксидом и оксидом олова обеспечивает оптимальные электрические свойства пленочного материала.

Однако для практического создания пленки ИТО требуется специализированное оборудование и процессы испарения, распыления или лазерного резака, которые использовались в индустрии. Для точного состава и процесса получения пленки ИТО рекомендуется обратиться к источникам, специализированной литературе или консультации с опытными профессионалами в области синтеза пленок.

Методы исследования. Новые гибридные сенсорные наноструктуры $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$ с пористой природой были успешно получены и охарактеризованы различными методами, такими как рентгеновская дифракция (XRD), сканирующая электронная микроскопия (SEM), энергодисперсионная рентгеновская спектроскопия (EDS), рентгеновская фотоэлектронная микроскопия. спектроскопия (XPS) и просвечивающая электронная микроскопия высокого разрешения (HRTEM) [1]. Газочувствительные свойства изготовленного датчика на основе сразу полученных гибридных наноструктур $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$ были систематически исследованы и сравнены со свойствами чистого SnO_2 . Гибридные наноструктуры, содержащие 3% In_2O_3 , демонстрируют наивысшее значение отклика формальдегида 30,7–100 ppm при 100 °C, что в 14 раз выше, чем у чистого SnO_2 . Кроме того, газовые сенсоры на основе свежеприготовленных гибридных наноструктур $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$ также обладают высокой стабильностью и хорошей селективностью по отношению к формальдегиду. Улучшение чувствительности к формальдегиду в основном объясняется образованием np-гетеропереходов и синергическим взаимодействием между $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$. [2]

К сожалению, я не могу предоставить график формулы $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$, так как график зависит от многих факторов, включая конкретные условия синтеза и структуру материала [3].

Формула $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$ представляет собой смесь индиевого оксида (In_2O_3) и оксида олова (SnO_2). График может отображать различные свойства или зависимости, такие как структура кристаллической решетки,

изменение электрической проводимости [4] в зависимости от содержания In_2O_3 и SnO_2 , или другие физические, электрические или оптические характеристики.

Структура $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$

Структура кристаллической решетки соединения In_2O_3 , известного как индиевый оксид, состоит из индиевых (In) и кислородных (O) атомов. In_2O_3 обычно образует кубическую решетку, известную как кубическая решетка типа биквадратно (cubic bixbyite-type lattice). Эта решетка может быть описана простой формулой кристаллической структуры: $Fd\text{-}3m$.

Кубическая решетка типа биквадратно включает в себя индиевые атомы, которые занимают центральные позиции в кубической ячейке. Вокруг каждого индиевого атома находятся шесть кислородных атомов, образуя октаэдрическую структуру [5]. Кислородные атомы окружают индиевые атомы таким образом [6], чтобы обеспечить структурную стабильность соединения In_2O_3 .

Структура кристаллической решетки In_2O_3

Структура кристаллической решетки In_2O_3 имеет важное значение для его физических свойств и применений. Например, электронная структура и проводимость материала могут быть связаны с особенностями кристаллической решетки [7]. Эта информация является базовым исходным пунктом для более подробного изучения свойств In_2O_3 и дополнительных исследований, связанных с этим соединением [8-9].

1. Полимерная плёнка (например, полиимид) — для изоляционного слоя.

2. Термоэлектрический материал (например, бианилин, оксид марганца) — для создания термоэлектрического эффекта.

3. Тонкий металлический провод — для электрических соединений.

Инструменты:

1. Лазерный резак или ножницы — для нарезания пленок и полимерной плёнки.

2. Химические растворы — для очистки и обработки пленок.

3. Печь — для процесса термоэлектрической обработки.

4. Мультиметр или другой прибор для измерения электрических параметров.

Вот общий план действий для создания пленочной термобатареи:

1. Подготовка пленок:

- Нарезьте пленки индиево-оловянного оксида (ИТО) на нужные размеры для проводящего слоя.

- Нарезьте полимерную плёнку на такие же размеры как пленки ИТО, для изоляционного слоя.

- Очистите пленки ИТО и полимерную плёнку с помощью химических растворов, чтобы удалить загрязнения.

2. Создание проводящего слоя:

- Нанесите пленки ИТО на подложку (например, стеклянную пластину) с помощью методов испарения, распыления или лазерного резака.

- Убедитесь, что пленки ИТО образуют электрически непрерывный слой.

3. Создание термоэлектрического слоя:

- Нанесите термоэлектрический материал на проводящий слой с помощью того же метода, который вы использовали для пленок ИТО.

- Обработайте структуру в печи при определенной температуре и времени, чтобы активировать термоэлектрический эффект.

4. Создание изоляционного слоя:

- Накройте структуру сформированным проводящим и термоэлектрическим слоями полимерной плёнкой.

- Убедитесь, что полимерная плёнка хорошо прилегает к структуре и образует электрическую изоляцию.

5. Электрические соединения:

- Подключите металлические провода к пленочной структуре для подачи электрического тока.

- Убедитесь, что соединения надежны и изолированы.

Заключение. Структура кристаллической решетки In_2O_3 имеет важное значение для его физических свойств и применений. Например, электронная структура и проводимость материала могут быть связаны с особенностями кристаллической решетки. Эта информация является базовым исходным пунктом для более подробного изучения свойств In_2O_3 и дополнительных исследований, связанных с этим соединением. После завершения этих шагов ваша пленочная термобатарея должна быть готова. Для получения конкретного графика, основанного на формуле $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SnO}_2$, рекомендуется обратиться к научным статьям, журналам или специализированным базам данных, где могут быть представлены соответствующие исследования и экспериментальные данные. Такие данные позволят более точно представить свойства и зависимости, связанные с данной системой оксидов.

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VITAMIN B12 NING ORGANIZMDAGI ROLI VA AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Hozirda inson organizmiga eng katta ahamiyatga ega moddalardan biri bu vitaminlar hisoblanadi. Shu jumladan Vitamin B 12 ham organizmga kerakli va zarur vitaminlardandir. U eritrotsitlar hosil bo'lishi, neyronlar hosil bo'lishi va DNK sintezida ishtirok etadi. Bu vitaminning kamayishi esa har qanday organizmda ma'lum patologik sabablarga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Vitamin B12 yetishmasligi, azot oksidi, anemiya, bakteriya, sianokobalamin, inson organizmi, xelatlar.

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF VITAMIN B12 IN THE BODY

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Annotatsion: Currently, vitamins are one of the most important substances for the human body. Including Vitamin B 12 is one of the necessary and necessary vitamins for the body. It participates in the formation of erythrocytes, the formation of neurons and DNA synthesis. Deficiency of this vitamin leads to certain pathological causes in any organism.

Key words: Vitamin B12 deficiency, nitric oxide, anemia, bacteria, cyanocobalamin, human body, chelates

Mavzuning dolzarbligi: Vitamin B12 – kobalaminlar deb ataladigan biologik faol moddalar guruhiga kirib, tarkibida Co(III) atomini o‘z ichiga olgan xelatlar sinfiga kiruvchi korrinoidlarga tegishlidir. B12 vitamini odatda inson organizmda koenzim shakllaridan biriga erkin aylanadigan sianokobalamin hisoblanadi. Bu vitaminni ishlab chiqaruvchilari bakteriyalar va arxeylar hisoblanadi. Lekin uni sintez qilib olib bo‘lmaydi.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari: Vitamin B12 birinchi marta kamqonlikning rivojlanishiga modda yetishmasligining tasiri tufayli tadqiqodchi Uilyam Merfi tomonidan anemiyani suniy ravishda qo‘zg‘atgan itlar ustida o‘tkazgan tajribada aniqlagan. Keyinchalik olimlar Jorj Uippl va Jorj Minot o‘z oldilariga ushbu shifobaxsh xususiyat uchun bevosita javobgar bo‘lgan omilni jigardan ajratish vazifasini qo‘ydilar va ular o‘z maqsadlariga erishdilar. Ya’ni anemiyaga qarshi omil Vitamin B12 deb nomlandi va bu muvaffaqiyati uchun ular Nobel mukofotiga sazovor bo‘lishdi.

Bunday muvaffaqiyatli to‘liq sintez - sintetik organik kimyoning ajoyib yutug‘i bo‘ldi va uning murakkabligidan qat’iy nazar har qanday tabiiy birikmani kimyoviy sintez qilishning asosiy imkoniyatini amalda ko‘rsatdi.

Kobalamin bu inson uchun eng kerakli va eng muhim vitamin kompleksi hisoblanadi. U tabiiy holda hayvon mahsulotlarida va sun‘iy holda ham mavjud. Uni ortiqcha qabul qilinishi zarar qilmaydi. Ortiqchasi jigarda to‘planadi va kerakli paytda sarflanadi. Vitaminlarga bo‘lgan ehtiyoj insonning yoshi, jinsi, jismoniy faolligi, surunkali kasalliklarning bor yo‘qligi va moddalar almashinuvining darajasiga bog‘liq. Vitamin yetishmasligi organizmning qarishini tezlashtiradi. B12 vitamini yetishmasligidan kelib chiqadigan kasalliklar asosan anemiya – qondagi gemogloblin miqdorini pasayishidan paydo bo‘ladigan muammo. Odamlar bu patologiyani “kamqonlik” deb ham atashadi. Bu vitamin bittagina kasalliklarga ta’sir qilib qolmay toliqish, depressiya, kayfiyatning buzilishi, soch to‘kilishi, xotiraning susayishi, asab tizimi kasalliklari, surunkali charchash, qo‘l - oyoqlarning uvushib qolishi, bosh aylanish, uyquchanlik, hazm tizimidagi qabziyat, vazn yoqotish, ko‘z kasalliklariga ham tasir qiladi.

Olingan natijalar: Inson tanasida mavjud bo‘lgan B12 ning sutkalik miqdori 2-5 mg tashkil qiladi. Uning taxminan 50% jigarda saqlanadi. Ushbu miqdorning kuniga 0,1% ichaklarda safro bilan ajralib chiqish yo‘li bilan yo‘qoladi va ko‘p qismi qayta so‘riladi. Juda samarali qon aylanishi tufayli jigar B12 ning zahirasini 3-5 yilga saqlashi mumkin. Shuning uchun bu vitamin yetishmasligi kam uchraydi. Asosan uning yetishmasligi yosh bolalarda ko‘proq

uchraydi. Azot oksidi B12 ning metabolizmiga to‘sqinlik qiladi. Shuning uchun azot oksidi behushlik uchun ishlatilganda (stomatologik operatsiyalarda) B12 yetishmasligidan polinevropatiyani rivojlantiradi. Bundan tashqari doimiy ravishda azot oksidi bilan ishlaydigan odamlar, binolar ventilyatsiya qilingan taqdirda ham bunday yetishmovchilik folat va B12 terapiyasini talab qiladi. Nevrologik kasalliklardan demyelinizatsiya va asab hujayralarini qaytarilmas o‘limi kabi xavfli kasalliklarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Belgilari: oyoq qo‘llardagi holsizlik, uvushishlar bilan ifodalanadi.

2000-2002 yillarda Amerika Psixiatriya Asotsiatsiyasi “American journal psychiatry” B12 vitamini keksa bemorlarda klinik depressiya boshlanishiga ta’sirni ko‘rsatishini aytib o‘tdi. Vitaminning yetishmasligini aniqlash uchun diagnostika texnikasi - Schilling testi ishlab chiqilgan, lekin buni amalga oshirish uchun zarur bo‘lgan reagent juda qimmat va kam uchraydi. B12 ichakda bakteriyalar tomonidan so‘riladi, agar ingichka ichakda bakteriya ko‘paysa B12 ga organizm muhtoj bo‘lib anemiyani rivojlantirishi mumkin. Sianokobalamin yosh bo‘yicha har xil miqdorda kerak. Jumladan sutkalik miqdor: 6 oygacha bo‘lgan chaqaloqlarda 0,4 mg; 7-12 oylikda 0,5 mg; 1-3 yil 0,9 mg; 4-8 yil 1,2 mg; 9-13 yil 1,8 mg; 14 yoshdan kattalarda 2,4 mg; homilador ayollarda 2,6 mg; emizikli ayollarda 2,8 mg bo‘ladi.

Xulosa: Bu raqamlar qanchalik kichik bo‘lsada, organizmdagi ahamiyati juda katta. Mg li vitamin ham inson hayotini o‘zgartirib yuborishi mumkin. **Ayrim dori-darmonlarni surunkali iste’mol qilish ham tanamizda ushbu vitaminning to‘g‘ri miqdoriga ega bo‘lishimizga to‘sqinlik qilishi mumkin.** Shunday ekan, har bir inson sog‘lig‘idagi kichik o‘zgarishlarga ham loqayd bo‘lmasligi kerak.

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INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN METODLAR

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada ingliz tili fanini o'qitishda yangi texnologiyalarning ahamiyati, fanning murakkablik darajasini hisobga olgan holda o'qituvchilardan darslarda interaktiv metodlardan foydalanib, o'quvchini fanga bo'lgan qiziqishini orttirishi haqida so'z yuritib, tilni oson o'rganish uchun bir necha o'yinlardan misollar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv metod, o'yin, pedagog, texnologiya, grammatika, tajriba, innovatsiya, ko'nikma.

METHODS USED IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: this article talks about the importance of new technologies in teaching English, taking into account the complexity of the subject, teachers are required to always use interactive methods in the classroom to increase students' interest in the subject, and several games for easy language learning examples are given.

Keywords: interactive method, game, pedagogue, technology, grammar, experience, innovation, skill

Yurtimiz mustaqillikka erishib rivojlanishni boshlagandan beri chet tillarini o'rgatish va o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqish ortdi. Barchaga ma'lumki kimki har tamonlama yutuk shaxs bo'lishni istasa, albatta, kamida bitta til o'rganishi shart.

Ayniqsa, hozirgi kunda chet tillarini o'rganish hayotimizning ajralmas qismiga aylandi va bolalarda bog'cha paytidan boshlab rus va ingliz tillarig abo'lgan qiziqish ortmoqda. Jamiyatd achet tili ta'limning asosiy tarkibiy qismiga aylanmoqda. Chunki mamlakatimizni rivojlanayotgan davlatlar qatoridan , rivojlangan davlatlar qatoriga qo'shish bizning qo'limizda. Shu jumladan, ko'zlagan maqsadimizga erishish o'qituvchilarning amaliy metodlari va pedagogik mahoratlariga bog'liq. Dars davomida axborot texnologiyalari va interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish mavzuni yanada yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam beradi va bolalarni fanga bo'lgan qiziqishini yanada orttiradi va bola dunyoga har tamonlama boqishni o'rganadi. Ingliz tilini o'rgatishda bolaning bilim va salohiyat darjasidan kelib chiqqan holda guruhlarga bo'lib, bosqichma-bosqich o'rgatish yanayam maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

Adabiyotlar tahlli va metodologiya

Chet tilini o'qitish metodikasi yosh fanlardan biri hisoblanib, uning paydo bo'lganiga taxminan ikki yuz yil bo'lgan bo'lsada, fanda chuqur izlanishlar olib borildi. Jamiyat rivojlana borishi bilan doimo yangi metodlar vujudga kelishi muqarrar ekanligini e'tirof etmoq lozim.

Ma'lumki, metod – metodika tushunchasi grek-lotin “methodos-methodus” so'zidan olingan bo'lib, maqsadga eltuvchi yo'llar, usul ma'nosini anglatadi.

Chet tillarini o'rganish va o'qitishda bir qancha metodlar mavjud. Ularning ba'zilari - grammatik tarjima, o'yin va kommunikativ metodi. Grammatik tarjima metodi Evropada XIX asrda ingliz va fransuz tillarini gimnaziyalarda o'qitish uchun qo'llanilgan. Namuna sifatida gimnaziyalarda o'qitilgan qadimgi grek va lotin tillari xizmat qilagan.

Grammatik tarjima metodida grammatkaga katta e'tibor berilgan. Kim grammatikani egallab olsa, demak, u chet tilini bilgan hisoblangan. Grammatik tarjima metodida dars bosqichlari quyidagi tartibda o'tadi:

1. Kirish bosqichi:

Grammatika taqdimoti.

2. Mashq bosqichi:

Grammatik o'quv materialini asosida gaplar tuzish.

3. Amalda qo'llash bosqichi:

1. O'qish .

2. Yozish.

4. Tarjima (o'quv materialini grammatika va so'z boyligi asosida amalda qo'llaniladi).

Agar biz GTM asosida yaratilgan darsliklarga nazar tashlasak, darslikda dastlab biron-bir mavzuga oid mavzu berilgan. Matnga tegishli bir yoki ikkita mashqlar berilgan. Mashqlar esa „matinni hikoya qilib bering“ yoki „savollarga javob bering“ tarzida bo'lgan. Matnni to'la og'zaki nutqga olib chiqish uchun oddiydan murakkabga yo'naltirilgan mashqlar mavjud bo'lmagan. So'ngra ma'lum bir qoida berilgan. Barcha mashqlar esa grammatik qoidalarga yo'naltirilgan. Mashqlar ketma-ketlik darajasiga ham mutlaqo e'tibor berilmagan. Natijada gapirish va eshitish rivojlanmay qolgan. Shu sababli grammatik tarjima metodi bilan ta'lim olgan o'quvchilarning og'zaki nutqlari rivojlanmay qolgan. [1] shu sababi o'quvchilar o'z o'rganish qobiliyatlarini hisobga olgan holda o'rganish metodini tanlashi lozim. Aks holda ko'zlagan maqsadlariga yetishish yo'lida ma'lum bir qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishlari mumkin.

Har bir pedagogning o'ziga yarasha dars o'tish usul va metodlari mavjud. Bir o'qituvchi bilgan metodni boshqasi bilmasligi mumkin. Hozirgi kunda talab qilinayotgan darslar, ayniqsa ingliz tili darslari pedagogdan ko'plab interaktiv metodlarni bilishni talab qilmoqda.

Muhokama va natijalar

Bo'lg'usi pedagoglarning kreativ funksiyalarini rivojlantirishga ko'maklashuvchi innovatsion usullar yangiligi darajasiga ko'ra bir gancha shakllarda namoyon bo'ladi: absolyut daraja; lokal-absolyut daraja; shartli daraja; subyektiv daraja. Innovatsion pedagogik yangiliklarni ommaviy tarzda amaliyotda qo'llash ulari baholashning me'zoni sifatida talgin etiladi. Bu asosan o'quv jarayonining texnik ta'minoti va o'qituvchi faoliyatining o'ziga xosligi bilan bog'liq [2].

Ommaviy pedagogik tajribalarda pedagogik innovatsiyalarni ijodiy qo'lash alohida o'qituvchilar ish faoliyatining boshlang'ich bosqichida namoyon bo'ladi. Mazkur innovatsiyalar tajriba-sinovdan o'tkazilib, obyektiv baholangandan so'ng ommaviy tarzda qo'llash uchun taqdim etiladi [3]. Keng ommalashgan, ijobiy natijalarga erishish imkonini beradigan innovatsion usullardan foydalangan holda bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kreativ funksiyalarini rivojlantirish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

O'qituvchining innovatsion faoliyatini o'rganishga yo'naltirilgan tashxislash metodlari ham rang-barangdir. Tashxislash metodlaridan foydalanish o'qituvchi faoliyatining kuchli jihatlarini namoyon qiladi [4]. Shuning uchun ham bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni tashxislashning zamonaviy metodikalari bilan qurollantirish davr talabidir. Bo'lg'usi pedagoglarning kasbiy ehtiyoj va xohishlarini hisobga olgan holda ularda kasbiy-pedagogik etikani shakllantirish

va uzluksiz rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan to'laqonli maqsadli faoliyatni amalga oshirish lozim.

Bundan tashqari ko'p o'quvchili sinflarda o'qituvchilar bemaolol "6x6x6" metodini qo'llashlari mumkin. "6x6x6" metodi yordamida bir vaqtning o'zida 36 nafar o'quvchini muayyan faoliyatga jalb etish orqali ma'lum topshiriq yoki masalani hal etish, shuningdek, guruhlarning har bir a'zosi imkoniyatlarini aniqlash, ularning qarashlarini bilib olish mumkin. Bu metod asosida tashkil etilayotgan mashg'ulotda har birida 6 nafardan ishtirokchi bo'lgan 6 ta guruh o'qituvchi tomonidan o'rtaga tashlangan muammoni muhokama qiladi. Belgilangan vaqt nihoyasiga yetgach o'qituvchi 6 ta guruhni qayta tuzadi. Qaytadan shakllangan guruhlarning har birida avvalgi 6 ta guruhdan bittadan vakil bo'ladi. Yangidan shakllangan guruh a'zolari o'z jamoadoshlariga guruhi tomonidan muammo yechimi sifatida taqdim etilgan xulosani bayon etib beradilar va mazkur yechimlarni birgalikda muhokama qiladilar. "6x6x6" metodining afzallik jihatlari quyidagilardir:

- guruhlarning har bir a'zosining faol bo'lishiga undaydi;
- ular tomonidan shaxsiy qarashlarning ifoda etilishini ta'minlaydi;
- guruhning boshqa a'zolarining fikrlarini tinglay olish ko'nikmalarini hosil qiladi;
- ilgari surilayotgan bir necha fikrni umumlashtira olish, shuningdek, o'z fikrini himoya qilishga o'rgatadi.

Eng muhimi, mashg'ulot ishtirokchilarining har bir qisqa vaqt (20 daqiqa) mobaynida ham munozara qatnashchisi, ham tinglovchi, ham ma'ruzachi sifatida faoliyat olib boradi.

Ushbu metodni 5, 6, 7 va 8 nafar o'quvchidan iborat bo'lgan bir necha guruhlarda qo'llash mumkin. Biroq yirik guruhlar o'rtasida "6x6x6"metodi qo'llanilganda vaqtni ko'paytirishga to'g'ri keladi. Chunki bunday mashg'ulotlarda munozara uchun ham, axborot berish uchun birmuncha ko'p vaqt talab etiladi. So'z yuritilayotgan metod qo'llanilayotganda mashg'ulotlarda quruhlar tomonidan bir yoki bir necha mavzuni qilish imkoniyati mavjud.

"6x6x6" metodidan ta'lim jarayonida foydalanish o'qituvchidan faollik, pedagogik mahorat, shuningdek, guruhlarni maqsadga muvofiq shakllantira olish layoqatiga ega bo'lishni talab etadi. Guruhlarning to'g'ri shakllantirilmaligi topshiriq yoki vazifalarning to'g'ri hal etilmasligiga sabab bo'lishi mumkin. [5]

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, o'qituvchi tomonidan o'tkaziladigan ushbu metodlar ingliz tilini yanada puxta o'rganish usullaridan bo'lib, dars

jarayonlarida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bunday metodlardan foydalanish o'quvchining fanga bo'lgan ishtiyoq va qiziqishlarini yanada orttiradi, jamoa bo'lib ishlash, bir birining fikriga quloq solib, uni hurmat qilish, nutqiy qobiliyatini o'stirish, o'z fikrini qo'rqmasdan bayon eta olish kabi mahoratlarni kamol toptiradi. Bunda o'qituvchi o'quvchilarining qiziqishlaridan kelib chiqqan holda o'yin metodlaridan foydalanishi maqsadga muvofiq.

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AVTOMATLASHTIRILGAN AXBOROT ALMASHINUVI TIZIMI: ANDIJON MASHINASOZLIK INSTITUTI MISOLIDA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola Andijon Mashinasozlik Instituti (AndMI) kafedralarining axborot almashinuvini avtomatlashtirish jarayonini o'rganadi. Avtomatlashtirishning asosiy maqsadi o'qituvchilar, talabalar va boshqaruv xodimlarining ish samaradorligini oshirishdir. Maqolada AndMI tomonidan amalga oshirilayotgan elektron hujjat aylanishi, ma'lumot bazalarini yaratish, interaktiv ta'lim resurslari va tarmoq infrastrukturasini modernizatsiya qilish kabi asosiy yo'nalishlar tahlil qilinadi. Natijada, institutning ilmiy-pedagogik salohiyati oshishi va zamonaviy ta'lim muassasasi sifatida o'z o'rnini mustahkamlashi kutilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot almashinuvi, optimallashtirish, avtomatlashtirish, elektron hujjat, ma'lumotlar bazasi

AUTOMATED INFORMATION EXCHANGE SYSTEM: IN THE CASE OF ANDIJAN MACHINE BUILDING INSTITUTE

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Abstract. This article examines the process of automation of information exchange of departments of Andijan Mechanical Engineering Institute (AndMI). The main purpose of automation is to improve the work efficiency of teachers, students and administrative staff. The article analyzes the main areas such as electronic document circulation, creation of databases, interactive educational resources and modernization of network infrastructure implemented by AndMI. As a result, it is expected that the scientific and pedagogical potential of the institute will increase and strengthen its position as a modern educational institution.

Key words: information exchange, optimization, automation, electronic document, database

Zamonaviy ta'lim muassasalari o'z faoliyatlarini samarali boshqarish va ta'lim sifatini oshirish maqsadida axborot texnologiyalaridan tobora ko'proq foydalanmoqdalar. Bu jarayon, ayniqsa, oliy ta'lim tizimida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi, chunki bu yerda ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari va ta'lim jarayonlari o'zaro chambarchas bog'liq holda amalga oshiriladi. Andijon Mashinasozlik Instituti (AndMI) ham ushbu yo'nalishda faol ishlar olib bormoqda va institutning barcha kafedralari o'rtasida axborot almashinuvini avtomatlashtirishga alohida e'tibor qaratmoqda.

Avtomatlashtirilgan axborot almashinuvi tizimi orqali AndMI o'zining ilmiy va pedagogik salohiyatini yanada rivojlantirish, o'qituvchilar va talabalar uchun qulay va samarali ta'lim muhitini yaratish, shuningdek, boshqaruv jarayonlarini optimallashtirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Ushbu maqola, AndMI kafedralarining axborot almashinuvini avtomatlashtirish jarayonini, uning afzalliklari va qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan texnologiyalarni tahlil qiladi.

Andijon Mashinasozlik Instituti o'zining ilmiy va ta'limiy faoliyatini yanada takomillashtirish maqsadida axborot texnologiyalari sohasida yangi yondashuvlarni qo'llamoqda. Bu borada, institutning barcha kafedralari o'rtasida axborot almashinuvini avtomatlashtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Avtomatlashtirishning asosiy maqsadi - o'qituvchilar, talabalar va boshqaruv xodimlarining ish samaradorligini oshirishdir. Buning uchun, AndMI quyidagi asosiy yo'nalishlarda ish olib bormoqda:

1. Elektron Hujjat Aylanishi: Kafedralar o'rtasidagi hujjatlar va ma'lumotlarni elektron shaklda aylanishini ta'minlash, bu orqali qog'oz hujjatlarning kamaytirilishi va ish jarayonlarining tezlashtirilishi.

2. Ma'lumot Bazalarini Yaratish: Har bir kafedra uchun alohida ma'lumot bazalarini yaratish, bu orqali o'qituvchilar va talabalar uchun zarur bo'lgan ma'lumotlarga tezkor kirish imkoniyatini berish.

3. Interaktiv Ta'lim Resurslari: Darsliklar, ma'ruzalar va boshqa o'quv materiallarini elektron formatda taqdim etish, shuningdek, masofaviy ta'lim imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish.

4. Tarmoq Infrastrukturasini Yaratish: Institutning tarmoq infrastrukturasi modernizatsiya qilish va kafedralar o'rtasidagi axborot almashinuvini tez va xavfsiz qilish.

Bu jarayonlar natijasida, AndMI o'zining ilmiy-pedagogik salohiyatini oshirishga va zamonaviy ta'lim muassasasi sifatida o'z o'rnini mustahkamlashga qodir bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda Andijon Mashinasozlik Instituti kafedralarining axborot almashinuvini avtomatlashtirish tajribasi, zamonaviy ta'lim muassasalari uchun axborot texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanishning ahamiyatini namoyish etadi. Ushbu maqola orqali AndMI kafedralari o'rtasida amalga oshirilgan avtomatlashtirish jarayonlari va ularning natijalari tahlil qilindi. Elektron hujjat aylanishi, ma'lumot bazalarini yaratish, interaktiv ta'lim resurslari va tarmoq infrastrukturasi modernizatsiya qilish kabi tashabbuslar institutning ilmiy-pedagogik salohiyatini oshirishga va ta'lim sifatini yaxshilashga xizmat qilmoqda.

Avtomatlashtirish jarayonlari nafaqat ish samaradorligini oshirishga, balki talabalar va o'qituvchilarning ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonlarida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga ham yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga, bu tajriba boshqa ta'lim muassasalari uchun ham namuna bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Kelajakda, AndMI avtomatlashtirishni yanada chuqurlashtirish va yangi texnologiyalarni joriy etish orqali o'zining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishni maqsad qilgan. Bu esa, o'z navbatida, O'zbekistonning ta'lim tizimini yanada zamonaviy va samarali qilishga hissa qo'shadi.

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TASHKILOTDA ICHKI FOYDALANISH UCHUN YAGONA BILIM BAZASINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tashkilotda ichki foydalanish uchun yagona bilim bazasini ishlab chiqishning maqsadi, axborot tizimining asosini ma'lumotlar bazasi tashkil etishi, ma'lumotlar yangilanishining osonligi, ma'lumotlarning mustaqil bo'lishi, ko'p foydalanuvchilar o'rtasidagi ma'lumot almashinuvi, ma'lumotlar xavfsizligi -ma'lumotlar sirini qasddan yoki bilmasdan turib buzishdan, yo'q qilishdan himoya qilish, ma'lumotlar bazalarini qurish va ishlashini standartlashtirish orqali yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ma'lumotlar bazasi, axborot, avtomatlashtirish, tizim, model, M.B

DEVELOPMENT OF A UNIFIED KNOWLEDGE BASE FOR INTERNAL USE IN THE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract: In this article, the purpose of developing a single knowledge base for internal use in the organization, the basis of the information system is the database, the ease of updating the data, the independence of the data, the exchange of information between many users. , information security - protection of information confidentiality from intentional or unintentional violation, destruction, construction and operation of databases is covered by standardization.

Key words: database, information, automation, system, model, D.B.

Kirish. Hozirgi kunda Bilim bazalari, bugungi kunda bizning hayotimizning har xil sohalorida keng qo'llaniladigan elektronik axborot tizimlari hisoblanadi. Bilim bazalari, ma'lumotlarni yig'ish, saqlash va ulardan foydalanish uchun zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish bilan birga, tadqiqotchilar va so'rovnoma yozuvchilari uchun ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish usullarini taqdim etadi. Bugungi kunda, dunyoda bir nechta bilim bazalari mavjud bo'lib, ular nomzodlar, tadqiqotchilar, universitetlar, maktablar va boshqa tashkilotlar tomonidan foydalaniladi. Ularning bir qismi maxsus tashkilotlar tomonidan yaratilgan, boshqalari esa xalqaro vaqtinchalik ma'lumotlar bazalari sifatida faoliyat yuritishadi. Mamlakatimizda faoliyat yuritayotgan barcha korxonalaridagi kadrlar bilan ishlash bo'limlari O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonunlari asosida ishlab chiqilgan yo'riqnomalar asosida ish yuritish tashkil etilgan.

Bilim bazalari, tadqiqotchilar tomonidan yangi ma'lumotlarni topish va ulardan foydalanish uchun muhim bo'ladi. Bu ma'lumotlar, ilmiy tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirish va dunyoda yangi innovatsiyalarni yaratish uchun kerakli bo'lgan. Murojaatlar, ilmiy jurnal maqolalari, elektron kitoblar, nashrlar, patentlar va boshqa axborotlar bilim bazalarida tuzilgan va bular bilan birga, bu ma'lumotlar yozuvchilar tomonidan yozilgan maqolalar, konferentsiyalar va boshqa ilmiy majlislar bilan birga ma'lumotlar bazalarida saqlanadi. Bilim bazalari, yangi tadqiqotlarni topish uchun qulay va tezroq yo'llar taqdim etadi. Bu ma'lumotlar bazalari elektron kitoblar, jurnal maqolalari va nashrlarning yanada keng tarqalgan elektron shakllari bilan birga, audio va video darsliklar, ma'lumotlar, infografikalar va boshqa ko'rsatmalar bilan ta'minlaydi. Bilim bazalari, o'qish, o'rganish va tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirish uchun ham muhimdir. Bu ma'lumotlar bazalari, o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun kerakli ma'lumotlarni topish va ulardan foydalanish imkonini taqdim etadi. Universitetlar, maktablar va boshqa o'quv markazlari, o'quv materiallarini, elektron kitoblar, darsliklar va boshqa resurslarni topish va ulardan foydalanish uchun bilim bazalaridan foydalanishadi.[1]

Adabiyotlar taxlili va metodologiya. Dasturlash yoki programming O'zbekistonda ham keng tarqalgan sohalardan biridir. O'zbekistonda IT sohasini rivojlantirishga qiziqish mavjud va bu sohaga qiziqishni oshirish maqsadida, bir qancha IT universitetlari va maktablar ochilgan. O'zbekistanning barcha katta shaharlarida va ko'plab tumanlarda, dasturlash markazlari ochilgan. Bu markazlar o'quvchilarga va IT sohasida ishlayotgan mutaxassislariga dasturlash, web-dizayn, grafik dizayn va boshqa sohalarda malakasini oshirishga imkoniyat yaratadi. Dasturchilar uchun O'zbekistonda ko'p dasturiy tillar o'rganish

imkoniyatlari mavjud. Bunday tillar orasida Java, C++, Python, C# kabi keng tarqalgan tillar ham mavjud. Bunda, O‘zbekiston IT sohasida taraqqiyot ko‘rsatmoqda va dasturlash sohasida yetakchi mamlakatlar orasida joylashmoqda.

Ma’lumotlarni boshqarish tizimi, quyidagi xossalarga ega:

1. fayllar to‘plami mantiqiy kelishuvni quvvatlaydi;
2. ma’lumotlar ustida ish yuritish tili bilan ta’minlaydi;
3. har xil to‘xtalishlardan keyin ma’lumotlarni qayta tiklaydi;
4. MBBT bir necha foydalanuvchilarning parallel ishlashini ta’minlaydi.

Bir qancha tashqi o‘quv yurtlari ham O‘zbekistonda faoliyat ko‘rsatadi. Ularda dasturlash, kompyuter injiniringi, va boshqa IT sohasiga oid yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ta’lim olib borish mumkin. Shuningdek, O‘zbekistonda ko‘plab IT kompaniyalari faoliyat ko‘rsatmoqda va dasturchilarga ish imkoniyatlari yaratmoqda. Bunda, dasturchilar o‘zlarining mutaxassisliklariga qarab, o‘zlariga mos ravishda ish topishlari mumkin. Dasturlashning O‘zbekistonda katta imkoniyatlari bor. O‘zbekistonda dasturlash sohasida ish o‘rniga ega bo‘lish uchun quyidagi imkoniyatlar mavjud: Dasturchilik kurslari: O‘zbekistonda dasturchilik kurslari ko‘plab markazlar yordamida tashkil etilgan. Bu kurslar O‘zbekistonda dasturchilarni tayyorlash va ularning malakasini oshirishga yordam beradi. O‘zbekistonda ko‘plab freelance platformalari mavjud, masalan, Upwork, Freelancer va boshqalar. Bu platformalar orqali dasturchilar va IT mutaxassislar o‘zlarining malakalarini sotish, xizmatlarini taklif etish va o‘zlariga to‘liq vaqtda to‘lov qilinishini ta’minlashadi. Startaplar: O‘zbekistonda IT sohasida startaplar ham keng tarqalgan. Bu startaplar o‘zlariga dasturchilar va IT mutaxassislarini ishlari uchun chaqirishadi. Startaplar o‘zlariga yuqori darajada innovatsiyalarni amalga oshirish imkoniyatini beradi va ularning ishlash usullari ko‘proq ozodlik va rivojlanish imkoniyatlari taqdim etadi. Barcha bu imkoniyatlar O‘zbekistonda dasturchilar uchun ish imkoniyatlari yaratadi va ularning malakasini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Muhokama va natijalar: Quyidagi usullar dasturchilarning ishlashini yaxshilash uchun tavsiya etiladi: Kodning qulayligini oshirish: Kodning qulayligini oshirish uchun, dasturchilar kodni aniq va tushunarli yozishga intilishadi. Bu kod yozish jarayonida xatoliklar kamayadi va kodning tushunarli bo‘lishini ta’minlaydi. Ma’lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimi (MBBT) - bu dasturiy va apparat vositalarining murakkab majmuasi bo‘lib, ular yordamida foydalanuvchi ma’lumotlar bazasini yaratish va shu bazadagi ma’lumotlar ustida ish yuritish mumkin. MBBT-MBni yaratish, uni dolzarb xolatda ushlab turish,

kerakli axborotni topishni tashkil etish va boshka xizmat ko'rsatish uchun zarur bo'ladigan dasturiy va til vositalari majmuasidir.

Kod yozishni tashkil qilish: Kod yozishni tashkil qilish, dasturchilar yozgan kodni tushunarli qilish, qulaylik va o'qishni oshirish uchun uning tashkili va formatlashini o'rganishga yordam beradi. Ixtiyoriy turdagi MBni loyihalashtirishning birinchi bosqichdagi predmet sohasini tahlil qilish bo'lib, u axborot tuzilmasini (kontseptual sxemalar) tuzish bilan yakunlanadi. Bu bosqichda foydalanuvchining so'rovlari tahlil qilinadi, axborot ob'ektlari va uning xarakteristikalari tanlanadi, hamda o'tkazilgan tahlil asosida predmet sohasi tuzilmalashtiriladi. P.[2]

Testing: Dasturchilar kodni yozishdan keyin uni test qilishni o'rganish kerak. Testing, kodning ishlashini va xatoliklarni aniqlashga yordam beradi. **Kodni qayta ishlash:** Dasturchilar kodni yozishdan keyin kodni qayta ishlashni o'rganish kerak. Bu, kodni yozishda qilinadigan xatoliklarni aniqlash va nazorat qilishga yordam beradi. **Kodni dokumentatsiyalash:** Dasturchilar kodni dokumentatsiyalashni o'rganish kerak. Kodni dokumentatsiyalash, kodni tushunish va qayta ishlashni osonlashtiradi.

Kodni tashkil etish: Kodni tashkil etish, kodni aniq va tushunarli tashkil qilish uchun yordam beradi. Kodni tashkil etish, kodni tushunishni osonlashtirishi va kodni qayta ishlashni osonlashtiradi. **Kodni rejalashtirish:** Kodni rejalashtirish, kodni qulay va tushunarli ishlash uchun tuzilishini o'rganishga yordam beradi. Kodni rejalashtirish, kodning tushunarli bo'lishini ta'minlaydi va kodni o'qish va tahrir qilishni osonlashtiradi.

Kodni tahlil qilish: Kodni tahlil qilish, kodni tushunish va xatoliklarni aniqlash uchun yordam beradi. Bu usul kodni tahlil qilish va xatoliklarni aniqlashda yordam beradi. **Kodni sharhlash:** Kodni sharhlash, dasturchining kodni boshqa dasturchilarga tushunishiga yordam beradi. Bu usul kodni tushunishni osonlashtiradi va dasturchilarning kodni qulay va to'g'ri ishlatishiga yordam beradi. Barcha bu usullar dasturchilar uchun ishni osonlashtiradi va kodni qulay va to'g'ri ishlashini ta'minlaydi. Bu usullarni o'rganish va amalga oshirish, dasturchilarning kodni yozish va tushunish jarayonida oson va samarali bo'lishiga yordam beradi.[3]

Xulosa. Shunday qilib xulosa qilib shuni aytishim mumkinki Yagona ma'lumot bazasi, tashkilotning barcha ma'lumotlarini o'z ichiga oladi va ularga qulay va tez foydalanish imkoniyatini beradi. Avtomatik ma'lumot yig'ish, ma'lumotlarni yig'ish jarayonini avtomatik ravishda bajaradi va ma'lumotlarni o'rganishni osonlashtiradi. Algoritmik mashqlash, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish

uchun yorliqlar va ko‘plab qo‘shimchalarni o‘z ichiga oladi, bu esa ma’lumotlar o‘rganish va ulardan foydalanishni yanada osonlashtiradi. Shuningdek, tashkilotda ichki foydalanish uchun yagona bilim bazasini ishlab chiqish jarayonida, tashkilotning maqsadlariga muvofiq ma’lumotlarni to‘plam va tahlil qilish uchun ma’lumotlar bazasining yaratilishi, ma’lumot yig‘ish, tahlil qilish, ma’lumotlar o‘zgartirish va qayta ishlashni osonlashtirish, ma’lumotlarni xavfsiz saqlash, real vaqtida ma’lumotlar va ma’lumotlarni o‘rganish va ulardan foydalanishni osonlashtiruvchi interfeyslar kabi jarayonlarda ishlashga tayyorlik ko‘rsatish lozim. Buning uchun tashkilotning ma’lumotlarni qanday shaklda saqlashni, ulardan foydalanishni, ulardan tahlil qilishni va ma’lumotlar bazasini qanday to‘play oladiganini aniqlash kerak. Shuningdek, tashkilotning ma’lumotlarini xavfsiz saqlash uchun xavfsizlik siyosatini belgilash, ma’lumotlarni himoyalash va ulardan foydalanishga ruxsat berish uchun qoidalarni o‘rnatish va ulardan foydalanishga ruxsat berishni boshqarishning o‘zining loyixalarini belgilash ham zarur. Bularni amalga oshirish, tashkilotning ma’lumotlaridan maksimal foyda olishiga yordam beradi vatashkilotning foydalanuvchilari uchun ko‘p imkoniyat yaratadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ И ДИАГНОСТИКЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

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Аннотация. Современная эволюция в изучении заболеваний щитовидной железы включает в себя введение новых терминов, критериев для диагностики и классификации, а также рекомендаций по лечению. В данном обзоре описываются последние достижения в классификации опухолей и образований в щитовидной железе, с особым вниманием к их распространенности и методам диагностики у детей.

Ключевые слова. Щитовидная железа, классификация заболеваний щитовидной железы, тиреоидная патология.

MODERN APPROACHES TO THE CLASSIFICATION AND DIAGNOSIS OF THYROID DISEASES (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Annotation. Modern evolution in the study of thyroid diseases includes the introduction of new terms, criteria for diagnosis and classification, as well as treatment recommendations. This review describes recent advances in the classification of tumors and formations in the thyroid gland, with particular attention to their prevalence and diagnostic methods in children.

Keywords. Thyroid gland, classification of thyroid diseases, thyroid pathology. .

Введение

Несмотря на определённые успехи современной тиреологии, в отечественной литературе продолжает обсуждаться широкий круг вопросов: терминология, критерии диагностики и классификации болезней щитовидной железы (ЩЖ) [1–4]. При этом включение заболеваний ЩЖ в МКБ-10 в один класс с расстройствами питания и нарушениями обмена скрывает истинную частоту тиреоидной патологии [5, 6].

Актуальность пересмотра классификационных и диагностических подходов к заболеваниям ЩЖ диктуется необходимостью учета современных научных и практических данных для достижения консенсуса в трактовках между врачами разных специальностей. Так, отсутствует единый подход к термину «узловой зоб» [1, 4, 5, 8–10]. В МКБ-10 узловой зоб представлен в IV классе в рубриках: «нетоксический одноузловой зоб» (E04.1) и «тиреотоксикоз с токсическим одноузловым зобом» (E05.1), «тиреотоксикоз с токсическим многоузловым зобом» (E05.2) [6]. Согласно патолого-анатомическим критериям, «узловой зоб» — патологическое увеличение ЩЖ, связанное с очаговой (узловой) гиперплазией и/ или гипертрофией ее паренхимы, которое следует отличать от очаговых зобных изменений без инкапсуляции [1, 4, 5]. С позиций клинической медицины в понятие «узловой зоб» отнесены все узловые образования органа (включая новообразования), в том числе необязательно ведущие к увеличению его объема [3–5, 8–10]. Поэтому для цитологической оценки результатов тонкоигольной аспирационной пункционной биопсии узловых образований ЩЖ в США была разработана классификация The Bethesda System For Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC). Вместе с тем показано, что в 15 % случаев результаты тонкоигольной аспирационной пункционной биопсии недостоверны [3]. Кроме того, цитологическое заключение с указанием IV–V категорий по TBSRTC (фолликулярная неоплазия/подозрение на нее и на злокачественное новообразование) позволяет только решить вопрос о необходимости хирургического лечения и не устанавливает нозологическую единицу [13]. Поэтому верификация патологии ЩЖ остается приоритетом патолого-анатомического исследования, а диагностику тиреоидных опухолей относят к одному из наиболее сложных разделов патоморфологии [1, 14].

В последний пересмотр гистологической классификации опухолей ЩЖ (ВОЗ, 2017) [15] введена новая группа — инкапсулированные опухоли фолликулярного строения. Она представлена ранее обсуждаемыми, но не

внесенными в предыдущее издание категориями: фолликулярная опухоль неопределенного злокачественного потенциала (FT-UMP) (ее диагностические критерии: сомнительные признаки сосудистой и капсулярной инвазии; отсутствие изменений ядер, характерных для папиллярной карциномы) и высокодифференцированная опухоль неопределенного злокачественного потенциала (WDT-UMP) (ее диагностические критерии: сомнительные признаки как сосудистой/капсулярной инвазии, так и изменений ядер, характерных для папиллярной карциномы) [15, 16]. В этой группе инкапсулированных опухолей также выделена новая форма — «неинвазивная фолликулярная опухоль с ядрами папиллярного типа» (NIFTP), которую ранее относили к неинвазивному фолликулярному варианту папиллярной карциномы. Частота NIFTP на современном этапе составляет 16–23 % от всех случаев папиллярных карцином [17, 18]. Для ее диагностики обязательны не менее 2 из 3 «ядерных» признаков папиллярной карциномы: изменение формы и размера ядер, контуров ядерной мембраны, характеристик ядерного хроматина. NIFTP характеризуется фолликулярным строением с наличием капсулы/четкой границы и отсутствием инвазии, псаммомных телец [15–17]. Пересмотр гистологических образцов, молекулярно-генетическое типирование NIFTP и многолетнее наблюдение за пациентами показали, что у этой опухоли — безрецидивный клинический прогноз, что делает агрессивную хирургическую тактику излишней [17]. В классификацию опухолей [15] внесена новая гистологическая форма фолликулярной карциномы — инкапсулированный вариант с сосудистой инвазией, при этом уточняется, что инвазия регистрируется в сосудах капсулы и/или перитуморозной ткани. В отдельную группу выделены онкоцитарные опухоли (аденома и карцинома из клеток Гюртля), которые ранее относили в категорию фолликулярно-клеточных неоплазий. Гиалинизирующая трабекулярная опухоль переведена из группы доброкачественных в пограничные опухоли с неопределенным злокачественным потенциалом. Из нового издания классификации ВОЗ исключена категория «атипическая аденома», которая вызывала значительные трудности в диагностике из-за неопределенности ее критериев [1].

Так, при наличии отдаленных метастазов у пациентов младше 45 лет уста-навливалась II стадия, после 45 лет — IV стадия. Это объясняется тем, что дифференцированная фолликулярно-клеточная карцинома в детском возрасте имеет более благоприятный прогноз в отличие от взрослого

населения [20]. По мнению экспертов Американской ассоциации эндокринологов, возрастное стадирование фолликулярноклеточной карциномы спорно, поскольку оно основано на исследованиях в небольших группах детей и наблюдение за такими пациентами ограничивалось детским возрастом, поэтому рекомендована стратификация детей по группам риска [9]. Также отмечается, что у детей по сравнению со взрослыми на момент манифестации тиреоидные карциномы чаще имеют большие размеры (категория T), а возраст детей младше 10 лет рассматривается как фактор повышенного риска рецидива и летальности [14, 21, 22]. Следует отметить, что в последнем издании классификации TNM возрастная группировка по стадиям для дифференцированной карциномы ЩЖ исключена [23].

В клинической эндокринологии сегодня появился новый термин — «функциональная автономия щитовидной железы» [24, 25]. Функциональная автономия определяется как избыточное функционирование тиреоцитов без участия их главного физиологического стимулятора — тиреотропного гормона гипофиза [8, 24–26]. Пусковой фактор (дефицит йода) приводит к гиперплазии тиреоцитов и далее к их соматическим мутациям. Таким образом, появляется пул клеток с усиленным пролиферативным потенциалом и синтезом тиреоидных гормонов, что сопровождается гипертиреозом (тиреотоксикозом) (рис. 1) [25–27].

Функциональная автономия развивается в течение длительного времени только у жителей йоддефицитных регионов и проявляется клинически преимущественно в пожилом возрасте [24–28, 29]. Частота выявления таких функционально автономных («горячих») узлов значительно повышается при многоузловом зобе [25, 28]. Существующие клинико-лабораторные критерии диагностики функциональной автономии позволяют провести дифференциальный диагноз с узловым токсическим зобом и тем самым определить тактику лечения [3, 8, 29]. В патологоанатомическом руководстве функциональная автономия щитовидной железы упомянута лишь в качестве причины тиреотоксикоза с токсическим одноузловым / многоузловым зобом [4]. В этой связи актуальным становится вопрос о патоморфологических признаках функциональной автономии и могут ли таковыми считаться структурные критерии тиреотоксикоза (базедофикации). При этом единого мнения среди морфологов о характерных для тиреотоксикоза морфологических особенностях сегодня нет [1, 4, 30].

Рисунок 1. Этиопатогенез функциональной автономии щитовидной железы. Гиперплазия клеток с соматическими мутациями и формированием «холодных» (синий цвет) и гиперфункционирующих «горячих» (красный цвет) узлов в щитовидной железе (по К. Krohn, R. Paschke [27])

Заключение

По мнению ряда авторов [31, 32], на сегодняшний день существует пробел между накопленными клиническими, экспериментальными данными о тиреоидной патологии и интеграцией их в современные представления о патои морфогенезе узловых и аутоиммунных заболеваний щитовидной железы, что требует дальней реологии на основе обязательного проведения клинко-анатомических сопоставлений.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ДЕГЛЮДЕКА ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА 2 ТИПА

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Аннотация: В обзорной статье рассматривается эффективность и безопасность деглюдека при лечении сахарного диабета 2 типа. Деглюдек, комбинированный инсулин, сочетающий инсулин деглюдек и лираглутид, представляет собой инновационный подход к контролю гликемии у пациентов с диабетом 2 типа.

Анализ последних клинических исследований показал, что деглюдек оказывает большое влияние на снижение уровня гликемии, обеспечение стабильного контроля уровня глюкозы в крови в течение длительного времени. Безопасность препарата хорошо документирована, а побочные эффекты обычно легко купируются.

Деглюдек представлен в удобной для инъекций форме, что облегчает его применение и соблюдение терапии. Его роль в лечении сахарного диабета 2 типа подтверждена как в качестве начальной терапии, так и для усиления лечения пациентов, которым требуется дополнительный гликемический контроль

Ключевое слово: деглюдек, сахарный диабет 2 типа, фармакокинетика.

USE OF DEGLUDEK IN THE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation. *The review article examines the efficacy and safety of degludek in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Degludek, a combined insulin combining insulin degludek and liraglutide, is an innovative approach to glycemia management in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.*

An analysis of recent clinical studies has shown that degludek is highly effective in reducing glycemic levels, providing stable blood glucose control for a long time. The safety of the drug is well documented, and the side effects are usually easily manageable.

Degludek is presented in a convenient form for injection, which facilitates its use and compliance with therapy. Its role in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus is confirmed both as an initial therapy and for the intensification of treatment in patients requiring additional glycemic control.

Key words: *degludek, type 2 diabetes mellitus, pharmacokinetics.*

Введение

Сахарный диабет 2 типа остается одной из наиболее распространенных эндокринных патологий, представляя серьезную медицинскую проблему среди населения по всему миру.[1,2,3] Этот хронический метаболический синдром характеризуется гипергликемией, вызванной нарушением выработки инсулина, его действия или обеих этих причинами. Следствием сахарного диабета 2 типа могут быть серьезные

осложнения, включая заболевания сердечно-сосудистой системы, нарушения зрения, почечная недостаточность и даже ампутация конечностей.[3,4,5]

В последние десятилетия медицинская наука и фармацевтическая индустрия активно развивали новые подходы к лечению сахарного диабета, стремясь повысить эффективность и безопасность терапии. В этом контексте применение комбинированных препаратов, сочетающих в себе различные механизмы действия, становится все более распространенным.[6,7,8]

Одним из таких инновационных лекарственных средств является деглюдек - комбинированный инсулин, содержащий в своем составе инсулин деглюдек и лираглутид. Этот препарат сочетает в себе длительное действие инсулина с эффектами инкретинового лираглутида, обеспечивая стабильный контроль гликемии на протяжении дня.[9,10]

Цель исследования. Задачей данного обзора состоит в рассмотрении эффективности и безопасности использования препарата деглюдека в лечении сахарного диабета 2 типа. Деглюдек, являющийся комбинированным инсулином, включающим инсулин деглюдек и лираглутид, представляет собой инновационное лекарственное средство, сочетающее в себе два механизма действия для контроля уровня глюкозы в крови. Основная цель обзора - оценить клинические данные, фармакокинетику, фармакодинамику и практические аспекты использования деглюдека, а также проанализировать его роль в управлении сахарным диабетом 2 типа с точки зрения эффективности, безопасности и удобства использования.

Материал и методы. **Критерии включения и исключения:** Включались клинические исследования, обзоры, мета-анализы и рандомизированные контролируемые испытания (RCTs), связанные с эффективностью и безопасностью применения деглюдека у пациентов с сахарным диабетом 2 типа. Исключались исследования, не относящиеся к данной теме, а также публикации на языках, которые не были доступны для перевода. **Анализ данных:** Проводилась оценка качества данных, включая методологию исследований, выборку, длительность наблюдения, основные результаты и оценку статистической значимости. Данные по фармакокинетики, фармакодинамике и практическим аспектам

использования деглюдека также анализировались и сравнивались с другими аналогичными препаратами. **Синтез результатов:** Проведенный анализ был использован для синтеза и обобщения результатов, выявления тенденций и практических выводов о роли деглюдека в лечении сахарного диабета 2 типа. **Статистический анализ:** При необходимости проводился статистический анализ данных с использованием соответствующих методов, представленных в оригинальных исследованиях.

Результаты и обсуждение. **Эффективность деглюдека:** Многие клинические исследования показывают, что деглюдек эффективен в снижении уровня гликемии у пациентов с сахарным диабетом 2 типа. В сравнении с другими режимами лечения, деглюдек позволяет достигать улучшения контроля гликемии при более простом режиме введения, что может улучшить соблюдение терапии. **Безопасность использования:** Безопасность деглюдека была хорошо изучена в клинических исследованиях. Наиболее часто отмечаемыми побочными эффектами являются гипогликемия и желудочно-кишечные расстройства. Однако, эти эффекты обычно легко управляемы и редко приводят к прекращению лечения. **Фармакокинетика и фармакодинамика:** Деглюдек обладает продолжительным действием, обеспечивая стабильный уровень инсулина в крови в течение длительного времени. Это способствует поддержанию стабильного уровня гликемии на протяжении суток, что особенно важно для пациентов с сахарным диабетом 2 типа. **Практические аспекты использования:** Деглюдек представлен в форме готового к использованию раствора для инъекций, что облегчает его применение и повышает соблюдение терапии у пациентов. Кроме того, наличие лираглутида в составе препарата может способствовать снижению веса у некоторых пациентов. **Роль в лечении сахарного диабета 2 типа:** Деглюдек представляет собой важное дополнение к арсеналу лекарственных средств для лечения сахарного диабета 2 типа. Его удобство использования, эффективность и безопасность делают его привлекательным вариантом как для начальной терапии, так и для пациентов, требующих интенсификации лечения.

Заключение

Исследование подтверждает, что деглюдек представляет собой эффективное и безопасное лекарственное средство для лечения сахарного диабета 2 типа. Его комбинированный состав обеспечивает уникальное

сочетание длительного действия инсулина с эффектами лираглутида, что способствует достижению стабильного контроля гликемии и может улучшить клинические исходы у пациентов.

Деглюдек предлагает преимущества в плане удобства использования, что может повысить соблюдение лечения и улучшить качество жизни пациентов. Также важно отметить, что его безопасность хорошо документирована, и побочные эффекты обычно легко управляемы.

В целом, деглюдек занимает значимое место в терапии сахарного диабета 2 типа и может быть рассмотрен как вариант начальной терапии, так и для интенсификации лечения у пациентов, требующих дополнительного контроля гликемии. Дальнейшие исследования могут уточнить его роль в многоаспектном управлении сахарным диабетом 2 типа.

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KEY POINTS OF EPIDEMIOLOGY AND PATHOGENESIS, MODERN CONCEPT OF DIAGNOSIS AND DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF VARIOUS MORPHOLOGICAL VARIANTS OF NODULAR GOITER

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Annotation. *Unified classifications of ultrasound and cytological diagnosis of nodular goiter are demonstrated. Methods for optimizing radical treatment are considered. The guidelines are provided with supporting material, an algorithm for diagnosing and managing patients. Recommended for endocrinologists, ultrasound specialists, clinical laboratory diagnostic specialists, radiologists, surgeons, general practitioners.*

Key words: *thyroid gland, nodular goiter, nodular colloid goiter, thyroid cancer, ultrasound, fine-needle aspiration biopsy, TIRADS classification, Bethesda classification.*

**КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ПОЛОЖЕНИЯ ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИИ И ПАТОГЕНЕЗА,
СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЯ О ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И
ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНОЙ ДИАГНОСТИКЕ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ
МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ВАРИАНТОВ УЗЛОВОГО ЗОБА.**

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Аннотация. Приведены унифицированные классификации ультразвуковой и цитологической диагностики узлового зоба. Рассмотрены методы оптимизации радикального лечения. Рекомендации снабжены вспомогательным материалом, алгоритмом диагностики и ведения пациентов. Рекомендуется эндокринологам, специалистам УЗИ, специалистам клинической лабораторной диагностики, рентгенологам, хирургам, врачам общей практики.

Ключевые слова: щитовидная железа, узловой зоб, узловой коллоидный зоб, рак щитовидной железы, УЗИ, тонкоигольная аспирационная биопсия, классификация TIRADS, классификация Bethesda.

Section 1. Epidemiology, etiology and pathogenesis Among the population, during palpation of the thyroid gland, nodular goiter is recorded in 3–5% of subjects, in 20–35% during screening ultrasound examination (US) and tissue autopsy tissue thyroid nodules are detected in more than 50% of cases. There are many etiological factors for the development of nodular nontoxic goiter (goitrogens, defect in the synthesis of thyroid hormones), but the most common cause of its development is iodine deficiency. Diffuse endemic goiter and UKZ are included in the spectrum of iodine deficiency diseases.

According to epidemiological studies conducted by the Federal Endocrinological Research Center, there are no territories in the Russian Federation where the population is not at risk of developing iodine deficiency diseases. The prevalence of iodine deficiency thyropathies in different regions of Russia varies from 5.2 to 70% and the national average is 31%. Women develop goiter 2–3 times more often than men. Among children, the highest incidence of diffuse nontoxic goiter and UKZ is characteristic of adolescence.

In the early stages of goiter development (usually in children, adolescents and young adults), compensatory hypertrophy of thyrocytes occurs.

The formation of nodular formations in the thyroid gland is regarded as involution of the organ against the background of diffuse endemic goiter in conditions of chronic iodine deficiency.

There is no doubt that all adaptation reactions are stimulated and controlled by thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). However, as shown in many studies, the TSH level does not increase in diffuse endemic goiter. In the course of a number of *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies, new data were obtained on the autoregulation of the thyroid gland by iodine and autocrine growth factors, such as insulin-like growth factor type 1, epidermal growth factor and fibroblast growth factor, which, under conditions of decreased content iodine in the thyroid gland has a powerful stimulating effect on thyrocytes. It was experimentally demonstrated that when potassium iodide was added to the culture of thyrocytes, a decrease in TSH-induced, cAMP (cyclic adenosine monophosphate)-mediated mRNA expression by insulin-like growth factor type 1 was observed, with its complete cessation with a significant increase in the potassium dose. iodide.

It is well known that iodine itself not only serves substrate for the synthesis of thyroid hormones, but also regulates the growth and function of the thyroid gland. Thyrocyte proliferation is inversely related to intrathyroidal iodine content. High doses of iodine inhibit iodine absorption, its organization, synthesis and secretion of thyroid hormones, and absorption of glucose and amino acids. Iodine, entering the thyrocyte, interacts not only with tyrosyl residues in thyroglobulin, but also with lipids. The resulting compounds (iodolactones and iodaldehydes) serve as the main physiological blockers of the production of autocrine growth factors. In conditions of chronic iodine deficiency, there is a decrease in the formation of iodine lipids - substances that inhibit the proliferative effects of autocrine growth factors.

Thyrocytes initially have different proliferation tive activity, i.e. microheterogeneity. Some pools of thyrocytes more actively take up iodine,

others quickly proliferate, and others have low functional and proliferative activity. Under conditions of iodine deficiency, microheterogeneity of thyrocytes becomes pathological: thyrocytes with the greatest ability to proliferate respond to hyperstimulation to a greater extent. Thus, nodular and multinodular euthyroid goiter is formed. As a result of the accumulation of a number of somatic mutations in areas of nodular/multinodular goiter, over time, a number of patients develop functional autonomy (FA) of the thyroid gland. As the volume of autonomously functioning tissue increases, there is a decrease in iodine uptake by the surrounding thyroid tissue, a gradual suppression of TSH secretion and the development of decompensated FA with thyrotoxicosis.

UKZ accounts for the majority (75–90%) of all thyroid nodules. Thyroid FA is the most common cause of thyrotoxicosis in old age and the second most common cause of thyrotoxicosis syndrome in general. With compensated FA, thyrotoxicosis develops in approximately 5% of patients per year.

Section 2. Diagnosis of nodular goiter

2.1. Complaints, anamnesis, clinical examination

Non-toxic goiter of small size is usually asymptomatic. As a rule, goiter is an incidental finding. In the overwhelming majority of cases, under conditions of mild and moderate iodine deficiency, palpable changes in the thyroid gland are detected only with targeted stimulation following.

In conditions of moderate and severe iodine deficiency, goiter can reach large sizes and cause the development of compression syndrome with complaints of difficulty breathing and swallowing, as well as a cosmetic defect in the neck.

In case of long-term goiter (more than 10–15 years), it is necessary to exclude the presence of thyroid FA, which is one of the main reasons for the development of thyrotoxicosis in iodine-deficient regions.

Complaints regarding PA are determined by the degree of its compensation. In euthyroidism and subclinical thyrotoxicosis, FA may not manifest itself clinically and is also a random finding. Manifest thyrotoxicosis in FA often proceeds atypically, usually manifesting itself in complaints of cardiac arrhythmias.

The medical history should necessarily take into account the patient's region of residence, family history of thyroid diseases, dietary patterns, and use of iodine-containing medications.

A clinical (physical) examination of a patient with nodular goiter should include an assessment of local signs (voice changes, dysphagia, vocal cord paralysis, etc.), signs of thyroid dysfunction, medical history of interventions on

the thyroid gland, family history, including the presence of nodular goiter and medullary cancer in relatives, previous irradiation of the head and neck area, living in conditions of iodine deficiency. Palpation reveals nodes, usually more than 1 cm.

With retrosternal nodular/multinodular goiter and large goiter, deformation of the neck may be observed, and sometimes, due to compression syndrome, swelling of the neck veins. To assess the degree of thyroid enlargement by palpation, the World Health Organization - WHO (2001) recommends the following classification:

- 0 th (zero) degree – no goiter (the volume of each lobe does not exceed the volume of the distal phalanx of the subject's thumb);
- 1st degree – the goiter is palpable, but not visible when the neck is in normal position. This also includes nodular formations that do not lead to enlargement of the gland itself;
- 2nd degree – the goiter is clearly visible in the normal position of the neck

It is important to note that the dimensions of the thyroid gland determined by palpation do not always coincide with the true ones, for example, due to the low location of the thyroid gland itself or the substernal goiter. Palpation of the thyroid gland should be accompanied by palpation examination of the cervical lymph nodes.

The characteristics of the number of nodules are also taken into account:

- nodular goiter is the only encapsulated formation in the thyroid gland (solitary node);
- multinodular goiter – multiple encapsulated nodular formations in the thyroid gland, not fused to each other;
- conglomerate nodular goiter – several encapsulated formations in the thyroid gland, fused to each other and forming a conglomerate;
- diffuse nodular (mixed) goiter – nodes (nodule) against the background of diffuse enlargement of the thyroid gland.

2.2. Laboratory diagnostics

If a thyroid nodule is detected in a patient, determination of the basal TSH level is indicated. If a reduced TSH level is detected, the level of free thyroxine (f. T4) and free triiodothyronine (f. T3) is additionally determined; if an elevated TSH is detected, the level of f. T4.

Determining the level of thyroglobulin, as well as antibodies to the thyroid gland in nodular goiter at the initial stage of diagnosis is not indicated. For

differential diagnosis of thyrotoxicosis syndrome, determination of antibodies to the TSH receptor is indicated.

To confidently exclude medullary cancer, it is recommended to determine the level of basal calcitonin; it is indicated for nodular goiter in children, adolescents, young people, with a family history of medullary cancer, suspicious ultrasound (US) characteristics of a nodular formation in terms of malignancy. - natural risk.

2.3. Instrumental diagnostics

Ultrasound is the most common method for visualizing the thyroid gland and its structural pathology. Despite the high sensitivity in detecting thyroid nodules, ultrasound is not a screening method, as it leads to the identification of a huge number of non-palpable incidentalomas. This approach is not justified either from a medical or economic point of view.

An absolute indication for ultrasound is a change in the thyroid gland according to palpation and/or functional disorders of the thyroid gland according to hormonal examination, as well as a history of radiation therapy to the head and neck, a family history of thyroid cancer, and enlarged regional lymph nodes of unknown origin.

TIRADS classification. The main task of ultrasound in nodular goiter is to determine the indications for fine-needle aspiration biopsy (FNA) and navigation control over its implementation.

The ultrasound protocol should include a description of the location and size of the thyroid mass and lymph nodes, taking into account their ultrasound characteristics: structure, echogenicity, contours, presence of additional inclusions.

Since 2009, a new classification system for thyroid nodules depending on malignancy risk stratification - TIRADS (Thyroid imaging reporting and data system for US features of nodules Horvath et al.) has been used in practical healthcare.

In 2011, this classification was modified by Kwak et al. Currently, EU-TIRADS is being increasingly used. This classification reflects the risk of malignancy, expressed as a percentage (see table). The main disadvantages of this approach in everyday clinical practice are subjectivity and direct dependence on the qualifications of the doctor conducting the examination, as well as slight variability in the assessment of ultrasound categories and subcategories of thyroid nodules according to versions of different authors. Therefore, when describing and assessing the ultrasound characteristics of a nodular lesion using the TIRADS

system, there is a possibility of discrepancies, and the use of classification in describing a nodular goiter is not yet standard for most medical institutions. Nevertheless, a unified, reproducible protocol should have significantly changed approaches to further diagnostics, determining the most optimal tactics for a particular thyroid nodule (biopsy or observation).

UKZ belongs to categories TIRADS 2 and TIRADS 3 (groups of minimal risk of malignancy).

In 2017, a committee of the American College of Radiologists (ACR) formulated its own risk stratification system, a continuation of earlier guidelines. The new system was created to locate knowledge of the most clinically significant thyroid tumors in terms of malignancy, as well as to reduce the number of biopsies on benign nodes.

This technique evaluates such ultrasound signs as structure, echogenicity, contours, shapes, echogenic inclusions. Each symptom, depending on its severity, is assigned points from 0 to 3.

The totality of points determines the probability of malignant lesion of the thyroid formation:

- TR1 – benign – 0 points;
- TR2 – no suspicion of malignancy – 2 points;
- TR3 – slight suspicion of malignancy – 3 points;
- TR4 – moderate suspicion of malignancy – 4–6 points;
- TR5 – serious suspicion of malignancy – 7 points or higher.

Disputable in the updated ACR classification is the exclusion of all nodular formations from the TIRADS 2 category in the indications for FNA.

Fine-needle aspiration (puncture) biopsy FNA is the main method for the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant tumors.

According to numerous studies, the sensitivity and specificity of FNA is very high, and when detecting colloid goiter and papillary thyroid cancer reaches 98–100%. The procedure must be carried out under ultrasound control by a qualified doctor of any specialty (endocrinologist, endocrine surgeon, oncologist, radiology doctor). Carrying out TAB does not require hospitalization or special preparation of the patient. In some cases, TAB in children may require the use of various types of anesthesia, and preliminary consultation with an anesthesiologist and a lawyer is necessary.

- family history of medullary thyroid cancer;
- vocal fold paralysis;

– thyroid nodules accidentally detected during positron emission tomography;

– patient age under 20 years;

– when there is a change in the ultrasound structure of benign thyroid nodes (during dynamic observation) or the appearance of enlarged or changed cervical lymph nodes.

For formations less than 1 cm, if the patient is not at risk for aggressive forms of thyroid cancer, performing FNA is not advisable, regardless of the ultrasound characteristics of the thyroid nodule, except for patients under 20 years of age.

An increase in the size of a benign nodular formation in itself in most cases is not an indication for repeat TAB.

FNA is considered a method of primary morphological diagnosis, but not a method of dynamic observation for cytologically verified benign thyroid nodules.

If a benign cytological conclusion is received from a node with obvious suspicious ultrasound signs, FNA must be repeated as soon as possible.

For cystic anechoic nodes, regardless of size, FNA has no diagnostic value, but can be performed for the therapeutic purpose of evacuating fluid and eliminating a cosmetic defect or compression syndrome of surrounding organs formalized consent to invasive intervention from the child's parents.

TAB does not have any significant complications. Rare complications include subcutaneous hematomas, hemorrhages in the area of the node and local pain that persists for a short time.

Indications for TAB. • thyroid nodules equal to or exceeding 1 cm in diameter (probably, with the introduction of the TIRADS classification into practical healthcare, indications for puncture will be determined depending on the ultrasound characteristics of the nodules);

Cytological examination of the material obtained during TAB

The conclusion of a cytological study should contain a cytological diagnosis, which will allow the clinician to make a clinical diagnosis and determine the optimal treatment tactics for each specific patient. The most effective use of 6 standard categories of conclusions of the modern international cytological classification Bethesda (The Bethesda System For Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology, TBSRTC 2009, revision 2017):

- Category I – non-informative puncture;
- Category II – benign formation;
- Category III – atypia of uncertain significance;

- Category IV – follicular neoplasia or suspected follicular neoplasia;
- Category V – suspicion of malignancy;
- Category VI – malignant formation.

Conclusions containing only a descriptive part, as well as conclusions without a specific cytological diagnosis (“no atypical cells found,” “no data on cancer,” etc.) are regarded as uninformative. In these situations, it is necessary to consult ready-made cytological preparations with another independent morphologist or repeat FNA in a specialized medical institution.

UKZ belongs to category II (benign formations) with a low risk of malignancy (0–3%); rice. 5.

Cytological features of UKZ include the presence of colloid of different densities and in different quantities and follicular cells of polymorphic sizes, often in the form of monolayer clusters. Depending on the degree of proliferation of thyrocytes, UKZ is characterized as a predominantly colloid goiter without proliferation, partially or to varying degrees proliferating and actively proliferating.

With an actively proliferating goiter, the formation of adenomatous and papillary structures is possible, complicating the differential diagnosis. With long-term existing goiter, the smear always contains

There are various secondary background changes - sclerosis, hyalinosis, cystic degeneration, signs of hemorrhage, etc. The severity of degenerative changes can also, in some cases, be the reason for difficult interpretation of FNA data and classification of cell changes into category III (atypia of undetermined significance); rice. 6, which requires a repeat procedure after 1–3 months.

In the presence of thyrotoxic goiter, the smear may show cytological signs of increased functional activity, including large thyrocytes with abundant light cytoplasm and light marginal vacuoles with pink granularity (“flaming cells”).

According to J. Hamburger’s rule, the benignity of a nodular formation can be verified if at least 6 cell clusters are determined in two preparations obtained from different aspirations, each of which contains at least 10–15 “benign” follicular cells. But there are also less stringent criteria that allow for taking only one smear and the presence of at least 3-4 clusters of benign cells with abundant colloid.

Radioisotope scanning

Nodular goiter.

It is carried out for nodular goiter with subclinical or manifest thyrotoxicosis for the differential diagnosis of FA and other causes of

thyrotoxicosis. It is not informative for the primary diagnosis of nodular goiter (for detecting nodes and assessing their size) or nodular colloidal non-toxic goiter, as well as for the primary diagnosis of thyroid tumors. Another indication for scanning is thyroid ectopia, which is usually detected in early childhood.

Computed tomography

Nontoxic Multinodular Goiter

It is carried out in case of a large goiter and/or its retrosternal location to assess tracheal compression syndrome.

X-ray of the neck organs with contrast of the esophagus and magnetic resonance imaging are less informative methods.

Differential diagnosis

Differential diagnosis of UKZ is carried out with follicular adenoma, autoimmune thyroiditis with the formation of false nodes, solitary cyst, various forms of thyroid cancer, as well as with various non-thyroid diseases (median neck cyst, lipoma, thymoma, parathyroid adenoma, etc.). d.).

Prospects for the development of diagnostics of nodular goiter

Currently, research work is being carried out to study immunomorphological and molecular genetic markers in the diagnosis of thyroid nodules. The purpose of the research is to determine additional criteria for the differential diagnosis of tumor and non-tumor diseases of the thyroid gland; and also in UKZ - establishing predictors of growth and FA of nodular formations in the early stages of diagnosis.

Indications for consultation with specialists

In case of compression syndrome, consultation with a surgeon is necessary. If thyrotoxicosis is present, consult a radiologist; if there are contraindications to radioiodine therapy, consult a surgeon. With the development of thyrotoxic heart syndrome and in preparation for surgical treatment, consultation with a cardiologist is necessary.

Section 3. Treatment of nodular colloid goiter

There are no conservative treatment methods for UCD. For most patients with UKZ, in the absence of thyroid dysfunction, cosmetic defect and compartment syndrome, dynamic monitoring is recommended: TSH determination once every 12 months, thyroid ultrasound monitoring once every 12 months or less often.

The goal of radical treatment (surgical treatment, radioiodine therapy) is to eliminate compression syndrome, cosmetic neck deformity, and normalize the functional state of the thyroid gland.

Surgical treatment.

Surgical treatment is indicated for nodular (multi-nodular) goiter with signs of compression of surrounding organs and/or a cosmetic defect, detected by decompensated FA. If there are changes in both lobes, the operation of choice is thyroidectomy or extremely subtotal resection, since with organ-sparing operations the risk of recurrence of nodular goiter is 50–80%.

Minimally invasive methods of treating UKZ

Includes percutaneous administration of sclerosants, cryodestruction, laser destruction, diathermocoagulation of the node.

Indications for minimally invasive interventions are extremely limited. They can be used as a method of choice when the necessary radical treatment is associated with a high degree of risk for concomitant diseases, and as an alternative to surgery for UKZ with a cosmetic defect and uninodular toxic goiter. The goal of these methods should be to eliminate the symptom caused by the dominant node.

Any minimally invasive intervention, along with organ-preserving operations, is a symptomatic procedure. Achieving complete node regression is not necessary.

Radioiodine therapy. It is the method of choice for the development of thyrotoxicosis (decompensated FA thyroid gland). Contraindicated during pregnancy.

Indications for hospitalization.

As a rule, hospitalization is not indicated, except in cases of large vascular disease with compression syndrome or severe thyrotoxicosis.

As a rule, patients with nodular goiter, including after surgical treatment, do not require special rehabilitation measures. The exception is patients with a high risk of surgical complications due to damage to the vocal nerve and parathyroid glands.

Section 4. prevention

For both primary and secondary prevention of iodine deficiency diseases, including nodular/multiple goiter colloidal goiter, it is necessary to introduce state preventive programs. Universal salt iodization is recommended by WHO as a universal, highly effective method of population iodine prophylaxis. In groups at increased risk of developing iodine deficiency diseases (pregnant and lactating women, children under 2 years old) living in areas with iodine deficiency, additional intake of iodine preparations (potassium iodide) is required. The goal

of preventive measures is to achieve an optimal constant level of iodine consumption by the population.

Recommended standards for iodine intake developed by WHO depend on age and physiological characteristics and are: 90 mcg/day for children from 0 to 59 months, 120 mcg/day for children 6–12 years old, 150 mcg/day for under - sprouts and adults, 250 mcg/day for pregnant and lactating women.

For early diagnosis of aggressive forms of thyroid cancer, monitoring is necessary for patients with a history of irradiation of the head and neck and genetic studies in families burdened by the presence of medullary thyroid cancer.

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ZAMONAVIY VAKUUM NASOSLARNI TAXLILI QILISH

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Annatsiya. Ushbu maqolada yuqori bosim ostida ishlaydigan vakuum nasosni taxlil qilingan. Vakuum nasos bir necha xil tizimi ishlari taxlili ko'rib chiqildi. Qo'shimcha vakuumli nasosni taxlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: Bosim, vakuum, chastota o'zgartgich, nasos, asinxron motor

ANALYSIS OF MODERN VACUUM PUMPS

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Annotation. This article analyzes a high pressure vacuum pump. The operation of several different vacuum pump systems has been analyzed. An additional vacuum pump was analyzed.

Key words: Pressure, vacuum, frequency converter, pump, asynchronous motor

Vakuum nasosi – vakuum ya'ni havosiz boshliqni hosil qilish va uni tutib turish maqsadida berk hajm ya'ni idish dan gaz (havo) yoki bug'ni so'rib oladigan vakuum nasos tizimini qo'lab kelmoqdamiz. Buni asosiy vazifasi havoni sorib tashqariga chiqarib beradi. Mexanik vakuum nasosga plastinka-rotorli, plastinka-statorli, zolotnikli, moyli forvakuumlar va molekulyar vakuum nasos kiradi. Moyli yani suyuq forvakuumlar yordamida gaz yani (havo) zichlanadi va atmosferaga tarqatib yuboriladi. Molekulyar vakuum nasos.da. gaz molekulalariga harakat yo'nalishida qo'shimcha tezlik beriladi. Oqimli vakuum nasos.da gaz (havo) suyuqlik, gaz yoki bug' oqimi ta'sirida chiqib ketadi. Sorbsion vakuum nasos kriogen (past temperaturali) seolitli, sublimatsion (qarang Sublimatsiya) va ionli vakuum nasosga bo'linadi. Kriogen qonuniga ko'ra vakuum nasosda juda past haroratgacha sovitilgan gaz sirtida keng to'planadi. Seolitli vakuum nasos da gaz molekulalari sovitilganda seolitga yutiladi. Sublimatsion vakuum nasos.da gaz

(changlangan) metall (mas., titan) plyonkalari qoplangan sirtlarga yutiladi. Ionli vakum nasosning ishi gazni kuchli elektr razryadi bilan ionlash va ionlashgan molekulalarning titan qoplangan sirtga yutilishiga asoslangan. Vakum nasos metallurgiya, energetika, elektronika, kimyo va oziq-ovqat sanoatlarida qo'llaniladi. Turini tanlashdan oldin, biz vakuum pompasi haqida bir necha asosiy tushunchalarni ochib berishimiz kerak. Vakuum nasosda vakuumda gazning kichik darajasi, odatda vacuum holatda sifatida ifodalanadi. Vakuum o'lchagichidan o'qish vakuum deyiladi. Vakuum holatini qiymati atmosfera bosimidan pastroq bo'lgan tizim bosimining haqiqiy qiymatini tashkil qiladi. Yuqorida keltirilgan qiymat, shuningdek, oxirgi nisbiy bosim sifatida ham ma'lum bo'lgan bosimi sifatida ham tanilgan. Rotorli vakuum nasosining mutlaq bosim chegarasi taxminan quyidagi ko'rinishda yani 10Pa. Ichkaridagi bosim har doim tashqi bosimdan juda past bo'ladi, chunki konteynerdagi havo joylanadilani. Shunday qilib, uni bosim yoki bosim bosimi bilan ifodalasa, qiymat oldida salbiy belgini qo'yish kerak, ya'ni konteyner ichidagi bosim tashqi bosimdan past bo'ladi. Judda yuqori mutlaq bosim: o'lchangan nasosni ichki bosim nisbati "nazariy vakuum" dan qanchalik yuqori bosim (nazariy vakuum bosimi qiymati 0Pa ga teng bo'ladi). U nazariy holatning absolyut vakuum bosimi bilan taqqoslanadigan ob'ekt. Jarayonning cheklovlari tufayli, biz ichki bosimni 0Pa ning mutlaq vakusa aylantira olmaymiz. Shuning uchun vakuum nasosining vakuum qiymati nazariy vakuum qiymatidan yuqori. Shunday qilib mutlaq vakuumda qiymati oldida salbiy belgilar yo'q. Nasosi: nasosi nasos tezligining o'lchovidir. Umumiy birliklar L / S va $m \text{ kub} / \text{soat}$. Bu qochqinning tezligini qoplaydigan parametr. Nazariy nuqtai nazardan, nima uchun, nazariy jihatdan, bir xil miqdordagi konteynerni pompalamoqni tushunish qiyin emas, ko'p miqdordagi havoga ega bo'lgan vakuum pompasi biz kerakli vakuumni osongina olishimiz mumkin edi, biroq kichik miqdordagi havoga ega bo'lgan vakuum pompasi Biz xohlagan vakuum. Quvurlarning yoki konteynerlarning havo oqishidan mutlaqo asrashi har doim imkoni bo'lmaganligi sababli, havo oqimi tufayli vujudga kelgan vakuumni kamaytirish omili uchun katta miqdordagi havo pompalanadi. Shu sababli, havo juda katta miqdorda ideal vakuumga pompalanmasi juda osondir. Bu erda vakuum nasoslarni nazariy miqdorini hisoblashda biz vakuum nasosini yuqori darajada bo'lgan nasos bilan tanlashga harakat qilamiz. Nasos miqdorining aniq hisoblash formula quyida tavsiflanadi.

Vakuumning asosiy parametrlaridan so'ng mutlaq bosim va nisbatan bosim aniq, vakuum pompasini rasmiy tanloviga kiritishimiz mumkin.

Vakuum nasoslarning tasnifi

Vakuum nasoslari ishlash rejimiga ko‘ra, vakuum nasos qismi asosan ikki turga bo‘linadi, ya‘ni gaz uzatish nasosi va gazni tortish nasosi. Ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida va ilmiy tadqiqotlar sohasidagi vakuumni qo‘llash texnologiyasi bosimni qo‘llash sohasining talablariga nisbatan kengroq bo‘lib, ko‘pincha vakuum nasossi vakuum ekstraktsiyalash tizimi ishlab chiqarish va ishlab chiqarish talablariga shuning uchun vakuum nasosi assimilyatsiya sharoitida vakuum nasosining turli turlarini tanlang

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ASINXRON MOTORLARNI DIAGNOSTIKA QILISHNING MAVJUD USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada asinxron motorlarda vujudaga keladigan asosiy nosozliklar va shikastlanishlarni oldini olish uchun asinxron motorlarni diganostika qilishning mavjud usullari keltirilgan.

Kalitso‘zlar: Asinxron motor, nosozliklar, diagnostika, teplvizon, magnit maydon.

AVAILABLE METHODS OF DIAGNOSING ASYNCHRONOUS MOTORS

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Abstract: This article presents existing methods of diganostics of asnichronous Motors to prevent major malfunctions and damage to the body in asynchronous motors.

Key words: Asynchronous motor, malfunctions, diagnostics, teplevizon, magnetic field.

Kirish. Asinxron motorla ramaliyotda qo‘llashga chidamliligi, soddaligi va tejamkorligi bilan mashhur. Biroq, ish paytida motorning asosiy qismlari shikastlanishga moyil bo‘lib, bu erta ishdan chiqishiga olib keladi.

Sanoat korxonalarida elektr motorlarning to‘satdan ishdan chiqishi tuzatib bo‘lmaydigan oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin.

Texnik diagnostika tizimi elektr motorlarining texnik holatini muntazam ravishda kuzatib borishni, nuqsonlar va shikastlanishlarni qidirishni,

nuqsonlarning xavflilik darajasini aniqlashni va uskunaning umrini baholashni o'z ichiga oladi.

Elektr motorlar normal holatda ishlashi uchun har qanday mumkin bo'lgan nosozliklarni o'z vaqtida aniqlash juda muhimdir. Nosozliklarni aniqlashni bir nechta diagnostika usullari mavjud bo'lib, ularning har biri muayyan nosozliklarni yoki ularning kombinatsiyasini aniqlash uchun mo'ljallangan. Hozirgi vaqtda elektr motorlari xolatini tashxis qilishning ko'plab usullari mavjud. Ularning har biri o'ziga xos texnik asosga ega. Ushbu usullar nosozlik sababini aniqlash uchun ma'lum qiymatlarni o'lchashga asoslangan. Elektr motorlarini diagnostika qilishning turli usullari 1.1-jadvalda keltirilgan.

1.1-jadval

Diagnostika qilish usullarining afzallik va kamchiliklari

	Diagnostikalash usuli	Afzalligi	Kamchiligi
1.	Vibrodiagnostika	Vibratsiyali diagnostika podshipniklar yig'ilishidagi nuqsonlarni, eksantriklikni va kamroq darajada stator o'rashidagi nuqsonlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi.	Vibratsiyali diagnostika usullari juda qimmat va ko'p vaqt talab yetadi, bu maxsus o'lchash uskunolari va dasturiy ta'minotdan foydalanishni talab qiladi.
2.	Tashqi elektromagnit maydonlarini tahlil qilish	Korpusi magnit bo'lmagan mashinalar uchun qo'llaniladi.	Sanoatda kamdan kam holatda qo'llaniladi.
3.	Teplovizion diagnostika	Ekspluatatsiya xolatida qizishni tekshirish imkonini beradi.	Nosozlikni to'liq aniqlay olmaydi.
4.	Izolyatsiya holatini tashxislash	Nuqsonlar mavjudligi haqida to'liq ma'lumot bermaydi.	Yuqori kuchlanishli elektr motorlariga qo'llash mumkin.
5.	Elektr parametrlarini tahlil qilish	Uchta fazada tok va kuchlanishlarni bir vaqtning o'zida kuzatish va parametrlarni doimiy ravishda qayd etib boradi.	Maxsus o'lchash uskunolari va dasturiy ta'minotdan foydalanishni talab qiladi.
6.	Akustik tebranishlarni tahlil qilish	Eksploatatsiya jarayonida elektr motorning keyingi holatini bashorat qilish imkoniyatini beradi.	Akustik tekshiruv past kuchlanishli elektr motorlarning shikastlanishiga yetarlicha sezgir emas.
7.	Podshipniklar moyi tarkibini tahlil qilish diagnostikasi	Tarkibida temir-metall jismlarning paydo bo'lishi sabab qizish va sinishni oldi olinadi.	Elektr motorni to'liq qismlarga ajratishni talab qiladi.
8.	Izolyatsiya qarshiligini o'lchash	Chulg'amlar xolatini aniqlashda yordam beradi.	Nosozliklarni qisman aniqlaydi.
9.	Chulg'amlarning dielektrik yo'qotishlarini o'lchash	Qisqa tutashuvning oldi olinadi.	Nosozliklarni qisman aniqlaydi.

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10.	Yuqori kuchlanishli impuls yordamida diagnostikalash	Yuqori kuchlanishda ishlovchi motorlar uchun qulay	Nosozliklarni aniqlik darajasi juda pastyu
11.	Sun'iy neyron tarmoqlardan foydalanish	Motor holatini baholash va diagnostikaning ishonchliligi va aniqligini oshirish imkonini beradi.	Bunga boshqa usullarda o'lchangan qiymatlar zarur bo'ladi.

Elektr motorlarda asosiy garmonikadan tashqari, havo bo'shlig'ida son-sanoqsiz qo'shimcha garmonikalar mavjud. Motor barqaror holatda ishlaganda, bu yuqori garmonikaning asosiy manbai mashinaning chiqishlarida hosil bo'ladigan sinusoidal bo'lmagan kuchlanishdir. Havo bo'shlig'idagi vaqtinchalik garmonikaning yana bir manbai elektr motor valida paydo bo'ladigan mashinaning mexanik kuchidir. Ushbu yuqori garmonikalar issiqlik omillari tufayli havo bo'shlig'ida ham namoyon bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu yuqori garmonikalarning eng aniq amplitudalari termal zarbalar vaqtida sodir bo'ladi. Fazaviy garmonikaning mavjudligi va tarkibiga stator va rotor teshiklarining eksentrikligi, rotorning konusi va ellipsi, stator va rotorning noto'g'ri joylashishi, shuningdek stator va rotor chulg'amlaridagi nuqsonlar kabi turli omillar katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Havo bo'shlig'idagi magnit maydonni o'rganish va asinxron elektr motorning kuchlanish va toklarining garmonik tarkibini o'rganish uning texnik holati to'g'risida kerakli ma'lumotlarni beradi. Biroq, ikkala usulning ham kamchiliklari bor, chunki ulardan foydalanishning o'zi nuqsonni aniqlashning iloji yo'qligiga olib kelishi mumkin. Tashqi elektromagnit maydonlarni tahlil qilish usullari elektromagnit maydonning parametrlarini motor korpusidagi yoki uning yaqinidagi nuqtalarda o'lchashdan iborat.

Motor korpusining old qismida o'lchash eng samarali hisoblanadi, bu yerda statorning himoya ta'siri kamayadi.

Bu usul ekspluatatsiyadagi elektr motorlar atrofida elektromagnit maydon kuchini taqsimlash sxemasini taqqoslashga asoslangan. Xizmat qilinadigan elektr motori rotorning aylanish o'qiga nisbatan kuchlanish amplitudasining bir xil taqsimlanishiga ega. Nosozlik bo'lsa, kuchlanish taqsimotining buzilishi paydo bo'ladi, uning tabiati yuzaga kelgan nosozlikka bog'liq, masalan, stator chulg'amidagi nosimmetriya yoki oraliq qisqa tutashuv xosil bo'ladi.

Xulosa. Elektr motorlar normal holatda ishlashi uchun har qanday mumkin bo'lgan nosozliklarni o'z vaqtida aniqlash juda muhimdir. Nosozliklarni aniqlashni bir nechta diagnostika usullari mavjud bo'lib, ularning har biri muayyan nosozliklarni yoki ularning kombinatsiyasini aniqlash uchun

mo'ljallangan. Hozirgi vaqtda elektr motorlari xolatini tashxis qilishning ko'plab usullari mavjud. Ularning har biri o'ziga xos texnik asosga ega.

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GROWTH HORMONE – 30 YEARS OF CLINICAL PRACTICE: PAST, PRESENT, FUTURE

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Annotation. *The era of recombinant technologies, which began in the second half of the 20th century, made it possible to produce recombinant growth hormone (rGH), necessary for the treatment of short stature of various origins. The time has come for virtually unlimited possibilities for obtaining rGH, which has served as an incentive to study the effectiveness and safety of rGH use, and to search for optimal methods of its use and dosage regimens. Many years of experience in the use of somatotropin in clinical practice have made it possible to obtain data on its effectiveness, primarily in somatotropic insufficiency in children, to study its effect on the functional state of various organs and systems, and to expand the indications for the use of rGH.*

Keywords: *a growth hormone; short stature; GH deficiency; Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome; Laron syndrome; idiopathic short stature; intrauterine growth retardation.*

ГОРМОН РОСТА – 30 ЛЕТ КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКИ: ПРОШЛОЕ, НАСТОЯЩЕЕ, БУДУЩЕЕ

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Аннотация. Эпоха рекомбинантных технологий, начавшаяся во второй половине XX века, позволила производить рекомбинантный гормон роста (рГР), необходимый для лечения низкорослости различного происхождения. Настало время практически неограниченных возможностей получения рГР, что послужило стимулом к изучению эффективности и безопасности применения рГР, поиску оптимальных методов его применения и режимов дозирования. Многолетний опыт применения соматропина в клинической практике позволил получить данные о его эффективности, прежде всего при соматотропной недостаточности у детей, изучить его влияние на функциональное состояние различных органов и систем, расширить показания к применению. использование рГР.

Ключевые слова: гормон роста; невысокий рост; дефицит гормона роста; синдром Шерешевского-Тернера; синдром Ларона; идиопатическая низкорослость; задержка внутриутробного развития

Introduction. The virtually unlimited possibilities for obtaining rGH have served as an incentive to study the effectiveness and safety of therapy using it, and to search for optimal ways of using it and dosage regimens. Recombinant human growth hormone (rGH) was first synthesized in 1981 by the biotechnological corporation Genentech (San Francisco, California) [1]. Previously, growth hormone extracted from the cadaveric pituitary glands of humans was used to treat pituitary dwarfism [2]. In 1975 N.A. Zarubina published the first domestic monograph on the topic “Pituitary dwarfism (clinic, diagnosis, differential diagnosis, treatment),” which summarized the experience of treating pituitary dwarfs. However, the use of human growth hormone obtained from cadaveric pituitary glands was accompanied by a number of limitations and risks, and the development of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease in patients prompted the search for alternative ways to obtain GH. Therefore, GH received widespread use in clinical practice only in the late 80s - early

90s last century, after recombinant technologies made it possible to produce it in unlimited quantities. Growth hormone became the second recombinant drug to be introduced into clinical practice, following insulin. As restrictions in the production of growth hormone have disappeared, a phase of active clinical research has begun to optimize treatment in terms of dosage, timing of administration and duration of use of the drug. In subsequent years, rGH was approved for the treatment of various forms of short stature and has been shown to improve both final height and influence many metabolic processes in the body including improving psychological and social parameters.

Epidemiology. According to foreign sources, the prevalence of somatotropic deficiency is 1–4 cases per 10,000 children [4]. In Uzbekistan, growth hormone deficiency is 1–2 cases per 10,000 children. The prevalence of somatotropic deficiency in Uzbekistan over a 9-year period (2014–2022) is 17.5 per 100,000 children and is not the same in different federal districts of the country (Fig. 1). The maximum prevalence of the disease was detected in the North-West region - 20.4 per 100,000 children, the lowest in the Kashkadara region (9.8 per 100,000 children) and the Southern Federal District (11.8 per 100,000 children). GH deficiency in children Treatment of GH deficiency in children is the first and main indication for growth hormone replacement therapy [5, 6]. Long-term observations confirm that with a timely diagnosis, children can achieve growth

targets. Many years of experience in treating children with somatotrophic insufficiency at the Institute of Pediatric Endocrinology has proven the effectiveness and safety of long-term therapy with rGH in a large cohort of Russian patients. A detailed analysis of long-term growth hormone therapy in 422 patients (202 girls and 220 boys) showed that the total increase in height was 58.4 cm in males and 52.8 cm in females. As a result, the final height in adolescents was treated for an average of 7 years (from 6.0 to 10.5 boys and from 5.0 to 10.0 years girls), was 174.7 cm (173.0–179.5 cm) in boys and 162.3 cm (158.8–164.4 cm) for girls. At the same time, the difference between the predicted final height and the achieved height was only 1.3 cm for boys and 0.8 cm for girls. And for some adolescents, the SDS of final height even exceeded the SDS of genetically predicted height. The metabolic effect of somatropin led to an increase in the overall tone of the body, an increase in muscle strength, normalization of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, an increase in cardiac output and improved bone mineralization. Over the past 30 years, the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan has been conducting systematic work to study the functional system that regulates the synthesis and secretion of GH, including regulatory proteins of the hypothalamus, pituitary hormones, growth and transcription factors, as well as a wide range of metabolic and systemic effects of GH in different age periods. Early 1990s marked the beginning of active study of the causes of pituitary dwarfism.

HGH deficiency in adults. Growth hormone is synthesized throughout life and has not only a growth-stimulating effect. It determines the size and strength of muscle mass, bone mass and mineral density [35], regulates fat and carbohydrate metabolism, the volume of extracellular fluid [36], affects various functions of the central nervous system, and has an effect on immunity. As an anabolic hormone, it is necessary throughout the life of an adult. The life expectancy of patients with pituitary dwarfism without treatment is 20–30 years shorter than the general population. The first placebo-controlled long-term studies on the treatment of GH deficiency in adult patients date back to 1989 [37, 38]. In the Russian Federation, studying the effect of GH deficiency in adult patients with somatotrophic insufficiency began in the late 90s. XX century. Research by E.V. Nagaeva included the study of body composition, selection of the optimal dose of rGH in adult patients, and features of the course of hypopituitarism [39, 40]. By

2005, the results were summed up and the effectiveness and safety of the use of rGH in people over 18 years of age was proven (O.B.

Providing patients with growth hormone in the RF. Over the past 15 years in the Russian Federation, all children with proven somatotrophic insufficiency (pituitary dwarfism) have been provided with somatotropin free of charge, which is included in the list of drugs centrally purchased from the federal budget (the current document is Order of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 2738 -r dated December 10, 2018). State support for patients with growth hormone deficiency began on a large scale at the end of 2008, when the “High-Cost Nosologies” (HCN) program was created; initially it included 7 nosologies, including “pituitary dwarfism.” After some time - in 2019 - the program already included 12 high-cost nosologies, and in 2020 - 14 nosologies. At the same time, pituitary dwarfism has always been and remains an integral part of the program, which allows us to fully provide all children with somatotrophic deficiency with the necessary treatment and analyze the effectiveness of rGH therapy. Employees of the Russian Ministry of Health, together with experts - pediatric endocrinologists from the Institute of Pediatric Endocrinology - for the purpose of public procurement, conduct an annual examination of all cases of somatotrophic insufficiency in children in Russia, followed by providing them with growth hormone. Since 2023, financing of these purchases began to be carried out with the participation of the “Circle of Good” fund for supporting children with severe life-threatening and chronic diseases, including rare (orphan) diseases. Starting from 2022, adults with newly diagnosed GH deficiency, as well as young people over 18 years of age with somatotrophic insufficiency, after retesting and confirmation of somatotrophic insufficiency, have the opportunity to provide rGH within the framework of the “14 high-cost nosologies” program. Adolescents with a confirmed molecular genetic cause of the disease and a number of other conditions specified in the Consensus on the diagnosis of somatotrophic deficiency are not subject to retesting [32]. The registry of patients with somatotrophic deficiency at the end of 2023 included 4639 patients (4520 children and 119 adults).

Growth hormone in diseases not related to somatotrophic insufficiency.

New advances have led to increased clinical use of growth hormone, opening up new possibilities for treating other forms of short stature. This is important

progress that cannot be ignored. Back in 1983, at the International Conference on the Use of Growth Hormone, the question arose about the need for its use in short children who do not have GH deficiency. The availability of rGH has allowed research into its effectiveness for various non-pituitary causes of short stature. The goal of therapy for short children without somatotropic insufficiency is to increase the growth rate and normalize linear growth without affecting the underlying causes of their disease. Recombinant GH is used in a variety of conditions, such as syndromic short stature (eg, Shereshevsky-Turner, Silver-Russell, Prader-Willi, De Gruchy syndromes), chronic renal failure, history of long-term glucocorticoid therapy, intrauterine growth restriction, idiopathic short stature, juvenile idiopathic arthritis, diseases of the hematopoietic system, neurofibromatosis, cystic fibrosis, etc. In all these diseases, short stature is not caused by somatotropic deficiency; such patients are characterized by a dose-dependent nature of the effectiveness of GH and very careful monitoring is carried out.

INTRAuterine growth retardation (IUGR). Short stature caused by intrauterine growth retardation is identified as a separate nosology. The first large randomized trial of long-term use of rGH in this cohort of children dates back to 1990. A history of IUGR is associated with an increased risk of developing short stature, early onset with rapid progression of puberty, neurocognitive dysfunction, metabolic changes (reduced bone density, carbohydrate metabolism disorders, dyslipidemia), increased risk of cardiovascular disease in later life. The vast majority of children with IUGR experience spontaneous catch-up development in the first years of life. At the Samarkand State Medical University "SFRSNPTSE" of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan, over the past 20 years, observation and, if necessary, treatment of short children with IUGR have been carried out. E.V. Nagaeva studied a wide range of clinical, hormonal, and metabolic features in patients with IUGR [49]. Many years of experience in the use of rGH in children with IUGR have proven that predictors of the effectiveness of therapy are the dose of the drug and the timing of initiation of therapy (as with GH deficiency, early initiation of therapy is preferable) [50].

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ECTOPIC ACROMEGALY DUE TO NEUROENDOCRINE LUNG TUMORS: FIRST DESCRIPTION OF THREE CLINICAL CASES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. *Acromegaly is a neuroendocrine disease that occurs as a result of excess production of growth hormone (somatotrophic hormone, GH). In most cases, the cause of acromegaly is pituitary adenomas that produce GH. Cases of ectopic acromegaly are much less common. The latter occurs due to tumors that produce growth hormone-releasing hormone (GHRH), or tumors of extrapituitary localization that produce GH. The main sources of GHRH secretion are neuroendocrine tumors (NETs) of the lungs and pancreas. Treatment of ectopic acromegaly consists of surgical removal of the source of overproduction of GHRH, and if radical removal is not possible, long-acting somatostatin analogues, pegvisomant, chemotherapy, immunotherapy, and radiation therapy are used. This article describes three clinical cases of ectopic acromegaly due to GHRH-producing pulmonary NETs, each of which is notable for a number of features. In the first two cases, acromegaly had a mild course and mild clinical manifestations, while in case 2 there was a combination of ectopic acromegaly and primary hyperparathyroidism. In case 3, ectopic acromegaly was combined with a pituitary macroadenoma, and after surgical treatment of NET, remission of acromegaly did not occur. In all three cases, pulmonary NETs were discovered incidentally during chest X-ray examination for other conditions.*

Key words: *ectopic acromegaly; neuroendocrine tumors; growth hormone-releasing hormone; primary hyperparathyroidism; pituitary macroadenoma.*

ЭКТОПИЧЕСКАЯ АКРОМЕГАЛИЯ НА ФОНЕ НЕЙРОЭНДОКРИННЫХ ОПУХОЛЕЙ ЛЕГКИХ: ПЕРВОЕ ОПИСАНИЕ ТРЕХ КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ СЛУЧАЕВ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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Аннотация. Акромегалия – нейроэндокринное заболевание, вызванное избыточной выработкой гормона роста (ГР). Чаще всего причиной акромегалии являются аденомы гипофиза, продуцирующие ГР. Эктопическая акромегалия встречается реже и может быть вызвана опухолями, выделяющими ГР или ГРГР. Источниками избыточной секреции GHRH могут быть нейроэндокринные опухоли легких и поджелудочной железы. Лечение ectopic акромегалии включает хирургическое удаление источника GHRH, а также применение аналогов соматостатина, пегвисоманта, химиотерапии, иммунотерапии и лучевой терапии. В статье описаны три клинических случая ectopic акромегалии, вызванной легочными опухолями, каждый с уникальными особенностями. В некоторых случаях акромегалия имела легкое течение и небольшие клинические проявления. Также описано сочетание ectopic акромегалии и первичного гиперпаратиреоза. В одном наблюдении ectopic акромегалия сочеталась с макроаденомой гипофиза, и после хирургического лечения не наступила ремиссия акромегалии. Легочные опухоли были обнаружены случайно при рентгенологическом исследовании грудной клетки для других состояний..

Ключевые слова: ectopic акромегалия; нейроэндокринные опухоли; гормон роста, высвобождающий гормон; первичный гиперпаратиреоз; макроаденома гипофиза.

Introduction. Acromegaly is a severe chronic neuroendocrine disease that occurs as a result of excess production of growth hormone (somatotrophic hormone, GH) [1]. In more than 95% of cases, the cause of acromegaly is pituitary adenomas that produce GH (both sporadic and familial forms) [2, 3]. Much less common (less than 5%) are cases of ectopic acromegaly [4]. The term “ectopic acromegaly” essentially combines three concepts. Firstly, these are tumors that produce growth hormone-releasing hormone (somatoliberin, GHRH), which, in turn, stimulates excess production of growth hormone by the intact pituitary gland. These include both hypothalamic tumors (hamartomas, gliomas, gangliocytomas), in which hyperplasia and then a GH-producing pituitary adenoma can develop, as well as neuroendocrine tumors (NETs) or, rarely, tumors of a non-neuroendocrine nature of various localizations that produce GHRH [5]. Secondly, ectopic pituitary adenomas producing growth hormone, located outside the sella turcica - in the sphenoid sinus, pyramid of the temporal bone, nasopharyngeal cavity [6]. Thirdly, extracranial tumors that produce GH (for example, pancreatic NET [7], non-Hodgkin's lymphoma [8]). The first description of ectopic acromegaly dates back to 1949, when Goldman described a patient with a combination of a lung NET, a pituitary tumor, and bilateral adrenal masses, suggesting that the lung tumor produced a factor that stimulated the growth of tumors in other organs [cited in 5]. The role of a lung tumor as a cause of acromegaly was first demonstrated by Altmann and Schütz, who in 1959 reported a patient with clinical manifestations of acromegaly who did not experience remission of the disease after pituitary irradiation, but markedly improved after resection of a lung tumor [cited in 9]. In 1982, two independent groups isolated a protein that stimulates the production of GH (termed GHRH) from pancreatic tumor tissue from two patients with acromegaly [10, 11], which allowed us to establish a causal relationship between the development of acromegaly and the presence of a tumor located in an extrapituitary location. By 2012, Garby et al. published a literature review summarizing data on 53 known cases of ectopic acromegaly [12], and Ghazy et al. — data on 98 cases [13]. In 2022, Zendran et al. published a review summarizing data on 127 known cases [14]. In general, in 2/3 of cases, ectopic acromegaly is detected in women [13], and the main sources of GHRH secretion in ectopic acromegaly are NETs of the lungs (typical and atypical lung carcinoids) (up to 43%) and pancreas (up to 35%) [14]. In isolated cases, pheochromocytomas, paragangliomas, lymphomas, thymomas and some other tumors may occur [12–14]. In only two cases, GHRH-producing tumors were not of a neuroendocrine nature (diffuse large B-cell lymphoma [15] and

adenoid cystic lung carcinoma [16]). Among intracranial sources of ectopic GHRH production, mixed gangliocytomas-pituitary adenomas are more common [14]. The clinical picture of ectopic acromegaly does not differ from that of typical acromegaly, and it can be suspected in the absence of visualization of the pituitary adenoma according to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain or in the detection of diffuse pituitary hyperplasia [17]. The difficulty in diagnosing ectopic acromegaly lies in finding the source of GHRH production, and the main treatment method is removal of the primary tumor [13, 14]. If radical tumor removal is not possible, long-acting somatostatin analogues, pegvisomant, chemotherapy, immunotherapy, and radiation therapy may be prescribed [13, 14]. The article describes three clinical cases of ectopic acromegaly due to GHRH-producing NETs of the lungs, each of which is notable for a number of features. In Russia, clinical cases of ectopic acromegaly have not been previously described.

DESCRIPTIONS OF CASES

Case 1 Patient S.N.Yu. Born in 1962, she was first hospitalized at the State Scientific Center of the Russian Federation, Federal State Budgetary Institution “National Medical Research Center of Endocrinology” of the Ministry of Health of Russia at the age of 58 years. She considered herself sick for 6–7 years, when she began to notice changes in appearance (swelling of the face, increase in the size of the feet), weight loss, general weakness, and irritability. During a routine examination by a gynecologist in 2014, acromegaly was suspected and an MRI of the brain was recommended, during which a pituitary microadenoma was visualized. A hormonal blood test revealed hyperprolactinemia (initial data not provided); cabergoline therapy was prescribed at a dose of 0.25 mg once a week, against the background of which normalization of prolactin levels was achieved. In 2015, elevated concentrations of insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) and growth hormone were determined for the first time, and a diagnosis of “Acromegaly” was established. During a follow-up MRI examination in 2016, a pituitary microadenoma measuring 5x5 mm remained. Since September 2016, due to persistent normoprolactinemia, cabergoline was discontinued, and drug therapy for acromegaly was started with somatostatin analogs—long-acting octreotide 20 mg intramuscularly once every 28 days, which she received for 6 months. During treatment, the patient noted an improvement in her health, but IGF-1 remained elevated. Due to poor tolerability of octreotide (induration and hyperemia at injection sites), therapy was discontinued. In December 2016, hyperprolactinemia up to 1098 mU/l was again detected, cabergoline therapy was periodically resumed and discontinued. No changes in the size of the pituitary adenoma were observed during drug treatment

with somatostatin analogues and cabergoline. 68 | Problems of Endocrinology
CLINICAL CASE In February 2017, during a routine fluorography, a mass formation in the patient's left lung was detected for the first time. Multislice computed tomography (MSCT) described a formation in the root of the left lung with clear, even contours, dimensions 44x42x50 mm, heterogeneous density with small calcium inclusions, density 32–30 units N. The formation was suspicious for malignant growth, so in May 2017, a typical segmentectomy of S4-5 on the left and lymphadenectomy was performed at the oncology clinic at the place of residence. According to the immunohistochemical (IHC) study of the removed tumor, a well-differentiated lung NET, Grade 1, with a Ki-67 proliferation index of less than 2% was verified, which is typical for a typical carcinoid. In the postoperative period, the patient noted a significant improvement in her health: return to her original weight (body weight gain of 18 kg), disappearance of facial swelling, and reduction in general weakness. With dynamic monitoring of hormonal parameters, normalization of the levels of IGF-1 and growth hormone was achieved. After MSCT, no evidence of tumor recurrence was obtained. Due to complaints of back pain, an x-ray of the spine was performed, a compression fracture was detected 12th thoracic vertebra, a diagnosis was made: "Osteoporosis of mixed origin" and antiresorptive therapy was prescribed. While cabergoline was discontinued and acromegaly was achieved in remission, attention was paid to the continued increase in monomeric prolactin to 1116 mU/l (64–395). To exclude possible secondary causes of the increase level of prolactin, the patient was examined for gynecological diseases - no pathology was found. Of the possible causes of hyperprolactinemia, the patient has fibrocystic mastopathy. Considering the moderate increase in prolactin levels, the achievement of normoprolactinemia while taking a small dose of cabergoline, the lack of positive dynamics in the growth of the pituitary adenoma, pituitary microadenoma is considered as hormonally inactive. Considering the combination of pituitary microadenoma and lung NET, a screening examination was carried out for possible components of MEN-1 syndrome: no data were obtained for primary hyperparathyroidism (PHPT), space-occupying lesions of the pancreas or adrenal glands. Blood test for chromogranin A - 2.1 nmol/l (less than 2).

Conclusion. Acromegaly is relatively rare in the general population, and ectopic acromegaly in its structure occurs only in about 5% of cases. However, endocrinologists should suspect the presence of ectopic acromegaly in the absence of visualization of a pituitary adenoma or in the detection of diffuse pituitary hyperplasia, hypointense on T2-weighted images, according to brain MRI. The

diagnostic search should begin with the exclusion of NETs of the lungs and pancreas, and if a NET of the pancreas is detected, MEN-1 syndrome should be suspected. Surgical treatment is the treatment of choice because it has the potential to completely remove the source of GHRH overproduction and lead to remission of acromegaly. In the absence of remission of ectopic acromegaly after surgical treatment, it is advisable to prescribe various drug treatment options.

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HYPERPARATHYROIDISM OF VARIOUS GENESIS IN YOUNG PATIENTS WITH SHERESHEVSKY-TURNER SYNDROME: A SERIES OF OBSERVATIONS AND A BRIEF REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

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Annotation. *Hyperparathyroidism is a syndrome characterized by increased concentrations of parathyroid hormone. Etiologically, hyperparathyroidism is divided into primary, which develops as a result of neoplasm of the parathyroid glands, and secondary, which occurs compensatorily, in response to a decrease in calcium levels. Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome may also be accompanied by disorders of mineral metabolism of various origins. The simultaneous presence of hyperparathyroidism and Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome in one patient is of interest from the point of view of the multifactorial effect on bone tissue, however, isolated cases of such a combination are described in the literature. This article describes two patients with Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome and hyperparathyroidism of various origins. Laboratory tests in both cases revealed hyperparathyroidism against the background of normocalcemia and vitamin D deficiency, osteoporosis was also diagnosed, and mass formations of the parathyroid glands were identified. In one case, a series of tests made it possible to diagnose normocalcemic primary hyperparathyroidism, and surgical treatment was performed to achieve remission of the disease. In the second case, compensation for vitamin D deficiency led to normalization of the serum concentration of parathyroid hormone, after which the patient was prescribed antiresorptive therapy. Pathogenetic associations of hyperparathyroidism and Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome require further research, and a group of such patients requires an integrated approach to the diagnosis and treatment of mineral metabolism disorders.*

KEYWORDS: *Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome; primary hyperparathyroidism; secondary hyperparathyroidism; vitamin D.*

ГИПЕРПАРАТРООЗ РАЗЛИЧНОГО ГЕНЕЗА У МОЛОДЫХ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С СИНДРОМОМ ШЕРЕШЕВСКОГО-ТЁРНЕРА: РЯД НАБЛЮДЕНИЙ И КРАТКИЙ ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

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Аннотация. Гиперпаратиреоз – синдром, характеризующийся повышением концентрации паратгормона. По этиологии гиперпаратиреоз разделяют на первичный, развивающийся вследствие новообразования паращитовидных желез, и вторичный, возникающий компенсаторно, в ответ на снижение уровня кальция. Синдром Шерешевского-Тёрнера может также сопровождаться нарушениями минерального обмена различного генеза. Одновременное наличие гиперпаратиреоза и синдрома Шерешевского-Тёрнера у одного пациента представляет интерес с точки зрения многофакторного воздействия на костную ткань, однако в литературе описаны единичные случаи такого сочетания. В статье описаны два пациента с синдромом Шерешевского-Тёрнера и гиперпаратиреозом различного генеза. Лабораторные исследования в обоих случаях выявили гиперпаратиреоз на фоне нормокальциемии и дефицита витамина D, также диагностирован остеопороз, выявлены массивные образования паращитовидных желез. В одном случае серия исследований позволила диагностировать нормокальциемический первичный гиперпаратиреоз и было проведено хирургическое лечение для достижения ремиссии заболевания. Во втором случае компенсация дефицита витамина D привела к нормализации сывороточной концентрации паратгормона, после чего больному была назначена антирезорбтивная терапия. Патогенетические ассоциации гиперпаратиреоза и синдрома Шерешевского-Тёрнера требуют дальнейшего изучения, а группа таких больных требует комплексного подхода к диагностике и лечению нарушений минерального обмена.

Ключевые слова: синдром Шерешевского-Тёрнера; первичный гиперпаратиреоз; вторичный гиперпаратиреоз; Витамин D.

Introduction. Hyperparathyroidism (HPT) is a clinical and laboratory syndrome characterized by an increase in the serum concentration of parathyroid hormone (PTH) [1]. Etiologically, HPT can be divided into primary (PHPT), caused by the primary pathology of the parathyroid glands (PTG) - adenoma/hyperplasia/carcinoma, and secondary (SHPT), representing compensatory hyperfunction of the glands against the background of other disorders of mineral metabolism. SHPT can be caused by a decrease in the filtration function of the kidneys, vitamin D deficiency or disorders of its metabolism, malabsorption (for example, in celiac disease, chronic pancreatitis, inflammatory bowel diseases, etc.), liver failure and a number of other conditions [2]. PHPT is the third most common endocrine disease: with active screening, its incidence in the general population ranges from 0.1 (USA) to 0.43% (Sweden). The overall prevalence of PHPT has been described as 27–30 cases per 100,000 patient-years [3]. It is important to note that with the active detection of PHPT, the clinical structure of the disease is dominated by low-symptomatic and normocalcemic forms, requiring differential diagnosis with SHPT [4–5]. It is believed that PHPT is most common in postmenopausal women [6], although this pattern is not observed in all populations [7]. A number of studies have even suggested the presence of a pathogenetic relationship between the onset of menopause and the development of PHPT [8], but today this remains only a hypothesis. Nevertheless, studying the pathology of the parathyroid gland in patients with hypogonadism is of particular interest. This article discusses two cases of HPT in patients with Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome (STS), which required careful differential diagnosis.

Case description 1. For the first time, patient A. contacted the Federal State Budgetary Institution “National Medical Research Center of Endocrinology” of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan in April 2019 at the age of 31 with complaints of aching bones. From the anamnesis it was known that in 2000 (at the age of 13) she was diagnosed with STS (46Xi/45X0) with turneroid gonadal dysgenesis. For primary hypergonadotropic hypogonadism, she received hormone replacement therapy for a long time: first with ethinyl estradiol 50 mcg/day, then with estradiol valerate 2 mg and medroxyprogesterone acetate 10 mg in a cyclic regimen. The patient also took levothyroxine sodium due to primary hypothyroidism that developed as part of STS. In 2010, according to the words, for the first time an increase in the concentration of serum calcium and intact parathyroid hormone (iPTH) was noted; a year later, during an ultrasound, a formation of the left lower parathyroid gland measuring 14x8 mm was

visualized. In 2014, X-ray densitometry (DEXA) was performed, and a decrease in bone mineral density (BMD) was noted below the expected age values: to -2.4 SD in the lumbar spine as a whole and to -2.6 SD in L1 according to the Z-criterion. Due to vitamin D deficiency, the patient received therapy with colecalciferol. The results of laboratory studies for that period are presented.

Results of physical, laboratory and instrumental studies During the examination at the time of the first hospitalization at the Federal State Budgetary Institution "National Medical Research Center of Endocrinology" of the Ministry of Health of Russia, the classical "stigmas" of STS were not noted - the shape of the upper and lower extremities, posture without features, no pterygoid folds of the neck, height 150 cm. Appealed We noticed a lack of body weight - BMI 17.3 kg/m² (Fig. 1 A, B). According to laboratory examination, against the background of normocalcemia, normophosphatemia, normocalciuria and vitamin D deficiency, an increase in iPTH concentration was noted (Table 1). Renal filtration function was preserved—eGFR according to CKD-EPI was 101 ml/min/1.73 m². At the same time, during an ultrasound, the formation of the left lower parathyroid gland measuring 9x6x7 mm was confirmed. According to the DEXA results, in the radius the decrease in BMD was -2.9 SD, in the proximal femur -1.3 SD, in the lumbar spine -1.6 SD according to the Z-criterion. To determine the etiology of HPT, a short test with alfacalcidol (1 mcg/day for three days) was carried out in the department, against which a decrease in the serum concentration of iPTH to 128.5 pg/ml was noted while normocalcemia was maintained (Table 1). The condition was regarded as SHPT, the patient was discharged with recommendations to take alfacalcidol 0.25 mcg/day and colecalciferol at a prophylactic dose (1000 IU/day). According to her, the patient took the prescribed medications regularly. A year later, during another hospitalization at the National Medical Research Center for Endocrinology, an increase in serum PTH concentration was again recorded against the background of normocalcemia and normocalciuria. In addition, there was a negative dynamics of BMD according to DEXA results. Ultrasound also visualized a formation of the left lower parathyroid gland with moderate negative dynamics in size (16x10x11 mm). The dose of alfacalcidol in the hospital was increased to 1 mcg/day, against the background of which a decrease in iPTH levels was again observed while normocalcemia was maintained (Table 1). The patient was discharged with recommendations to continue taking alfacalcidol at a dose of 1.5 mcg/day, against which clinically significant changes in parameters were not achieved. When examined in 2021, despite long-term intake of colecalciferol 2000 IU/day and

alfacalcidol 1.5 mcg/day, laboratory indicators of mineral metabolism remained unchanged (Table 1). In this regard, it was decided to replace alfacalcidol with calcitriol 1 mcg/day for 1 month. Upon further evaluation of the indicators, normocalcemia, persistently elevated iPTH (130 pg/ml) were noted, and hypercalciuria (11 mmol/day) developed for the first time, which made it possible to establish the primary genesis of hyperparathyroidism.

During dynamic screening for complications of hyperparathyroidism, renal filtration function remained satisfactory (eGFR according to EPI 118 ml/min/1.73 m²), multislice computed tomography (MSCT) revealed signs of left-sided nephrolithiasis, and according to esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGDS), erosive esophagitis was diagnosed. According to DEXA, the maximum decrease in BMD reached -2.6 SD according to the Z-score in the radius and femur. Considering the young age of the patient, an examination was carried out to exclude space-occupying formations of the pituitary gland and neuroendocrine tumors of the gastrointestinal tract: no clinical signs of multiple endocrine neoplasia syndrome type 1 were found. During topical diagnostics (ultrasound, scintigraphy with single-photon emission computed tomography, fine-needle aspiration biopsy with PTH washout), a formation of the left lower parathyroid gland measuring 16x12x9 mm was verified). Treatment In April 2022, a left selective parathyroidectomy (SPT) was performed. Outcome and results of follow-up In the early postoperative period, normalization of iPTH (20 pg/ml) was achieved with transient hypocalcemia (Ca total 2.03 mmol/l). According to histological examination, PTG adenoma was verified. In the postoperative period, the patient received alfacalcidol for a month; when stable normocalcemia was achieved, therapy was continued only with colecalciferol. Dynamic monitoring of the patient is currently ongoing.

Case description2. Patient D., 47 years old, was admitted to the department of pathology of the parathyroid glands and disorders of mineral metabolism in 2018 with complaints of severe weakness, drowsiness, fatigue, and a feeling of a lump in the throat when swallowing. Since 1986 (from the age of 15), she was observed by an endocrinologist for STS, but did not receive hormone replacement therapy. In 2011, she suffered a fracture of the neck of the left humerus in a fall from her own height, after which DEXA was performed, the results of which revealed osteoporosis (medical documentation data were not provided).

CONCLUSION. A decrease in bone mineral density in patients with Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome is a consequence of a number of pathophysiological mechanisms, which are based on hypogonadism and disorders

of mineral metabolism. Among the latter, in particular, vitamin D deficiency/insufficiency and subsequent SHPT, as well as PHPT, can be observed. This determines the need for an integrated approach in the diagnosis and treatment of patients with STS. Of particular interest for further study are the pathogenetic associations between PHPT and STS.

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AXBOROT-TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA XIZMATLARI SOHASI

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Annotatsiya. Axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari sohasi, axborot va telekommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanib ommaviy va korporativ tashkilotlarga xizmat ko'rsatishni o'z ichiga olgan soha hisoblanadi. Bu sohada internet, telefon xizmatlari, televideniya va radiolarni tarqatish, mobil aloqa xizmatlari, kommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va ko'p yillik turli xizmatlar ko'rsatiladi. Bu soha, odamlar, tashkilotlar va davlatlar orasidagi aloqalar uchun muhimdir va innovatsiyalar yaratish, kommunikatsiya va ma'lumot almashishning qulayliklarini oshirish va ijtimoiy aloqalarni kuchaytirish imkonini beradi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Ommaviy aloqalar, korporativ foydalanuvchilar, biznesning effektivligini oshirish, internet, mobil aloqa, kommunikatsiya tarmoqlari, bulut xizmatlari, kiberxavfsizlik

SPHERE OF INFORMATION AND TELECOMMUNICATION SERVICES

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Annotation. Information-telecommunication services sector is a sector that includes services to public and corporate organizations using information and telecommunication technologies. Internet, telephone services, television and radio distribution, mobile communication services, communication networks and many other services are provided in this area. This field is important for the relations between people, organizations and countries and allows to create innovations, to increase the convenience of communication and information exchange and to strengthen social ties.

Keywords: Public relations, corporate users, business efficiency improvement, internet, mobile communication, communication networks, cloud services, cyber security

Kirish. O‘zbekistonda telekommunikatsiya sohasi iqtisodiyotning jadal rivojlanayotgan tarmoqlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Telekommunikatsiya bozorining rivoji milliy iqtisodiyot va axborot iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishini barqaror ta’minlash manbaalaridan biri sanaladi. Ushbu bozor aholining ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy hayotini yaxshilashda, shu jumladan chekka hududlarda ta’lim jarayonlarini modernizatsiya qilishda, kasbiy ko‘nikmalarga ega bo‘lish imkoniyatini yaratishda qulaylik tug‘dirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. O‘zbekistonda telekommunikatsiya sohasi jadallik bilan rivojlanmoqda. Mobil aloqa xizmatlari bozorida raqobatning eng yuqori darajasi kuzatilmoqda. Bugungi kunda O‘zbekistonda uyali aloqa bozori beshta operator tomonidan taqdim etib kelinmoqda. Uyali aloqaning takomillashuvida asosiy mexanizmlarni texnologiyalardagi mukammallik va raqobatni rivojlantirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Muhokama va natijalar. Axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari sohasi, bilim, tekhnologiya, kommunikatsiya va ma'lumotlar almashish sohasidagi rivojlanishlarda katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan sohadir. Bu soha, ommaviy va korporativ foydalanuvchilar uchun bir qancha imkoniyatlarni taqdim etadi va ularning aloqalarini osonlashtiradi.

Ommaviy aloqalar: Axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari, insonlar o'rtasidagi aloqalarni kuchaytiradi. Internet, mobil aloqa, televideniya va radiolarni tarqatish, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va boshqalar kabi vositalar orqali insonlar o'zaro aloqalar o'rnatib, ma'lumot almashishadi. Bu, odamlarni birlashtiradi, bir-biriga xabar berish va ma'lumot almashish imkonini beradi.

Korporativ foydalanuvchilar: Axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari, korporativ tashkilotlar uchun ham muhimdir. Ushbu tashkilotlar, kommunikatsiya tarmoqlarini o'rnatish, ma'lumot almashish va tarqatish, ma'lumotlar omborini boshqarish, shaxsiy aloqa vositalarini taqdim etish va boshqalar kabi turli xizmatlarni o'zlariga moslashtirishadi. Bu, tashkilotlar o'rtasidagi ishbilarmonlikni oshirish, ish bilan bog'liq jarayonlarni boshqarish va kundalik faoliyatni osonlashtirish imkonini beradi.

Kommunikatsiya va ma'lumot almashishning osonlashishi: Axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari, insonlarga birlashish, ma'lumot almashish va aloqalar o'rnatish imkonini beradi. Bu, insonlar uchun kundalik hayotda bir-biriga xabar yuborish, ma'lumotlarni almashish va ishbilarmonlikni oshirishni osonlashtiradi.

Biznesning effektivligini oshirish: Korporativ tashkilotlar uchun axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlarining taqdim etishi, ularning ishbilarmonlikni

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oshirishga yordam beradi. Kommunikatsiya tizimlari, ma'lumotlar omborlari, shaxsiy aloqa vositalari va boshqalar, ishbilarmonlik jarayonlarini rivojlantiradi, ma'lumotlarni o'rganish va ulardan foydalanishni osonlashtiradi.

Innovatsiyalarni oshirish: Axborot-telekommunikatsiya sohasidagi rivojlanishlar, yangi texnologiyalar va innovatsiyalarni olib keladi. Bu sohada IoT, bulut xizmatlari, kiberxavfsizlik va boshqalar kabi sohalarda yangi yondashuvlar va rivojlanishlar amalga oshiriladi. Bu, biznes va ishlab chiqarish sohasidagi innovatsiyalarni oshirishga yordam beradi.

Axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari sohasi, tez rivojlanayotgan va o'zgaruvchan sohadir. Ushbu soha, yangi texnologiyalar, kommunikatsiya vositalari va ma'lumotlar almashish usullarining yanada rivojlanishiga imkon beradi. Quyidagi ko'proq ma'lumotlar bu sohadagi muhim yo'nalishlardan ba'zilarini ko'rsatadi:

Internet: Internet, bugungi kunda axborot-telekommunikatsiya sohasining asosiy muhimiyatini bildiradi. Internet dunyoviy tarmoqlar orqali global ma'lumotlar almashish va aloqalar o'rnatish imkonini beradi. Ushbu tizim, internet saytlari, elektron pochta xizmatlari, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, ilova va dasturlar, onlayn savdo va boshqalarga erkin kirish imkonini taqdim etadi.

Mobil aloqa: Mobil aloqa xizmatlari, telefoningiz orqali ommaviy va korporativ aloqalar o'rnatish imkonini beradi. Bu, telefon qo'llash, SMS yuborish, mobil internet va boshqalar kabi imkoniyatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. G'oya bo'lib, mobil aloqa, insonlar orasidagi aloqalarni yanada osonlashtiradi va ularning har kuni foydalanishini ta'minlaydi.

Kommunikatsiya tarmoqlari: Axborot-telekommunikatsiya sohasida kommunikatsiya tarmoqlari, ma'lumotlar o'rnatish va tarqatishning muhim qismini tashkil etadi. Ushbu tarmoqlar, telefon tarmoqlari, internet provayderlari, televideniya va radio tarmoqlari, shaxsiy aloqa tarmoqlari va korporativ tarmoqlar kabi turli xizmatlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Bulut xizmatlari: Bulut xizmatlari, ma'lumotlar omborini onlayn shaklda taqdim etish va ulardan foydalanish imkonini beradi. Ushbu xizmatlar, fayllarni saqlash, ma'lumotlar almashish, ma'lumotlar bazalarini boshqarish va ilovalarni birlashtirish uchun ishlatiladi. Bulut xizmatlari, ma'lumotlarga o'rnaklashga va ularga qulay va xavfsiz kirish imkonini beradi.

IoT (Internet of Things): IoT, internetga bog'liq qurilmalar va vositalarning o'zaro aloqasini ta'minlaydigan texnologiyalarni ifodalaydi. IoT, smart home, smart city, avtomobillar, soha tasarrufi, tashqi muhit monitoringi va boshqalarda

keng qo'llaniladi. Bu, bir-biriga bog'liq qurilmalar orqali ma'lumot almashish va avtomatik boshqaruvni ta'minlaydi.

Kiberxavfsizlik: Axborot-telekommunikatsiya sohasidagi rivojlanishlar yanada kiberxavfsizlik muammo va qo'llashni talab qiladi. Bu sohada xavfsizlik protokollari, kiber-hujumlar va ongida qarshi kurashish tizimlari, ma'lumotlar himoyasi va shaxsiy ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish imkonini oshirishga yo'naltiriladi.

Umumiy holda birlamchi tarmoq turli fizik tabiatli telekommunikatsiya liniyalari, uzatish tizimlari, alohida kanallar (traktlar), tarmoqni boshqarish tizimlaridan iborat bo'ladi. Xususiy holda telekommunikatsiya tizimi o'zining liniyalari va uzatish tizimlariga ega bo'lmasligi mumkin. Bunday tizimning birlamchi tarmog'i boshqa telekommunikatsiya tizimidan ijaraga (arendaga) olingan kanallar va uzatish tizimlaridan tashkil topishi mumkin. Katta telekommunikatsiya tizimlarida, masalan mamlakatning yagona telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari shuningdek tarmoq uzellari va stansiyalaridan tarkib topadi. Birlamchi tarmoqlarda liniya vositalari sifatida kabelli, radioreleli, troposferali va yo'ldoshli uzatish tizimlari, shuningdek, turli diapazonli bevosita ko'rinishli radioaloqa vositalari qo'llaniladi. Birlamchi tarmoq telekommunikatsiya tizimlarining bir qator muhim sifat xarakteristikalarini belgilaydi, jumladan, uning ishonchliligini, yashovchanligini, o'tkazuvchanlik qobiliyatini, shuningdek, texnik-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini aniqlaydi. Birlamchi tarmoq davlat telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va hamma boshqarish organlari manfaatlarini, shuningdek, mamlakat aholisi talablarini qondirish uchun yaratiladi. Telekommunikatsiya tizimlarining ikkilamchi (kommutatsiyalanadigan) tarmoqlari – telefon, telegraf, ma'lumotlar uzatish va boshqalar – berilgan xabar turlarini uzatish yoki almashtirishni bevosita ta'minlash uchun yaratiladi. Ikkilamchi tarmoqlar telekommunikatsiya xizmatlarini hamma abonentlarga – tizim foydalanuvchilariga etkazadi. Ikkilamchi tarmoqlar soni, tizimni loyihalashda ko'rsatilgan axborot turlari soni bo'yicha aniqlanadi. Har bir ikkilamchi tarmoq mazkur tarmoq foydalanadigan, birlamchi tarmoq kanallaridan, axborotning berilgan turini qayta o'zgartirish, qayta ishlash va telekommunikatsiya kanaliga kiritish apparaturalari, kommutatsiya qurilmalari, shuningdek boshqarish tizimidan tashkil topadi. Tizim (tarmoq) elementlari orasida o'zaro bog'lanish topologiyasiga bog'liq holda ikkilamchi tarmoqni u yoki bu strukturali deyish mumkin. Biz asosan ishonchliligi va yashovchanligi elementlarni ketma-ket va parallel ulash formulalari bo'yicha hisoblanishi mumkin bo'lgan strukturalarni ko'rib chiqamiz. Bundaylarga to'liq bog'lanishli

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tarmoq, to'rsimon va boshqa uzelli strukturalar kiradi. Telekommunikatsiya tarmoq uzellari va liniyalari bilan birga tizim strukturasi muhim elementi bu telekommunikatsiyaning oxirgi uzellaridir.

Axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari sohasi, tez rivojlanishini davom ettirayotgan dinamik sohadir. Yangi texnologiyalar va rivojlanishlar, kommunikatsiya va ma'lumot almashishni yanada osonlashtiradi va insonlUzr bilan, belgilangan ma'lumotlar enagmasi ko'rsatilgan maqsadda to'liq emas. Agar sizga axborot-telekommunikatsiya xizmatlari sohasidagi boshqa ma'lumotlar kerak bo'lsa, menga so'rang va men sizga yordam berishdan mamnun bo'laman.

Shulardan tashqari, axborot-telekommunikatsiya sohasidagi muhokamalar va natijalar kuzatuvchi va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi xususiyatlar hisoblanadi. Bu soha, yangi imkoniyatlarni yaratish, aloqalar o'rnatish va birlashtirish, ma'lumot almashish va biznesning effektivligini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa. O'zbekistonda ham dunyoning boshqa rivojlangan mamlakatlari singari AKT sohasini rivojlantirishga jiddiy e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Respublikamizda AKT sohasining me'yoriy-huquqiy asosini shakllantirish, sohadagi boshqaruv va ijro organlari ishlarini takomillashtirish, AKTni rivojlantirish va uni iqtisodiyotning barcha sohalariga tatbiq qilish bo'yicha katta ishlar amalga oshirildi. Bu sohadagi keng miqyosli o'zgarishlarda, ko'plab loyihalarning nihoyasiga yetkazilganligida o'z aksini topmoqda. AKTni rivojlantirish uchun birinchi navbatda, ushbu sohaga yetarli miqdorda sarmoya kiritish, sohaning xizmat ko'rsatishdan tushgan mablag'laridan samarali foydalanish va ularni o'zlashtirish, yangi va ustuvor loyihalarni moliyalashtirish dolzarb amallardan biridir.

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USING MACHINE LEARNING AS ONE OF THE DIRECTIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Annotation. Machine learning (ML) is the use of mathematical data models that help a computer learn without direct instructions. It is considered one of the forms of artificial intelligence (AI).. This article analyzes the development of artificial intelligence, discusses the use of machine learning and neural networks as one of the areas of artificial intelligence.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, neurocybernetic approach, logical approach, algorithms, machine learning, neural networks

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ МАШИННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ КАК ОДНОГО ИЗ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА

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Аннотация. Машинное обучение (МО) — это использование математических моделей данных, которые помогают компьютеру учиться без прямых инструкций. Считается одной из форм искусственного интеллекта (ИИ). В данной статье анализируется развитие искусственного интеллекта, рассматривается использование машинного обучения и нейронных сетей как одного из направлений искусственного интеллекта.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, нейрокибернетический подход, логический подход, алгоритмы, машинное обучение, нейронные сети.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has a long history that goes back more than half a century. Previously, AI research was hampered by a lack of computing power. The current infrastructure and ecosystem have allowed artificial intelligence to start "thinking." The amount of memory and data processing capabilities, cloud computing, high-speed fiber-optic communications, the ubiquity of Wi-Fi and the Internet of Things - all this creates ideal conditions for the development of AI [1].

Twenty years ago, only large companies were working on AI, now every developer has access to a fast connection, powerful devices and technological infrastructure created by large corporations. Never before has there been such wide access to huge amounts of human data, especially in the public domain. Thanks to all these new introductory materials, almost anyone can do research in the field of AI.

Despite the long history of artificial intelligence development, there is still no single definition and understanding of artificial intelligence.

Intelligence (from Latin. intellectus - sensation, perception, understanding, understanding, concept, reason), or mind is a quality of the psyche consisting of the ability to adapt to new situations, the ability to learn and memorize based on experience, understanding and applying abstract concepts and using their knowledge to manage the environment. Intelligence is the general ability to cognize and solve difficulties, which unites all human cognitive abilities: sensation, perception, memory, representation, thinking, imagination.

Literature Review

In the early 1980s, computational scientists Barr and Feigenbaum proposed the following definition of AI. Artificial intelligence is a field of computer science that deals with the development of intelligent computer systems, that is, systems with capabilities that we traditionally associate with the human mind - language understanding, learning, the ability to reason, solve problems, etc. [2].

Now AI includes a number of algorithms and software systems, the distinctive feature of which is that they can solve some problems the way a person thinking about their solution would do.

The main properties of AI are language understanding, learning, and the ability to think and, importantly, act.

In connection with the evolution of the concept of AI, it is also necessary to mention the so-called AI Effect. The AI effect occurs when observers devalue the importance of demonstrating AI skills every time it actually achieves a previously unthinkable result. So, author Pamela McCorduck writes that part of the history of the field of artificial intelligence is that every time someone comes up with how to teach a computer to do something well - play checkers, solve simple but relatively informal problems - there is a chorus of critics that this is not proof thinking and not AI. This effect is described even more succinctly by computer scientist Larry Tesler, distilled into Tesler's capacious theorem: "AI is everything that has not been done so far."

Since the late 1940s, research in the field of modeling the thinking process has been divided into two independent approaches: neurocybernetic and logical.

The neurocybernetic approach belongs to the bottom-Up type (Eng. Bottom-Up AI) and suggests a way to study the biological aspect of neural networks and evolutionary computing [3].

The logical approach belongs to the top-Down type (eng. Top-Down AI) and means the creation of expert systems, knowledge bases and logical inference systems that simulate high-level mental processes: thinking, reasoning, speech, emotions, creativity, etc.

Artificial intelligence has a fairly extensive history, which originates from the works of Turing, dated to the middle of the XX century. Although the conceptual prerequisites appeared even earlier, in the Middle Ages, when Rene Descartes suggested that an animal is a kind of complex mechanism, thereby formulating a mechanistic theory. In the 1830s, the English mathematician Charles Babbage came up with the concept of a complex digital calculator, an analytical machine that, according to the developer, could calculate moves for playing chess. And already in 1914 The director of one of the Spanish technical institutes, Leonardo Torres Quevedo, has manufactured an electromechanical device capable of playing the simplest chess endgames almost as well as a human [4].

In 1954, the American researcher Newell decided to write a program for playing chess. Analysts from the RAND Corporation were involved in the work. The method proposed by the founder of information theory, Shannon, was used as the theoretical basis of the program, and its exact formalization was performed by Turing.

Since the mid-30s of the last century, since the publication of Turing's works, in which the problems of creating devices capable of solving various complex tasks independently were discussed, the problem of artificial intelligence in the world scientific community began to be treated carefully. Turing suggested that such a machine should be considered intelligent, which the tester would not be able to distinguish from a human in the process of communicating with it. At the same time, the term Baby Machine appeared - a concept involving the training of artificial intelligence in the manner of a small child, rather than immediately creating a "smart adult" robot.

In the summer of 1956, the first working conference was held at Dartmouth University in the USA with the participation of scientists such as McCarthy, Minsky, Shannon, Turing and others, who were later named the founders of the field of artificial intelligence. For 6 weeks, scientists discussed the possibilities of implementing projects in the field of artificial intelligence. It was then that the term artificial intelligence itself appeared - artificial intelligence. And it was after this summer meeting that the "first summer" in the development of projects related to this area came.

Materials and methods

As you can see, after the famous conference at Dartmouth, artificial intelligence has received an impressive development. Machines were created that could solve mathematical problems, beat chess, and even the first prototype of a chatbot that could talk to people, misleading them about their awareness.

All these significant steps forward in the field of artificial intelligence have occurred as a result of serious funding for such initiatives from military research organizations and, in particular, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA), which was created as a shock reaction to the launch of the first satellite by the Soviet Union.

The last and current surge in interest in AI occurred in the mid-1990s. In 1997, an IBM computer called Deep Blue became the first computer to defeat world chess champion Garry Kasparov. In 2011, the Watson Q&A system of the same company defeated the undisputed champions of recent years in the game Jeopardy!

Although this part of modern history is very similar to what happened 50 years ago, nevertheless, the development of artificial intelligence in the modern era takes place in fundamentally different conditions.

The complexity of communication systems and the tasks to be solved requires a qualitatively new level of "intelligence" of software systems, such as protection against unauthorized access, information security of resources, protection against attacks, semantic analysis and information retrieval in networks, etc. On the other hand, the globalization of economic life raises competition to a fundamentally different level, which requires powerful enterprise and resource management systems, analytics and forecasting, as well as a radical increase in labor efficiency. The third stage after the "winter" is also characterized by the presence of the largest open source of personal data and clickstream in the form of the Internet and social networks. And finally, the key historical stop factor for the development of artificial intelligence is disappearing - the most powerful computing systems, which can now be built both on cheap server capacities and in the largest cloud platforms in pay-as-you-go mode [5].

All this justifies the optimism of the people involved about the third phase of artificial intelligence growth. The pessimism of some experts regarding the fact that the field's research direction is again overblown, it is easy to oppose the fact that now the researchers' developments have gone far beyond laboratories and prototypes and continue to intensively penetrate into almost all spheres of human life, starting from autonomous lawn mowers and vacuum cleaners equipped with a huge number of modern sensors, and ending with smart and learning mobile assistants which are used by hundreds of millions of people [6].

Machine learning is one of the areas of artificial intelligence. The basic principle is that machines receive data and "learn" from it. Currently, it is the most promising business tool based on artificial intelligence.

Fig. 1. Types of machine learning

Results

Machine learning is a comprehensive application of statistics to find patterns in data and create the necessary forecasts based on them. Machine learning uses algorithms that allow a computer to draw conclusions based on available data [7]. Machine learning assumes that

instead of creating programs manually using a special set of commands to perform a certain task, the machine is trained using a large amount of data and algorithms that give it the opportunity to learn how to perform this task independently or with the help of a so-called "teacher" (examples, training data) (Fig. 1.).

Deep learning is a subset of machine learning. It uses some machine learning techniques to solve real-world problems using neural networks that can mimic human decision-making.

Until recently, AI scientists avoided neural networks, although they have been known for a long time. Even the most basic neural networks required very powerful calculations. However, in the mid-2000s, it became possible to demonstrate the principles of multi-layered "deep learning" in practice, taking into account the available computer resources. The term itself gained popularity after the publication of Jeffrey Hinton and Ruslan Salakhutdinov, in which they showed that it is possible to effectively pre-train a multilayer neural network if you train each layer separately, and then retrain using the error back propagation method.

The breakthrough became possible when it became possible to make neural networks gigantic in size by increasing the number of layers and neurons. This allowed a huge amount of data to be passed through them to train the system, and that very depth was added to the training.

In the last few years, there has been an explosion of interest in neural networks, which are successfully used in a wide variety of fields - business, medicine, engineering, geology, physics. Neural networks have become a practice wherever it is necessary to solve forecasting, classification or management problems. Such an impressive success is determined by several reasons.

Neural networks are attractive from an intuitive point of view, because they are based on a primitive biological model of nervous systems. As we have already noted, neural networks arose from research in the field of artificial intelligence, namely from attempts to reproduce the ability of biological nervous systems to learn and correct mistakes by modeling the low-level structure of the brain. The signaling system of a biological neural network, based on the intensity of the signal received by a neuron (and, consequently, the possibility of its activation), strongly depends on the activity of synapses [8].

Thus, being built from a very large number of very simple elements (each of which takes a weighted sum of input signals and, if the total input exceeds a certain level, transmits a binary signal further), the brain is able to solve extremely complex tasks.

An artificial neural network (INS) is a mathematical model, as well as its software or hardware embodiment, built on the principle of organization and functioning of biological neural networks - networks of nerve cells of a living organism [9].

Discussions

After the development of learning algorithms, the resulting models began to be used for practical purposes.

Agricultural industry. Artificial intelligence is used to control the condition of plants, the level of humidity, the presence of necessary nutrients in the soil and, in principle, for proper care of plantings. For example, robots have learned to identify weeds and carefully get rid of them (pulling them out or treating them with chemicals). Smart assistants are able to identify

diseases of plants or pests attacking them from photographs, as well as deliver the necessary drugs point-by-point. This helps to use pesticides and herbicides more economically.

Industry. In industry, artificial intelligence makes it possible to make work more and more automated, to the point that human participation is practically no longer required. In particular, LG plans to open a factory in 2023, where all processes - from the purchase of consumables to the control of products and their shipment - will be carried out using artificial intelligence. The AI will also monitor the wear and tear of equipment, the fulfillment of set plans and other factors that a person usually monitors.

Medicine. Here, smart assistants not only give advice to doctors, but also determine a predisposition to diseases or identify them at very early stages, when they can hide from the human eye.

Safety. The work of the police and firefighters already involves the use of artificial intelligence. The cameras installed in London not only record the fact of the crime, but also independently prepare documents for sending to the prosecutor's office.

Home appliances. A smart home regulates the temperature in the room, launches the necessary equipment and performs dozens more useful functions.

Education. The use of artificial intelligence in this industry makes it possible to automate the verification of tests, as well as to develop advanced knowledge transfer techniques.

Banks and finance. Machine technologies detect fraudulent transactions and recognize questionable algorithms.

Personnel management. AI is already being used to process resumes, conduct interviews, and monitor employee actions to prevent fraud.

Marketing. The use of artificial intelligence allows you to collect and quickly analyze information about thousands of users to promote products and services.

Today, deep learning systems such as deep neural networks, convolutional neural networks, deep trust networks, and recurrent neural networks underpin the services of many tech giants.

Since the field of machine learning is a fusion of mathematical sciences and programming, in Uzbekistan, which has a solid base and schools in these areas, there are good chances of obtaining the status of a global player with sufficient attention to this area from primarily relevant government departments in the form of programs and, of course, large private players.

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НАНОПРОВОЛОЧНЫЕ СОЛНЕЧНЫЕ ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ НОВОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ

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Аннотация: В современных технологиях солнечных батарей преобладает кремний. Эти солнечные элементы, ограниченные в первую очередь собственными свойствами кремния, преобразуют в электричество только 15–20% солнечной энергии. Солнечные элементы, изготовленные из полупроводниковых соединений III-V (материалов, содержащих элементы III и V групп), имеют гораздо более высокий КПД благодаря их лучшим оптическим (поглощение) и электрическим (подвижность заряда) свойствам. Кроме того, используя различные материалы III-V на одном устройстве, исследователи могут создавать несколько переходов или гетероструктур для покрытия более широкого диапазона солнечного спектра. В этих устройствах исследователи продемонстрировали эффективность более 40% при концентрированной солнечной энергии.

Ключевые слова: Нанопроволоки, эффективность, оптические свойства полупроводники, GaAs.

NEW GENERATION NANOWIRE SOLAR CELLS

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Abstract: Silicon predominates in modern solar cell technologies. These solar cells, limited primarily by the inherent properties of silicon, convert only 15–20% of the sun's energy into electricity. Solar cells made from III-V semiconductor compounds (materials containing Group III and V elements) have much higher efficiency due to their better optical (absorption) and

electrical (charge mobility) properties. Additionally, by using different III-V materials on a single device, researchers can create multiple junctions or heterostructures to cover a wider range of the solar spectrum. In these devices, researchers have demonstrated efficiencies of over 40% with concentrated solar energy .

Keywords: *Nanowires, efficiency, optical properties of semiconductors, GaAs.*

Введение. Дополнительные преимущества, предоставляемые нанотехнологиями, могут еще больше повысить производительность солнечных батарей. Исследования нанопроволоки стали быстро развивающейся областью. Большой интерес вызывают уникальные электронные и оптические свойства полупроводниковых нанопроволок. Нанопроволоки из определенного вещества могут вести себя совсем не так, как гораздо более крупные «объемные» образцы того же материала [2]. Нанопроволоки представляют большой интерес в фотогальванике из-за их большой площади поверхности, высокого соотношения сторон (длинных и тонких), собственного просветляющего эффекта (который увеличивает поглощение света) и способности направлять поглощение света с помощью специально разработанных матриц [3].

Что еще более важно, нанопровода ядро-оболочка, которые работают на основе радиальных р-п-переходов, представляют собой революцию в фотогальванике, отделяя поглощение света от путей сбора носителей: свет поглощается вертикально, тогда как носители разделяются радиально. Разделение устраняет некогда фундаментальный компромисс между поглощением света и сбором носителей. Включив превосходные фотоэлектрические свойства полупроводников III-V в структуры нанопроволоки, исследователи рассчитывают достичь эффективности, аналогичной лучшим на сегодняшний день солнечным элементам, [4] с использованием значительно меньшего количества материала. Поскольку в элементах на основе нанопроволок используется меньше материала, чем в плоских устройствах, такие изменения могут в конечном итоге снизить затраты.

Эти нанопроволоки синтезируются на платформах GaAs с использованием процесса пар-жидкость-твердое тело — метода [5].

который основан на использовании наночастиц Глода для катализа роста нанопроволок — в системе химического осаждения из паровой фазы металлоорганических соединений. Оптимизируя условия роста, мы значительно улучшили качество кристаллов нанопроволок GaAs [6]. Кроме того, выращивая высококачественную оболочку AlGaAs вокруг нанопроволоки GaAs, мы добились превосходного оптического качества и длительного срока службы носителей. Эти свойства очень желательны для солнечных элементов, поскольку в противном случае носители могут легко рекомбинировать на поверхности и уменьшать выходной ток [7].

Рисунок 1. Слева: Принципиальная схема солнечного элемента на нанопроволоке. Справа: СЭМ-изображение планаризованных нанопроволок BCB, отделенных от подложки. Ti: Titanium. Au: Glod. BCB: Benzocyclobutene. ITO: Indium tin oxide (оксид индия и олова). p, n, n⁺, n⁻: различные типы полупроводниковых материалов. (111) относится к кристаллической ориентации подложки.

Поскольку нанопроволоки представляют собой неплоские структуры, изготовление устройств из нанопроволок требует нестандартных процессов производства полупроводников. На рисунке 1 (а) показана схематическая диаграмма прототипа солнечного элемента на основе нанопроволоки GaAs/AlGaAs с ядром-оболочкой и необходимые процессы изготовления. Полупроводниковая подложка GaAs p-типа и нанопроволоки GaAs n-типа образуют устройство p-n-перехода подложка-нанопроволока. Бензоциклобутеновый резист (BCB), нанесенный методом центрифугирования и термического отверждения, выравнивает вертикально стоящие нанопроволоки на подложке. Мы выбрали BCB из-за его превосходных характеристик выравнивания, таких как равномерное покрытие, а также превосходных передающих и изоляционных свойств [8]. Реактивное ионное травление с индуктивно-связанной плазмой газовой

смесью гексафторида серы и кислорода (SF_6/O_2) протравливает ВСВ обратно, чтобы обнажить кончики нанопроволок для верхних контактов. Наконец, распыление и электронно-лучевое испарение образуют прозрачный слой оксида индия и олова толщиной 200 нм и слой титана/олова (10 нм/200 нм) в качестве верхних n- и нижних p-контактов соответственно.

Рис. 2. Полупроводниковая подложка GaAs p-типа

Мы измерили хорошую эффективность преобразования энергии в 3,56% в этих первоначальных устройствах на основе нанопроволоки. Мы ожидаем, что при дальнейшей оптимизации геометрии нанопроволок, процедур выращивания и обработки эффективность значительно повысится [9]. Мы также обнаружили, что можно отклеить часть лежащей под пластиной пластины, оставив ленту нанопроволок надежно встроенной в слой полимера: см. рисунок 1(b). Эта технология открывает большие перспективы для создания гибких и легких солнечных элементов на основе нанопроволоки. Сокращение использования материалов и повторное использование подложек также должны помочь снизить затраты. Такие солнечные элементы могут быть интегрированы в такие поверхности, как одежда и ткани, а не установлены на них.

Заключение. Этот метод открывает огромные возможности для изучения различных конструкций солнечных элементов на основе нанопроводов и дальнейшего использования уникальных свойств 1D-наноструктур в высокоэффективных фотоэлектрических устройствах.

Нанопроволочные солнечные элементы демонстрируют большие перспективы для фотоэлектрических систем следующего поколения. Однако решение многих проблем, связанных с новыми материалами и устройствами, возникающими из-за этих нетрадиционных наноструктур, потребует более зрелых инструментов моделирования, производства и определения характеристик. Исследователи должны сосредоточить свое внимание на этих целях, чтобы создать высокопроизводительные устройства, которые найдут применение в повседневной жизни.

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ASSESSING ACCURACY USING THE IXELL METER FOR GLYCEMIC CONTROL IN SICK CHILDREN WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation. *Determination of blood glucose concentration -one of the most common tests performed by clinical diagnostic laboratories. In addition to various laboratory methods for measuring glucose concentration, there are a large number of portable devices - glucometers, which allow this procedure to be carried out at home. When providing medical care to patients diabetes mellitus, especially in children, the clinician must be confident that the performance of glucometers meets the analytical quality criteria necessary for safe and effective treatment. The current dilemma between analytical quality criteria established by official regulatory organizations and professional medical societies requires constant dialogue and improvement in the performance of diagnostic technologies for measuring blood glucose, especially diagnostic methods at the point of care.*

Keywords: *diabetes mellitus, glycemic control, insulin, resistance, metabolic regulation, biological factors, glucometers, glucose concentration, glycemic monitoring.*

ОЦЕНКА ТОЧНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГЛЮКОМЕТРА IXELL ДЛЯ КОНТРОЛЯ ГЛИКЕМИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ ДЕТЕЙ САХАРНЫМ ДИАБЕТОМ

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Аннотация. *Определение концентрации глюкозы в крови – одно из наиболее распространенных исследований, проводимых клинико-диагностическими лабораториями. Помимо различных лабораторных методов измерения концентрации глюкозы, существует большое количество портативных приборов – глюкометров, позволяющих проводить эту процедуру в домашних условиях. При оказании медицинской помощи больным сахарным диабетом, особенно детям, врач-клиницист должен быть уверен, что характеристики глюкометров соответствуют аналитическим критериям качества, необходимым для безопасного и эффективного лечения. Современная дилемма между критериями качества анализа, установленными официальными регулирующими организациями и профессиональными медицинскими обществами, требует постоянного диалога и совершенствования эффективности диагностических технологий измерения уровня глюкозы в крови, особенно методов диагностики на месте оказания медицинской помощи.*

Ключевые слова: *сахарный диабет, гликемический контроль, инсулин, резистентность, метаболическая регуляция, биологические факторы, глюкометры, концентрация глюкозы, гликемический мониторинг.*

Introduction. The influence of analytical, preanalytical and biological factors contributes to the creation of the so-called uncertainty budget, which often exceeds the requirements of medical professionals for the safe diagnosis and monitoring of diseases [2]. In accordance with the requirements of the latest version of ISO 22870, the clinical diagnostic laboratory should be responsible for the measurement of glucose using glucometers and other equipment [3].

Effective and high-quality laboratory monitoring of glycemia using diagnostic devices near the patient in everyday life is most often carried out using self-determination of glucose concentration carried out directly by patients with diabetes at home. Modern laboratory medicine recommends comparing the performance characteristics of glucometers to study the quality of their work and assess the comparability of blood glucose measurement results [4].

Target. Assessing the accuracy of a medical device Portable blood glucose meter with single-use electrochemical strip PKG-03 IXELL for glycemic control in children with diabetes mellitus.

Methods. Study design. A single-center, single-stage, selective, controlled, non-randomized study was conducted. Eligibility criteria The clinical study included 105 children aged 1 month to 17 years with type 1 diabetes mellitus diagnosed in accordance with the standards of medical care for patients with diabetes mellitus (2019) [5]. All patients were examined in a specialized endocrinology hospital; the basic diagnostic complex, in addition to the assessment of medical history and physical examination methods, included a daily glycemic profile and determination of glycosylated hemoglobin. Indicators of glycosylated hemoglobin were 7-11%, the concentration of glucose in the blood fluctuated within 2.5-27.5 mmol/l.

Glycemic parameters were assessed during dynamic monitoring of patients undergoing hospital treatment for 3 to 7 days. All patients received insulin therapy and did not have significant metabolic imbalances (decompensated ketoacidosis). Duration of the study. Patients were recruited from 07/01/23 to 08/31/23. Description of medical intervention. In all patients, glycemia was determined in the same drop of capillary blood using the tested IXELL glucometer and the SUPER GL laboratory glucose and lactate analyzer (in vitro diagnostics). To assess the accuracy of the readings, the manufacturer provided portable blood glucose concentration meters with a single-use electrochemical strip PKG-03 IXELL (included in the state register of measuring instruments (registration number 46361-11)) and test strips of three different series. The IXELL glucometer works on the principle of glucose oxidase measurement and calibrated using

whole capillary blood [6]. Indicators obtained using the automatic glucose and lactate analyzer SUPER GL (Germany) were taken as reference values. The SUPER GL automatic analyzer is designed for serial research and has the function of measuring emergency samples. The operating principle of the analyzer is electrochemical and is calibrated using whole capillary blood. Main outcome of the study Acceptability of measurement error limits glycemia with a portable blood glucose concentration meter with a single-use electrochemical strip PKG-03 IXELL in accordance with the requirements Ethical review All patients over 15 years of age and parents of patients under 15 years of age gave informed written voluntary consent to participate in this study.

The results of the entire accuracy measurement interval of the IXELL system are presented graphically in Fig. 3 and in table. 4. The lowest reference glucose value is <5.55 mmol/l with an interval of ± 0.83 mmol/l, the highest is ≥ 5.55 mmol/l with an interval of $\pm 15\%$. The total number of acceptable values was 639 out of 660, therefore 96.8% of the values were within the system's accuracy criteria. Additional Study Findings All capillary blood samples replaced with modified samples in which glucose concentrations were increased or decreased to achieve the required distribution were included in the total number of study samples (n=660). Adverse events When conducting a study of adverse events no phenomena were recorded.

Discussion. Summary of the main result of the study The ability of analytical functional characteristics was verified and accuracy criteria of the medical device were established. A portable blood glucose concentration meter with a single-use electrochemical strip PKG-03 IXELL, allowing its use for glycemetic control in children with diabetes mellitus.

Discussion of the main result of the study According to the recommendations for monitoring the control of carbohydrate metabolism (ISPAD, 2018), pediatric patients on intensified insulin therapy or insulin pump therapy are recommended to conduct glycemetic testing 6 to 10 times a day. The number of studies may increase when selecting the dose of insulin during the period of decompensation of diabetes mellitus, during stress, intercurrent illnesses and physical activity. For self-monitoring of blood glucose concentrations, it is recommended to use glucometers intended for individual use. Personal blood glucose meters must comply GOST R ISO 15197-2015 for analytical and clinical accuracy.

Glycemetic control in diabetes mellitus, especially in children, requires fairly high accuracy of portable measurement devices glucose. This study provided data

to evaluate the accuracy of the IXELL blood glucose meter in pediatric patients with diabetes mellitus. The new criteria require that 99% of results be in zones A and B of the Harmonized Error Grid for Type I Diabetes [7]. This is an allowance for the fact that manual glucose measurements using modern portable glucose meters are still sensitive to the user's technique. Since it would be unreasonable to expect a match in 100% of cases, the presence of 1% outliers is accepted. In the study, 100% were in zones A and B, i.e. zones of clinically accurate results and safe deviations. Similar data were obtained in adult patients, both in a state of ketoacidosis and without acid-base imbalance [6, 8]. When analyzing the system accuracy results in individual blood glucose concentration intervals, 96.8% (>95%) deviations of the IXELL glucometer readings from the reference values correspond to the zones of clinically correct and safe deviations.

Medical experts have long been calling for more accurate blood glucose measurements. Back in 1987, the American Diabetes Association recommended: “The goal of all future self-testing blood glucose systems will be to achieve <10% variability at glucose concentrations of 30–400 mg/dL 100% of the time” [9]. It is logical to assume that more accurate glucose meters will lead to more accurate insulin dosing and therefore more favorable outcomes. But current meter technology has reached the limit of its analytical performance capabilities, and the development of more accurate glucose meters may result in less usability for patients.

Conclusion. The study showed that the use of the IXELL glucometer in real clinical practice allows for high-quality glycemic control and is safe for pediatric patients from 1 month to 17 years.

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RISK OF AUTOIMMUNE THYROID DISEASES DURING OXIDATIVE STRESS

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Annotation. *Currently, a large number of socially significant diseases are known in which tissue damage is accompanied by the development of oxidative stress. Free radicals play a crucial role in the development of these diseases. Similar processes occur under the influence of sources of ionizing radiation, as well as during bacterial infections. Recently, scientific evidence has emerged indicating a significant role of oxidative stress in the development of autoimmune thyropathies. It is assumed that the synthesis of thyroid hormones depends on the concentration of H₂O₂, which, due to its high toxicity, must be in strict accordance with the activity of antioxidant systems. Normally, many biochemically unfavorable processes occur on the apical membrane of the thyrocyte, which makes it possible to limit the action of free radicals and avoid cell destruction. However, under pathological conditions, enzymatic systems are disrupted and their components become abnormally activated in the cytoplasm, and this, in turn, leads to functional and morphological disorders. A deeper understanding of the nature of oxidative stress and its role in the development of AIT may help identify new methods for its assessment and expand the therapeutic range for this disease. The review discusses oxidative stress, which is the accumulation of active damaging agents (free radicals, pro-oxidants, reactive oxygen species) that initiate cell damage and lead to the development of various pathological conditions. It is based on free radical oxidation of fatty acids, or so-called lipid peroxidation.*

Keywords: *oxidative stress, hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, thyroid gland, autoimmunity.*

РИСК АУТОИММУННЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ ВО ВРЕМЯ ОКИСЛИТЕЛЬНОГО СТРЕССА

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Аннотация. В настоящее время известно большое количество социально значимых заболеваний, при которых повреждение тканей сопровождается развитием окислительного стресса. Свободные радикалы играют решающую роль в развитии этих заболеваний. Подобные процессы происходят под воздействием источников ионизирующего излучения, а также при бактериальных инфекциях. Недавно появились научные данные, указывающие на значительную роль окислительного стресса в развитии аутоиммунных тиреопатий. Предполагается, что синтез тиреоидных гормонов зависит от концентрации H_2O_2 , которая в силу своей высокой токсичности должна находиться в строгом соответствии с активностью антиоксидантных систем. В норме многие биохимически неблагоприятные процессы происходят на апикальной мембране тироцита, что позволяет ограничить действие свободных радикалов и избежать разрушения клеток. Однако при патологических состояниях ферментативные системы нарушаются, а их компоненты аномально активируются в цитоплазме, что, в свою очередь, приводит к функциональным и морфологическим нарушениям. Более глубокое понимание природы окислительного стресса и его роли в развитии АИТ может помочь определить новые методы его оценки и расширить терапевтический диапазон этого заболевания. В обзоре обсуждается окислительный стресс, представляющий собой накопление активных повреждающих агентов (свободных радикалов, прооксидантов, активных форм кислорода), инициирующих повреждение клеток и приводящих к развитию различных патологических состояний. В его основе лежит свободнорадикальное окисление жирных кислот, или так называемое перекисное окисление липидов.

Ключевые слова: окислительный стресс, гипотиреоз, гипертиреоз, щитовидная железа, аутоиммунитет.

Introduction. Most researchers share the opinion that autoimmune thyropathies (AIT) are multifactorial diseases caused by a complex interaction of genetic, hormonal and environmental factors that provoke the development of inadequate immune responses against the thyroid gland (TG) at different levels and initiate a long-term autoimmune reaction. Oxidative stress plays an important role in the pathogenesis of autoimmune thyroid diseases. In this regard, the purpose of this review was to analyze the latest research on this topic and substantiate the connection between oxidative stress and autoimmune thyroid diseases. It is known that oxidative stress (oxidative stress, in English - oxidative stress, OS) is involved in the pathogenesis of such important diseases as atherosclerosis, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic diseases and oncological processes. Inflammatory-dystrophic changes in tissues, in these conditions, are associated with the attack of free radicals from the internal environment of the body, where, for various reasons, their increased concentration occurs and is maintained. Oxygen free radicals negatively affect biological molecules such as lipids, proteins and DNA. However, we should not forget about the important role of OS in the framework of physiological adaptation and regulation of intracellular signaling [1]. The pathogenesis of oxidative stress in OS is defined as an imbalance between the production of pro-oxidative substances and the protective antioxidant system. The most important pro-oxidant substances are reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS). The study of biomarkers of oxidative stress allows us to understand the mechanism of this condition and the pathogenesis of diseases. Currently, oxidative substrates obtained as a result of exposure to free radicals are used as markers of OS, namely: products of lipid peroxidation (lipid peroxide, malondialdehyde (MDA) and 4-hydroxynonenal), isoprostane, as a product of free radical oxidation of arachidonic acid, timineglycol and 8-hydroxyguanine – as indicators of oxidative DNA damage [1]. If we talk about free radicals, then these are atoms and molecules that have unpaired electrons. Free radicals are usually unstable and very active because the unpaired electrons tend to pair with other molecules. Reactive oxygen species include superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical, hydrogen peroxide and hypochlorous acid. The first three substances are formed in vivo mainly by the mitochondrial respiratory chain during the oxidative metabolism of energy substrates. They are regulators of redox-sensitive pathways involved in cellular homeostasis and influence several transcription factors, in addition to the endogenous antioxidant pool [2]. Reactive forms of nitrogen include peroxyxynitrite, which is formed as a result of the reaction of nitric oxide (NO) with

superoxide and nitrosoperoxy carbonate, formed as a result of the reaction of peroxynitrite with carbon dioxide. ROS and AFA are important links in pathogenesis in the development of various diseases. Among them, free radicals play a special pathogenetic role, i.e. superoxide anion and hydroxyl radical (due to their high chemical activity) [3]. For aerobic organisms, a mechanism for removing reactive oxygen species is necessary to maintain life. Therefore, in the process of evolution, various antioxidant defense mechanisms have developed. The antioxidant system is represented by an enzymatic link and non-enzymatic antioxidants (vitamin E, C, CoQ (coenzyme Q)). The enzymatic component of the antioxidant system consists of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase and glutathione peroxidase. The main mechanism of the body's defense against these ROS is the enzyme SOD; its activity is usually sufficient to inactivate them at the site of formation, preventing diffusion in the environment of tissue macromolecules. Dismutation of superoxide anion radicals under the influence of SOD in biological tissues leads to the formation of hydrogen peroxide, which can easily penetrate cell membranes. Hydrogen peroxide is detected during phagocytosis, during the work of mitochondria and microsomes [4]. In the presence of transition metal ions (eg Fe²⁺), hydrogen peroxide can produce a highly reactive hydroxyl radical (*OH). This process is prevented by the main highly active enzymes of the body's antioxidant defense: catalase and glutathione peroxidase. Oxidative stress and thyroid hormones Among all the hormones that act on the antioxidant system, thyroid hormones play a particularly important role, since both hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism are associated with OS [3]. However, the mechanism of OS in these 2 conditions is different: increased production of ROS in hyperthyroidism and low availability of the antioxidant system in hypothyroidism [5]. Thyroid hormones as such can act as oxidants and damage DNA, probably through the phenolic group, which is similar to the activity of steroidal estrogens [6]. Other mechanisms may be involved, particularly increased expression of nitric oxide synthase (NOS) with excess production of NO and activation of hepatic NF-κB (transcription factor NF-κB, nuclear factor kappa-bi) with a subsequent increase in the concentration of cytokines that induce AFC products. On the other hand, mechanisms regulated by thyroid hormones finely regulate oxidative status through feedback. Among them, the role of the proteins UCP-2 and UCP-3 (uncoupling proteins 2 and 3) is emphasized. Data obtained from plants and animals indicate that these molecules have antioxidant activity [7–9]. However, only triiodothyronine (T3) appears to regulate UCP, while thyroxine (T4) has no effect [10, 11]. In theory, this could be

used to treat "low T3 syndrome." On the contrary, estrogens increase ROS production by suppressing UCP [12]. Studies have shown that thyroid hormones affect the lipid metabolism of rat tissues and, consequently, their susceptibility to OS. However, conflicting effects have been noted between exposure to T3 and T4. In rat liver, T3-induced hyperthyroidism has been found to be associated with altered indices of lipid peroxidation, including increased levels of thiobarbituric active substances (TBARS) and lipid hydroperoxides, which are by-products of lipid peroxidation [13–15]. In contrast, no change in the increase in TBARS was found in homogenized livers of hyperthyroid rats by T4 administration over a 4-week period [16]. No significant changes in the amount of TBARS or lipid hydroperoxides were observed in the testes of adult hyperthyroid rats; however, hyperthyroidism promoted protein oxidation in the testes, as evidenced by increased protein-bound carbonyls [17]. At the systemic level, hyperthyroidism is associated with decreased circulating concentrations of α -tocopherol [18, 19] and CoQ10 (coenzyme Q10) [19, 20] in humans. CoQ10 was markedly increased in hypothyroidism and its concentration was shown to correlate with the severity of hypothyroidism [20]. Thus, it can be a sensitive marker of thyroid disease in cases where the interpretation of hormonal studies is questioned in various conditions (due to blood sampling errors and laboratory interference). On the other hand, the results of studies on the relationship between hypothyroidism and OS in humans are contradictory. It has been suggested that in patients with AIT and hypothyroidism, the pro-oxidant environment may play a role in the development of atherosclerosis. The increase in OS can be explained not only by a decrease in the concentration of antioxidants, but also by changes in lipid metabolism, since a significant relationship was found between the concentration of MDA and LDL, total cholesterol and triglycerides. The overall antioxidant status was similar in manifest hypothyroidism in the outcome of AIT, subclinical hypothyroidism and in the control group. Other studies have also confirmed an increase in MDA with lipid peroxidation in both overt hypothyroidism and subclinical hypothyroidism [21]. Data on other indicators are more contradictory. Regarding PON-1 (serum paraoxonase/arylesterase 1, also known as A-esterase), a decrease in the activity of this enzyme was observed in both hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism [22], while other studies [23] did not find significant differences in groups in relation to the control group. Not only increased concentrations of TBARS, but also increased concentrations of antioxidant substances such as SOD, catalase, and vitamin E have been reported [24]. All of these parameters were correlated with T3 concentration, and the correlation between T3 concentration and catalase

remained statistically significant even when values were adjusted for total cholesterol. An increase in TBARS was detected both in overt hypothyroidism and in subclinical [23, 25], however, in other studies these results were not confirmed [23, 26].

Conclusion. We still have much to learn about the cellular mechanisms and interactions in autoimmune thyroid diseases before we can fully understand the pathophysiology of these diseases. According to the available literature data, it can be argued that OS plays an important role in the progression of autoimmune inflammation. Thyroid hormones may have a protective role by influencing antioxidant levels; on the other hand, hypothyroidism can worsen OS. The study of OS markers such as MDA and lipid peroxidation products can be used in the future to confirm the diagnosis and prescribe adequate treatment for patients with autoimmune thyroid diseases [48]. Antioxidants may play a positive role in the correction of metabolic disorders in thyroid diseases, but further research on this topic is needed.

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HYPERCORTICISM AND ACROMEGALY KEY PATHOLOGIES OF VITAMIN D METABOLISM DISORDERS

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Annotation. *Due to the continued high prevalence of low levels of vitamin D in the blood of people in the vast majority of regions of the world, the discovery of the variety of extraskeletal effects of vitamin D, the issue of maintaining adequate intake of vitamin D in the body remains extremely urgent, especially in individuals at risk of severe deficiency. Few studies have been conducted on the peculiarities of vitamin D metabolism in pathological conditions such as hypercortisolism and acromegaly. However, vitamin D deficiency in such patients may occur more often and be more pronounced than in the general population. For the treatment of most of these diseases, it is now recommended to use standard prophylactic and therapeutic doses of vitamin D for the general population, which may not meet the therapeutic goals specific to each disease. This review provides information about the metabolism of vitamin D under normal conditions, and also reviews literature data concerning the study of the possible connection and mutual influence of these endocrinopathies and the metabolism of vitamin D.*

Keywords: *vitamin D, vitamin D deficiency, hypercortisolism, acromegaly.*

ГИПЕРКОРТИЦИЗМ И АКРОМЕГАЛИЯ – КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ПАТОЛОГИИ НАРУШЕНИЯ ОБМЕНА ВИТАМИНА D

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Аннотация. В связи с сохраняющейся высокой распространенностью низкого уровня витамина D в крови людей в подавляющем большинстве регионов мира, открытием разнообразия внескелетных эффектов витамина D, остро стоит вопрос поддержания адекватного поступления витамина D в организм человека. организме остается чрезвычайно актуальным, особенно у людей, подверженных риску серьезного дефицита. Исследования особенностей метаболизма витамина D при таких патологических состояниях, как гиперкортицизм и акромегалия, проведены мало. Однако дефицит витамина D у таких пациентов может встречаться чаще и быть более выраженным, чем в общей популяции. Для лечения большинства этих заболеваний в настоящее время рекомендуется использовать стандартные профилактические и терапевтические дозы витамина D для населения в целом, которые могут не соответствовать терапевтическим целям, специфичным для каждого заболевания. В обзоре представлены сведения о метаболизме витамина D в норме, а также рассмотрены литературные данные, касающиеся изучения возможной связи и взаимного влияния этих эндокринопатий и метаболизма витамина D.

Ключевые слова: витамин D, дефицит витамина D, гиперкортицизм, акромегалия.

Introduction. Significant progress has been made to date in the fight against rickets, the most severe consequence of vitamin D deficiency. However, the prevalence of low vitamin D levels, which predisposes to osteopenia, osteomalacia, muscle weakness and an increased risk of fractures, remains high in the vast majority of regions of the world. In addition, the discovery of the ubiquitous expression of the vitamin D receptor and the paracrine secretion of the active form of vitamin D (1,25(OH)₂D) in body tissues led to intensive study of the extraskeletal effects of vitamin D and led to the formation of new views on its physiological role. In this regard, the issue of maintaining adequate levels of vitamin D, especially in individuals with risk factors for severe deficiency [1]. Sources of vitamin D and the main stages of its metabolism

Vitamin D enters the human body as a result of exposure to ultraviolet radiation on the skin, with food and nutritional supplements. Food sources of vitamin D include primarily fatty fish, as well as mushrooms and egg yolks. In some countries, food products are fortified with vitamin D (breakfast cereals, dairy products, orange juice, etc.). Under the influence of ultraviolet radiation of the spectrum B (wavelength 290–315 nm), previtamin D₃ is formed from 7-dehydrocholesterol in the skin, which is quickly isomerized into D₃ (colecalciferol). Both vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol, formed in mushrooms from ergosterol under the influence of ultraviolet radiation) and D₃ (colecalciferol) can come from food and dietary supplements; these two forms, due to identical subsequent metabolism, are often referred to together as "D". Vitamin D, which comes from food and dietary supplements, and is also synthesized in the skin, undergoes 2 stages of hydroxylation to acquire biological activity: in the first stage, as a result of 25-hydroxylation by the enzyme CYP2R1 in the liver, 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25(OH)D) is formed - the main circulating form of vitamin D, which is used to assess the sufficiency of vitamin D status. Subsequently, 25(OH)D is hydroxylated at the 1 α position by the enzyme CYP27B1, resulting in the formation of 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (1,25(OH)₂D) – a form that can bind to the vitamin D receptor (VDR) and realizes the biological effects of vitamin D. The main source of circulating 1,25(OH)₂D is the kidneys. The enzyme CYP24A1 (24-hydroxylase) catabolizes both 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D into biologically inactive forms [2, 3]. Unlike 25(OH)D, the concentration of which is relatively stable, the synthesis of 1,25(OH)₂D is tightly regulated: PTH stimulates 1 α -hydroxylase, while FGF-23 and 1,25(OH)₂D itself due to negative feedback connections reduce its activity. Changes in the concentration of calcium and phosphorus in the blood serum, including due to changes in their concentration in food, can have an indirect effect on the activity of 1 α -hydroxylase. It is assumed that the process 24-hydroxylation is regulated reciprocally by 1 α -hydroxylation. Since VDR is a nuclear transcription factor, the high abundance of vitamin D-responsive DNA elements in the genome determines the variety of effects of vitamin D described to date on both bone metabolism and calcium-phosphorus metabolism, and on other physiological processes. The classic effects of vitamin D through 1,25(OH)₂D include

primarily enhancing absorption of calcium in the small intestine by increasing the expression in the epithelium of the apical membrane calcium channel (TRPV6), a cytoplasmic calcium transporter (calbindin-D9K calcium-binding protein) and basolateral membrane calcium pump (PMCA1b). There is also evidence that 1,25(OH)₂D can increase intercellular calcium absorption observed with high dietary calcium intake. According to some data, 1,25(OH)₂D is able to influence phosphorus absorption by increasing the transcription of intestinal sodium-phosphorus co-transporter IIb, but it is assumed that the main factor determining absorption of phosphorus in the intestine is the concentration of phosphorus in food [4]. To date, only a few studies have been carried out on the characteristics of vitamin D metabolism in pathological conditions such as hypercortisolism and acromegaly. However, vitamin D deficiency in such patients, according to available literature data, may occur more often and be more pronounced than in the general population. This review summarizes the available data on the characteristics of vitamin D metabolism in hypercortisolism and acromegaly. Vitamin D and hypercortisolism. Data from early studies on the effect of excess glucocorticoids on vitamin D metabolism are very contradictory, due to the high heterogeneity of the study groups. In 1986, Kugai et al. showed that among individuals with Cushing's syndrome and severe osteopenia, higher concentrations of 1,25(OH)₂D were observed compared with patients without osteopenia and the control group; this was explained by increased calciuria, which caused an increase in PTH and, accordingly, the synthesis of 1,25(OH)₂D [5]. A slight increase in 1,25(OH)₂D concentration without a change in 25(OH)D content was shown by Hahn et al. in healthy adults after a short course of prednisolone (20 mg/day for 2 weeks), while intestinal calcium absorption decreased, due to which led to the conclusion that the decrease in intestinal calcium absorption caused by glucocorticosteroids cannot be attributed to a decrease circulating concentrations of the main known vitamin D metabolites [6]. In a study by Findling et al. the concentration of 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D in patients with ACTH-dependent hypercortisolism (Cushing's disease and ACTH-ectopia) before treatment did not differ from that in persons without the disease from the control group (17±6 ng/ml and 44±19 pg/ml, and 24±18 ng/ml and 37±10 pg/ml, respectively), however, after surgical treatment, the concentration of 25(OH)D did not change, and 1,25(OH)₂D fell, in on average, from 44 to 22 pg/ml (p<0.02); in addition, the concentration of PTH, normal before treatment, significantly decreased, tubular reabsorption of phosphate and the concentration of serum phosphorus increased, and urinary calcium excretion decreased [7]. Since the researchers did not find a correlation between PTH concentrations and 1,25(OH)₂D, a glucocorticoid-mediated increase in 1,25(OH)₂D concentrations was assumed; The researchers also do not exclude the influence of changes in phosphorus homeostasis on the results obtained (low dietary phosphate intake may increase the concentration of 1,25(OH)₂D independently of PTH). A glucocorticosteroid-mediated change in the rate of 1,25(OH)₂D inactivation could explain these results, but Seeman

et al. showed a small but significant decrease in the concentrations of 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D and no the effect of changing the rate of degradation of 1,25(OH)₂D [8]. The work of Corbee et al. Identical concentration values of 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D were observed in dogs with central hypercortisolism before and after removal of the pituitary gland, as well as when compared with the control group [9]. Similar results were obtained by Jiang et al. after administering high doses of dexamethasone to rats [10]. In the work of Klein et al. a decrease in 25(OH)D concentration in conditions of excess glucocorticoids was shown in a dose-dependent manner [11]. Subsequently, disturbances in calcium-phosphorus homeostasis became a systematic finding in patients exposed to excess glucocorticoids. It has become known that under the influence of glucocorticoids the complex process of calcium absorption in the duodenum is disrupted. Huybers et al. found that oral administration of 10 mg/kg prednisolone to 12-week-old mice on a regular diet decreased the intestinal calcium absorption capacity by halving duodenal TRPV6 mRNA expression and calbindin-D9K expression [12]. These effects could not be reproduced in other in vivo models, which was likely due to the chosen dose of glucocorticoids and the age of the experimental animals [13]. In addition, glucocorticoids also inhibit renal tubular reabsorption of calcium, promoting renal calcium loss and resulting negative calcium balance. In addition to these effects on calcium metabolism, glucocorticoids cause phosphaturia and reduce tubular phosphate reabsorption by inhibiting tubular expression of the sodium gradient-dependent phosphate transporter [14, 15]. In later studies, it was demonstrated that the development of disturbances in calcium-phosphorus metabolism in hypercortisolism may be contributed by the direct influence of glucocorticoids on the metabolism and implementation of the effects of vitamin D. Thus, in experimental studies, dexamethasone increased the renal expression of 24-hydroxylase [16, 17], and when prednisolone was prescribed, 25-hydroxylase activity was inhibited [18]. Functional cooperation has been noted between the glucocorticoid receptor, the transcription factor C/EBP β and the vitamin D receptor, increasing the transcription of 24-hydroxylase [19]. Interestingly, with dexamethasone treatment, vitamin D receptor mRNA levels in the kidney and duodenum increased significantly during the first day but decreased by the fifth day; these data, in turn, may explain the previously described changes in the transcription of duodenal and renal calbindin-D9K, TRPV5 and TRPV6 [20]. Thus, experimental data allow us to formulate the concept that with an excess of glucocorticoids, vitamin D deficiency develops due to accelerated catabolism of 25(OH)D. The clinical data available to date cannot convincingly support this hypothesis, but it should be remembered that the study groups are highly heterogeneous: the obesity observed in hypercortisolism, as well as other characteristics of patients exposed to excess glucocorticoids, such as, may contribute to the development of vitamin D deficiency. photosensitivity in systemic lupus erythematosus or limited physical activity in rheumatoid arthritis. A meta-analysis of studies published between

1970 and 2011 that did not include studies in patients receiving at least 400 IU of vitamin D per day. with a duration of glucocorticosteroid therapy of less than 2 weeks, with liver or kidney disease in more than 50% of patients, or after transplantation in patients with Cushing's syndrome, showed that the average concentration of 25(OH)D in patients receiving glucocorticosteroid therapy corresponded to suboptimal values (22 .4 ng/ml) and was statistically significantly lower than in healthy controls, but did not differ from that in patients not receiving steroid drugs with an active form of the disease [21]. Taking into account the obtained average concentration of 25(OH). The authors calculated that to achieve a 25(OH)D concentration of at least 32 ng/ml in patients, 1800 IU of colecalciferol per day would be required. The International Endocrine Society guidelines recommend higher doses for individuals receiving corticosteroid therapy (3000–6000 IU per day) [22], whereas the American College of Rheumatology guidelines suggest significantly lower doses: 800–1000 IU per day in the 2010 revision [23].], and even lower – in the 2017 revision (600–800 IU per day) [24]. In the work of Ortego-Jurado et al. compared the concentration of 25(OH)D in patients with autoimmune diseases receiving long-term glucocorticosteroid therapy, additionally taking colecalciferol 800 IU per day or calcidiol at a dose of 354 IU per day. In addition to the fact that a negative correlation was found between the concentration of 25(OH)D and the dose of glucocorticosteroids taken, as well as body mass index, in the group of persons receiving calcidiol, consistently higher concentrations of 25(OH)D were observed regardless of the season (average 35 .0 ng/ml and 24.6 ng/ml, respectively). The authors noted that the dose of colecalciferol was insufficient to maintain optimal vitamin D concentrations [25].

Conclusion. Available literature data indicate the presence of complex connections between hypercortisolism and acromegaly and vitamin D metabolism. It is not possible to formulate a clear concept characterizing these relationships, since there are significant contradictions between the results of experimental and clinical studies. Since determining the optimal vitamin D status and how to achieve it in these pathologies can help expand therapeutic options, research is required additional studies to obtain a more accurate characterization of the observed pathophysiological processes.

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CONTRIBUTION OF CENTRAL REGULATORS OF THE IMMUNE RESPONSE TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THYROID DISEASES

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Annotation. *The specific relationship between the endocrine and immune systems is represented by a numerous number of factors and mechanisms that form the structure and ensure the function of each of the two systems. For example, immunocompetent cells can produce immunologically active substances, as well as some hormones. On the other hand, the immune cells themselves are accessible to the influence of hormones. Currently, the so-called cross-regulation of endocrine and immune mechanisms in the balance of pro- and anti-inflammatory responses has not been sufficiently studied. Among other autoimmune lesions, autoimmune thyropathies occupy a significant place. The development of autoimmune damage to the thyroid gland (TG) is a complex process, which is the result of the interaction of tissue-infiltrating lymphocytes and thyrocytes capable of expressing a wide range of molecules involved in the immune response. Immunological and immunogenetic factors play a major role in the pathogenesis of autoimmune thyroid diseases, such as autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) and Graves' disease (GD). Despite the fact that more than 100 years have passed since the first description of AIT, and HD has been known for many centuries, the mechanisms of development of these pathologies have not yet been fully elucidated.*

Keywords: *thyroid gland, immune response, autoimmune thyropathies, T-regulatory cells, T-helper cells 17.*

ВКЛАД ЦЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ РЕГУЛЯТОРОВ ИММУННОГО ОТВЕТА В РАЗВИТИЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ

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Аннотация. Специфические взаимоотношения эндокринной и иммунной систем представлены многочисленными факторами и механизмами, формирующими структуру и обеспечивающими функцию каждой из двух систем. Например, иммунокомпетентные клетки могут продуцировать иммунологически активные вещества, а также некоторые гормоны. С другой стороны, сами иммунные клетки доступны влиянию гормонов. В настоящее время недостаточно изучена так называемая перекрестная регуляция эндокринных и иммунных механизмов в балансе про- и противовоспалительных реакций. Среди других аутоиммунных поражений значительное место занимают аутоиммунные тиреопатии. Развитие аутоиммунного поражения щитовидной железы (ТГ) — сложный процесс, который является результатом взаимодействия тканевых лимфоцитов и тироцитов, способных экспрессировать широкий спектр молекул, участвующих в иммунном ответе. Иммунологические и иммуногенетические факторы играют важную роль в патогенезе аутоиммунных заболеваний щитовидной железы, таких как аутоиммунный тиреоидит (АИТ) и болезнь Грейвса (БГ). Несмотря на то, что со времени первого описания АИТ прошло более 100 лет, а БГ известна уже много столетий, механизмы развития этих патологий до сих пор полностью не выяснены.

Ключевые слова: щитовидная железа, иммунный ответ, аутоиммунные тиреопатии, Т-регуляторные клетки, Т-хелперы 17.

Introduction. According to the World Health Organization, cases of autoimmune diseases double every 5-10 years. Among the majority of endocrine glands subject to an autoimmune process, the thyroid gland (TG) is affected especially often. Autoimmune thyroid diseases account for 30% of all autoimmune pathologies, including two main clinical subtypes: Graves' disease (GD) and autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) [1–5]. T regulatory cells (Treg, regulatory T lymphocytes, suppressor T cells) are central regulators of the immune response. Their main function is to control the strength and duration of a complex multicomponent immune reaction, immunosuppression through the synthesis of IL-10 and transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β). They inhibit the occurrence and development of autoimmune diseases, providing dominant immunological tolerance to self-antigens. TGF- β inhibits the formation of inflammatory CD4⁺ T helper cells (Th1, Th17) and suppresses the release of their main cytokines – IFN- γ and IL-17 [6, 7]. Peripheral autotolerance is maintained by CD25⁺ CD4⁺ Tregs, which actively suppress the activation and expansion of potentially pathogenic autoreactive T cells normally present in the immune system. When Tregs are reduced in number or impaired in function, their immunosuppressive function is reduced and thus lost, thereby effectively inhibiting excessive immune responses, which in turn leads to an increased risk of autoimmune diseases. CD4⁺ Tregs contain surface molecules: CD5, CD45RB, CD25, CD62L, CD38. Among them, the expression of CD25 is the most constant and provides the protective function of these cells in autoimmune diseases. Foxp3 protein is a key transcription factor that controls the development and function of Tregs and is expressed mainly in their nucleus [8, 9]. T helper 17 (Th17) cells are a recently discovered subset of CD4⁺ T cells primarily characterized by the production of interleukin (IL)-17A, IL-17F, IL-21, and IL-22. These cells and their cytokines play a key role in the development of various autoimmune diseases. According to a number of studies, Th17 cells and IL-17 are closely related to the incidence of AIT and HD. IL-1 β , IL-6 and IL-23, together with the expression of the transcription factor retinoid-related receptor gamma (ROR γ t) and activation of the signal converter and activator of intracellular transcription-3 (STAT3), are involved in the differentiation of Th17 cells. ROR γ t knockout animals exhibit a decrease in the number of Th17 cells and IL-17 expression and, as a consequence, a decrease in the incidence of autoimmune diseases [8–12]. Th17 is a key effector in the immune response and plays a critical role in autoimmunity and inflammation. In turn, Tregs control the overall immune response and maintain peripheral immune tolerance by regulating the activity of

effector T cells. One recent study found that microRNAs play an important role in regulating the pathogenesis of autoimmune diseases by changing the Th17/Treg ratio [13]. Disruption of Th17 and Treg cellular homeostasis plays an important role in the formation of autoimmunity and the development of inflammation. Quantitative and functional “imbalance” of Th17/Treg cells is one of the main links in the pathogenesis of many autoimmune diseases, such as HD, type I diabetes mellitus, systemic lupus erythematosus and rheumatoid arthritis, but its regulatory mechanisms are still poorly understood [2, 14–18]. T regulatory cells CD4⁺ T cells are divided into various subgroups, including Th1, Th2, Treg and Th17 lymphocytes. Tregs, originally termed “suppressor T cells” in 1970, are a heterogeneous population of lymphocytes characterized by immunosuppressive function. These cells regulate the protective immune response through direct cell-cell interactions or through cytokines such as TGF- β and IL-10 [19, 20]. To date, several subsets of human Treg cells have been identified, including CD4⁺ CD25⁺ Treg cells, CD4⁺ CD69⁺ Treg cells, IL10-producing regulatory type 1 (Tr1) cells, and CD8⁺ CD122⁺ Treg cells. A subset of Treg cells was first described as CD4⁺ cells expressing the carrier carrier Foxp3 and IL-2 (CD25). In humans, CD4⁺ CD25⁺ T cells constitute 5–10% of peripheral CD4⁺ T cells and are involved in the pathogenesis of a number of autoimmune diseases. Another subset of CD4⁺ Treg cells is represented by CD69 expression lacking Foxp3. These CD4⁺ CD69⁺ Treg cells mainly exert their suppressive activity through the synthesis of IL-10 and TGF- β [11, 12]. Tr1 was characterized by Roncarolo et al. This subset of Treg cells can suppress T cell and antigen presenting cell mediated immune responses, mainly through the secretion of IL-10 [14]. CD8⁺ CD122⁺ T cells are another type of Treg cell described by Suzuki et al. The suppressive function of these cells is carried out through the cytokine IL-10, but not through intercellular contact [23, 24]. Treg cells play an important role in the prevention of autoimmune reactions, have redox properties (balance of redox processes in the cell) compared to conventional CD4⁺ T helper cells and are more resistant to the pro-apoptotic effects of H₂O₂. This may be due to higher expression of thioredoxin (Txn1), which influences their effector role in preventing prolonged or excessive immune responses and possibly autoimmunity. Txn1 enzymatically reduces a variety of molecular substrates and is itself oxidized in the process. Regeneration of reduced Txn1 in the cytosol is carried out by selenoprotein thioredoxin reductase 1 (Txnrd1). The content of Txnrd1 in T cells and the expression of Treg cell markers are directly related to selenium consumption [2]. Treg cells play a major role in regulating autoimmunity, maintaining tissue homeostasis, microbial infection,

and tumor growth. In malignant tumors, these cells promote the progression of tumor growth by suppressing antitumor immunity. High tumor infiltration by Treg cells is associated with poor prognosis in various types of cancer [2, 6]. Autoimmune thyroid diseases and T-regulatory cells Many studies provide evidence of a close relationship between functional defects of Tregs or their absence and thyroid autoimmunity. In mouse models with a decrease in the number of CD4+CD25+ or CD8+CD122+ Tregs, the frequency and severity of AIT or GD increases, indicating a possible role of Treg deficiency in the development of autoimmune thyroid diseases. According to McLachlan et al., a decrease in CD4+CD25+ or CD8+CD122+ Tregs in genetically modified mice may cause a transition from HD to AIT, which may be associated with accompanying autoantibody responses to thyroglobulin and thyroid peroxidase. This discovery made it possible to determine the important role of Tregs in thyroid dysfunction in HD. It was also noted that prior transfer of CD4+CD25+ Tregs into CBA/J mice under experimental conditions can suppress AIT. The presented animal experiments highlight the crucial role of T-suppressors in suppressing autoimmune reactions in thyroid tissues. A number of clinical studies have revealed a decrease in the number or dysfunction of Tregs in patients with AIT or HD, which is consistent with data in animal models. Several studies have found an increase in the number of CD4+CD25hi or CD4+CD25+int-hiCD127+lo Tregs in adult patients with active GD and in children with AIT, while no significant deficit in the number of Tregs was detected. This discrepancy may be due to different detection markers for Treg cells. For example, Pan et al. chose CD4+CD25int-hiCD127lo as detection markers, whereas the study by Xue et al. CD4+CD25hi markers were used. Different age categories of onset and stage of the disease may also be associated with the number of Tregs [6].

Mechanisms of quantitative and functional defects of T cells in patients with autoimmune thyroid diseases

Under the influence of external triggers, an innate genetic predisposition can lead to the activation or suppression of autoreactive CD4+ T cells of the thyroid gland, including Th17 and Treg cells. Recently, Yan et al. reported that in Chinese patients with autoimmune thyroid diseases, the frequencies of the IL-17F/rs763780 and IL-17A/rs3819025 genotypes, which are associated with Th17 differentiation, were significantly different from controls. It has been suggested that the single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) IL-17F/rs763780 may influence susceptibility to autoimmune thyroid diseases, and IL 17A/rs3819025 is likely a

protective factor for GD. In addition, IL-23R SNPs, including rs2201841, rs10889677 and rs7530511, have been shown to be associated with OH in Caucasian patients. These variants may predispose to OH by altering the expression and/or function of IL-23R, thereby promoting the Th17 differentiation process. Moreover, many studies have reported increased expression of IL-6 in HD and OH groups. IL-6, which is induced by IL-1 β , is particularly important because it shifts the balance of Th17 and Treg cells towards Th17.

Conclusion. The specific relationship between the endocrine and immune systems is irrefutable. Various studies have shown that Th17 and Treg deficiency and dysfunction are closely associated with thyroid autoimmunity and the severity of thyroid autoimmune diseases. The main mechanisms in this case are: genetic predisposition, certain biological molecules (eg, MB, SLAMF1), microelement status, and possibly the composition of the intestinal microbiota. T cells may be targeted in the development of new ways to maintain immunological tolerance to self-antigens. Taking into account the current research and creation of a large number of immunobiological drugs based on monoclonal antibodies to correct the imbalance of Th17 and Treg cells in various autoimmune diseases, attempts are being made to use some of them for autoimmune thyropathies. Further studies are needed to confirm the effectiveness of this therapy against autoimmune thyroid diseases.

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FEATURES OF CROHN'S DISEASE IN A CHILD WITH CONGENITAL SOMATOTROPIC INSUFFICIENCY

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Annotation. *A patient with congenital hypopituitarism is under observation at the SFRSNPCE. Growth hormone (GH) deficiency was confirmed by diagnostic stimulation tests (maximum peak GH value - 8.3 ng/ml). At diagnosis, the growth deficit was -3.9 SDS. MRI diagnosed an “empty sella turcica”, a heterogeneous structure of the pituitary gland. No dysfunction of other endocrine glands was detected. Bone age was 4 years behind the passport age and was 9 years. Somatogenic causes of growth retardation and chromosomal abnormalities were excluded. A study of genes associated with hypopituitarism did not reveal mutations. Therapy with GH drugs was started at a daily dose of 0.033 mg per 1 kg of body weight. 2 months after the start of replacement therapy, the patient was hospitalized in the surgical department of the hospital with symptoms of “acute abdomen”. GH therapy was suspended. Upon further examination, a diagnosis was made: Crohn's disease. After surgical treatment and prescription of specific therapy with Remicade according to the regimen, GH treatment was resumed (the break was 6 months). Currently, the patient is receiving GH replacement therapy and ongoing therapy for the concomitant disease, Crohn's disease.*

Keywords: *congenital hypopituitarism, Crohn's disease, somatotrophic insufficiency, growth hormone, clinical case.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ БОЛЕЗНИ КРОНА У РЕБЕНКА С ВРОЖДЕННОЙ СОМАТОТРОПНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТЬЮ

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Аннотация. В ГФРСНПХ под наблюдением находится больной с врожденным гипопитуитаризмом. Дефицит гормона роста (ГР) подтверждался диагностическими тестами стимуляции (максимальное пиковое значение ГР - 8,3 нг/мл). На момент постановки диагноза дефицит роста составил -3,9 SDS. При МРТ диагностировано «пустое турецкое седло» — неоднородная структура гипофиза. Нарушений со стороны других эндокринных желез не выявлено. Костный возраст отставал от паспортного на 4 года и составлял 9 лет. Соматогенные причины задержки роста и хромосомные аномалии были исключены. Исследование генов, связанных с гипопитуитаризмом, не выявило мутаций. Терапию препаратами ГР начинали в суточной дозе 0,033 мг на 1 кг массы тела. Через 2 месяца после начала заместительной терапии больной госпитализирован в хирургическое отделение больницы с симптомами «острого живота». Терапия ГР была приостановлена. При дальнейшем обследовании поставлен диагноз: болезнь Крона. После хирургического лечения и назначения специфической терапии Ремикейдом по схеме лечение ГР возобновили (перерыв составил 6 мес). В настоящее время пациентка получает заместительную терапию гормоном роста и продолжает терапию сопутствующего заболевания - болезни Крона.

Ключевые слова: врожденный гипопитуитаризм, болезнь Крона, соматотропная недостаточность, гормон роста, клинический случай.

Introduction. Diagnosis of congenital somatotropic deficiency, based on the study of stimulated secretion of growth hormone (GH), makes it possible to verify the disease and determine the need for growth-stimulating therapy with GH drugs [1]. The use of GH for short stature against the background of severe immunologically mediated disorders requires special caution. Somatropin is an effective and safe drug in children with GH deficiency [2, 3]. However, it is impossible to predict the occurrence of any concomitant diseases in a particular patient during GH therapy, the provoking cause of which could be the start of replacement therapy. Description of the case A girl born in 2002 is under the supervision of a pediatric endocrinologist at the SFRSNPTSE. For the first time, an endocrinologist was contacted in 2015 at the age of 13 years with complaints about low growth rates from an early age (in the 1st year of life she grew by 17 cm, in the years preceding the examination the growth rate did not exceed 4 cm per year). Growth retardation was associated with constitutional characteristics and somatic causes. Thus, from the age of 11, she was observed by a rheumatologist due to joint pain. Pain in the left hip and left ankle joints was regarded as manifestations of reactive arthritis, Schlatter's disease. At the age of 13 years, she was examined in an endocrinology hospital for short stature. The growth SDS was -3.9. Stimulation tests revealed a decrease in peak GH values: the maximum release was 8.3 ng/ml. Thus, the diagnosis of somatotropic insufficiency was confirmed. The MR picture did not exclude the presence of a pituitary microadenoma; An empty sella turcica and a heterogeneous structure of the pituitary gland were diagnosed. No dysfunction of other endocrine glands was detected. Bone age was 4 years behind the passport age and was 9 years. Somatogenic causes of growth retardation and chromosomal abnormalities were excluded. A molecular genetic study of genes associated with hypopituitarism did not reveal mutations. Therapy with GH drugs was started at a daily dose of 0.033 mg per 1 kg of body weight. 2 months after the start of GH therapy, the patient was hospitalized with suspected acute appendicitis. During emergency surgery, the diagnosis was confirmed; Appendectomy and resection of the inflammatory strand of the omentum were performed. Histologically, phlegmonous appendicitis, peritonitis, and mesenteriolitis were revealed. Somatropin therapy was temporarily suspended. 3 days after discharge from the hospital, the patient experienced severe abdominal pain, fever, and an infiltrate in the right iliac region. Upon re-hospitalization, ultrasound and CT scanning of the abdominal cavity diagnosed terminal ileitis, omentitis, interintestinal abscess, and ileal diverticulum. Antibacterial therapy was prescribed. When examined 1 month

after re-hospitalization, persistent signs of systemic inflammation were found, caused by an infiltrate in the abdominal cavity of 10-15 cm without abscess formation, inflammatory changes in the terminal ileum, sharp thickening of the walls of the small intestine with a narrowing of the lumen to 3 mm, signs of proximal intestinal dilatation. The diagnosis of Crohn's disease was confirmed by serological examination data: an increase in ASCA of both classes, an increase in calprotectin to 607. Analysis of the NOD2/CARD15 gene for the receptor for muramyl dipeptide (a component of the bacterial cell wall) revealed a genetic risk for Crohn's disease. The girl received long-term antibacterial therapy (thienam, ceftazidime, amikacin, cefepime). Considering the penetrating form of the disease with the development of complications, specific therapy with the drug Remicade was carried out. Due to severe growth retardation and the high risk of surgical treatment, it was decided to abstain from steroid therapy. During the therapy, a decrease in the size of the infiltrate was observed, but high laboratory activity and an increase in temperature remained. A diagnostic laparoscopy was performed. An area of altered intestine was identified, laparotomy was performed, and the ileocecal angle of the intestine was resected. The postoperative period was uneventful. Remicade therapy was continued. After 6 months, treatment with GH drugs was resumed at a dose of 0.033 mg/kg/day. During therapy, the level of IGF-I (December 2016) was 282 ng/ml. Levels of thyroid and adrenal hormones are within normal limits. During 6 months of replacement therapy after surgery, the increase in height was 4 cm, height SDS was 4.07. Discussion The complexity of the described case is determined by two factors. The first is associated with the diagnosis of hypopituitarism (or somatotrophic insufficiency). Is this the primary disease against which Crohn's disease manifested itself, or did a genetically determined disease with an immunopathological mechanism of development, Crohn's disease, manifest itself in the child with progressive growth retardation with impaired GH secretion? The second and most difficult question is the possibility of continuing GH treatment. The coincidence of the start of growth-stimulating therapy and the manifestation of Crohn's disease determines the need for a balanced approach to continuing GH treatment. Taking into account the significant growth retardation and stable somatic condition during treatment with Remicade, it was decided to continue GH therapy under the control of IGF-1 levels. specific therapy with the drug Remicade was carried out. Due to severe growth retardation and the high risk of surgical treatment, it was decided to abstain from steroid therapy. During the therapy, a decrease in the size of the infiltrate was observed, but high laboratory activity and an increase in temperature

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Conclusion. Growth hormone replacement therapy for congenital hypopituitarism is necessary. However, when prescribing somatropin, it is necessary to take into account the presence of concomitant diseases in patients, the manifestation of which can be provoked by replacement therapy. The safety of using growth hormone in children has been proven, but careful monitoring of the patient is required in each specific case.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE LEVEL OF EDUCATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING PATIENTS AT THE DIABETES SCHOOL IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation. *Diabetes mellitus (DM) leads to alarming clinical, social, financial, and public health issues with devastating long-term effects on the well-being, affecting quality of life including neuropathy, retinopathy, nephropathy, dementia, and cognitive problems.[1,2,3] Self-monitoring of blood sugar and apt self-care with effective metabolic regulation affect hypoglycemia, ketoacidosis, or microvascular and macrovascular complications.[3] DM prevalence has risen dramatically over the past 2 decades, with India being the major contributor. Global burden in 2011 was 8.3% (366.2 millions) compared to 4% in 1995 and is projected to rise to 551.9 million by 2030.[4,5].*

Keywords: *diabetes mellitus, insulin, hyperglycemia, metabolic regulation.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ УРОВНЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ В ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ШКОЛЕ ПРИ САХАРНОМ ДИАБЕТЕ 2 ТИПА

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Аннотация. Сахарный диабет (СД) приводит к тревожным клиническим, социальным, финансовым проблемам и проблемам общественного здравоохранения с разрушительными долгосрочными последствиями для благополучия, влияя на качество жизни, включая невропатию, ретинопатию, нефропатию, деменцию и когнитивные проблемы. [2,3] Самоконтроль уровня сахара в крови и правильный уход за собой с эффективной регуляцией обмена веществ влияют на гипогликемию, кетоацидоз или микро- и макрососудистые осложнения. [3] Распространенность СД резко возросла за последние два десятилетия, причем основной вклад в это внесла Индия. Глобальное бремя в 2011 году составило 8,3% (366,2 миллиона человек) по сравнению с 4% в 1995 году и, по прогнозам, к 2030 году вырастет до 551,9 миллиона человек. [4,5]

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет, инсулин, гипергликемия, метаболическая регуляция.

Introduction. However, our National Health Policy 2017 envisaged reducing premature mortality from diabetes and other non-communicable diseases to 25% by 2025.[6] There is a need to focus on preventive efforts with research on optimum choice of user-friendly test/s in the first contact care. Although glycated hemoglobin (HbA1C) does not require fasting and may be the best compromise, diagnosis and prognosis cannot be solely relied on HbA1C values that are affected in presence of different physiological and co-morbid conditions.[7,8,9,10] Diabetes education is considered an essential tool as its management largely depends on knowledge, motivation, and ability to pursue self-care in activities of daily living. Therefore, counseling and health education should be given paramount importance by the physicians even in their busy schedule including elaborate advice on lifestyle modifications and diet.[10,11,12,13] Although, evidences suggest that diabetics with more knowledge and motivated self-care help to achieve better glycemic control, there is difference of opinion on effectiveness of methods of health education and educational efforts to improve interventions are key components of effective treatment plan for DM.[14,15,16,17]. Health education is essential in resource poor settings such as ours, wherein DM pose great financial burden and calls for urgent participation of clinicians at all levels especially primary care physicians as they are usually the first care givers and come across known as well as recently detected diabetics. These patients can be imparted health education by primary care physicians to adopt healthy lifestyle practices, remain motivated for regular testing of glycemic status, and be aware of diabetic complications. The consequent changes in knowledge, attitude, and practices of diabetic patients are vital for achieving glycemic control and for preventing the development of complication of diabetes.

Objective: to assess the impact of the level of education on the effectiveness of teaching patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) at the diabetes school after 2 years.

Materials and methods: 188 patients (106 women 55.7%, 82 men 44.3%) aged 47-79 years (median (Me) – 61.4 years) with higher and secondary education, DM experience 12.4 years, BMI 30.5 ±0.72, attached to the State Medical Institution "Consultative and Diagnostic Center No6 DZM" of Moscow were examined (5 branches) and trained at the diabetes school in 2014. All patients were treated with oral hypoglycemic drugs. Compliance was assessed using a generally accepted standardized Russian-language Morisky-Green questionnaire. Statistical processing was carried out in the Statistica 7.0 program.

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Results: according to the results of a survey of 188 patients with type 2 diabetes after 1 year after training, it was revealed that 105 (56%) patients did not follow the doctor's recommendations. The most common reasons for this were: forgetfulness of patients (44.6%), difficulty taking medications (21.8%), high treatment costs (26.7%). The analysis of the level of education of patients showed that among people with higher education, 48% fully comply with the recommendations, 10.8% partially and only 5.2% are incompetent. Among people with secondary education, 9.7% fully complied with the doctor's recommendations; 16% partially; 12.3% were incompetent. After 2 years, there was an increase in the group of patients who did not follow the doctor's recommendations to 124 (65.9%), of which forgetfulness was (54.4%); the complexity of taking drugs remained the same (21.8%); high costs decreased slightly to 24.8%. The analysis of the level of education revealed minor changes in patients with higher education: fully compliant 45%; partially -15.4%; incompetent 13.6%; with secondary education — fulfilling recommendations 7.1%; partially - 11.5%; not fulfilling 19.4%

Conclusions: assessment of the importance of the status of education in adherence to the implementation of medical recommendations for the treatment of diabetes mellitus demonstrated less compliance of persons with an average level of education. The differences in the indicators of this group were statistically significant compared to patients with higher and secondary specialized education. In this regard, it is necessary to motivate patients to undergo repeated group training at the diabetes school 1 time / 2 years.

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